

Palindromic-Type Palindromes - I

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Abstract

In the previous papers [9, 13], the author worked with **palindromic-type expressions**. These expressions are by use of operations addition and multiplications. When the operations are removed, we get normal even order palindromes. In the previous works, it is limited to particular cases including patterns. The final sum is either palindromic or non palindromic. The aim of this paper is to write **palindromic-type expressions** when final sums are palindromes. The results are with multiple choices representations, i.e., in some cases palindromes can be written in terms of different **palindromic-type expressions**. Due to high quantity of numbers, the work is limited to 7 digits palindromes. In the another part of the work [14], the **palindromic-type expressions** are given, where the final sums are not palindromes.

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1 Introduction

A palindromic number is the number that remains the same when its digits are reversed, for example, 121, 3333, 161161, etc. In [6, 7], author worked on palindromic patterns and wrote them in terms of single digit "a". We shall define **palindromic-type expressions**, i.e., the numbers are not palindromes but appears like palindromes. They are separated by operations of additions and/or multiplications, for example,

- 1343×3421
- 1225×5221
- $16 + 61$
- $1825 + 5281$, etc.

When we remove the operation sign, they becomes palindromes. These types of numbers we call as **palindromic-type expressions**. Some studies in this direction can be seen in [4]. Let us separate these numbers in two categories:

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- **Type 1:**

$$1596 \times 6951 = 2793 \times 3972$$

$$616248 \times 842616 = 645408 \times 804546.$$

- **Type 2:**

$$234 \times 111 + 111 \times 432 = 25974 + 47952 := 73926.$$

$$10011 \times 11 + 11 \times 11001 = 110121 + 121011 := 231132.$$

The difference is that the first type is only with **multiplication**, and second type is with **addition** and **multiplication**. The work on first type can be seen in author's work [10, 12]. This work is concentrated only on **Type 2**, i.e., **palindromic-type expressions** with **addition** and **multiplication**.

Let's analyse both the expressions given in Type 2. In the first expressions the final sum is non-palindrome, in the second expression the final sum is palindrome. In this case the **palindromic-type expressions** are

$$234 \times 111 + 111 \times 432 = 25974 + 47952$$

$$10011 \times 11 + 11 \times 11001 = 110121 + 121011.$$

Without operations, in each case, we get different palindromes:

- (i) 234111111432 and 2597447952;
- (ii) 1001111111001 and 110121121011.

Since these becomes equal by using operations, that's why we call them as **palindromic-type expressions**. For simplicity, these can be written as

$$ab \times cd + dc \times ba = ef + fe := G, \quad (1.1)$$

where

$$ab : \text{Palindrome or Non-Palindrome};$$

$$cd : \text{Palindrome or Non-Palindrome};$$

$$G : \text{Palindrome or Non-Palindrome}.$$

1.1 Particular Cases

- (i) In case of **squared expressions**, we have $ab = cd$ and $dc = ba$

$$(ab)^2 + (ba)^2 = ef + fa := G \quad (1.2)$$

where " G " may or may not be a palindrome.

- (ii) ab, ba, cd, dc, ef and fa all palindromes, where the total sums " G " may or may not be a palindrome.
- (iii) ab, ba, cd and dc are of equal lengths, where " G " may or may not be a palindrome.

In this paper, our aim to bring general results according to (1.1), where the total sum " G " is always palindrome. For the case, the total sum " G " non-palindrome is done in another work. Due to high quantity of numbers the work is limited to seven digits sum of " G ".

For study in this direction in different situations refer author's work [6, 7, 8]. This work is revised version of author's previous works [9, 13]. For summary of author's work on recreation of numbers refer [11]. From historical point of view refer [1, 2, 3, 5].

2 Palindromic-Type Palindromes

This section brings palindromic numbers, those can be decompose in **palindromic-type expressions**. The work is separated according to number of digits. Due to high quantity of numbers, the work is limited to 7-digits or length 7 palindromes.

2.1 Three Digits Palindromic Sum

$$242 := 11 \times 11 + 11 \times 11 = 121 + 121$$

$$363 := 12 \times 11 + 11 \times 21 = 132 + 231$$

$$484 := 13 \times 11 + 11 \times 31 = 143 + 341$$

$$:= 22 \times 11 + 11 \times 22 = 242 + 242$$

$$585 := 12 \times 12 + 21 \times 21 = 144 + 441$$

2.2 Four Digits Palindromic Sum

$$2222 := 101 \times 11 + 11 \times 101 = 1111 + 1111$$

$$2442 := 111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111 = 1221 + 1221$$

$$2662 := 121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121 = 1331 + 1331$$

$$2882 := 131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131 = 1441 + 1441$$

$$3333 := 101 \times 12 + 21 \times 101 = 1212 + 2121$$

$$:= 102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201 = 1122 + 2211$$

$$3553 := 112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211 = 1232 + 2321$$

$$3663 := 111 \times 12 + 21 \times 111 = 1332 + 2331$$

$$3773 := 122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221 = 1342 + 2431$$

$$3993 := 121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121 = 1452 + 2541$$

$$:= 132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231 = 1452 + 2541$$

$$4444 := 101 \times 13 + 31 \times 101 = 1313 + 3131$$

$$:= 101 \times 22 + 22 \times 101 = 2222 + 2222$$

$$:= 103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301 = 1133 + 3311$$

$$:= 202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202 = 2222 + 2222$$

$$4554 := 102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201 = 2142 + 2412$$

$$4664 := 113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311 = 1243 + 3421$$

$$:= 212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212 = 2332 + 2332$$

$$4884 := 111 \times 13 + 31 \times 111 = 1443 + 3441$$

$$:= 111 \times 22 + 22 \times 111 = 2442 + 2442$$

$$:= 112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211 = 2352 + 2532$$

$$:= 123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321 = 1353 + 3531$$

$$:= 222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222 = 2442 + 2442$$

$$5445 := 102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201 = 1224 + 4221$$

$$5555 := 101 \times 14 + 41 \times 101 = 1414 + 4141$$

$$:= 101 \times 23 + 32 \times 101 = 2323 + 3232$$

$$:= 104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401 = 1144 + 4411$$

$$:= 203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302 = 2233 + 3322$$

$$5775 := 102 \times 31 + 13 \times 201 = 3162 + 2613$$

$$:= 103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301 = 2163 + 3612$$

$$:= 112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211 = 1344 + 4431$$

$$:= 114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411 = 1254 + 4521$$

$$:= 213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312 = 2343 + 3432$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5995 &:= 124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421 = 1364 + 4631 \\ &:= 223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322 = 2453 + 3542 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512 = 2365 + 5632 \\ &:= 314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413 = 3454 + 4543 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6666 &:= 101 \times 15 + 51 \times 101 = 1515 + 5151 \\ &:= 101 \times 24 + 42 \times 101 = 2424 + 4242 \\ &:= 101 \times 33 + 33 \times 101 = 3333 + 3333 \\ &:= 102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201 = 2244 + 4422 \\ &:= 105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501 = 1155 + 5511 \\ &:= 202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202 = 2424 + 4242 \\ &:= 204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402 = 2244 + 4422 \\ &:= 303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303 = 3333 + 3333 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8778 &:= 102 \times 23 + 32 \times 201 = 2346 + 6432 \\ &:= 203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302 = 2436 + 6342 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6886 &:= 115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511 = 1265 + 5621 \\ &:= 214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412 = 2354 + 4532 \\ &:= 313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313 = 3443 + 3443 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8888 &:= 101 \times 17 + 71 \times 101 = 1717 + 7171 \\ &:= 101 \times 26 + 62 \times 101 = 2626 + 6262 \\ &:= 101 \times 35 + 53 \times 101 = 3535 + 5353 \\ &:= 101 \times 44 + 44 \times 101 = 4444 + 4444 \\ &:= 103 \times 22 + 22 \times 301 = 2266 + 6622 \\ &:= 107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701 = 1177 + 7711 \\ &:= 202 \times 13 + 31 \times 202 = 2626 + 6262 \\ &:= 202 \times 22 + 22 \times 202 = 4444 + 4444 \\ &:= 206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602 = 2266 + 6622 \\ &:= 301 \times 22 + 22 \times 103 = 6622 + 2266 \\ &:= 305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503 = 3355 + 5533 \\ &:= 404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404 = 4444 + 4444 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6996 &:= 102 \times 41 + 14 \times 201 = 4182 + 2814 \\ &:= 104 \times 21 + 12 \times 401 = 2184 + 4812 \\ &:= 212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212 = 2544 + 4452 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9669 &:= 102 \times 14 + 41 \times 201 = 1428 + 8241 \\ &:= 104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401 = 1248 + 8421 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7557 &:= 102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201 = 1326 + 6231 \\ &:= 103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301 = 1236 + 6321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7777 &:= 101 \times 16 + 61 \times 101 = 1616 + 6161 \\ &:= 101 \times 25 + 52 \times 101 = 2525 + 5252 \\ &:= 101 \times 34 + 43 \times 101 = 3434 + 4343 \\ &:= 106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601 = 1166 + 6611 \\ &:= 205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502 = 2255 + 5522 \\ &:= 304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403 = 3344 + 4433 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9999 &:= 101 \times 18 + 81 \times 101 = 1818 + 8181 \\ &:= 101 \times 27 + 72 \times 101 = 2727 + 7272 \\ &:= 101 \times 36 + 63 \times 101 = 3636 + 6363 \\ &:= 101 \times 45 + 54 \times 101 = 4545 + 5454 \\ &:= 102 \times 33 + 33 \times 201 = 3366 + 6633 \\ &:= 108 \times 11 + 11 \times 801 = 1188 + 8811 \\ &:= 114 \times 12 + 21 \times 411 = 1368 + 8631 \\ &:= 207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702 = 2277 + 7722 \\ &:= 303 \times 12 + 21 \times 303 = 3636 + 6363 \\ &:= 306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603 = 3366 + 6633 \\ &:= 405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504 = 4455 + 5544 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7887 &:= 102 \times 32 + 23 \times 201 = 3264 + 4623 \\ &:= 113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311 = 1356 + 6531 \\ &:= 203 \times 21 + 12 \times 302 = 4263 + 3624 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7997 &:= 112 \times 13 + 31 \times 211 = 1456 + 6541 \\ &:= 116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611 = 1276 + 6721 \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Five Digits Palindromic Sum

$$\begin{aligned} 12221 &:= 101 \times 29 + 92 \times 101 = 2929 + 9292 \\ &:= 101 \times 38 + 83 \times 101 = 3838 + 8383 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 101 \times 47 + 74 \times 101 = 4747 + 7474 \\ &:= 101 \times 56 + 65 \times 101 = 5656 + 6565 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 209 \times 11 + 11 \times 902 = 2299 + 9922$$

$$:= 308 \times 11 + 11 \times 803 = 3388 + 8833$$

$$:= 407 \times 11 + 11 \times 704 = 4477 + 7744$$

$$:= 506 \times 11 + 11 \times 605 = 5566 + 6655$$

$$20402 := 101 \times 101 + 101 \times 101 = 10201 + 10201$$

$$22022 := 1001 \times 11 + 11 \times 1001 = 11011 + 11011$$

$$22422 := 111 \times 101 + 101 \times 111 = 11211 + 11211$$

$$23232 := 1011 \times 11 + 11 \times 1101 = 11121 + 12111$$

$$24442 := 1021 \times 11 + 11 \times 1201 = 11231 + 13211$$

$$:= 1111 \times 11 + 11 \times 1111 = 12221 + 12221$$

$$:= 121 \times 101 + 101 \times 121 = 12221 + 12221$$

$$24642 := 111 \times 111 + 111 \times 111 = 12321 + 12321$$

$$25652 := 1031 \times 11 + 11 \times 1301 = 11341 + 14311$$

$$:= 1121 \times 11 + 11 \times 1211 = 12331 + 13321$$

$$26462 := 131 \times 101 + 101 \times 131 = 13231 + 13231$$

$$26862 := 1041 \times 11 + 11 \times 1401 = 11451 + 15411$$

$$:= 1131 \times 11 + 11 \times 1311 = 12441 + 14421$$

$$:= 1221 \times 11 + 11 \times 1221 = 13431 + 13431$$

$$:= 121 \times 111 + 111 \times 121 = 13431 + 13431$$

$$28482 := 141 \times 101 + 101 \times 141 = 14241 + 14241$$

$$30603 := 102 \times 101 + 101 \times 201 = 10302 + 20301$$

$$32623 := 112 \times 101 + 101 \times 211 = 11312 + 21311$$

$$33033 := 1001 \times 12 + 21 \times 1001 = 12012 + 21021$$

$$:= 1002 \times 11 + 11 \times 2001 = 11022 + 22011$$

$$33633 := 111 \times 102 + 201 \times 111 = 11322 + 22311$$

$$34243 := 1012 \times 11 + 11 \times 2101 = 11132 + 23111$$

$$:= 1102 \times 11 + 11 \times 2011 = 12122 + 22121$$

$$34443 := 1011 \times 21 + 12 \times 1101 = 21231 + 13212$$

$$34643 := 122 \times 101 + 101 \times 221 = 12322 + 22321$$

$$35253 := 1011 \times 12 + 21 \times 1101 = 12132 + 23121$$

$$35453 := 1022 \times 11 + 11 \times 2201 = 11242 + 24211$$

$$:= 1112 \times 11 + 11 \times 2111 = 12232 + 23221$$

$$:= 1202 \times 11 + 11 \times 2021 = 13222 + 22231$$

$$35853 := 1021 \times 21 + 12 \times 1201 = 21441 + 14412$$

$$:= 112 \times 111 + 111 \times 211 = 12432 + 23421$$

$$36663 := 1032 \times 11 + 11 \times 2301 = 11352 + 25311$$

$$:= 1111 \times 12 + 21 \times 1111 = 13332 + 23331$$

$$:= 1122 \times 11 + 11 \times 2211 = 12342 + 24321$$

$$:= 1212 \times 11 + 11 \times 2121 = 13332 + 23331$$

$$:= 1302 \times 11 + 11 \times 2031 = 14322 + 22341$$

$$:= 121 \times 102 + 201 \times 121 = 12342 + 24321$$

$$:= 132 \times 101 + 101 \times 231 = 13332 + 23331$$

$$37473 := 1021 \times 12 + 21 \times 1201 = 12252 + 25221$$

$$37873 := 1042 \times 11 + 11 \times 2401 = 11462 + 26411$$

$$:= 1132 \times 11 + 11 \times 2311 = 12452 + 25421$$

$$:= 1222 \times 11 + 11 \times 2221 = 13442 + 24431$$

$$:= 1312 \times 11 + 11 \times 2131 = 14432 + 23441$$

$$:= 1402 \times 11 + 11 \times 2041 = 15422 + 22451$$

$$38683 := 142 \times 101 + 101 \times 241 = 14342 + 24341$$

$$38883 := 1121 \times 12 + 21 \times 1211 = 13452 + 25431$$

$$39693 := 1031 \times 12 + 21 \times 1301 = 12372 + 27321$$

$$:= 131 \times 102 + 201 \times 131 = 13362 + 26331$$

$$40804 := 103 \times 101 + 101 \times 301 = 10403 + 30401$$

$$42824 := 113 \times 101 + 101 \times 311 = 11413 + 31411$$

$$:= 212 \times 101 + 101 \times 212 = 21412 + 21412$$

$$44044 := 1001 \times 13 + 31 \times 1001 = 13013 + 31031$$

$$:= 1001 \times 22 + 22 \times 1001 = 22022 + 22022$$

$$:= 1003 \times 11 + 11 \times 3001 = 11033 + 33011$$

$$:= 2002 \times 11 + 11 \times 2002 = 22022 + 22022$$

$$44844 := 111 \times 103 + 301 \times 111 = 11433 + 33411$$

$$:= 123 \times 101 + 101 \times 321 = 12423 + 32421$$

$$:= 202 \times 111 + 111 \times 202 = 22422 + 22422$$

$$:= 222 \times 101 + 101 \times 222 = 22422 + 22422$$

$$**45054** := 1002 \times 21 + 12 \times 2001 = 21042 + 24012$$

$$:= 2001 \times 12 + 21 \times 1002 = 24012 + 21042$$

$$**45254** := 1013 \times 11 + 11 \times 3101 = 11143 + 34111$$

$$:= 1103 \times 11 + 11 \times 3011 = 12133 + 33121$$

$$:= 2012 \times 11 + 11 \times 2102 = 22132 + 23122$$

$$**45654** := 1011 \times 31 + 13 \times 1101 = 31341 + 14313$$

$$**46464** := 1011 \times 22 + 22 \times 1101 = 22242 + 24222$$

$$:= 1012 \times 21 + 12 \times 2101 = 21252 + 25212$$

$$:= 1023 \times 11 + 11 \times 3201 = 11253 + 35211$$

$$:= 1113 \times 11 + 11 \times 3111 = 12243 + 34221$$

$$:= 1203 \times 11 + 11 \times 3021 = 13233 + 33231$$

$$:= 2022 \times 11 + 11 \times 2202 = 22242 + 24222$$

$$:= 2112 \times 11 + 11 \times 2112 = 23232 + 23232$$

$$:= 3111 \times 11 + 11 \times 1113 = 34221 + 12243$$

$$**46864** := 133 \times 101 + 101 \times 331 = 13433 + 33431$$

$$:= 232 \times 101 + 101 \times 232 = 23432 + 23432$$

$$**47274** := 1011 \times 13 + 31 \times 1101 = 13143 + 34131$$

$$:= 1102 \times 21 + 12 \times 2011 = 23142 + 24132$$

$$**47674** := 1033 \times 11 + 11 \times 3301 = 11363 + 36311$$

$$:= 1123 \times 11 + 11 \times 3211 = 12353 + 35321$$

$$:= 1213 \times 11 + 11 \times 3121 = 13343 + 34331$$

$$:= 1303 \times 11 + 11 \times 3031 = 14333 + 33341$$

$$:= 2032 \times 11 + 11 \times 2302 = 22352 + 25322$$

$$:= 2122 \times 11 + 11 \times 2212 = 23342 + 24332$$

$$**47874** := 1022 \times 21 + 12 \times 2201 = 21462 + 26412$$

$$**48684** := 1112 \times 21 + 12 \times 2111 = 23352 + 25332$$

$$**48884** := 1021 \times 22 + 22 \times 1201 = 22462 + 26422$$

$$:= 1043 \times 11 + 11 \times 3401 = 11473 + 37411$$

$$:= 1111 \times 13 + 31 \times 1111 = 14443 + 34441$$

$$:= 1111 \times 22 + 22 \times 1111 = 24442 + 24442$$

$$:= 1133 \times 11 + 11 \times 3311 = 12463 + 36421$$

$$:= 1223 \times 11 + 11 \times 3221 = 13453 + 35431$$

$$:= 1313 \times 11 + 11 \times 3131 = 14443 + 34441$$

$$:= 1403 \times 11 + 11 \times 3041 = 15433 + 33451$$

$$:= 2042 \times 11 + 11 \times 2402 = 22462 + 26422$$

$$:= 2132 \times 11 + 11 \times 2312 = 23452 + 25432$$

$$:= 2222 \times 11 + 11 \times 2222 = 24442 + 24442$$

$$:= 121 \times 103 + 301 \times 121 = 12463 + 36421$$

$$:= 143 \times 101 + 101 \times 341 = 14443 + 34441$$

$$:= 202 \times 121 + 121 \times 202 = 24442 + 24442$$

$$:= 242 \times 101 + 101 \times 242 = 24442 + 24442$$

$$**49494** := 1202 \times 21 + 12 \times 2021 = 25242 + 24252$$

$$**50805** := 102 \times 102 + 201 \times 201 = 10404 + 40401$$

$$**53835** := 112 \times 102 + 201 \times 211 = 11424 + 42411$$

$$**54045** := 1002 \times 12 + 21 \times 2001 = 12024 + 42021$$

$$**55055** := 1001 \times 14 + 41 \times 1001 = 14014 + 41041$$

$$:= 1001 \times 23 + 32 \times 1001 = 23023 + 32032$$

$$:= 1004 \times 11 + 11 \times 4001 = 11044 + 44011$$

$$:= 2003 \times 11 + 11 \times 3002 = 22033 + 33022$$

$$**55455** := 1102 \times 12 + 21 \times 2011 = 13224 + 42231$$

$$**56265** := 1012 \times 12 + 21 \times 2101 = 12144 + 44121$$

$$:= 1014 \times 11 + 11 \times 4101 = 11154 + 45111$$

$$:= 1104 \times 11 + 11 \times 4011 = 12144 + 44121$$

$$:= 2013 \times 11 + 11 \times 3102 = 22143 + 34122$$

$$:= 2103 \times 11 + 11 \times 3012 = 23133 + 33132$$

$$**56865** := 1011 \times 41 + 14 \times 1101 = 41451 + 15414$$

$$:= 1202 \times 12 + 21 \times 2021 = 14424 + 42441$$

$$:= 122 \times 102 + 201 \times 221 = 12444 + 44421$$

$$**57075** := 1002 \times 31 + 13 \times 2001 = 31062 + 26013$$

$$:= 1003 \times 21 + 12 \times 3001 = 21063 + 36012$$

$$**57475** := 1024 \times 11 + 11 \times 4201 = 11264 + 46211$$

$$:= 1114 \times 11 + 11 \times 4111 = 12254 + 45221$$

$$:= 1204 \times 11 + 11 \times 4021 = 13244 + 44231$$

$$:= 2023 \times 11 + 11 \times 3202 = 22253 + 35222$$

$$:= 2113 \times 11 + 11 \times 3112 = 23243 + 34232$$

$$:= 2203 \times 11 + 11 \times 3022 = 24233 + 33242$$

$$\mathbf{57675} := 1011 \times 32 + 23 \times 1101 = 32352 + 25323$$

$$:= 1112 \times 12 + 21 \times 2111 = 13344 + 44331$$

$$\mathbf{58485} := 1011 \times 23 + 32 \times 1101 = 23253 + 35232$$

$$:= 1013 \times 21 + 12 \times 3101 = 21273 + 37212$$

$$:= 1022 \times 12 + 21 \times 2201 = 12264 + 46221$$

$$\mathbf{58685} := 1012 \times 31 + 13 \times 2101 = 31372 + 27313$$

$$:= 1034 \times 11 + 11 \times 4301 = 11374 + 47311$$

$$:= 1124 \times 11 + 11 \times 4211 = 12364 + 46321$$

$$:= 1214 \times 11 + 11 \times 4121 = 13354 + 45331$$

$$:= 1304 \times 11 + 11 \times 4031 = 14344 + 44341$$

$$:= 2033 \times 11 + 11 \times 3302 = 22363 + 36322$$

$$:= 2123 \times 11 + 11 \times 3212 = 23353 + 35332$$

$$:= 2213 \times 11 + 11 \times 3122 = 24343 + 34342$$

$$:= 2303 \times 11 + 11 \times 3032 = 25333 + 33352$$

$$\mathbf{59295} := 1011 \times 14 + 41 \times 1101 = 14154 + 45141$$

$$:= 1103 \times 21 + 12 \times 3011 = 23163 + 36132$$

$$\mathbf{59895} := 1023 \times 21 + 12 \times 3201 = 21483 + 38412$$

$$:= 1044 \times 11 + 11 \times 4401 = 11484 + 48411$$

$$:= 1122 \times 12 + 21 \times 2211 = 13464 + 46431$$

$$:= 1134 \times 11 + 11 \times 4311 = 12474 + 47421$$

$$:= 1224 \times 11 + 11 \times 4221 = 13464 + 46431$$

$$:= 1314 \times 11 + 11 \times 4131 = 14454 + 45441$$

$$:= 1404 \times 11 + 11 \times 4041 = 15444 + 44451$$

$$:= 2043 \times 11 + 11 \times 3402 = 22473 + 37422$$

$$:= 2133 \times 11 + 11 \times 3312 = 23463 + 36432$$

$$:= 2223 \times 11 + 11 \times 3222 = 24453 + 35442$$

$$:= 2313 \times 11 + 11 \times 3132 = 25443 + 34452$$

$$:= 2403 \times 11 + 11 \times 3042 = 26433 + 33462$$

$$:= 132 \times 102 + 201 \times 231 = 13464 + 46431$$

$$\mathbf{66066} := 1001 \times 15 + 51 \times 1001 = 15015 + 51051$$

$$:= 1001 \times 24 + 42 \times 1001 = 24024 + 42042$$

$$:= 1001 \times 33 + 33 \times 1001 = 33033 + 33033$$

$$:= 1002 \times 22 + 22 \times 2001 = 22044 + 44022$$

$$:= 1005 \times 11 + 11 \times 5001 = 11055 + 55011$$

$$:= 2002 \times 12 + 21 \times 2002 = 24024 + 42042$$

$$:= 2004 \times 11 + 11 \times 4002 = 22044 + 44022$$

$$:= 3003 \times 11 + 11 \times 3003 = 33033 + 33033$$

$$\mathbf{67276} := 1015 \times 11 + 11 \times 5101 = 11165 + 56111$$

$$:= 1105 \times 11 + 11 \times 5011 = 12155 + 55121$$

$$:= 2014 \times 11 + 11 \times 4102 = 22154 + 45122$$

$$:= 2104 \times 11 + 11 \times 4012 = 23144 + 44132$$

$$:= 3013 \times 11 + 11 \times 3103 = 33143 + 34133$$

$$\mathbf{67476} := 2012 \times 21 + 12 \times 2102 = 42252 + 25224$$

$$\mathbf{68286} := 2012 \times 12 + 21 \times 2102 = 24144 + 44142$$

$$\mathbf{68486} := 1012 \times 22 + 22 \times 2101 = 22264 + 46222$$

$$:= 1025 \times 11 + 11 \times 5201 = 11275 + 57211$$

$$:= 1102 \times 22 + 22 \times 2011 = 24244 + 44242$$

$$:= 1115 \times 11 + 11 \times 5111 = 12265 + 56221$$

$$:= 1205 \times 11 + 11 \times 5021 = 13255 + 55231$$

$$:= 2024 \times 11 + 11 \times 4202 = 22264 + 46222$$

$$:= 2114 \times 11 + 11 \times 4112 = 23254 + 45232$$

$$:= 2204 \times 11 + 11 \times 4022 = 24244 + 44242$$

$$:= 3023 \times 11 + 11 \times 3203 = 33253 + 35233$$

$$:= 3113 \times 11 + 11 \times 3113 = 34243 + 34243$$

$$\mathbf{68886} := 1011 \times 42 + 24 \times 1101 = 42462 + 26424$$

$$:= 2022 \times 21 + 12 \times 2202 = 42462 + 26424$$

$$\mathbf{69096} := 1002 \times 41 + 14 \times 2001 = 41082 + 28014$$

$$:= 1004 \times 21 + 12 \times 4001 = 21084 + 48012$$

$$\mathbf{69696} := 1011 \times 33 + 33 \times 1101 = 33363 + 36333$$

$$:= 1035 \times 11 + 11 \times 5301 = 11385 + 58311$$

$$:= 1125 \times 11 + 11 \times 5211 = 12375 + 57321$$

$$:= 1215 \times 11 + 11 \times 5121 = 13365 + 56331$$

$$:= 1305 \times 11 + 11 \times 5031 = 14355 + 55341$$

$$:= 2034 \times 11 + 11 \times 4302 = 22374 + 47322$$

$$:= 2112 \times 12 + 21 \times 2112 = 25344 + 44352$$

$$:= 2124 \times 11 + 11 \times 4212 = 23364 + 46332$$

$$:= 2214 \times 11 + 11 \times 4122 = 24354 + 45342$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 2304 \times 11 + 11 \times 4032 = 25344 + 44352 \\ &:= 3033 \times 11 + 11 \times 3303 = 33363 + 36333 \\ &:= 3123 \times 11 + 11 \times 3213 = 34353 + 35343 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{75057} &:= 1002 \times 13 + 31 \times 2001 = 13026 + 62031 \\ &:= 1003 \times 12 + 21 \times 3001 = 12036 + 63021 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{76467} := 1103 \times 12 + 21 \times 3011 = 13236 + 63231$$

$$\mathbf{76667} := 1102 \times 13 + 31 \times 2011 = 14326 + 62341$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77077} &:= 1001 \times 16 + 61 \times 1001 = 16016 + 61061 \\ &:= 1001 \times 25 + 52 \times 1001 = 25025 + 52052 \\ &:= 1001 \times 34 + 43 \times 1001 = 34034 + 43043 \\ &:= 1006 \times 11 + 11 \times 6001 = 11066 + 66011 \\ &:= 2005 \times 11 + 11 \times 5002 = 22055 + 55022 \\ &:= 3004 \times 11 + 11 \times 4003 = 33044 + 44033 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{77277} := 1013 \times 12 + 21 \times 3101 = 12156 + 65121$$

$$\mathbf{77877} := 1203 \times 12 + 21 \times 3021 = 14436 + 63441$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{78087} &:= 1002 \times 32 + 23 \times 2001 = 32064 + 46023 \\ &:= 2003 \times 21 + 12 \times 3002 = 42063 + 36024 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{78287} &:= 1012 \times 13 + 31 \times 2101 = 13156 + 65131 \\ &:= 1016 \times 11 + 11 \times 6101 = 11176 + 67111 \\ &:= 1106 \times 11 + 11 \times 6011 = 12166 + 66121 \\ &:= 2015 \times 11 + 11 \times 5102 = 22165 + 56122 \\ &:= 2105 \times 11 + 11 \times 5012 = 23155 + 55132 \\ &:= 3014 \times 11 + 11 \times 4103 = 33154 + 45133 \\ &:= 3104 \times 11 + 11 \times 4013 = 34144 + 44143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{78687} := 1113 \times 12 + 21 \times 3111 = 13356 + 65331$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{79497} &:= 1023 \times 12 + 21 \times 3201 = 12276 + 67221 \\ &:= 1026 \times 11 + 11 \times 6201 = 11286 + 68211 \\ &:= 1116 \times 11 + 11 \times 6111 = 12276 + 67221 \\ &:= 1206 \times 11 + 11 \times 6021 = 13266 + 66231 \\ &:= 2013 \times 21 + 12 \times 3102 = 42273 + 37224 \\ &:= 2025 \times 11 + 11 \times 5202 = 22275 + 57222 \\ &:= 2115 \times 11 + 11 \times 5112 = 23265 + 56232 \\ &:= 2205 \times 11 + 11 \times 5022 = 24255 + 55242 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 3024 \times 11 + 11 \times 4203 = 33264 + 46233 \\ &:= 3114 \times 11 + 11 \times 4113 = 34254 + 45243 \\ &:= 3204 \times 11 + 11 \times 4023 = 35244 + 44253 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{79897} := 1112 \times 13 + 31 \times 2111 = 14456 + 65441$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{87078} &:= 1002 \times 23 + 32 \times 2001 = 23046 + 64032 \\ &:= 2003 \times 12 + 21 \times 3002 = 24036 + 63042 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88088} &:= 1001 \times 17 + 71 \times 1001 = 17017 + 71071 \\ &:= 1001 \times 26 + 62 \times 1001 = 26026 + 62062 \\ &:= 1001 \times 35 + 53 \times 1001 = 35035 + 53053 \\ &:= 1001 \times 44 + 44 \times 1001 = 44044 + 44044 \\ &:= 1003 \times 22 + 22 \times 3001 = 22066 + 66022 \\ &:= 1007 \times 11 + 11 \times 7001 = 11077 + 77011 \\ &:= 2002 \times 13 + 31 \times 2002 = 26026 + 62062 \\ &:= 2002 \times 22 + 22 \times 2002 = 44044 + 44044 \\ &:= 2006 \times 11 + 11 \times 6002 = 22066 + 66022 \\ &:= 3005 \times 11 + 11 \times 5003 = 33055 + 55033 \\ &:= 4004 \times 11 + 11 \times 4004 = 44044 + 44044 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{88488} := 2103 \times 12 + 21 \times 3012 = 25236 + 63252$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{89298} &:= 1017 \times 11 + 11 \times 7101 = 11187 + 78111 \\ &:= 1107 \times 11 + 11 \times 7011 = 12177 + 77121 \\ &:= 2013 \times 12 + 21 \times 3102 = 24156 + 65142 \\ &:= 2016 \times 11 + 11 \times 6102 = 22176 + 67122 \\ &:= 2106 \times 11 + 11 \times 6012 = 23166 + 66132 \\ &:= 3015 \times 11 + 11 \times 5103 = 33165 + 56133 \\ &:= 3105 \times 11 + 11 \times 5013 = 34155 + 55143 \\ &:= 4014 \times 11 + 11 \times 4104 = 44154 + 45144 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{89698} := 1102 \times 23 + 32 \times 2011 = 25346 + 64352$$

$$\mathbf{89698} := 2012 \times 31 + 13 \times 2102 = 62372 + 27326$$

$$\mathbf{89898} := 2203 \times 12 + 21 \times 3022 = 26436 + 63462$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{96069} &:= 1002 \times 14 + 41 \times 2001 = 14028 + 82041 \\ &:= 1004 \times 12 + 21 \times 4001 = 12048 + 84021 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{97479} := 1104 \times 12 + 21 \times 4011 = 13248 + 84231$$

$$\mathbf{97879} := 1102 \times 14 + 41 \times 2011 = 15428 + 82451$$

$$98289 := 1014 \times 12 + 21 \times 4101 = 12168 + 86121$$

$$98889 := 1204 \times 12 + 21 \times 4021 = 14448 + 84441$$

$$99099 := 1001 \times 18 + 81 \times 1001 = 18018 + 81081$$

$$:= 1001 \times 27 + 72 \times 1001 = 27027 + 72072$$

$$:= 1001 \times 36 + 63 \times 1001 = 36036 + 63063$$

$$:= 1001 \times 45 + 54 \times 1001 = 45045 + 54054$$

$$:= 1002 \times 33 + 33 \times 2001 = 33066 + 66033$$

$$:= 1008 \times 11 + 11 \times 8001 = 11088 + 88011$$

$$:= 2007 \times 11 + 11 \times 7002 = 22077 + 77022$$

$$:= 3003 \times 12 + 21 \times 3003 = 36036 + 63063$$

$$:= 3006 \times 11 + 11 \times 6003 = 33066 + 66033$$

$$:= 4005 \times 11 + 11 \times 5004 = 44055 + 55044$$

$$99699 := 1114 \times 12 + 21 \times 4111 = 13368 + 86331$$

2.4 Six Digits Palindromic Sum

$$121121 := 1001 \times 29 + 92 \times 1001 = 29029 + 92092$$

$$:= 1001 \times 38 + 83 \times 1001 = 38038 + 83083$$

$$:= 1001 \times 47 + 74 \times 1001 = 47047 + 74074$$

$$:= 1001 \times 56 + 65 \times 1001 = 56056 + 65065$$

$$:= 2009 \times 11 + 11 \times 9002 = 22099 + 99022$$

$$:= 3008 \times 11 + 11 \times 8003 = 33088 + 88033$$

$$:= 4007 \times 11 + 11 \times 7004 = 44077 + 77044$$

$$:= 5006 \times 11 + 11 \times 6005 = 55066 + 66055$$

$$202202 := 1001 \times 101 + 101 \times 1001 = 101101 + 101101$$

$$213312 := 1011 \times 101 + 101 \times 1101 = 102111 + 111201$$

$$220022 := 10001 \times 11 + 11 \times 10001 = 110011 + 110011$$

$$222222 := 10101 \times 11 + 11 \times 10101 = 111111 + 111111$$

$$:= 1001 \times 111 + 111 \times 1001 = 111111 + 111111$$

$$224422 := 10201 \times 11 + 11 \times 10201 = 112211 + 112211$$

$$:= 1021 \times 101 + 101 \times 1201 = 103121 + 121301$$

$$:= 1111 \times 101 + 101 \times 1111 = 112211 + 112211$$

$$226622 := 10301 \times 11 + 11 \times 10301 = 113311 + 113311$$

$$228822 := 10401 \times 11 + 11 \times 10401 = 114411 + 114411$$

$$231132 := 10011 \times 11 + 11 \times 11001 = 110121 + 121011$$

$$233332 := 10111 \times 11 + 11 \times 11101 = 111221 + 122111$$

$$234432 := 1011 \times 111 + 111 \times 1101 = 112221 + 122211$$

$$235532 := 10211 \times 11 + 11 \times 11201 = 112321 + 123211$$

$$:= 1031 \times 101 + 101 \times 1301 = 104131 + 131401$$

$$:= 1121 \times 101 + 101 \times 1211 = 113221 + 122311$$

$$237732 := 10311 \times 11 + 11 \times 11301 = 113421 + 124311$$

$$239932 := 10411 \times 11 + 11 \times 11401 = 114521 + 125411$$

$$242242 := 10021 \times 11 + 11 \times 12001 = 110231 + 132011$$

$$:= 11011 \times 11 + 11 \times 11011 = 121121 + 121121$$

$$:= 1001 \times 121 + 121 \times 1001 = 121121 + 121121$$

$$244442 := 10121 \times 11 + 11 \times 12101 = 111331 + 133111$$

$$:= 11111 \times 11 + 11 \times 11111 = 122221 + 122221$$

$$246642 := 10221 \times 11 + 11 \times 12201 = 112431 + 134211$$

$$:= 11211 \times 11 + 11 \times 11211 = 123321 + 123321$$

$$:= 1021 \times 111 + 111 \times 1201 = 113331 + 133311$$

$$:= 1041 \times 101 + 101 \times 1401 = 105141 + 141501$$

$$:= 1111 \times 111 + 111 \times 1111 = 123321 + 123321$$

$$:= 1131 \times 101 + 101 \times 1311 = 114231 + 132411$$

$$:= 1221 \times 101 + 101 \times 1221 = 123321 + 123321$$

$$248842 := 10321 \times 11 + 11 \times 12301 = 113531 + 135311$$

$$:= 11311 \times 11 + 11 \times 11311 = 124421 + 124421$$

$$253352 := 10031 \times 11 + 11 \times 13001 = 110341 + 143011$$

$$:= 11021 \times 11 + 11 \times 12011 = 121231 + 132121$$

$$255552 := 10131 \times 11 + 11 \times 13101 = 111441 + 144111$$

$$:= 11121 \times 11 + 11 \times 12111 = 122331 + 133221$$

$$:= 1011 \times 121 + 121 \times 1101 = 122331 + 133221$$

$$\begin{aligned}
257752 &:= 10231 \times 11 + 11 \times 13201 = 112541 + 145211 \\
&:= 11221 \times 11 + 11 \times 12211 = 123431 + 134321 \\
&:= 1051 \times 101 + 101 \times 1501 = 106151 + 151601 \\
&:= 1141 \times 101 + 101 \times 1411 = 115241 + 142511 \\
&:= 1231 \times 101 + 101 \times 1321 = 124331 + 133421
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
258852 &:= 1031 \times 111 + 111 \times 1301 = 114441 + 144411 \\
&:= 1121 \times 111 + 111 \times 1211 = 124431 + 134421
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
259952 &:= 10331 \times 11 + 11 \times 13301 = 113641 + 146311 \\
&:= 11321 \times 11 + 11 \times 12311 = 124531 + 135421
\end{aligned}$$

$$262262 := 1001 \times 131 + 131 \times 1001 = 131131 + 131131$$

$$\begin{aligned}
264462 &:= 10041 \times 11 + 11 \times 14001 = 110451 + 154011 \\
&:= 11031 \times 11 + 11 \times 13011 = 121341 + 143121 \\
&:= 12021 \times 11 + 11 \times 12021 = 132231 + 132231
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
266662 &:= 10141 \times 11 + 11 \times 14101 = 111551 + 155111 \\
&:= 11131 \times 11 + 11 \times 13111 = 122441 + 144221 \\
&:= 12121 \times 11 + 11 \times 12121 = 133331 + 133331
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
268862 &:= 10241 \times 11 + 11 \times 14201 = 112651 + 156211 \\
&:= 11231 \times 11 + 11 \times 13211 = 123541 + 145321 \\
&:= 12221 \times 11 + 11 \times 12221 = 134431 + 134431 \\
&:= 1021 \times 121 + 121 \times 1201 = 123541 + 145321 \\
&:= 1061 \times 101 + 101 \times 1601 = 107161 + 161701 \\
&:= 1111 \times 121 + 121 \times 1111 = 134431 + 134431 \\
&:= 1151 \times 101 + 101 \times 1511 = 116251 + 152611 \\
&:= 1241 \times 101 + 101 \times 1421 = 125341 + 143521 \\
&:= 1331 \times 101 + 101 \times 1331 = 134431 + 134431
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
275572 &:= 10051 \times 11 + 11 \times 15001 = 110561 + 165011 \\
&:= 11041 \times 11 + 11 \times 14011 = 121451 + 154121 \\
&:= 12031 \times 11 + 11 \times 13021 = 132341 + 143231
\end{aligned}$$

$$276672 := 1011 \times 131 + 131 \times 1101 = 132441 + 144231$$

$$\begin{aligned}
277772 &:= 10151 \times 11 + 11 \times 15101 = 111661 + 166111 \\
&:= 11141 \times 11 + 11 \times 14111 = 122551 + 155221 \\
&:= 12131 \times 11 + 11 \times 13121 = 133441 + 144331
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
279972 &:= 10251 \times 11 + 11 \times 15201 = 112761 + 167211 \\
&:= 11241 \times 11 + 11 \times 14211 = 123651 + 156321 \\
&:= 12231 \times 11 + 11 \times 13221 = 134541 + 145431 \\
&:= 1071 \times 101 + 101 \times 1701 = 108171 + 171801 \\
&:= 1161 \times 101 + 101 \times 1611 = 117261 + 162711
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 1251 \times 101 + 101 \times 1521 = 126351 + 153621 \\
&:= 1341 \times 101 + 101 \times 1431 = 135441 + 144531
\end{aligned}$$

$$282282 := 1001 \times 141 + 141 \times 1001 = 141141 + 141141$$

$$\begin{aligned}
286682 &:= 10061 \times 11 + 11 \times 16001 = 110671 + 176011 \\
&:= 11051 \times 11 + 11 \times 15011 = 121561 + 165121 \\
&:= 12041 \times 11 + 11 \times 14021 = 132451 + 154231 \\
&:= 13031 \times 11 + 11 \times 13031 = 143341 + 143341
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
288882 &:= 10161 \times 11 + 11 \times 16101 = 111771 + 177111 \\
&:= 11151 \times 11 + 11 \times 15111 = 122661 + 166221 \\
&:= 12141 \times 11 + 11 \times 14121 = 133551 + 155331 \\
&:= 13131 \times 11 + 11 \times 13131 = 144441 + 144441
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
297792 &:= 10071 \times 11 + 11 \times 17001 = 110781 + 187011 \\
&:= 11061 \times 11 + 11 \times 16011 = 121671 + 176121 \\
&:= 12051 \times 11 + 11 \times 15021 = 132561 + 165231 \\
&:= 13041 \times 11 + 11 \times 14031 = 143451 + 154341 \\
&:= 1011 \times 141 + 141 \times 1101 = 142551 + 155241
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
299992 &:= 10171 \times 11 + 11 \times 17101 = 111881 + 188111 \\
&:= 11161 \times 11 + 11 \times 16111 = 122771 + 177221 \\
&:= 12151 \times 11 + 11 \times 15121 = 133661 + 166331 \\
&:= 13141 \times 11 + 11 \times 14131 = 144551 + 155441
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
303303 &:= 1001 \times 102 + 201 \times 1001 = 102102 + 201201 \\
&:= 1002 \times 101 + 101 \times 2001 = 101202 + 202101
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
314413 &:= 1012 \times 101 + 101 \times 2101 = 102212 + 212201 \\
&:= 1102 \times 101 + 101 \times 2011 = 111302 + 203111
\end{aligned}$$

$$315513 := 1011 \times 201 + 102 \times 1101 = 203211 + 112302$$

$$323323 := 1001 \times 112 + 211 \times 1001 = 112112 + 211211$$

$$324423 := 1011 \times 102 + 201 \times 1101 = 103122 + 221301$$

$$\begin{aligned}
325523 &:= 1022 \times 101 + 101 \times 2201 = 103222 + 222301 \\
&:= 1112 \times 101 + 101 \times 2111 = 112312 + 213211 \\
&:= 1202 \times 101 + 101 \times 2021 = 121402 + 204121 \\
327723 &:= 1021 \times 201 + 102 \times 1201 = 205221 + 122502 \\
330033 &:= 10001 \times 12 + 21 \times 10001 = 120012 + 210021 \\
&:= 10002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20001 = 110022 + 220011 \\
332233 &:= 10102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20101 = 111122 + 221111 \\
333333 &:= 10101 \times 12 + 21 \times 10101 = 121212 + 212121 \\
&:= 1002 \times 111 + 111 \times 2001 = 111222 + 222111 \\
334433 &:= 10202 \times 11 + 11 \times 20201 = 112222 + 222211 \\
336633 &:= 10201 \times 12 + 21 \times 10201 = 122412 + 214221 \\
&:= 10302 \times 11 + 11 \times 20301 = 113322 + 223311 \\
&:= 1011 \times 211 + 112 \times 1101 = 213321 + 123312 \\
&:= 1032 \times 101 + 101 \times 2301 = 104232 + 232401 \\
&:= 1111 \times 102 + 201 \times 1111 = 113322 + 223311 \\
&:= 1122 \times 101 + 101 \times 2211 = 113322 + 223311 \\
&:= 1212 \times 101 + 101 \times 2121 = 122412 + 214221 \\
&:= 1302 \times 101 + 101 \times 2031 = 131502 + 205131 \\
338833 &:= 10402 \times 11 + 11 \times 20401 = 114422 + 224411 \\
339933 &:= 10301 \times 12 + 21 \times 10301 = 123612 + 216321 \\
&:= 1031 \times 201 + 102 \times 1301 = 207231 + 132702 \\
341143 &:= 10012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21001 = 110132 + 231011 \\
&:= 11002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20011 = 121022 + 220121 \\
342243 &:= 10011 \times 21 + 12 \times 11001 = 210231 + 132012 \\
343343 &:= 10112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21101 = 111232 + 232111 \\
&:= 11102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20111 = 122122 + 221221 \\
&:= 1001 \times 122 + 221 \times 1001 = 122122 + 221221 \\
345543 &:= 10111 \times 21 + 12 \times 11101 = 212331 + 133212 \\
&:= 10212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21201 = 112332 + 233211 \\
&:= 1011 \times 112 + 211 \times 1101 = 113232 + 232311 \\
&:= 1012 \times 111 + 111 \times 2101 = 112332 + 233211 \\
&:= 1021 \times 102 + 201 \times 1201 = 104142 + 241401 \\
&:= 1102 \times 111 + 111 \times 2011 = 122322 + 223221 \\
347743 &:= 10312 \times 11 + 11 \times 21301 = 113432 + 234311 \\
&:= 11302 \times 11 + 11 \times 20311 = 124322 + 223421 \\
&:= 1042 \times 101 + 101 \times 2401 = 105242 + 242501 \\
&:= 1132 \times 101 + 101 \times 2311 = 114332 + 233411 \\
&:= 1222 \times 101 + 101 \times 2221 = 123422 + 224321 \\
&:= 1312 \times 101 + 101 \times 2131 = 132512 + 215231 \\
&:= 1402 \times 101 + 101 \times 2041 = 141602 + 206141 \\
348843 &:= 10211 \times 21 + 12 \times 11201 = 214431 + 134412 \\
&:= 1121 \times 201 + 102 \times 1211 = 225321 + 123522 \\
349943 &:= 10412 \times 11 + 11 \times 21401 = 114532 + 235411 \\
&:= 11402 \times 11 + 11 \times 20411 = 125422 + 224521 \\
&:= 1021 \times 211 + 112 \times 1201 = 215431 + 134512 \\
351153 &:= 10011 \times 12 + 21 \times 11001 = 120132 + 231021 \\
352253 &:= 10022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22001 = 110242 + 242011 \\
&:= 11012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21011 = 121132 + 231121 \\
&:= 12002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20021 = 132022 + 220231 \\
354453 &:= 10021 \times 21 + 12 \times 12001 = 210441 + 144012 \\
&:= 10111 \times 12 + 21 \times 11101 = 121332 + 233121 \\
&:= 10122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22101 = 111342 + 243111 \\
&:= 11112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21111 = 122232 + 232221 \\
&:= 12102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20121 = 133122 + 221331 \\
356653 &:= 10222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22201 = 112442 + 244211 \\
&:= 11212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21211 = 123332 + 233321 \\
&:= 12202 \times 11 + 11 \times 20221 = 134222 + 222431 \\
357753 &:= 10121 \times 21 + 12 \times 12101 = 212541 + 145212 \\
&:= 10211 \times 12 + 21 \times 11201 = 122532 + 235221 \\
&:= 1011 \times 221 + 122 \times 1101 = 223431 + 134322
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1022 \times 111 + 111 \times 2201 = 113442 + 244311 \\ &:= 1112 \times 111 + 111 \times 2111 = 123432 + 234321 \\ &:= 1121 \times 102 + 201 \times 1211 = 114342 + 243411 \\ &:= 1202 \times 111 + 111 \times 2021 = 133422 + 224331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{358853} &:= 10322 \times 11 + 11 \times 22301 = 113542 + 245311 \\ &:= 11312 \times 11 + 11 \times 21311 = 124432 + 234421 \\ &:= 12302 \times 11 + 11 \times 20321 = 135322 + 223531 \\ &:= 1052 \times 101 + 101 \times 2501 = 106252 + 252601 \\ &:= 1111 \times 112 + 211 \times 1111 = 124432 + 234421 \\ &:= 1142 \times 101 + 101 \times 2411 = 115342 + 243511 \\ &:= 1232 \times 101 + 101 \times 2321 = 124432 + 234421 \\ &:= 1322 \times 101 + 101 \times 2231 = 133522 + 225331 \\ &:= 1412 \times 101 + 101 \times 2141 = 142612 + 216241 \\ &:= 1502 \times 101 + 101 \times 2051 = 151702 + 207151 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{363363} &:= 10032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23001 = 110352 + 253011 \\ &:= 11011 \times 12 + 21 \times 11011 = 132132 + 231231 \\ &:= 11022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22011 = 121242 + 242121 \\ &:= 12012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21021 = 132132 + 231231 \\ &:= 13002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20031 = 143022 + 220341 \\ &:= 1001 \times 132 + 231 \times 1001 = 132132 + 231231 \\ &:= 1002 \times 121 + 121 \times 2001 = 121242 + 242121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{365563} &:= 10132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23101 = 111452 + 254111 \\ &:= 11122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22111 = 122342 + 243221 \\ &:= 12112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21121 = 133232 + 232331 \\ &:= 13102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20131 = 144122 + 221441 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366663} &:= 10031 \times 21 + 12 \times 13001 = 210651 + 156012 \\ &:= 11111 \times 12 + 21 \times 11111 = 133332 + 233331 \\ &:= 1011 \times 122 + 221 \times 1101 = 123342 + 243321 \\ &:= 1031 \times 102 + 201 \times 1301 = 105162 + 261501 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{367763} &:= 10232 \times 11 + 11 \times 23201 = 112552 + 255211 \\ &:= 11222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22211 = 123442 + 244321 \\ &:= 12212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21221 = 134332 + 233431 \\ &:= 13202 \times 11 + 11 \times 20231 = 145222 + 222541 \\ &:= 1021 \times 112 + 211 \times 1201 = 114352 + 253411 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{369963} := 10131 \times 21 + 12 \times 13101 = 212751 + 157212$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10332 \times 11 + 11 \times 23301 = 113652 + 256311 \\ &:= 11211 \times 12 + 21 \times 11211 = 134532 + 235431 \\ &:= 11322 \times 11 + 11 \times 22311 = 124542 + 245421 \\ &:= 12312 \times 11 + 11 \times 21321 = 135432 + 234531 \\ &:= 13302 \times 11 + 11 \times 20331 = 146322 + 223641 \\ &:= 1032 \times 111 + 111 \times 2301 = 114552 + 255411 \\ &:= 1062 \times 101 + 101 \times 2601 = 107262 + 262701 \\ &:= 1122 \times 111 + 111 \times 2211 = 124542 + 245421 \\ &:= 1152 \times 101 + 101 \times 2511 = 116352 + 253611 \\ &:= 1212 \times 111 + 111 \times 2121 = 134532 + 235431 \\ &:= 1221 \times 102 + 201 \times 1221 = 124542 + 245421 \\ &:= 1302 \times 111 + 111 \times 2031 = 144522 + 225441 \\ &:= 1332 \times 101 + 101 \times 2331 = 134532 + 235431 \\ &:= 1422 \times 101 + 101 \times 2241 = 143622 + 226341 \\ &:= 1512 \times 101 + 101 \times 2151 = 152712 + 217251 \\ &:= 1602 \times 101 + 101 \times 2061 = 161802 + 208161 \\ &:= 2421 \times 101 + 101 \times 1242 = 244521 + 125442 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{372273} := 10021 \times 12 + 21 \times 12001 = 120252 + 252021$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{374473} &:= 10042 \times 11 + 11 \times 24001 = 110462 + 264011 \\ &:= 11032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23011 = 121352 + 253121 \\ &:= 12022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22021 = 132242 + 242231 \\ &:= 13012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21031 = 143132 + 231341 \\ &:= 14002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20041 = 154022 + 220451 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{375573} &:= 10121 \times 12 + 21 \times 12101 = 121452 + 254121 \\ &:= 11021 \times 21 + 12 \times 12011 = 231441 + 144132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{376673} &:= 10142 \times 11 + 11 \times 24101 = 111562 + 265111 \\ &:= 11132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23111 = 122452 + 254221 \\ &:= 12122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22121 = 133342 + 243331 \\ &:= 13112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21131 = 144232 + 232441 \\ &:= 14102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20141 = 155122 + 221551 \\ &:= 1012 \times 121 + 121 \times 2101 = 122452 + 254221 \\ &:= 1102 \times 121 + 121 \times 2011 = 133342 + 243331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{378873} &:= 10041 \times 21 + 12 \times 14001 = 210861 + 168012 \\ &:= 10221 \times 12 + 21 \times 12201 = 122652 + 256221 \\ &:= 10242 \times 11 + 11 \times 24201 = 112662 + 266211 \\ &:= 11121 \times 21 + 12 \times 12111 = 233541 + 145332 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 11232 \times 11 + 11 \times 23211 = 123552 + 255321$$

$$:= 12222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22221 = 134442 + 244431$$

$$:= 13212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21231 = 145332 + 233541$$

$$:= 14202 \times 11 + 11 \times 20241 = 156222 + 222651$$

$$:= 1011 \times 231 + 132 \times 1101 = 233541 + 145332$$

$$:= 1131 \times 102 + 201 \times 1311 = 115362 + 263511$$

$$\mathbf{383383} := 1001 \times 142 + 241 \times 1001 = 142142 + 241241$$

$$\mathbf{384483} := 11021 \times 12 + 21 \times 12011 = 132252 + 252231$$

$$\mathbf{385583} := 10052 \times 11 + 11 \times 25001 = 110572 + 275011$$

$$:= 11042 \times 11 + 11 \times 24011 = 121462 + 264121$$

$$:= 12032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23021 = 132352 + 253231$$

$$:= 13022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22031 = 143242 + 242341$$

$$:= 14012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21041 = 154132 + 231451$$

$$:= 15002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20051 = 165022 + 220561$$

$$\mathbf{387783} := 10152 \times 11 + 11 \times 25101 = 111672 + 276111$$

$$:= 11031 \times 21 + 12 \times 13011 = 231651 + 156132$$

$$:= 11121 \times 12 + 21 \times 12111 = 133452 + 254331$$

$$:= 11142 \times 11 + 11 \times 24111 = 122562 + 265221$$

$$:= 12132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23121 = 133452 + 254331$$

$$:= 13122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22131 = 144342 + 243441$$

$$:= 14112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21141 = 155232 + 232551$$

$$:= 15102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20151 = 166122 + 221661$$

$$:= 1011 \times 132 + 231 \times 1101 = 133452 + 254331$$

$$:= 1041 \times 102 + 201 \times 1401 = 106182 + 281601$$

$$\mathbf{389983} := 10252 \times 11 + 11 \times 25201 = 112772 + 277211$$

$$:= 11242 \times 11 + 11 \times 24211 = 123662 + 266321$$

$$:= 12232 \times 11 + 11 \times 23221 = 134552 + 255431$$

$$:= 13222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22231 = 145442 + 244541$$

$$:= 14212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21241 = 156332 + 233651$$

$$:= 15202 \times 11 + 11 \times 20251 = 167222 + 222761$$

$$:= 1021 \times 122 + 221 \times 1201 = 124562 + 265421$$

$$:= 1022 \times 121 + 121 \times 2201 = 123662 + 266321$$

$$:= 1031 \times 112 + 211 \times 1301 = 115472 + 274511$$

$$:= 1112 \times 121 + 121 \times 2111 = 134552 + 255431$$

$$:= 1202 \times 121 + 121 \times 2021 = 145442 + 244541$$

$$\mathbf{393393} := 10031 \times 12 + 21 \times 13001 = 120372 + 273021$$

$$:= 1002 \times 131 + 131 \times 2001 = 131262 + 262131$$

$$\mathbf{396693} := 10062 \times 11 + 11 \times 26001 = 110682 + 286011$$

$$:= 10131 \times 12 + 21 \times 13101 = 121572 + 275121$$

$$:= 11052 \times 11 + 11 \times 25011 = 121572 + 275121$$

$$:= 12021 \times 12 + 21 \times 12021 = 144252 + 252441$$

$$:= 12042 \times 11 + 11 \times 24021 = 132462 + 264231$$

$$:= 13032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23031 = 143352 + 253341$$

$$:= 14022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22041 = 154242 + 242451$$

$$:= 15012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21051 = 165132 + 231561$$

$$:= 16002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20061 = 176022 + 220671$$

$$\mathbf{398893} := 10162 \times 11 + 11 \times 26101 = 111782 + 287111$$

$$:= 11152 \times 11 + 11 \times 25111 = 122672 + 276221$$

$$:= 12142 \times 11 + 11 \times 24121 = 133562 + 265331$$

$$:= 13132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23131 = 144452 + 254441$$

$$:= 14122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22141 = 155342 + 243551$$

$$:= 15112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21151 = 166232 + 232661$$

$$:= 16102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20161 = 177122 + 221771$$

$$\mathbf{399993} := 10231 \times 12 + 21 \times 13201 = 122772 + 277221$$

$$:= 11041 \times 21 + 12 \times 14011 = 231861 + 168132$$

$$:= 12121 \times 12 + 21 \times 12121 = 145452 + 254541$$

$$:= 1011 \times 241 + 142 \times 1101 = 243651 + 156342$$

$$:= 1141 \times 102 + 201 \times 1411 = 116382 + 283611$$

$$\mathbf{404404} := 1001 \times 103 + 301 \times 1001 = 103103 + 301301$$

$$:= 1001 \times 202 + 202 \times 1001 = 202202 + 202202$$

$$:= 1003 \times 101 + 101 \times 3001 = 101303 + 303101$$

$$:= 2002 \times 101 + 101 \times 2002 = 202202 + 202202$$

$$\mathbf{405504} := 1002 \times 201 + 102 \times 2001 = 201402 + 204102$$

$$\mathbf{415514} := 1013 \times 101 + 101 \times 3101 = 102313 + 313201$$

$$:= 1103 \times 101 + 101 \times 3011 = 111403 + 304111$$

$$:= 2012 \times 101 + 101 \times 2102 = 203212 + 212302$$

$$\mathbf{417714} := 1011 \times 301 + 103 \times 1101 = 304311 + 113403$$

$$:= 1012 \times 201 + 102 \times 2101 = 203412 + 214302$$

$$\mathbf{424424} := 1001 \times 113 + 311 \times 1001 = 113113 + 311311$$

$$:= 1001 \times 212 + 212 \times 1001 = 212212 + 212212$$

$$:= 2002 \times 111 + 111 \times 2002 = 222222 + 222222$$

$$**426624** := 1011 \times 202 + 202 \times 1101 = 204222 + 222402$$

$$**446644** := 10303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30301 = 113333 + 333311$$

$$:= 1023 \times 101 + 101 \times 3201 = 103323 + 323301$$

$$:= 20302 \times 11 + 11 \times 20302 = 223322 + 223322$$

$$:= 1101 \times 202 + 202 \times 1011 = 222402 + 204222$$

$$**447744** := 1011 \times 212 + 212 \times 1101 = 214332 + 233412$$

$$:= 1102 \times 201 + 102 \times 2011 = 221502 + 205122$$

$$:= 1202 \times 201 + 102 \times 2021 = 241602 + 206142$$

$$:= 1113 \times 101 + 101 \times 3111 = 112413 + 314211$$

$$:= 1203 \times 101 + 101 \times 3021 = 121503 + 305121$$

$$**448844** := 10201 \times 13 + 31 \times 10201 = 132613 + 316231$$

$$:= 2022 \times 101 + 101 \times 2202 = 204222 + 222402$$

$$:= 10201 \times 22 + 22 \times 10201 = 224422 + 224422$$

$$:= 2112 \times 101 + 101 \times 2112 = 213312 + 213312$$

$$:= 10403 \times 11 + 11 \times 30401 = 114433 + 334411$$

$$**429924** := 1022 \times 201 + 102 \times 2201 = 205422 + 224502$$

$$:= 20402 \times 11 + 11 \times 20402 = 224422 + 224422$$

$$:= 1012 \times 211 + 112 \times 2101 = 213532 + 235312$$

$$**435534** := 1002 \times 211 + 112 \times 2001 = 211422 + 224112$$

$$:= 1021 \times 202 + 202 \times 1201 = 206242 + 242602$$

$$:= 1011 \times 103 + 301 \times 1101 = 104133 + 331401$$

$$:= 1043 \times 101 + 101 \times 3401 = 105343 + 343501$$

$$:= 1111 \times 103 + 301 \times 1111 = 114433 + 334411$$

$$**437734** := 1033 \times 101 + 101 \times 3301 = 104333 + 333401$$

$$:= 1111 \times 202 + 202 \times 1111 = 224422 + 224422$$

$$:= 1123 \times 101 + 101 \times 3211 = 113423 + 324311$$

$$:= 1133 \times 101 + 101 \times 3311 = 114433 + 334411$$

$$:= 1213 \times 101 + 101 \times 3121 = 122513 + 315221$$

$$:= 1223 \times 101 + 101 \times 3221 = 123523 + 325321$$

$$:= 1303 \times 101 + 101 \times 3031 = 131603 + 306131$$

$$:= 1313 \times 101 + 101 \times 3131 = 132613 + 316231$$

$$:= 2032 \times 101 + 101 \times 2302 = 205232 + 232502$$

$$:= 1403 \times 101 + 101 \times 3041 = 141703 + 307141$$

$$:= 2122 \times 101 + 101 \times 2212 = 214322 + 223412$$

$$:= 2042 \times 101 + 101 \times 2402 = 206242 + 242602$$

$$:= 2132 \times 101 + 101 \times 2312 = 215332 + 233512$$

$$**438834** := 1011 \times 311 + 113 \times 1101 = 314421 + 124413$$

$$:= 2222 \times 101 + 101 \times 2222 = 224422 + 224422$$

$$:= 1112 \times 201 + 102 \times 2111 = 223512 + 215322$$

$$**450054** := 10002 \times 21 + 12 \times 20001 = 210042 + 240012$$

$$**440044** := 10001 \times 13 + 31 \times 10001 = 130013 + 310031$$

$$:= 10001 \times 22 + 22 \times 10001 = 220022 + 220022$$

$$**451154** := 10013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31001 = 110143 + 341011$$

$$:= 10003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30001 = 110033 + 330011$$

$$:= 11003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30011 = 121033 + 330121$$

$$:= 20002 \times 11 + 11 \times 20002 = 220022 + 220022$$

$$:= 20012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21002 = 220132 + 231022$$

$$**442244** := 10103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30101 = 111133 + 331111$$

$$:= 20102 \times 11 + 11 \times 20102 = 221122 + 221122$$

$$**453354** := 10011 \times 31 + 13 \times 11001 = 310341 + 143013$$

$$:= 10102 \times 21 + 12 \times 20101 = 212142 + 241212$$

$$:= 10113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31101 = 111243 + 342111$$

$$**444444** := 10101 \times 13 + 31 \times 10101 = 131313 + 313131$$

$$:= 10101 \times 22 + 22 \times 10101 = 222222 + 222222$$

$$:= 11103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30111 = 122133 + 331221$$

$$:= 10203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30201 = 112233 + 332211$$

$$:= 20112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21102 = 221232 + 232122$$

$$:= 20202 \times 11 + 11 \times 20202 = 222222 + 222222$$

$$**455554** := 10213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31201 = 112343 + 343211$$

$$:= 1001 \times 123 + 321 \times 1001 = 123123 + 321321$$

$$:= 11203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30211 = 123233 + 332321$$

$$:= 1001 \times 222 + 222 \times 1001 = 222222 + 222222$$

$$:= 20212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21202 = 222332 + 233222$$

$$:= 1003 \times 111 + 111 \times 3001 = 111333 + 333111$$

$$\begin{aligned}
456654 &:= 10202 \times 21 + 12 \times 20201 = 214242 + 242412 \\
&:= 1011 \times 113 + 311 \times 1101 = 114243 + 342411 \\
&:= 1013 \times 111 + 111 \times 3101 = 112443 + 344211 \\
&:= 1103 \times 111 + 111 \times 3011 = 122433 + 334221 \\
&:= 2012 \times 111 + 111 \times 2102 = 223332 + 233322
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
457754 &:= 10111 \times 31 + 13 \times 11101 = 313441 + 144313 \\
&:= 10313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31301 = 113443 + 344311 \\
&:= 11303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30311 = 124333 + 333421 \\
&:= 20312 \times 11 + 11 \times 21302 = 223432 + 234322 \\
&:= 1102 \times 211 + 112 \times 2011 = 232522 + 225232
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
459954 &:= 1011 \times 321 + 123 \times 1101 = 324531 + 135423 \\
&:= 10302 \times 21 + 12 \times 20301 = 216342 + 243612 \\
&:= 10413 \times 11 + 11 \times 31401 = 114543 + 345411 \\
&:= 11403 \times 11 + 11 \times 30411 = 125433 + 334521 \\
&:= 20412 \times 11 + 11 \times 21402 = 224532 + 235422 \\
&:= 1053 \times 101 + 101 \times 3501 = 106353 + 353601 \\
&:= 1143 \times 101 + 101 \times 3411 = 115443 + 344511 \\
&:= 1212 \times 201 + 102 \times 2121 = 243612 + 216342 \\
&:= 1233 \times 101 + 101 \times 3321 = 124533 + 335421 \\
&:= 1323 \times 101 + 101 \times 3231 = 133623 + 326331 \\
&:= 1413 \times 101 + 101 \times 3141 = 142713 + 317241 \\
&:= 1503 \times 101 + 101 \times 3051 = 151803 + 308151 \\
&:= 2052 \times 101 + 101 \times 2502 = 207252 + 252702 \\
&:= 2142 \times 101 + 101 \times 2412 = 216342 + 243612 \\
&:= 2232 \times 101 + 101 \times 2322 = 225432 + 234522
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
462264 &:= 10011 \times 22 + 22 \times 11001 = 220242 + 242022 \\
&:= 10012 \times 21 + 12 \times 21001 = 210252 + 252012 \\
&:= 10023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32001 = 110253 + 352011 \\
&:= 11013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31011 = 121143 + 341121 \\
&:= 12003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30021 = 132033 + 330231 \\
&:= 20022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22002 = 220242 + 242022 \\
&:= 21012 \times 11 + 11 \times 21012 = 231132 + 231132
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
464464 &:= 10123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32101 = 111353 + 353111 \\
&:= 11113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31111 = 122243 + 342221 \\
&:= 12103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30121 = 133133 + 331331 \\
&:= 20122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22102 = 221342 + 243122 \\
&:= 21112 \times 11 + 11 \times 21112 = 232232 + 232232
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 1001 \times 133 + 331 \times 1001 = 133133 + 331331 \\
&:= 1001 \times 232 + 232 \times 1001 = 232232 + 232232
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
465564 &:= 10112 \times 21 + 12 \times 21101 = 212352 + 253212 \\
&:= 1002 \times 221 + 122 \times 2001 = 221442 + 244122
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
466664 &:= 10021 \times 31 + 13 \times 12001 = 310651 + 156013 \\
&:= 10111 \times 22 + 22 \times 11101 = 222442 + 244222 \\
&:= 10223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32201 = 112453 + 354211 \\
&:= 11213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31211 = 123343 + 343321 \\
&:= 12203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30221 = 134233 + 332431 \\
&:= 20222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22202 = 222442 + 244222 \\
&:= 21212 \times 11 + 11 \times 21212 = 233332 + 233332 \\
&:= 1021 \times 103 + 301 \times 1201 = 105163 + 361501
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
468864 &:= 10323 \times 11 + 11 \times 32301 = 113553 + 355311 \\
&:= 11313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31311 = 124443 + 344421 \\
&:= 12303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30321 = 135333 + 333531 \\
&:= 20322 \times 11 + 11 \times 22302 = 223542 + 245322 \\
&:= 21312 \times 11 + 11 \times 21312 = 234432 + 234432 \\
&:= 10212 \times 21 + 12 \times 21201 = 214452 + 254412 \\
&:= 1011 \times 222 + 222 \times 1101 = 224442 + 244422 \\
&:= 1023 \times 111 + 111 \times 3201 = 113553 + 355311 \\
&:= 1113 \times 111 + 111 \times 3111 = 123543 + 345321 \\
&:= 1203 \times 111 + 111 \times 3021 = 133533 + 335331 \\
&:= 1302 \times 201 + 102 \times 2031 = 261702 + 207162 \\
&:= 2022 \times 111 + 111 \times 2202 = 224442 + 244422 \\
&:= 2112 \times 111 + 111 \times 2112 = 234432 + 234432
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
471174 &:= 10011 \times 13 + 31 \times 11001 = 130143 + 341031 \\
&:= 11002 \times 21 + 12 \times 20011 = 231042 + 240132
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
473374 &:= 10033 \times 11 + 11 \times 33001 = 110363 + 363011 \\
&:= 11023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32011 = 121253 + 352121 \\
&:= 12013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31021 = 132143 + 341231 \\
&:= 13003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30031 = 143033 + 330341 \\
&:= 20032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23002 = 220352 + 253022 \\
&:= 21022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22012 = 231242 + 242132
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
474474 &:= 10022 \times 21 + 12 \times 22001 = 210462 + 264012 \\
&:= 11102 \times 21 + 12 \times 20111 = 233142 + 241332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
475574 &:= 10111 \times 13 + 31 \times 11101 = 131443 + 344131 \\
&:= 10133 \times 11 + 11 \times 33101 = 111463 + 364111 \\
&:= 11123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32111 = 122353 + 353221 \\
&:= 12113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31121 = 133243 + 342331 \\
&:= 13103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30131 = 144133 + 331441 \\
&:= 20132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23102 = 221452 + 254122 \\
&:= 21122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22112 = 232342 + 243232 \\
477774 &:= 10122 \times 21 + 12 \times 22101 = 212562 + 265212 \\
&:= 10233 \times 11 + 11 \times 33201 = 112563 + 365211 \\
&:= 11202 \times 21 + 12 \times 20211 = 235242 + 242532 \\
&:= 11223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32211 = 123453 + 354321 \\
&:= 12213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31221 = 134343 + 343431 \\
&:= 13203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30231 = 145233 + 332541 \\
&:= 20232 \times 11 + 11 \times 23202 = 222552 + 255222 \\
&:= 21222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22212 = 233442 + 244332 \\
&:= 1011 \times 123 + 321 \times 1101 = 124353 + 353421 \\
479974 &:= 10031 \times 31 + 13 \times 13001 = 310961 + 169013 \\
&:= 10211 \times 13 + 31 \times 11201 = 132743 + 347231 \\
&:= 10333 \times 11 + 11 \times 33301 = 113663 + 366311 \\
&:= 11323 \times 11 + 11 \times 32311 = 124553 + 355421 \\
&:= 12313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31321 = 135443 + 344531 \\
&:= 13303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30331 = 146333 + 333641 \\
&:= 20332 \times 11 + 11 \times 23302 = 223652 + 256322 \\
&:= 21322 \times 11 + 11 \times 22312 = 234542 + 245432 \\
&:= 1012 \times 221 + 122 \times 2101 = 223652 + 256322 \\
&:= 1121 \times 103 + 301 \times 1211 = 115463 + 364511 \\
&:= 1202 \times 211 + 112 \times 2021 = 253622 + 226352 \\
483384 &:= 11012 \times 21 + 12 \times 21011 = 231252 + 252132 \\
484484 &:= 10021 \times 22 + 22 \times 12001 = 220462 + 264022 \\
&:= 10043 \times 11 + 11 \times 34001 = 110473 + 374011 \\
&:= 11011 \times 13 + 31 \times 11011 = 143143 + 341341 \\
&:= 11011 \times 22 + 22 \times 11011 = 242242 + 242242 \\
&:= 11033 \times 11 + 11 \times 33011 = 121363 + 363121 \\
&:= 12023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32021 = 132253 + 352231 \\
&:= 13013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31031 = 143143 + 341341 \\
&:= 14003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30041 = 154033 + 330451 \\
&:= 20042 \times 11 + 11 \times 24002 = 220462 + 264022 \\
&:= 21032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23012 = 231352 + 253132 \\
&:= 22022 \times 11 + 11 \times 22022 = 242242 + 242242 \\
&:= 1001 \times 143 + 341 \times 1001 = 143143 + 341341 \\
&:= 1001 \times 242 + 242 \times 1001 = 242242 + 242242 \\
&:= 1003 \times 121 + 121 \times 3001 = 121363 + 363121 \\
&:= 2002 \times 121 + 121 \times 2002 = 242242 + 242242 \\
486684 &:= 10032 \times 21 + 12 \times 23001 = 210672 + 276012 \\
&:= 10143 \times 11 + 11 \times 34101 = 111573 + 375111 \\
&:= 11112 \times 21 + 12 \times 21111 = 233352 + 253332 \\
&:= 11133 \times 11 + 11 \times 33111 = 122463 + 364221 \\
&:= 12123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32121 = 133353 + 353331 \\
&:= 13113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31131 = 144243 + 342441 \\
&:= 14103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30141 = 155133 + 331551 \\
&:= 20142 \times 11 + 11 \times 24102 = 221562 + 265122 \\
&:= 21132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23112 = 232452 + 254232 \\
&:= 22122 \times 11 + 11 \times 22122 = 243342 + 243342 \\
488884 &:= 10121 \times 22 + 22 \times 12101 = 222662 + 266222 \\
&:= 10243 \times 11 + 11 \times 34201 = 112673 + 376211 \\
&:= 11111 \times 13 + 31 \times 11111 = 144443 + 344441 \\
&:= 11111 \times 22 + 22 \times 11111 = 244442 + 244442 \\
&:= 11233 \times 11 + 11 \times 33211 = 123563 + 365321 \\
&:= 12223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32221 = 134453 + 354431 \\
&:= 13213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31231 = 145343 + 343541 \\
&:= 14203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30241 = 156233 + 332651 \\
&:= 20242 \times 11 + 11 \times 24202 = 222662 + 266222 \\
&:= 21232 \times 11 + 11 \times 23212 = 233552 + 255332 \\
&:= 22222 \times 11 + 11 \times 22222 = 244442 + 244442 \\
&:= 1021 \times 113 + 311 \times 1201 = 115373 + 373511 \\
&:= 1102 \times 221 + 122 \times 2011 = 243542 + 245342 \\
489984 &:= 10132 \times 21 + 12 \times 23101 = 212772 + 277212 \\
&:= 11212 \times 21 + 12 \times 21211 = 235452 + 254532 \\
&:= 1011 \times 232 + 232 \times 1101 = 234552 + 255432 \\
&:= 1402 \times 201 + 102 \times 2041 = 281802 + 208182 \\
492294 &:= 12002 \times 21 + 12 \times 20021 = 252042 + 240252 \\
495594 &:= 10053 \times 11 + 11 \times 35001 = 110583 + 385011
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 11022 \times 21 + 12 \times 22011 = 231462 + 264132 \\ &:= 11043 \times 11 + 11 \times 34011 = 121473 + 374121 \\ &:= 12033 \times 11 + 11 \times 33021 = 132363 + 363231 \\ &:= 12102 \times 21 + 12 \times 20121 = 254142 + 241452 \\ &:= 13023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32031 = 143253 + 352341 \\ &:= 14013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31041 = 154143 + 341451 \\ &:= 15003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30051 = 165033 + 330561 \\ &:= 20052 \times 11 + 11 \times 25002 = 220572 + 275022 \\ &:= 21042 \times 11 + 11 \times 24012 = 231462 + 264132 \\ &:= 22032 \times 11 + 11 \times 23022 = 242352 + 253242 \\ &:= 1002 \times 231 + 132 \times 2001 = 231462 + 264132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{497794} &:= 10153 \times 11 + 11 \times 35101 = 111683 + 386111 \\ &:= 11021 \times 31 + 13 \times 12011 = 341651 + 156143 \\ &:= 11143 \times 11 + 11 \times 34111 = 122573 + 375221 \\ &:= 12133 \times 11 + 11 \times 33121 = 133463 + 364331 \\ &:= 13123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32131 = 144353 + 353441 \\ &:= 14113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31141 = 155243 + 342551 \\ &:= 15103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30151 = 166133 + 331661 \\ &:= 20152 \times 11 + 11 \times 25102 = 221672 + 276122 \\ &:= 21142 \times 11 + 11 \times 24112 = 232562 + 265232 \\ &:= 22132 \times 11 + 11 \times 23122 = 243452 + 254342 \\ &:= 1013 \times 121 + 121 \times 3101 = 122573 + 375221 \\ &:= 1031 \times 103 + 301 \times 1301 = 106193 + 391601 \\ &:= 1103 \times 121 + 121 \times 3011 = 133463 + 364331 \\ &:= 2012 \times 121 + 121 \times 2102 = 243452 + 254342 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{498894} &:= 10042 \times 21 + 12 \times 24001 = 210882 + 288012 \\ &:= 11122 \times 21 + 12 \times 22111 = 233562 + 265332 \\ &:= 12202 \times 21 + 12 \times 20221 = 256242 + 242652 \\ &:= 1011 \times 133 + 331 \times 1101 = 134463 + 364431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{499994} &:= 10253 \times 11 + 11 \times 35201 = 112783 + 387211 \\ &:= 11243 \times 11 + 11 \times 34211 = 123673 + 376321 \\ &:= 12233 \times 11 + 11 \times 33221 = 134563 + 365431 \\ &:= 13223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32231 = 145453 + 354541 \\ &:= 14213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31241 = 156343 + 343651 \\ &:= 15203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30251 = 167233 + 332761 \\ &:= 20252 \times 11 + 11 \times 25202 = 222772 + 277222 \\ &:= 21242 \times 11 + 11 \times 24212 = 233662 + 266332 \\ &:= 22232 \times 11 + 11 \times 23222 = 244552 + 255442 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{504405} := 1002 \times 102 + 201 \times 2001 = 102204 + 402201$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{505505} &:= 1001 \times 104 + 401 \times 1001 = 104104 + 401401 \\ &:= 1001 \times 203 + 302 \times 1001 = 203203 + 302302 \\ &:= 1004 \times 101 + 101 \times 4001 = 101404 + 404101 \\ &:= 2003 \times 101 + 101 \times 3002 = 202303 + 303202 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{507705} &:= 1002 \times 301 + 103 \times 2001 = 301602 + 206103 \\ &:= 1003 \times 201 + 102 \times 3001 = 201603 + 306102 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{516615} &:= 1014 \times 101 + 101 \times 4101 = 102414 + 414201 \\ &:= 1102 \times 102 + 201 \times 2011 = 112404 + 404211 \\ &:= 1104 \times 101 + 101 \times 4011 = 111504 + 405111 \\ &:= 2013 \times 101 + 101 \times 3102 = 203313 + 313302 \\ &:= 2103 \times 101 + 101 \times 3012 = 212403 + 304212 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{519915} &:= 1011 \times 401 + 104 \times 1101 = 405411 + 114504 \\ &:= 1013 \times 201 + 102 \times 3101 = 203613 + 316302 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{525525} &:= 1001 \times 114 + 411 \times 1001 = 114114 + 411411 \\ &:= 1001 \times 213 + 312 \times 1001 = 213213 + 312312 \\ &:= 1012 \times 102 + 201 \times 2101 = 103224 + 422301 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{527725} &:= 1024 \times 101 + 101 \times 4201 = 103424 + 424301 \\ &:= 1114 \times 101 + 101 \times 4111 = 112514 + 415211 \\ &:= 1204 \times 101 + 101 \times 4021 = 121604 + 406121 \\ &:= 2023 \times 101 + 101 \times 3202 = 204323 + 323402 \\ &:= 2113 \times 101 + 101 \times 3112 = 213413 + 314312 \\ &:= 2203 \times 101 + 101 \times 3022 = 222503 + 305222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{528825} &:= 1011 \times 302 + 203 \times 1101 = 305322 + 223503 \\ &:= 1103 \times 201 + 102 \times 3011 = 221703 + 307122 \\ &:= 1202 \times 102 + 201 \times 2021 = 122604 + 406221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{534435} := 1002 \times 112 + 211 \times 2001 = 112224 + 422211$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{537735} &:= 1002 \times 311 + 113 \times 2001 = 311622 + 226113 \\ &:= 1011 \times 203 + 302 \times 1101 = 205233 + 332502 \\ &:= 1112 \times 102 + 201 \times 2111 = 113424 + 424311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
538835 &:= 1034 \times 101 + 101 \times 4301 = 104434 + 434401 & &:= 20003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30002 = 220033 + 330022 \\
&:= 1102 \times 301 + 103 \times 2011 = 331702 + 207133 \\
&:= 1124 \times 101 + 101 \times 4211 = 113524 + 425311 \\
&:= 1214 \times 101 + 101 \times 4121 = 122614 + 416221 \\
&:= 1304 \times 101 + 101 \times 4031 = 131704 + 407131 \\
&:= 2033 \times 101 + 101 \times 3302 = 205333 + 333502 \\
&:= 2123 \times 101 + 101 \times 3212 = 214423 + 324412 \\
&:= 2213 \times 101 + 101 \times 3122 = 223513 + 315322 \\
&:= 2303 \times 101 + 101 \times 3032 = 232603 + 306232 \\
540045 &:= 10002 \times 12 + 21 \times 20001 = 120024 + 420021 \\
543345 &:= 10102 \times 12 + 21 \times 20101 = 121224 + 422121 \\
545545 &:= 1001 \times 124 + 421 \times 1001 = 124124 + 421421 \\
&:= 1001 \times 223 + 322 \times 1001 = 223223 + 322322 \\
546645 &:= 10202 \times 12 + 21 \times 20201 = 122424 + 424221 \\
&:= 1011 \times 104 + 401 \times 1101 = 105144 + 441501 \\
&:= 1022 \times 102 + 201 \times 2201 = 104244 + 442401 \\
547745 &:= 1003 \times 211 + 112 \times 3001 = 211633 + 336112 \\
&:= 1102 \times 112 + 211 \times 2011 = 123424 + 424321 \\
549945 &:= 10302 \times 12 + 21 \times 20301 = 123624 + 426321 \\
&:= 1011 \times 312 + 213 \times 1101 = 315432 + 234513 \\
&:= 1044 \times 101 + 101 \times 4401 = 105444 + 444501 \\
&:= 1134 \times 101 + 101 \times 4311 = 114534 + 435411 \\
&:= 1203 \times 201 + 102 \times 3021 = 241803 + 308142 \\
&:= 1212 \times 102 + 201 \times 2121 = 123624 + 426321 \\
&:= 1224 \times 101 + 101 \times 4221 = 123624 + 426321 \\
&:= 1314 \times 101 + 101 \times 4131 = 132714 + 417231 \\
&:= 1404 \times 101 + 101 \times 4041 = 141804 + 408141 \\
&:= 2043 \times 101 + 101 \times 3402 = 206343 + 343602 \\
&:= 2133 \times 101 + 101 \times 3312 = 215433 + 334512 \\
&:= 2223 \times 101 + 101 \times 3222 = 224523 + 325422 \\
&:= 2313 \times 101 + 101 \times 3132 = 233613 + 316332 \\
&:= 2403 \times 101 + 101 \times 3042 = 242703 + 307242 \\
550055 &:= 10001 \times 14 + 41 \times 10001 = 140014 + 410041 \\
&:= 10001 \times 23 + 32 \times 10001 = 230023 + 320032 \\
&:= 10004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40001 = 110044 + 440011 \\
552255 &:= 10104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40101 = 111144 + 441111 \\
&:= 11002 \times 12 + 21 \times 20011 = 132024 + 420231 \\
&:= 20103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30102 = 221133 + 331122 \\
554455 &:= 10204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40201 = 112244 + 442211 \\
&:= 20203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30202 = 222233 + 332222 \\
555555 &:= 10101 \times 14 + 41 \times 10101 = 141414 + 414141 \\
&:= 10101 \times 23 + 32 \times 10101 = 232323 + 323232 \\
&:= 11102 \times 12 + 21 \times 20111 = 133224 + 422331 \\
&:= 1004 \times 111 + 111 \times 4001 = 111444 + 444111 \\
&:= 2003 \times 111 + 111 \times 3002 = 222333 + 333222 \\
556655 &:= 10304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40301 = 113344 + 443311 \\
&:= 20303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30302 = 223333 + 333322 \\
&:= 1012 \times 112 + 211 \times 2101 = 113344 + 443311 \\
558855 &:= 10404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40401 = 114444 + 444411 \\
&:= 11202 \times 12 + 21 \times 20211 = 134424 + 424431 \\
&:= 20403 \times 11 + 11 \times 30402 = 224433 + 334422 \\
&:= 1011 \times 213 + 312 \times 1101 = 215343 + 343512 \\
&:= 1122 \times 102 + 201 \times 2211 = 114444 + 444411 \\
561165 &:= 10012 \times 12 + 21 \times 21001 = 120144 + 441021 \\
&:= 10014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41001 = 110154 + 451011 \\
&:= 11004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40011 = 121044 + 440121 \\
&:= 20013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31002 = 220143 + 341022 \\
&:= 21003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30012 = 231033 + 330132 \\
563365 &:= 10114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41101 = 111254 + 452111 \\
&:= 11104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40111 = 122144 + 441221 \\
&:= 20113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31102 = 221243 + 342122 \\
&:= 21103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30112 = 232133 + 331232 \\
564465 &:= 10011 \times 41 + 14 \times 11001 = 410451 + 154014 \\
&:= 10112 \times 12 + 21 \times 21101 = 121344 + 443121 \\
&:= 12002 \times 12 + 21 \times 20021 = 144024 + 420441 \\
&:= 1002 \times 122 + 221 \times 2001 = 122244 + 442221
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
565565 &:= 10214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41201 = 112354 + 453211 \\
&:= 11204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40211 = 123244 + 442321 \\
&:= 20213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31202 = 222343 + 343222 \\
&:= 21203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30212 = 233233 + 332332 \\
&:= 1001 \times 134 + 431 \times 1001 = 134134 + 431431 \\
&:= 1001 \times 233 + 332 \times 1001 = 233233 + 332332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
567765 &:= 10212 \times 12 + 21 \times 21201 = 122544 + 445221 \\
&:= 10314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41301 = 113454 + 454311 \\
&:= 12102 \times 12 + 21 \times 20121 = 145224 + 422541 \\
&:= 20313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31302 = 223443 + 344322 \\
&:= 21303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30312 = 234333 + 333432 \\
&:= 40311 \times 11 + 11 \times 11304 = 443421 + 124344 \\
&:= 1002 \times 321 + 123 \times 2001 = 321642 + 246123 \\
&:= 1011 \times 114 + 411 \times 1101 = 115254 + 452511 \\
&:= 1014 \times 111 + 111 \times 4101 = 112554 + 455211 \\
&:= 1032 \times 102 + 201 \times 2301 = 105264 + 462501 \\
&:= 1104 \times 111 + 111 \times 4011 = 122544 + 445221 \\
&:= 2013 \times 111 + 111 \times 3102 = 223443 + 344322 \\
&:= 2103 \times 111 + 111 \times 3012 = 233433 + 334332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
569965 &:= 10111 \times 41 + 14 \times 11101 = 414551 + 155414 \\
&:= 10414 \times 11 + 11 \times 41401 = 114554 + 455411 \\
&:= 11404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40411 = 125444 + 444521 \\
&:= 20413 \times 11 + 11 \times 31402 = 224543 + 345422 \\
&:= 21403 \times 11 + 11 \times 30412 = 235433 + 334532 \\
&:= 1021 \times 203 + 302 \times 1201 = 207263 + 362702 \\
&:= 1102 \times 311 + 113 \times 2011 = 342722 + 227243 \\
&:= 1103 \times 211 + 112 \times 3011 = 232733 + 337232 \\
&:= 1112 \times 112 + 211 \times 2111 = 124544 + 445421 \\
&:= 1202 \times 301 + 103 \times 2021 = 361802 + 208163
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
570075 &:= 10002 \times 31 + 13 \times 20001 = 310062 + 260013 \\
&:= 10003 \times 21 + 12 \times 30001 = 210063 + 360012
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
572275 &:= 10024 \times 11 + 11 \times 42001 = 110264 + 462011 \\
&:= 11014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41011 = 121154 + 451121 \\
&:= 12004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40021 = 132044 + 440231 \\
&:= 20023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32002 = 220253 + 352022 \\
&:= 21013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31012 = 231143 + 341132 \\
&:= 22003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30022 = 242033 + 330242
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
573375 &:= 10011 \times 32 + 23 \times 11001 = 320352 + 253023 \\
&:= 10103 \times 21 + 12 \times 30101 = 212163 + 361212 \\
&:= 11012 \times 12 + 21 \times 21011 = 132144 + 441231
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
574475 &:= 10102 \times 31 + 13 \times 20101 = 313162 + 261313 \\
&:= 10124 \times 11 + 11 \times 42101 = 111364 + 463111 \\
&:= 11114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41111 = 122254 + 452221 \\
&:= 12104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40121 = 133144 + 441331 \\
&:= 20123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32102 = 221353 + 353122 \\
&:= 21113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31112 = 232243 + 342232 \\
&:= 22103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30122 = 243133 + 331342
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
576675 &:= 10203 \times 21 + 12 \times 30201 = 214263 + 362412 \\
&:= 10224 \times 11 + 11 \times 42201 = 112464 + 464211 \\
&:= 11112 \times 12 + 21 \times 21111 = 133344 + 443331 \\
&:= 11214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41211 = 123354 + 453321 \\
&:= 12204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40221 = 134244 + 442431 \\
&:= 13002 \times 12 + 21 \times 20031 = 156024 + 420651 \\
&:= 20223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32202 = 222453 + 354222 \\
&:= 21213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31212 = 233343 + 343332 \\
&:= 22203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30222 = 244233 + 332442
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
578875 &:= 10021 \times 41 + 14 \times 12001 = 410861 + 168014 \\
&:= 10111 \times 32 + 23 \times 11101 = 323552 + 255323 \\
&:= 10202 \times 31 + 13 \times 20201 = 316262 + 262613 \\
&:= 10324 \times 11 + 11 \times 42301 = 113564 + 465311 \\
&:= 11314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41311 = 124454 + 454421 \\
&:= 12304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40321 = 135344 + 443531 \\
&:= 20323 \times 11 + 11 \times 32302 = 223553 + 353322 \\
&:= 21313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31312 = 234443 + 344432 \\
&:= 22303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30322 = 245333 + 333542 \\
&:= 1022 \times 112 + 211 \times 2201 = 114464 + 464411 \\
&:= 1102 \times 122 + 221 \times 2011 = 134444 + 444431
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
579975 &:= 10303 \times 21 + 12 \times 30301 = 216363 + 363612 \\
&:= 11212 \times 12 + 21 \times 21211 = 134544 + 445431 \\
&:= 13102 \times 12 + 21 \times 20131 = 157224 + 422751 \\
&:= 1011 \times 223 + 322 \times 1101 = 225453 + 354522 \\
&:= 1024 \times 111 + 111 \times 4201 = 113664 + 466311 \\
&:= 1114 \times 111 + 111 \times 4111 = 123654 + 456321
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1132 \times 102 + 201 \times 2311 = 115464 + 464511 \\ &:= 1204 \times 111 + 111 \times 4021 = 133644 + 446331 \\ &:= 2023 \times 111 + 111 \times 3202 = 224553 + 355422 \\ &:= 2113 \times 111 + 111 \times 3112 = 234543 + 345432 \\ &:= 2203 \times 111 + 111 \times 3022 = 244533 + 335442 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{582285} &:= 10011 \times 23 + 32 \times 11001 = 230253 + 352032 \\ &:= 10013 \times 21 + 12 \times 31001 = 210273 + 372012 \\ &:= 10022 \times 12 + 21 \times 22001 = 120264 + 462021 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{583385} &:= 10012 \times 31 + 13 \times 21001 = 310372 + 273013 \\ &:= 10034 \times 11 + 11 \times 43001 = 110374 + 473011 \\ &:= 11024 \times 11 + 11 \times 42011 = 121264 + 462121 \\ &:= 12014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41021 = 132154 + 451231 \\ &:= 13004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40031 = 143044 + 440341 \\ &:= 20033 \times 11 + 11 \times 33002 = 220363 + 363022 \\ &:= 21023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32012 = 231253 + 352132 \\ &:= 22013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31022 = 242143 + 341242 \\ &:= 23003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30032 = 253033 + 330352 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{585585} &:= 10113 \times 21 + 12 \times 31101 = 212373 + 373212 \\ &:= 10122 \times 12 + 21 \times 22101 = 121464 + 464121 \\ &:= 10134 \times 11 + 11 \times 43101 = 111474 + 474111 \\ &:= 11124 \times 11 + 11 \times 42111 = 122364 + 463221 \\ &:= 12012 \times 12 + 21 \times 21021 = 144144 + 441441 \\ &:= 12114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41121 = 133254 + 452331 \\ &:= 13104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40131 = 144144 + 441441 \\ &:= 20133 \times 11 + 11 \times 33102 = 221463 + 364122 \\ &:= 21123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32112 = 232353 + 353232 \\ &:= 22113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31122 = 243243 + 342342 \\ &:= 23103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30132 = 254133 + 331452 \\ &:= 1001 \times 144 + 441 \times 1001 = 144144 + 441441 \\ &:= 1001 \times 243 + 342 \times 1001 = 243243 + 342342 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{587785} &:= 10111 \times 23 + 32 \times 11101 = 232553 + 355232 \\ &:= 10112 \times 31 + 13 \times 21101 = 313472 + 274313 \\ &:= 10234 \times 11 + 11 \times 43201 = 112574 + 475211 \\ &:= 11224 \times 11 + 11 \times 42211 = 123464 + 464321 \\ &:= 12214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41221 = 134354 + 453431 \\ &:= 13204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40231 = 145244 + 442541 \\ &:= 20233 \times 11 + 11 \times 33202 = 222563 + 365222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 21223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32212 = 233453 + 354332 \\ &:= 22213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31222 = 244343 + 343442 \\ &:= 23203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30232 = 255233 + 332552 \\ &:= 1003 \times 221 + 122 \times 3001 = 221663 + 366122 \\ &:= 1012 \times 122 + 221 \times 2101 = 123464 + 464321 \\ &:= 1021 \times 104 + 401 \times 1201 = 106184 + 481601 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{588885} &:= 10213 \times 21 + 12 \times 31201 = 214473 + 374412 \\ &:= 10222 \times 12 + 21 \times 22201 = 122664 + 466221 \\ &:= 12112 \times 12 + 21 \times 21121 = 145344 + 443541 \\ &:= 14002 \times 12 + 21 \times 20041 = 168024 + 420861 \\ &:= 1011 \times 124 + 421 \times 1101 = 125364 + 463521 \\ &:= 1042 \times 102 + 201 \times 2401 = 106284 + 482601 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{589985} &:= 10334 \times 11 + 11 \times 43301 = 113674 + 476311 \\ &:= 11324 \times 11 + 11 \times 42311 = 124564 + 465421 \\ &:= 12314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41321 = 135454 + 454531 \\ &:= 13304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40331 = 146344 + 443641 \\ &:= 20333 \times 11 + 11 \times 33302 = 223663 + 366322 \\ &:= 21323 \times 11 + 11 \times 32312 = 234553 + 355432 \\ &:= 22313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31322 = 245443 + 344542 \\ &:= 23303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30332 = 256333 + 333652 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{591195} &:= 10011 \times 14 + 41 \times 11001 = 140154 + 451041 \\ &:= 11003 \times 21 + 12 \times 30011 = 231063 + 360132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{594495} &:= 10023 \times 21 + 12 \times 32001 = 210483 + 384012 \\ &:= 10044 \times 11 + 11 \times 44001 = 110484 + 484011 \\ &:= 11022 \times 12 + 21 \times 22011 = 132264 + 462231 \\ &:= 11034 \times 11 + 11 \times 43011 = 121374 + 473121 \\ &:= 11103 \times 21 + 12 \times 30111 = 233163 + 361332 \\ &:= 12024 \times 11 + 11 \times 42021 = 132264 + 462231 \\ &:= 13014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41031 = 143154 + 451341 \\ &:= 14004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40041 = 154044 + 440451 \\ &:= 20043 \times 11 + 11 \times 34002 = 220473 + 374022 \\ &:= 21033 \times 11 + 11 \times 33012 = 231363 + 363132 \\ &:= 22023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32022 = 242253 + 352242 \\ &:= 23013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31032 = 253143 + 341352 \\ &:= 24003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30042 = 264033 + 330462 \\ &:= 1002 \times 132 + 231 \times 2001 = 132264 + 462231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
596695 &:= 10021 \times 32 + 23 \times 12001 = 320672 + 276023 \\
&:= 10022 \times 31 + 13 \times 22001 = 310682 + 286013 \\
&:= 10111 \times 14 + 41 \times 11101 = 141554 + 455141 \\
&:= 10144 \times 11 + 11 \times 44101 = 111584 + 485111 \\
&:= 11134 \times 11 + 11 \times 43111 = 122474 + 474221 \\
&:= 12124 \times 11 + 11 \times 42121 = 133364 + 463331 \\
&:= 13114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41131 = 144254 + 452441 \\
&:= 14104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40141 = 155144 + 441551 \\
&:= 20143 \times 11 + 11 \times 34102 = 221573 + 375122 \\
&:= 21133 \times 11 + 11 \times 33112 = 232463 + 364232 \\
&:= 22123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32122 = 243353 + 353342 \\
&:= 23113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31132 = 254243 + 342452 \\
&:= 24103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30142 = 265133 + 331562
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
597795 &:= 10123 \times 21 + 12 \times 32101 = 212583 + 385212 \\
&:= 11122 \times 12 + 21 \times 22111 = 133464 + 464331 \\
&:= 11203 \times 21 + 12 \times 30211 = 235263 + 362532 \\
&:= 13012 \times 12 + 21 \times 21031 = 156144 + 441651 \\
&:= 1002 \times 331 + 133 \times 2001 = 331662 + 266133
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
598895 &:= 10244 \times 11 + 11 \times 44201 = 112684 + 486211 \\
&:= 11234 \times 11 + 11 \times 43211 = 123574 + 475321 \\
&:= 12224 \times 11 + 11 \times 42221 = 134464 + 464431 \\
&:= 13214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41231 = 145354 + 453541 \\
&:= 14204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40241 = 156244 + 442651 \\
&:= 20243 \times 11 + 11 \times 34202 = 222673 + 376222 \\
&:= 21233 \times 11 + 11 \times 33212 = 233563 + 365332 \\
&:= 22223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32222 = 244453 + 354442 \\
&:= 23213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31232 = 255343 + 343552 \\
&:= 24203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30242 = 266233 + 332662
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
606606 &:= 1001 \times 105 + 501 \times 1001 = 105105 + 501501 \\
&:= 1001 \times 204 + 402 \times 1001 = 204204 + 402402 \\
&:= 1001 \times 303 + 303 \times 1001 = 303303 + 303303 \\
&:= 1002 \times 202 + 202 \times 2001 = 202404 + 404202 \\
&:= 1005 \times 101 + 101 \times 5001 = 101505 + 505101 \\
&:= 2002 \times 102 + 201 \times 2002 = 204204 + 402402 \\
&:= 2004 \times 101 + 101 \times 4002 = 202404 + 404202 \\
&:= 3003 \times 101 + 101 \times 3003 = 303303 + 303303
\end{aligned}$$

$$609906 := 1002 \times 401 + 104 \times 2001 = 401802 + 208104$$

$$:= 1004 \times 201 + 102 \times 4001 = 201804 + 408102$$

$$\begin{aligned}
617716 &:= 1015 \times 101 + 101 \times 5101 = 102515 + 515201 \\
&:= 1105 \times 101 + 101 \times 5011 = 111605 + 506111 \\
&:= 2014 \times 101 + 101 \times 4102 = 203414 + 414302 \\
&:= 2104 \times 101 + 101 \times 4012 = 212504 + 405212 \\
&:= 3013 \times 101 + 101 \times 3103 = 304313 + 313403
\end{aligned}$$

$$618816 := 2012 \times 201 + 102 \times 2102 = 404412 + 214404$$

$$\begin{aligned}
626626 &:= 1001 \times 115 + 511 \times 1001 = 115115 + 511511 \\
&:= 1001 \times 214 + 412 \times 1001 = 214214 + 412412 \\
&:= 1001 \times 313 + 313 \times 1001 = 313313 + 313313
\end{aligned}$$

$$627726 := 2012 \times 102 + 201 \times 2102 = 205224 + 422502$$

$$\begin{aligned}
628826 &:= 1012 \times 202 + 202 \times 2101 = 204424 + 424402 \\
&:= 1025 \times 101 + 101 \times 5201 = 103525 + 525301 \\
&:= 1102 \times 202 + 202 \times 2011 = 222604 + 406222 \\
&:= 1115 \times 101 + 101 \times 5111 = 112615 + 516211 \\
&:= 1205 \times 101 + 101 \times 5021 = 121705 + 507121 \\
&:= 2024 \times 101 + 101 \times 4202 = 204424 + 424402 \\
&:= 2114 \times 101 + 101 \times 4112 = 213514 + 415312 \\
&:= 2204 \times 101 + 101 \times 4022 = 222604 + 406222 \\
&:= 3023 \times 101 + 101 \times 3203 = 305323 + 323503 \\
&:= 3113 \times 101 + 101 \times 3113 = 314413 + 314413
\end{aligned}$$

$$636636 := 1002 \times 212 + 212 \times 2001 = 212424 + 424212$$

$$\begin{aligned}
639936 &:= 1002 \times 411 + 114 \times 2001 = 411822 + 228114 \\
&:= 1011 \times 303 + 303 \times 1101 = 306333 + 333603 \\
&:= 1035 \times 101 + 101 \times 5301 = 104535 + 535401 \\
&:= 1125 \times 101 + 101 \times 5211 = 113625 + 526311 \\
&:= 1215 \times 101 + 101 \times 5121 = 122715 + 517221 \\
&:= 1305 \times 101 + 101 \times 5031 = 131805 + 508131 \\
&:= 2034 \times 101 + 101 \times 4302 = 205434 + 434502 \\
&:= 2112 \times 102 + 201 \times 2112 = 215424 + 424512 \\
&:= 2124 \times 101 + 101 \times 4212 = 214524 + 425412 \\
&:= 2214 \times 101 + 101 \times 4122 = 223614 + 416322 \\
&:= 2304 \times 101 + 101 \times 4032 = 232704 + 407232 \\
&:= 3033 \times 101 + 101 \times 3303 = 306333 + 333603
\end{aligned}$$

$$:= 3123 \times 101 + 101 \times 3213 = 315423 + 324513$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{646646} &:= 1001 \times 125 + 521 \times 1001 = 125125 + 521521 \\ &:= 1001 \times 224 + 422 \times 1001 = 224224 + 422422 \\ &:= 1001 \times 323 + 323 \times 1001 = 323323 + 323323 \\ &:= 2002 \times 112 + 211 \times 2002 = 224224 + 422422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{648846} &:= 1011 \times 204 + 402 \times 1101 = 206244 + 442602 \\ &:= 2022 \times 102 + 201 \times 2202 = 206244 + 442602 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{657756} := 1011 \times 105 + 501 \times 1101 = 106155 + 551601$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{659956} &:= 1004 \times 211 + 112 \times 4001 = 211844 + 448112 \\ &:= 1012 \times 212 + 212 \times 2101 = 214544 + 445412 \\ &:= 1102 \times 212 + 212 \times 2011 = 233624 + 426332 \\ &:= 2012 \times 211 + 112 \times 2102 = 424532 + 235424 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{660066} &:= 10001 \times 15 + 51 \times 10001 = 150015 + 510051 \\ &:= 10001 \times 24 + 42 \times 10001 = 240024 + 420042 \\ &:= 10001 \times 33 + 33 \times 10001 = 330033 + 330033 \\ &:= 10002 \times 22 + 22 \times 20001 = 220044 + 440022 \\ &:= 10005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50001 = 110055 + 550011 \\ &:= 20002 \times 12 + 21 \times 20002 = 240024 + 420042 \\ &:= 20004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40002 = 220044 + 440022 \\ &:= 30003 \times 11 + 11 \times 30003 = 330033 + 330033 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{662266} &:= 10105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50101 = 111155 + 551111 \\ &:= 20104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40102 = 221144 + 441122 \\ &:= 30103 \times 11 + 11 \times 30103 = 331133 + 331133 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{663366} := 20102 \times 12 + 21 \times 20102 = 241224 + 422142$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{664466} &:= 10102 \times 22 + 22 \times 20101 = 222244 + 442222 \\ &:= 10205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50201 = 112255 + 552211 \\ &:= 20204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40202 = 222244 + 442222 \\ &:= 30203 \times 11 + 11 \times 30203 = 332233 + 332233 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666666} &:= 10101 \times 15 + 51 \times 10101 = 151515 + 515151 \\ &:= 10101 \times 24 + 42 \times 10101 = 242424 + 424242 \\ &:= 10101 \times 33 + 33 \times 10101 = 333333 + 333333 \\ &:= 10305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50301 = 113355 + 553311 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 20202 \times 12 + 21 \times 20202 = 242424 + 424242$$

$$:= 20304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40302 = 223344 + 443322$$

$$:= 30303 \times 11 + 11 \times 30303 = 333333 + 333333$$

$$:= 1001 \times 135 + 531 \times 1001 = 135135 + 531531$$

$$:= 1001 \times 234 + 432 \times 1001 = 234234 + 432432$$

$$:= 1001 \times 333 + 333 \times 1001 = 333333 + 333333$$

$$:= 1002 \times 222 + 222 \times 2001 = 222444 + 444222$$

$$:= 1005 \times 111 + 111 \times 5001 = 111555 + 555111$$

$$:= 2004 \times 111 + 111 \times 4002 = 222444 + 444222$$

$$:= 3003 \times 111 + 111 \times 3003 = 333333 + 333333$$

$$\mathbf{668866} := 10202 \times 22 + 22 \times 20201 = 224444 + 444422$$

$$:= 10405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50401 = 114455 + 554411$$

$$:= 20404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40402 = 224444 + 444422$$

$$:= 30403 \times 11 + 11 \times 30403 = 334433 + 334433$$

$$:= 2012 \times 112 + 211 \times 2102 = 225344 + 443522$$

$$\mathbf{669966} := 20302 \times 12 + 21 \times 20302 = 243624 + 426342$$

$$:= 1002 \times 421 + 124 \times 2001 = 421842 + 248124$$

$$:= 1011 \times 214 + 412 \times 1101 = 216354 + 453612$$

$$:= 2032 \times 102 + 201 \times 2302 = 207264 + 462702$$

$$\mathbf{671176} := 10015 \times 11 + 11 \times 51001 = 110165 + 561011$$

$$:= 11005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50011 = 121055 + 550121$$

$$:= 20014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41002 = 220154 + 451022$$

$$:= 21004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40012 = 231044 + 440132$$

$$:= 30013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31003 = 330143 + 341033$$

$$\mathbf{672276} := 20012 \times 21 + 12 \times 21002 = 420252 + 252024$$

$$\mathbf{673376} := 10115 \times 11 + 11 \times 51101 = 111265 + 562111$$

$$:= 11105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50111 = 122155 + 551221$$

$$:= 20114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41102 = 221254 + 452122$$

$$:= 21104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40112 = 232144 + 441232$$

$$:= 30113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31103 = 331243 + 342133$$

$$\mathbf{675576} := 10011 \times 51 + 15 \times 11001 = 510561 + 165015$$

$$:= 10215 \times 11 + 11 \times 51201 = 112365 + 563211$$

$$:= 11205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50211 = 123255 + 552321$$

$$:= 20112 \times 21 + 12 \times 21102 = 422352 + 253224$$

$$:= 20214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41202 = 222354 + 453222$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 21204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40212 = 233244 + 442332 \\ &:= 30213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31203 = 332343 + 343233 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{677776} &:= 10315 \times 11 + 11 \times 51301 = 113465 + 564311 \\ &:= 11305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50311 = 124355 + 553421 \\ &:= 20314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41302 = 223454 + 454322 \\ &:= 21304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40312 = 234344 + 443432 \\ &:= 30313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31303 = 333443 + 344333 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{678876} &:= 20212 \times 21 + 12 \times 21202 = 424452 + 254424 \\ &:= 1011 \times 115 + 511 \times 1101 = 116265 + 562611 \\ &:= 1015 \times 111 + 111 \times 5101 = 112665 + 566211 \\ &:= 1105 \times 111 + 111 \times 5011 = 122655 + 556221 \\ &:= 2014 \times 111 + 111 \times 4102 = 223554 + 455322 \\ &:= 2104 \times 111 + 111 \times 4012 = 233544 + 445332 \\ &:= 3013 \times 111 + 111 \times 3103 = 334443 + 344433 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{679976} &:= 10415 \times 11 + 11 \times 51401 = 114565 + 565411 \\ &:= 11405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50411 = 125455 + 554521 \\ &:= 20414 \times 11 + 11 \times 41402 = 224554 + 454422 \\ &:= 21404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40412 = 235444 + 444532 \\ &:= 30413 \times 11 + 11 \times 31403 = 334543 + 345433 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{681186} := 20012 \times 12 + 21 \times 21002 = 240144 + 441042$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{682286} &:= 10012 \times 22 + 22 \times 21001 = 220264 + 462022 \\ &:= 10025 \times 11 + 11 \times 52001 = 110275 + 572011 \\ &:= 11002 \times 22 + 22 \times 20011 = 242044 + 440242 \\ &:= 11015 \times 11 + 11 \times 51011 = 121165 + 561121 \\ &:= 12005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50021 = 132055 + 550231 \\ &:= 20024 \times 11 + 11 \times 42002 = 220264 + 462022 \\ &:= 21014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41012 = 231154 + 451132 \\ &:= 22004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40022 = 242044 + 440242 \\ &:= 30023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32003 = 330253 + 352033 \\ &:= 31013 \times 11 + 11 \times 31013 = 341143 + 341143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{684486} &:= 10011 \times 42 + 24 \times 11001 = 420462 + 264024 \\ &:= 10125 \times 11 + 11 \times 52101 = 111375 + 573111 \\ &:= 11115 \times 11 + 11 \times 51111 = 122265 + 562221 \\ &:= 12105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50121 = 133155 + 551331 \\ &:= 20022 \times 21 + 12 \times 22002 = 420462 + 264024 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 20112 \times 12 + 21 \times 21102 = 241344 + 443142 \\ &:= 20124 \times 11 + 11 \times 42102 = 221364 + 463122 \\ &:= 21114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41112 = 232254 + 452232 \\ &:= 22104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40122 = 243144 + 441342 \\ &:= 30123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32103 = 331353 + 353133 \\ &:= 31113 \times 11 + 11 \times 31113 = 342243 + 342243 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{686686} &:= 10112 \times 22 + 22 \times 21101 = 222464 + 464222 \\ &:= 10225 \times 11 + 11 \times 52201 = 112475 + 574211 \\ &:= 11102 \times 22 + 22 \times 20111 = 244244 + 442442 \\ &:= 11215 \times 11 + 11 \times 51211 = 123365 + 563321 \\ &:= 12205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50221 = 134255 + 552431 \\ &:= 20224 \times 11 + 11 \times 42202 = 222464 + 464222 \\ &:= 21214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41212 = 233354 + 453332 \\ &:= 22204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40222 = 244244 + 442442 \\ &:= 30223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32203 = 332453 + 354233 \\ &:= 31213 \times 11 + 11 \times 31213 = 343343 + 343343 \\ &:= 1001 \times 145 + 541 \times 1001 = 145145 + 541541 \\ &:= 1001 \times 244 + 442 \times 1001 = 244244 + 442442 \\ &:= 1001 \times 343 + 343 \times 1001 = 343343 + 343343 \\ &:= 2002 \times 122 + 221 \times 2002 = 244244 + 442442 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{687786} &:= 20122 \times 21 + 12 \times 22102 = 422562 + 265224 \\ &:= 20212 \times 12 + 21 \times 21202 = 242544 + 445242 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{688886} &:= 10325 \times 11 + 11 \times 52301 = 113575 + 575311 \\ &:= 11315 \times 11 + 11 \times 51311 = 124465 + 564421 \\ &:= 12305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50321 = 135355 + 553531 \\ &:= 20324 \times 11 + 11 \times 42302 = 223564 + 465322 \\ &:= 21314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41312 = 234454 + 454432 \\ &:= 22304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40322 = 245344 + 443542 \\ &:= 30323 \times 11 + 11 \times 32303 = 333553 + 355333 \\ &:= 31313 \times 11 + 11 \times 31313 = 344443 + 344443 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{690096} &:= 10002 \times 41 + 14 \times 20001 = 410082 + 280014 \\ &:= 10004 \times 21 + 12 \times 40001 = 210084 + 480012 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{693396} &:= 10011 \times 33 + 33 \times 11001 = 330363 + 363033 \\ &:= 10035 \times 11 + 11 \times 53001 = 110385 + 583011 \\ &:= 10104 \times 21 + 12 \times 40101 = 212184 + 481212 \\ &:= 11025 \times 11 + 11 \times 52011 = 121275 + 572121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 12015 \times 11 + 11 \times 51021 = 132165 + 561231 \\ &:= 13005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50031 = 143055 + 550341 \\ &:= 20034 \times 11 + 11 \times 43002 = 220374 + 473022 \\ &:= 21012 \times 12 + 21 \times 21012 = 252144 + 441252 \\ &:= 21024 \times 11 + 11 \times 42012 = 231264 + 462132 \\ &:= 22014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41022 = 242154 + 451242 \\ &:= 23004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40032 = 253044 + 440352 \\ &:= 30033 \times 11 + 11 \times 33003 = 330363 + 363033 \\ &:= 31023 \times 11 + 11 \times 32013 = 341253 + 352143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{695596} &:= 10102 \times 41 + 14 \times 20101 = 414182 + 281414 \\ &:= 10135 \times 11 + 11 \times 53101 = 111485 + 584111 \\ &:= 11125 \times 11 + 11 \times 52111 = 122375 + 573221 \\ &:= 12115 \times 11 + 11 \times 51121 = 133265 + 562331 \\ &:= 13105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50131 = 144155 + 551441 \\ &:= 20134 \times 11 + 11 \times 43102 = 221474 + 474122 \\ &:= 21124 \times 11 + 11 \times 42112 = 232364 + 463232 \\ &:= 22114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41122 = 243254 + 452342 \\ &:= 23104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40132 = 254144 + 441452 \\ &:= 30133 \times 11 + 11 \times 33103 = 331463 + 364133 \\ &:= 31123 \times 11 + 11 \times 32113 = 342353 + 353243 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{696696} &:= 10204 \times 21 + 12 \times 40201 = 214284 + 482412 \\ &:= 20032 \times 21 + 12 \times 23002 = 420672 + 276024 \\ &:= 21112 \times 12 + 21 \times 21112 = 253344 + 443352 \\ &:= 1002 \times 232 + 232 \times 2001 = 232464 + 464232 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{697796} &:= 10235 \times 11 + 11 \times 53201 = 112585 + 585211 \\ &:= 11225 \times 11 + 11 \times 52211 = 123475 + 574321 \\ &:= 12215 \times 11 + 11 \times 51221 = 134365 + 563431 \\ &:= 13205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50231 = 145255 + 552541 \\ &:= 20234 \times 11 + 11 \times 43202 = 222574 + 475222 \\ &:= 21224 \times 11 + 11 \times 42212 = 233464 + 464332 \\ &:= 22214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41222 = 244354 + 453442 \\ &:= 23204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40232 = 255244 + 442552 \\ &:= 30233 \times 11 + 11 \times 33203 = 332563 + 365233 \\ &:= 31223 \times 11 + 11 \times 32213 = 343453 + 354343 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{699996} &:= 10111 \times 33 + 33 \times 11101 = 333663 + 366333 \\ &:= 10304 \times 21 + 12 \times 40301 = 216384 + 483612 \\ &:= 10335 \times 11 + 11 \times 53301 = 113685 + 586311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 11325 \times 11 + 11 \times 52311 = 124575 + 575421 \\ &:= 12315 \times 11 + 11 \times 51321 = 135465 + 564531 \\ &:= 13305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50331 = 146355 + 553641 \\ &:= 20132 \times 21 + 12 \times 23102 = 422772 + 277224 \\ &:= 20334 \times 11 + 11 \times 43302 = 223674 + 476322 \\ &:= 21212 \times 12 + 21 \times 21212 = 254544 + 445452 \\ &:= 21324 \times 11 + 11 \times 42312 = 234564 + 465432 \\ &:= 22314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41322 = 245454 + 454542 \\ &:= 23304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40332 = 256344 + 443652 \\ &:= 30333 \times 11 + 11 \times 33303 = 333663 + 366333 \\ &:= 31323 \times 11 + 11 \times 32313 = 344553 + 355443 \\ &:= 1002 \times 431 + 134 \times 2001 = 431862 + 268134 \\ &:= 1011 \times 125 + 521 \times 1101 = 126375 + 573621 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{705507} &:= 1002 \times 103 + 301 \times 2001 = 103206 + 602301 \\ &:= 1003 \times 102 + 201 \times 3001 = 102306 + 603201 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{707707} &:= 1001 \times 106 + 601 \times 1001 = 106106 + 601601 \\ &:= 1001 \times 205 + 502 \times 1001 = 205205 + 502502 \\ &:= 1001 \times 304 + 403 \times 1001 = 304304 + 403403 \\ &:= 1006 \times 101 + 101 \times 6001 = 101606 + 606101 \\ &:= 2005 \times 101 + 101 \times 5002 = 202505 + 505202 \\ &:= 3004 \times 101 + 101 \times 4003 = 303404 + 404303 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{708807} &:= 1002 \times 302 + 203 \times 2001 = 302604 + 406203 \\ &:= 2003 \times 201 + 102 \times 3002 = 402603 + 306204 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{717717} := 1103 \times 102 + 201 \times 3011 = 112506 + 605211$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{718817} &:= 1016 \times 101 + 101 \times 6101 = 102616 + 616201 \\ &:= 1102 \times 103 + 301 \times 2011 = 113506 + 605311 \\ &:= 1106 \times 101 + 101 \times 6011 = 111706 + 607111 \\ &:= 2015 \times 101 + 101 \times 5102 = 203515 + 515302 \\ &:= 2105 \times 101 + 101 \times 5012 = 212605 + 506212 \\ &:= 3014 \times 101 + 101 \times 4103 = 304414 + 414403 \\ &:= 3104 \times 101 + 101 \times 4013 = 313504 + 405313 \\ &:= 6101 \times 101 + 101 \times 1016 = 616201 + 102616 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{726627} := 1013 \times 102 + 201 \times 3101 = 103326 + 623301$$

$$\mathbf{727727} := 1001 \times 116 + 611 \times 1001 = 116116 + 611611$$

$$:= 1001 \times 215 + 512 \times 1001 = 215215 + 512512$$

$$:= 1001 \times 314 + 413 \times 1001 = 314314 + 413413$$

$$**729927** := 1026 \times 101 + 101 \times 6201 = 103626 + 626301$$

$$:= 1116 \times 101 + 101 \times 6111 = 112716 + 617211$$

$$:= 1203 \times 102 + 201 \times 3021 = 122706 + 607221$$

$$:= 1206 \times 101 + 101 \times 6021 = 121806 + 608121$$

$$:= 2025 \times 101 + 101 \times 5202 = 204525 + 525402$$

$$:= 2103 \times 201 + 102 \times 3012 = 422703 + 307224$$

$$:= 2115 \times 101 + 101 \times 5112 = 213615 + 516312$$

$$:= 2205 \times 101 + 101 \times 5022 = 222705 + 507222$$

$$:= 3024 \times 101 + 101 \times 4203 = 305424 + 424503$$

$$:= 3114 \times 101 + 101 \times 4113 = 314514 + 415413$$

$$:= 3204 \times 101 + 101 \times 4023 = 323604 + 406323$$

$$**735537** := 1002 \times 113 + 311 \times 2001 = 113226 + 622311$$

$$**736637** := 1012 \times 103 + 301 \times 2101 = 104236 + 632401$$

$$**738837** := 1002 \times 312 + 213 \times 2001 = 312624 + 426213$$

$$:= 1113 \times 102 + 201 \times 3111 = 113526 + 625311$$

$$**745547** := 1003 \times 112 + 211 \times 3001 = 112336 + 633211$$

$$**747747** := 1001 \times 126 + 621 \times 1001 = 126126 + 621621$$

$$:= 1001 \times 225 + 522 \times 1001 = 225225 + 522522$$

$$:= 1001 \times 324 + 423 \times 1001 = 324324 + 423423$$

$$:= 1023 \times 102 + 201 \times 3201 = 104346 + 643401$$

$$**749947** := 1102 \times 113 + 311 \times 2011 = 124526 + 625421$$

$$:= 1112 \times 103 + 301 \times 2111 = 114536 + 635411$$

$$**750057** := 10002 \times 13 + 31 \times 20001 = 130026 + 620031$$

$$:= 10003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30001 = 120036 + 630021$$

$$**753357** := 10103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30101 = 121236 + 632121$$

$$**754457** := 10102 \times 13 + 31 \times 20101 = 131326 + 623131$$

$$**756657** := 10203 \times 12 + 21 \times 30201 = 122436 + 634221$$

$$**758857** := 10202 \times 13 + 31 \times 20201 = 132626 + 626231$$

$$:= 1103 \times 112 + 211 \times 3011 = 123536 + 635321$$

$$:= 2003 \times 211 + 112 \times 3002 = 422633 + 336224$$

$$**759957** := 10303 \times 12 + 21 \times 30301 = 123636 + 636321$$

$$:= 1011 \times 205 + 502 \times 1101 = 207255 + 552702$$

$$:= 1123 \times 102 + 201 \times 3211 = 114546 + 645411$$

$$**762267** := 11003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30011 = 132036 + 630231$$

$$**763367** := 11002 \times 13 + 31 \times 20011 = 143026 + 620341$$

$$**765567** := 11103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30111 = 133236 + 632331$$

$$:= 1002 \times 123 + 321 \times 2001 = 123246 + 642321$$

$$**767767** := 11102 \times 13 + 31 \times 20111 = 144326 + 623441$$

$$:= 1001 \times 136 + 631 \times 1001 = 136136 + 631631$$

$$:= 1001 \times 235 + 532 \times 1001 = 235235 + 532532$$

$$:= 1001 \times 334 + 433 \times 1001 = 334334 + 433433$$

$$:= 1012 \times 113 + 311 \times 2101 = 114356 + 653411$$

$$:= 1013 \times 112 + 211 \times 3101 = 113456 + 654311$$

$$:= 1022 \times 103 + 301 \times 2201 = 105266 + 662501$$

$$**768867** := 11203 \times 12 + 21 \times 30211 = 134436 + 634431$$

$$:= 1002 \times 322 + 223 \times 2001 = 322644 + 446223$$

$$:= 1011 \times 106 + 601 \times 1101 = 107166 + 661701$$

$$:= 1033 \times 102 + 201 \times 3301 = 105366 + 663501$$

$$**770077** := 10001 \times 16 + 61 \times 10001 = 160016 + 610061$$

$$:= 10001 \times 25 + 52 \times 10001 = 250025 + 520052$$

$$:= 10001 \times 34 + 43 \times 10001 = 340034 + 430043$$

$$:= 10006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60001 = 110066 + 660011$$

$$:= 20005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50002 = 220055 + 550022$$

$$:= 30004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40003 = 330044 + 440033$$

$$**771177** := 10013 \times 12 + 21 \times 31001 = 120156 + 651021$$

$$**772277** := 10106 \times 11 + 11 \times 60101 = 111166 + 661111$$

$$:= 20105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50102 = 221155 + 551122$$

$$:= 30104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40103 = 331144 + 441133$$

$$**774477** := 10113 \times 12 + 21 \times 31101 = 121356 + 653121$$

$$:= 10206 \times 11 + 11 \times 60201 = 112266 + 662211$$

$$:= 12003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30021 = 144036 + 630441$$

$$:= 20205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50202 = 222255 + 552222$$

$$:= 30204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40203 = 332244 + 442233$$

$$**776677** := 10306 \times 11 + 11 \times 60301 = 113366 + 663311$$

$$:= 12002 \times 13 + 31 \times 20021 = 156026 + 620651$$

$$:= 20305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50302 = 223355 + 553322$$

$$:= 30304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40303 = 333344 + 443333$$

$$**777777** := 10101 \times 16 + 61 \times 10101 = 161616 + 616161$$

$$:= 10101 \times 25 + 52 \times 10101 = 252525 + 525252$$

$$:= 10101 \times 34 + 43 \times 10101 = 343434 + 434343$$

$$:= 10213 \times 12 + 21 \times 31201 = 122556 + 655221$$

$$:= 12103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30121 = 145236 + 632541$$

$$:= 1006 \times 111 + 111 \times 6001 = 111666 + 666111$$

$$:= 2005 \times 111 + 111 \times 5002 = 222555 + 555222$$

$$:= 3004 \times 111 + 111 \times 4003 = 333444 + 444333$$

$$**778877** := 10406 \times 11 + 11 \times 60401 = 114466 + 664411$$

$$:= 20405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50402 = 224455 + 554422$$

$$:= 30404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40403 = 334444 + 444433$$

$$**780087** := 10002 \times 32 + 23 \times 20001 = 320064 + 460023$$

$$:= 20003 \times 21 + 12 \times 30002 = 420063 + 360024$$

$$**781187** := 10012 \times 13 + 31 \times 21001 = 130156 + 651031$$

$$:= 10016 \times 11 + 11 \times 61001 = 110176 + 671011$$

$$:= 11006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60011 = 121066 + 660121$$

$$:= 20015 \times 11 + 11 \times 51002 = 220165 + 561022$$

$$:= 21005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50012 = 231055 + 550132$$

$$:= 30014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41003 = 330154 + 451033$$

$$:= 31004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40013 = 341044 + 440143$$

$$**783387** := 10116 \times 11 + 11 \times 61101 = 111276 + 672111$$

$$:= 11013 \times 12 + 21 \times 31011 = 132156 + 651231$$

$$:= 11106 \times 11 + 11 \times 60111 = 122166 + 661221$$

$$:= 20103 \times 21 + 12 \times 30102 = 422163 + 361224$$

$$:= 20115 \times 11 + 11 \times 51102 = 221265 + 562122$$

$$:= 21105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50112 = 232155 + 551232$$

$$:= 30114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41103 = 331254 + 452133$$

$$:= 31104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40113 = 342144 + 441243$$

$$**785587** := 10102 \times 32 + 23 \times 20101 = 323264 + 462323$$

$$:= 10112 \times 13 + 31 \times 21101 = 131456 + 654131$$

$$:= 10216 \times 11 + 11 \times 61201 = 112376 + 673211$$

$$:= 11206 \times 11 + 11 \times 60211 = 123266 + 662321$$

$$:= 20215 \times 11 + 11 \times 51202 = 222365 + 563222$$

$$:= 21205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50212 = 233255 + 552332$$

$$:= 30214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41203 = 332354 + 453233$$

$$:= 31204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40213 = 343244 + 442343$$

$$:= 1003 \times 122 + 221 \times 3001 = 122366 + 663221$$

$$**786687** := 11001 \times 16 + 61 \times 10011 = 176016 + 610671$$

$$:= 11113 \times 12 + 21 \times 31111 = 133356 + 653331$$

$$:= 13003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30031 = 156036 + 630651$$

$$:= 20203 \times 21 + 12 \times 30202 = 424263 + 362424$$

$$**787787** := 10316 \times 11 + 11 \times 61301 = 113476 + 674311$$

$$:= 11306 \times 11 + 11 \times 60311 = 124366 + 663421$$

$$:= 20315 \times 11 + 11 \times 51302 = 223465 + 564322$$

$$:= 21305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50312 = 234355 + 553432$$

$$:= 30314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41303 = 333454 + 454333$$

$$:= 31304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40313 = 344344 + 443443$$

$$:= 1001 \times 146 + 641 \times 1001 = 146146 + 641641$$

$$:= 1001 \times 245 + 542 \times 1001 = 245245 + 542542$$

$$:= 1001 \times 344 + 443 \times 1001 = 344344 + 443443$$

$$**789987** := 10212 \times 13 + 31 \times 21201 = 132756 + 657231$$

$$:= 10416 \times 11 + 11 \times 61401 = 114576 + 675411$$

$$:= 11213 \times 12 + 21 \times 31211 = 134556 + 655431$$

$$:= 11406 \times 11 + 11 \times 60411 = 125466 + 664521$$

$$:= 13002 \times 13 + 31 \times 20031 = 169026 + 620961$$

$$:= 13103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30131 = 157236 + 632751$$

$$:= 20303 \times 21 + 12 \times 30302 = 426363 + 363624$$

$$:= 20415 \times 11 + 11 \times 51402 = 224565 + 565422$$

$$:= 21405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50412 = 235455 + 554532$$

$$:= 30414 \times 11 + 11 \times 41403 = 334554 + 455433$$

$$:= 31404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40413 = 345444 + 444543$$

$$:= 1011 \times 116 + 611 \times 1101 = 117276 + 672711$$

$$:= 1016 \times 111 + 111 \times 6101 = 112776 + 677211$$

$$:= 1023 \times 112 + 211 \times 3201 = 114576 + 675411$$

$$:= 1043 \times 102 + 201 \times 3401 = 106386 + 683601$$

$$:= 1106 \times 111 + 111 \times 6011 = 122766 + 667221$$

$$:= 2015 \times 111 + 111 \times 5102 = 223665 + 566322$$

$$:= 2105 \times 111 + 111 \times 5012 = 233655 + 556332$$

$$:= 3014 \times 111 + 111 \times 4103 = 334554 + 455433$$

$$:= 3104 \times 111 + 111 \times 4013 = 344544 + 445443$$

$$**792297** := 10023 \times 12 + 21 \times 32001 = 120276 + 672021$$

$$:= 10026 \times 11 + 11 \times 62001 = 110286 + 682011$$

$$:= 11016 \times 11 + 11 \times 61011 = 121176 + 671121$$

$$:= 12006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60021 = 132066 + 660231$$

$$:= 20013 \times 21 + 12 \times 31002 = 420273 + 372024$$

$$:= 20025 \times 11 + 11 \times 52002 = 220275 + 572022$$

$$:= 21015 \times 11 + 11 \times 51012 = 231165 + 561132$$

$$:= 22005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50022 = 242055 + 550242$$

$$:= 30024 \times 11 + 11 \times 42003 = 330264 + 462033$$

$$:= 31014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41013 = 341154 + 451143$$

$$:= 32004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40023 = 352044 + 440253$$

$$**794497** := 10126 \times 11 + 11 \times 62101 = 111386 + 683111$$

$$:= 11012 \times 13 + 31 \times 21011 = 143156 + 651341$$

$$:= 11116 \times 11 + 11 \times 61111 = 122276 + 672221$$

$$:= 12106 \times 11 + 11 \times 60121 = 133166 + 661331$$

$$:= 20125 \times 11 + 11 \times 52102 = 221375 + 573122$$

$$:= 21115 \times 11 + 11 \times 51112 = 232265 + 562232$$

$$:= 22105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50122 = 243155 + 551342$$

$$:= 30124 \times 11 + 11 \times 42103 = 331364 + 463133$$

$$:= 31114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41113 = 342254 + 452243$$

$$:= 32104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40123 = 353144 + 441353$$

$$**795597** := 10011 \times 52 + 25 \times 11001 = 520572 + 275025$$

$$:= 10123 \times 12 + 21 \times 32101 = 121476 + 674121$$

$$:= 12013 \times 12 + 21 \times 31021 = 144156 + 651441$$

$$:= 20113 \times 21 + 12 \times 31102 = 422373 + 373224$$

$$:= 1002 \times 133 + 331 \times 2001 = 133266 + 662331$$

$$**796697** := 10226 \times 11 + 11 \times 62201 = 112486 + 684211$$

$$:= 11216 \times 11 + 11 \times 61211 = 123376 + 673321$$

$$:= 12206 \times 11 + 11 \times 60221 = 134266 + 662431$$

$$:= 20225 \times 11 + 11 \times 52202 = 222475 + 574222$$

$$:= 21215 \times 11 + 11 \times 51212 = 233365 + 563332$$

$$:= 22205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50222 = 244255 + 552442$$

$$:= 30224 \times 11 + 11 \times 42203 = 332464 + 464233$$

$$:= 31214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41213 = 343354 + 453343$$

$$:= 32204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40223 = 354244 + 442453$$

$$**798897** := 10223 \times 12 + 21 \times 32201 = 122676 + 676221$$

$$:= 10326 \times 11 + 11 \times 62301 = 113586 + 685311$$

$$:= 11112 \times 13 + 31 \times 21111 = 144456 + 654441$$

$$:= 11316 \times 11 + 11 \times 61311 = 124476 + 674421$$

$$:= 12113 \times 12 + 21 \times 31121 = 145356 + 653541$$

$$:= 12306 \times 11 + 11 \times 60321 = 135366 + 663531$$

$$:= 14003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30041 = 168036 + 630861$$

$$:= 20213 \times 21 + 12 \times 31202 = 424473 + 374424$$

$$:= 20325 \times 11 + 11 \times 52302 = 223575 + 575322$$

$$:= 21315 \times 11 + 11 \times 51312 = 234465 + 564432$$

$$:= 22305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50322 = 245355 + 553542$$

$$:= 30324 \times 11 + 11 \times 42303 = 333564 + 465333$$

$$:= 31314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41313 = 344454 + 454443$$

$$:= 32304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40323 = 355344 + 443553$$

$$:= 1002 \times 332 + 233 \times 2001 = 332664 + 466233$$

$$:= 1012 \times 123 + 321 \times 2101 = 124476 + 674421$$

$$:= 1032 \times 103 + 301 \times 2301 = 106296 + 692601$$

$$**799997** := 1022 \times 113 + 311 \times 2201 = 115486 + 684511$$

$$:= 1103 \times 122 + 221 \times 3011 = 134566 + 665431$$

$$**807708** := 1002 \times 203 + 302 \times 2001 = 203406 + 604302$$

$$:= 2003 \times 102 + 201 \times 3002 = 204306 + 603402$$

$$**808808** := 1001 \times 107 + 701 \times 1001 = 107107 + 701701$$

$$:= 1001 \times 206 + 602 \times 1001 = 206206 + 602602$$

$$:= 1001 \times 305 + 503 \times 1001 = 305305 + 503503$$

$$:= 1001 \times 404 + 404 \times 1001 = 404404 + 404404$$

$$:= 1003 \times 202 + 202 \times 3001 = 202606 + 606202$$

$$:= 1007 \times 101 + 101 \times 7001 = 101707 + 707101$$

$$:= 2002 \times 103 + 301 \times 2002 = 206206 + 602602$$

$$:= 2002 \times 202 + 202 \times 2002 = 404404 + 404404$$

$$:= 2006 \times 101 + 101 \times 6002 = 202606 + 606202$$

$$:= 3005 \times 101 + 101 \times 5003 = 303505 + 505303$$

$$:= 4004 \times 101 + 101 \times 4004 = 404404 + 404404$$

$$**819918** := 1017 \times 101 + 101 \times 7101 = 102717 + 717201$$

$$:= 1107 \times 101 + 101 \times 7011 = 111807 + 708111$$

$$:= 2016 \times 101 + 101 \times 6102 = 203616 + 616302$$

$$:= 2103 \times 102 + 201 \times 3012 = 214506 + 605412$$

$$:= 2106 \times 101 + 101 \times 6012 = 212706 + 607212$$

$$:= 3012 \times 201 + 102 \times 2103 = 605412 + 214506$$

$$:= 3015 \times 101 + 101 \times 5103 = 304515 + 515403$$

$$:= 3105 \times 101 + 101 \times 5013 = 313605 + 506313$$

$$:= 4014 \times 101 + 101 \times 4104 = 405414 + 414504$$

$$**828828** := 1001 \times 117 + 711 \times 1001 = 117117 + 711711$$

$$:= 1001 \times 216 + 612 \times 1001 = 216216 + 612612$$

$$:= 1001 \times 315 + 513 \times 1001 = 315315 + 513513$$

$$:= 1001 \times 414 + 414 \times 1001 = 414414 + 414414$$

$$:= 2013 \times 102 + 201 \times 3102 = 205326 + 623502$$

$$**837738** := 1002 \times 213 + 312 \times 2001 = 213426 + 624312$$

$$**839938** := 1012 \times 203 + 302 \times 2101 = 205436 + 634502$$

$$:= 2012 \times 103 + 301 \times 2102 = 207236 + 632702$$

$$**848848** := 1001 \times 127 + 721 \times 1001 = 127127 + 721721$$

$$:= 1001 \times 226 + 622 \times 1001 = 226226 + 622622$$

$$:= 1001 \times 325 + 523 \times 1001 = 325325 + 523523$$

$$:= 1001 \times 424 + 424 \times 1001 = 424424 + 424424$$

$$:= 1003 \times 212 + 212 \times 3001 = 212636 + 636212$$

$$:= 2002 \times 113 + 311 \times 2002 = 226226 + 622622$$

$$:= 2002 \times 212 + 212 \times 2002 = 424424 + 424424$$

$$**849948** := 2023 \times 102 + 201 \times 3202 = 206346 + 643602$$

$$**857758** := 2003 \times 112 + 211 \times 3002 = 224336 + 633422$$

$$**867768** := 1002 \times 223 + 322 \times 2001 = 223446 + 644322$$

$$**868868** := 1001 \times 137 + 731 \times 1001 = 137137 + 731731$$

$$:= 1001 \times 236 + 632 \times 1001 = 236236 + 632632$$

$$:= 1001 \times 335 + 533 \times 1001 = 335335 + 533533$$

$$:= 1001 \times 434 + 434 \times 1001 = 434434 + 434434$$

$$**870078** := 10002 \times 23 + 32 \times 20001 = 230046 + 640032$$

$$:= 20003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30002 = 240036 + 630042$$

$$**873378** := 20103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30102 = 241236 + 632142$$

$$**875578** := 10102 \times 23 + 32 \times 20101 = 232346 + 643232$$

$$**876678** := 20203 \times 12 + 21 \times 30202 = 242436 + 634242$$

$$**879978** := 20303 \times 12 + 21 \times 30302 = 243636 + 636342$$

$$:= 1011 \times 107 + 701 \times 1101 = 108177 + 771801$$

$$:= 2013 \times 112 + 211 \times 3102 = 225456 + 654522$$

$$**880088** := 10001 \times 17 + 71 \times 10001 = 170017 + 710071$$

$$:= 10001 \times 26 + 62 \times 10001 = 260026 + 620062$$

$$:= 10001 \times 35 + 53 \times 10001 = 350035 + 530053$$

$$:= 10001 \times 44 + 44 \times 10001 = 440044 + 440044$$

$$:= 10003 \times 22 + 22 \times 30001 = 220066 + 660022$$

$$:= 10007 \times 11 + 11 \times 70001 = 110077 + 770011$$

$$:= 20002 \times 13 + 31 \times 20002 = 260026 + 620062$$

$$:= 20002 \times 22 + 22 \times 20002 = 440044 + 440044$$

$$:= 20006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60002 = 220066 + 660022$$

$$:= 30005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50003 = 330055 + 550033$$

$$:= 40004 \times 11 + 11 \times 40004 = 440044 + 440044$$

$$**882288** := 10107 \times 11 + 11 \times 70101 = 111177 + 771111$$

$$:= 20106 \times 11 + 11 \times 60102 = 221166 + 661122$$

$$:= 21003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30012 = 252036 + 630252$$

$$:= 30105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50103 = 331155 + 551133$$

$$:= 40104 \times 11 + 11 \times 40104 = 441144 + 441144$$

$$**884488** := 10103 \times 22 + 22 \times 30101 = 222266 + 662222$$

$$:= 10207 \times 11 + 11 \times 70201 = 112277 + 772211$$

$$:= 20102 \times 13 + 31 \times 20102 = 261326 + 623162$$

$$:= 20102 \times 22 + 22 \times 20102 = 442244 + 442244$$

$$:= 20206 \times 11 + 11 \times 60202 = 222266 + 662222$$

$$:= 30205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50203 = 332255 + 552233$$

$$:= 40204 \times 11 + 11 \times 40204 = 442244 + 442244$$

$$**885588** := 21103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30112 = 253236 + 632352$$

$$**886688** := 10307 \times 11 + 11 \times 70301 = 113377 + 773311$$

$$:= 20306 \times 11 + 11 \times 60302 = 223366 + 663322$$

$$:= 30305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50303 = 333355 + 553333$$

$$:= 40304 \times 11 + 11 \times 40304 = 443344 + 443344$$

$$**888888** := 10101 \times 17 + 71 \times 10101 = 171717 + 717171$$

$$:= 10101 \times 26 + 62 \times 10101 = 262626 + 626262$$

$$:= 10101 \times 35 + 53 \times 10101 = 353535 + 535353$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 10101 \times 44 + 44 \times 10101 = 444444 + 444444 \\
&:= 10203 \times 22 + 22 \times 30201 = 224466 + 664422 \\
&:= 10407 \times 11 + 11 \times 70401 = 114477 + 774411 \\
&:= 20202 \times 13 + 31 \times 20202 = 262626 + 626262 \\
&:= 20202 \times 22 + 22 \times 20202 = 444444 + 444444 \\
&:= 20406 \times 11 + 11 \times 60402 = 224466 + 664422 \\
&:= 21203 \times 12 + 21 \times 30212 = 254436 + 634452 \\
&:= 30405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50403 = 334455 + 554433 \\
&:= 40404 \times 11 + 11 \times 40404 = 444444 + 444444 \\
&:= 1001 \times 147 + 741 \times 1001 = 147147 + 741741 \\
&:= 1001 \times 246 + 642 \times 1001 = 246246 + 642642 \\
&:= 1001 \times 345 + 543 \times 1001 = 345345 + 543543 \\
&:= 1001 \times 444 + 444 \times 1001 = 444444 + 444444 \\
&:= 1003 \times 222 + 222 \times 3001 = 222666 + 666222 \\
&:= 1007 \times 111 + 111 \times 7001 = 111777 + 777111 \\
&:= 2002 \times 123 + 321 \times 2002 = 246246 + 642642 \\
&:= 2002 \times 222 + 222 \times 2002 = 444444 + 444444 \\
&:= 2006 \times 111 + 111 \times 6002 = 222666 + 666222 \\
&:= 3005 \times 111 + 111 \times 5003 = 333555 + 555333 \\
&:= 4004 \times 111 + 111 \times 4004 = 444444 + 444444
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{891198} &:= 10017 \times 11 + 11 \times 71001 = 110187 + 781011 \\
&:= 11007 \times 11 + 11 \times 70011 = 121077 + 770121 \\
&:= 20013 \times 12 + 21 \times 31002 = 240156 + 651042 \\
&:= 20016 \times 11 + 11 \times 61002 = 220176 + 671022 \\
&:= 21006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60012 = 231066 + 660132 \\
&:= 30015 \times 11 + 11 \times 51003 = 330165 + 561033 \\
&:= 31005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50013 = 341055 + 550143 \\
&:= 40014 \times 11 + 11 \times 41004 = 440154 + 451044
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{893398} &:= 10117 \times 11 + 11 \times 71101 = 111287 + 782111 \\
&:= 11002 \times 23 + 32 \times 20011 = 253046 + 640352 \\
&:= 11107 \times 11 + 11 \times 70111 = 122177 + 771221 \\
&:= 20012 \times 31 + 13 \times 21002 = 620372 + 273026 \\
&:= 20116 \times 11 + 11 \times 61102 = 221276 + 672122 \\
&:= 21106 \times 11 + 11 \times 60112 = 232166 + 661232 \\
&:= 30115 \times 11 + 11 \times 51103 = 331265 + 562133 \\
&:= 31105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50113 = 342155 + 551243 \\
&:= 40114 \times 11 + 11 \times 41104 = 441254 + 452144
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{894498} := 20113 \times 12 + 21 \times 31102 = 241356 + 653142$$

$$:= 22003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30022 = 264036 + 630462$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{895598} &:= 10217 \times 11 + 11 \times 71201 = 112387 + 783211 \\
&:= 11207 \times 11 + 11 \times 70211 = 123277 + 772321 \\
&:= 20216 \times 11 + 11 \times 61202 = 222376 + 673222 \\
&:= 21206 \times 11 + 11 \times 60212 = 233266 + 662332 \\
&:= 30215 \times 11 + 11 \times 51203 = 332365 + 563233 \\
&:= 31205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50213 = 343255 + 552343 \\
&:= 40214 \times 11 + 11 \times 41204 = 442354 + 453244
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{897798} &:= 10011 \times 71 + 17 \times 11001 = 710781 + 187017 \\
&:= 10317 \times 11 + 11 \times 71301 = 113487 + 784311 \\
&:= 11307 \times 11 + 11 \times 70311 = 124377 + 773421 \\
&:= 20112 \times 31 + 13 \times 21102 = 623472 + 274326 \\
&:= 20213 \times 12 + 21 \times 31202 = 242556 + 655242 \\
&:= 20316 \times 11 + 11 \times 61302 = 223476 + 674322 \\
&:= 21306 \times 11 + 11 \times 60312 = 234366 + 663432 \\
&:= 22103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30122 = 265236 + 632562 \\
&:= 30315 \times 11 + 11 \times 51303 = 333465 + 564333 \\
&:= 31305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50313 = 344355 + 553443 \\
&:= 40314 \times 11 + 11 \times 41304 = 443454 + 454344 \\
&:= 1002 \times 233 + 332 \times 2001 = 233466 + 664332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{898898} := 11102 \times 23 + 32 \times 20111 = 255346 + 643552$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{899998} &:= 10417 \times 11 + 11 \times 71401 = 114587 + 785411 \\
&:= 11407 \times 11 + 11 \times 70411 = 125477 + 774521 \\
&:= 20416 \times 11 + 11 \times 61402 = 224576 + 675422 \\
&:= 21406 \times 11 + 11 \times 60412 = 235466 + 664532 \\
&:= 30415 \times 11 + 11 \times 51403 = 334565 + 565433 \\
&:= 31405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50413 = 345455 + 554543 \\
&:= 40414 \times 11 + 11 \times 41404 = 444554 + 455444
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{906609} &:= 1002 \times 104 + 401 \times 2001 = 104208 + 802401 \\
&:= 1004 \times 102 + 201 \times 4001 = 102408 + 804201
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{909909} &:= 1001 \times 108 + 801 \times 1001 = 108108 + 801801 \\
&:= 1001 \times 207 + 702 \times 1001 = 207207 + 702702 \\
&:= 1001 \times 306 + 603 \times 1001 = 306306 + 603603 \\
&:= 1001 \times 405 + 504 \times 1001 = 405405 + 504504 \\
&:= 1002 \times 303 + 303 \times 2001 = 303606 + 606303
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1008 \times 101 + 101 \times 8001 = 101808 + 808101 \\ &:= 2007 \times 101 + 101 \times 7002 = 202707 + 707202 \\ &:= 3003 \times 102 + 201 \times 3003 = 306306 + 603603 \\ &:= 3006 \times 101 + 101 \times 6003 = 303606 + 606303 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1001 \times 435 + 534 \times 1001 = 435435 + 534534 \\ &:= 1002 \times 323 + 323 \times 2001 = 323646 + 646323 \\ &:= 1034 \times 102 + 201 \times 4301 = 105468 + 864501 \\ &:= 1104 \times 112 + 211 \times 4011 = 123648 + 846321 \\ &:= 3003 \times 112 + 211 \times 3003 = 336336 + 633633 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{918819} &:= 1104 \times 102 + 201 \times 4011 = 112608 + 806211 \\ \mathbf{927729} &:= 1014 \times 102 + 201 \times 4101 = 103428 + 824301 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{972279} &:= 11004 \times 12 + 21 \times 40011 = 132048 + 840231 \\ \mathbf{974479} &:= 11002 \times 14 + 41 \times 20011 = 154028 + 820451 \\ \mathbf{975579} &:= 11104 \times 12 + 21 \times 40111 = 133248 + 842331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{929929} &:= 1001 \times 118 + 811 \times 1001 = 118118 + 811811 \\ &:= 1001 \times 217 + 712 \times 1001 = 217217 + 712712 \\ &:= 1001 \times 316 + 613 \times 1001 = 316316 + 613613 \\ &:= 1001 \times 415 + 514 \times 1001 = 415415 + 514514 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{978879} &:= 11204 \times 12 + 21 \times 40211 = 134448 + 844431 \\ &:= 1012 \times 114 + 411 \times 2101 = 115368 + 863511 \\ &:= 1014 \times 112 + 211 \times 4101 = 113568 + 865311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{936639} := 1002 \times 114 + 411 \times 2001 = 114228 + 822411$$

$$\mathbf{979979} := 11102 \times 14 + 41 \times 20111 = 155428 + 824551$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{939939} &:= 1002 \times 313 + 313 \times 2001 = 313626 + 626313 \\ &:= 1114 \times 102 + 201 \times 4111 = 113628 + 826311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{981189} := 10014 \times 12 + 21 \times 41001 = 120168 + 861021$$

$$\mathbf{947749} := 1012 \times 104 + 401 \times 2101 = 105248 + 842501$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{984489} &:= 10114 \times 12 + 21 \times 41101 = 121368 + 863121 \\ &:= 12004 \times 12 + 21 \times 40021 = 144048 + 840441 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{948849} := 1024 \times 102 + 201 \times 4201 = 104448 + 844401$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{987789} &:= 10214 \times 12 + 21 \times 41201 = 122568 + 865221 \\ &:= 12104 \times 12 + 21 \times 40121 = 145248 + 842541 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{949949} &:= 1001 \times 128 + 821 \times 1001 = 128128 + 821821 \\ &:= 1001 \times 227 + 722 \times 1001 = 227227 + 722722 \\ &:= 1001 \times 326 + 623 \times 1001 = 326326 + 623623 \\ &:= 1001 \times 425 + 524 \times 1001 = 425425 + 524524 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{988889} &:= 12002 \times 14 + 41 \times 20021 = 168028 + 820861 \\ &:= 1022 \times 104 + 401 \times 2201 = 106288 + 882601 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{956659} := 1004 \times 112 + 211 \times 4001 = 112448 + 844211$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{989989} &:= 1001 \times 148 + 841 \times 1001 = 148148 + 841841 \\ &:= 1001 \times 247 + 742 \times 1001 = 247247 + 742742 \\ &:= 1001 \times 346 + 643 \times 1001 = 346346 + 643643 \\ &:= 1001 \times 445 + 544 \times 1001 = 445445 + 544544 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{960069} &:= 10002 \times 14 + 41 \times 20001 = 140028 + 820041 \\ &:= 10004 \times 12 + 21 \times 40001 = 120048 + 840021 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{963369} := 10104 \times 12 + 21 \times 40101 = 121248 + 842121$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{990099} &:= 10001 \times 18 + 81 \times 10001 = 180018 + 810081 \\ &:= 10001 \times 27 + 72 \times 10001 = 270027 + 720072 \\ &:= 10001 \times 36 + 63 \times 10001 = 360036 + 630063 \\ &:= 10001 \times 45 + 54 \times 10001 = 450045 + 540054 \\ &:= 10002 \times 33 + 33 \times 20001 = 330066 + 660033 \\ &:= 10008 \times 11 + 11 \times 80001 = 110088 + 880011 \\ &:= 20007 \times 11 + 11 \times 70002 = 220077 + 770022 \\ &:= 30003 \times 12 + 21 \times 30003 = 360036 + 630063 \\ &:= 30006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60003 = 330066 + 660033 \\ &:= 40005 \times 11 + 11 \times 50004 = 440055 + 550044 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{965569} := 10102 \times 14 + 41 \times 20101 = 141428 + 824141$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{966669} &:= 10204 \times 12 + 21 \times 40201 = 122448 + 844221 \\ &:= 1002 \times 124 + 421 \times 2001 = 124248 + 842421 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{969969} &:= 10304 \times 12 + 21 \times 40301 = 123648 + 846321 \\ &:= 1001 \times 138 + 831 \times 1001 = 138138 + 831831 \\ &:= 1001 \times 237 + 732 \times 1001 = 237237 + 732732 \\ &:= 1001 \times 336 + 633 \times 1001 = 336336 + 633633 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 1002 \times 134 + 431 \times 2001 = 134268 + 862431$$

$$\begin{aligned} 992299 &:= 10108 \times 11 + 11 \times 80101 = 111188 + 881111 \\ &:= 20107 \times 11 + 11 \times 70102 = 221177 + 771122 \\ &:= 30106 \times 11 + 11 \times 60103 = 331166 + 661133 \\ &:= 40105 \times 11 + 11 \times 50104 = 441155 + 551144 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 998899 &:= 10408 \times 11 + 11 \times 80401 = 114488 + 884411 \\ &:= 20407 \times 11 + 11 \times 70402 = 224477 + 774422 \\ &:= 30406 \times 11 + 11 \times 60403 = 334466 + 664433 \\ &:= 40405 \times 11 + 11 \times 50404 = 444455 + 554444 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 993399 &:= 11014 \times 12 + 21 \times 41011 = 132168 + 861231 \\ &:= 30103 \times 12 + 21 \times 30103 = 361236 + 632163 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 999999 &:= 10101 \times 18 + 81 \times 10101 = 181818 + 818181 \\ &:= 10101 \times 27 + 72 \times 10101 = 272727 + 727272 \\ &:= 10101 \times 36 + 63 \times 10101 = 363636 + 636363 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 994499 &:= 10208 \times 11 + 11 \times 80201 = 112288 + 882211 \\ &:= 20207 \times 11 + 11 \times 70202 = 222277 + 772222 \\ &:= 30206 \times 11 + 11 \times 60203 = 332266 + 662233 \\ &:= 40205 \times 11 + 11 \times 50204 = 442255 + 552244 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10101 \times 45 + 54 \times 10101 = 454545 + 545454 \\ &:= 11214 \times 12 + 21 \times 41211 = 134568 + 865431 \\ &:= 13104 \times 12 + 21 \times 40131 = 157248 + 842751 \\ &:= 30303 \times 12 + 21 \times 30303 = 363636 + 636363 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 996699 &:= 10102 \times 33 + 33 \times 20101 = 333366 + 663333 \\ &:= 10308 \times 11 + 11 \times 80301 = 113388 + 883311 \\ &:= 11114 \times 12 + 21 \times 41111 = 133368 + 863331 \\ &:= 13004 \times 12 + 21 \times 40031 = 156048 + 840651 \\ &:= 20307 \times 11 + 11 \times 70302 = 223377 + 773322 \\ &:= 30203 \times 12 + 21 \times 30203 = 362436 + 634263 \\ &:= 30306 \times 11 + 11 \times 60303 = 333366 + 663333 \\ &:= 40305 \times 11 + 11 \times 50304 = 443355 + 553344 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1002 \times 333 + 333 \times 2001 = 333666 + 666333 \\ &:= 1008 \times 111 + 111 \times 8001 = 111888 + 888111 \\ &:= 2007 \times 111 + 111 \times 7002 = 222777 + 777222 \\ &:= 3006 \times 111 + 111 \times 6003 = 333666 + 666333 \\ &:= 4005 \times 111 + 111 \times 5004 = 444555 + 555444 \end{aligned}$$

2.5 Seven Digits Palindromic Sum

$$:= 50006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60005 = 550066 + 660055$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1112111 &:= 1001 \times 209 + 902 \times 1001 = 209209 + 902902 \\ &:= 1001 \times 308 + 803 \times 1001 = 308308 + 803803 \\ &:= 1001 \times 407 + 704 \times 1001 = 407407 + 704704 \\ &:= 1001 \times 506 + 605 \times 1001 = 506506 + 605605 \\ &:= 2009 \times 101 + 101 \times 9002 = 202909 + 909202 \\ &:= 3008 \times 101 + 101 \times 8003 = 303808 + 808303 \\ &:= 4007 \times 101 + 101 \times 7004 = 404707 + 707404 \\ &:= 5006 \times 101 + 101 \times 6005 = 505606 + 606505 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1222221 &:= 10101 \times 29 + 92 \times 10101 = 292929 + 929292 \\ &:= 10101 \times 38 + 83 \times 10101 = 383838 + 838383 \\ &:= 10101 \times 47 + 74 \times 10101 = 474747 + 747474 \\ &:= 10101 \times 56 + 65 \times 10101 = 565656 + 656565 \\ &:= 31304 \times 12 + 21 \times 40313 = 375648 + 846573 \\ &:= 2009 \times 111 + 111 \times 9002 = 222999 + 999222 \\ &:= 3008 \times 111 + 111 \times 8003 = 333888 + 888333 \\ &:= 4007 \times 111 + 111 \times 7004 = 444777 + 777444 \\ &:= 5006 \times 111 + 111 \times 6005 = 555666 + 666555 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1210121 &:= 10001 \times 29 + 92 \times 10001 = 290029 + 920092 \\ &:= 10001 \times 38 + 83 \times 10001 = 380038 + 830083 \\ &:= 10001 \times 47 + 74 \times 10001 = 470047 + 740074 \\ &:= 10001 \times 56 + 65 \times 10001 = 560056 + 650065 \\ &:= 20009 \times 11 + 11 \times 90002 = 220099 + 990022 \\ &:= 30008 \times 11 + 11 \times 80003 = 330088 + 880033 \\ &:= 40007 \times 11 + 11 \times 70004 = 440077 + 770044 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2004002 &:= 1001 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1001 = 1002001 + 1002001 \\ 2020202 &:= 10001 \times 101 + 101 \times 10001 = 1010101 + 1010101 \\ 2040402 &:= 10101 \times 101 + 101 \times 10101 = 1020201 + 1020201 \\ 2060602 &:= 10201 \times 101 + 101 \times 10201 = 1030301 + 1030301 \\ 2080802 &:= 10301 \times 101 + 101 \times 10301 = 1040401 + 1040401 \end{aligned}$$

$$2114112 := 1011 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1101 = 1012011 + 1102101$$

$$2122212 := 10011 \times 101 + 101 \times 11001 = 1011111 + 1111101$$

$$2142412 := 10111 \times 101 + 101 \times 11101 = 1021211 + 1121201$$

$$2162612 := 10211 \times 101 + 101 \times 11201 = 1031311 + 1131301$$

$$2182812 := 10311 \times 101 + 101 \times 11301 = 1041411 + 1141401$$

$$2200022 := 100001 \times 11 + 11 \times 100001 = 1100011 + 1100011$$

$$2212122 := 100101 \times 11 + 11 \times 101001 = 1101111 + 1111011$$

$$2220222 := 10001 \times 111 + 111 \times 10001 = 1110111 + 1110111$$

$$2224222 := 100201 \times 11 + 11 \times 102001 = 1102211 + 1122011$$

$$:= 101101 \times 11 + 11 \times 101101 = 1112111 + 1112111$$

$$:= 10021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12001 = 1012121 + 1212101$$

$$:= 11011 \times 101 + 101 \times 11011 = 1112111 + 1112111$$

$$:= 1021 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1201 = 1022021 + 1202201$$

$$:= 1111 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1111 = 1112111 + 1112111$$

$$2226222 := 1101 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1011 = 1113111 + 1113111$$

$$2234322 := 1011 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1101 = 1022121 + 1212201$$

$$2236322 := 100301 \times 11 + 11 \times 103001 = 1103311 + 1133011$$

$$:= 101201 \times 11 + 11 \times 102101 = 1113211 + 1123111$$

$$2242422 := 10101 \times 111 + 111 \times 10101 = 1121211 + 1121211$$

$$2244422 := 10121 \times 101 + 101 \times 12101 = 1022221 + 1222201$$

$$:= 11111 \times 101 + 101 \times 11111 = 1122211 + 1122211$$

$$2248422 := 100401 \times 11 + 11 \times 104001 = 1104411 + 1144011$$

$$:= 101301 \times 11 + 11 \times 103101 = 1114311 + 1134111$$

$$:= 102201 \times 11 + 11 \times 102201 = 1124211 + 1124211$$

$$2264622 := 10201 \times 111 + 111 \times 10201 = 1132311 + 1132311$$

$$:= 10221 \times 101 + 101 \times 12201 = 1032321 + 1232301$$

$$:= 11211 \times 101 + 101 \times 11211 = 1132311 + 1132311$$

$$2284822 := 10321 \times 101 + 101 \times 12301 = 1042421 + 1242401$$

$$:= 11311 \times 101 + 101 \times 11311 = 1142411 + 1142411$$

$$2286822 := 10301 \times 111 + 111 \times 10301 = 1143411 + 1143411$$

$$2310132 := 100011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110001 = 1100121 + 1210011$$

$$2322232 := 100111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111001 = 1101221 + 1221011$$

$$:= 101011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110101 = 1111121 + 1211111$$

$$2326232 := 10031 \times 101 + 101 \times 13001 = 1013131 + 1313101$$

$$:= 11021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12011 = 1113121 + 1213111$$

$$2332332 := 10011 \times 111 + 111 \times 11001 = 1111221 + 1221111$$

$$2334332 := 100211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112001 = 1102321 + 1232011$$

$$:= 101111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111101 = 1112221 + 1222111$$

$$:= 102011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110201 = 1122121 + 1212211$$

$$:= 1031 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1301 = 1032031 + 1302301$$

$$:= 1121 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1211 = 1122121 + 1212211$$

$$2338332 := 1101 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 1011 = 1124121 + 1214211$$

$$2346432 := 100311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113001 = 1103421 + 1243011$$

$$:= 101211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112101 = 1113321 + 1233111$$

$$:= 102111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111201 = 1123221 + 1223211$$

$$:= 103011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110301 = 1133121 + 1213311$$

$$:= 10131 \times 101 + 101 \times 13101 = 1023231 + 1323201$$

$$:= 11121 \times 101 + 101 \times 12111 = 1123221 + 1223211$$

$$:= 1111 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1111 = 1123221 + 1223211$$

$$2354532 := 10111 \times 111 + 111 \times 11101 = 1122321 + 1232211$$

$$:= 1021 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1201 = 1032231 + 1322301$$

$$2358532 := 100411 \times 11 + 11 \times 114001 = 1104521 + 1254011$$

$$:= 101311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113101 = 1114421 + 1244111$$

$$:= 102211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112201 = 1124321 + 1234211$$

$$:= 103111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111301 = 1134221 + 1224311$$

$$:= 104011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110401 = 1144121 + 1214411$$

$$2366632 := 10231 \times 101 + 101 \times 13201 = 1033331 + 1333301$$

$$:= 11221 \times 101 + 101 \times 12211 = 1133321 + 1233311$$

$$2376732 := 10211 \times 111 + 111 \times 11201 = 1133421 + 1243311$$

$$2386832 := 10331 \times 101 + 101 \times 13301 = 1043431 + 1343401$$

$$:= 11321 \times 101 + 101 \times 12311 = 1143421 + 1243411$$

$$2398932 := 10311 \times 111 + 111 \times 11301 = 1144521 + 1254411$$

$$2420242 := 100021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120001 = 1100231 + 1320011$$

$$:= 110011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110011 = 1210121 + 1210121$$

$$:= 10001 \times 121 + 121 \times 10001 = 1210121 + 1210121$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2428242 &:= 10041 \times 101 + 101 \times 14001 = 1014141 + 1414101 \\ &:= 11031 \times 101 + 101 \times 13011 = 1114131 + 1314111 \\ &:= 12021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12021 = 1214121 + 1214121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2432342 &:= 100121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121001 = 1101331 + 1331011 \\ &:= 101021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120101 = 1111231 + 1321111 \\ &:= 110111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111011 = 1211221 + 1221121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2444442 &:= 100221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122001 = 1102431 + 1342011 \\ &:= 101121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121101 = 1112331 + 1332111 \\ &:= 102021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120201 = 1122231 + 1322211 \\ &:= 110211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112011 = 1212321 + 1232121 \\ &:= 111111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111111 = 1222221 + 1222221 \\ &:= 10021 \times 111 + 111 \times 12001 = 1112331 + 1332111 \\ &:= 10101 \times 121 + 121 \times 10101 = 1222221 + 1222221 \\ &:= 11011 \times 111 + 111 \times 11011 = 1222221 + 1222221 \\ &:= 1041 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1401 = 1042041 + 1402401 \\ &:= 1131 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1311 = 1132131 + 1312311 \\ &:= 1221 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1221 = 1222221 + 1222221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2448442 &:= 10141 \times 101 + 101 \times 14101 = 1024241 + 1424201 \\ &:= 11131 \times 101 + 101 \times 13111 = 1124231 + 1324211 \\ &:= 12121 \times 101 + 101 \times 12121 = 1224221 + 1224221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2456542 &:= 100321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123001 = 1103531 + 1353011 \\ &:= 101221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122101 = 1113431 + 1343111 \\ &:= 102121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121201 = 1123331 + 1333211 \\ &:= 103021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120301 = 1133231 + 1323311 \\ &:= 110311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113011 = 1213421 + 1243121 \\ &:= 111211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112111 = 1223321 + 1233221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1112111 &:= 1001 \times 209 + 902 \times 1001 = 209209 + 902902 \\ &:= 1001 \times 308 + 803 \times 1001 = 308308 + 803803 \\ &:= 1001 \times 407 + 704 \times 1001 = 407407 + 704704 \\ &:= 1001 \times 506 + 605 \times 1001 = 506506 + 605605 \\ &:= 2009 \times 101 + 101 \times 9002 = 202909 + 909202 \\ &:= 3008 \times 101 + 101 \times 8003 = 303808 + 808303 \\ &:= 4007 \times 101 + 101 \times 7004 = 404707 + 707404 \\ &:= 5006 \times 101 + 101 \times 6005 = 505606 + 606505 \end{aligned}$$

$$1210121 := 10001 \times 29 + 92 \times 10001 = 290029 + 920092$$

$$:= 10001 \times 38 + 83 \times 10001 = 380038 + 830083$$

$$:= 10001 \times 47 + 74 \times 10001 = 470047 + 740074$$

$$:= 10001 \times 56 + 65 \times 10001 = 560056 + 650065$$

$$:= 20009 \times 11 + 11 \times 90002 = 220099 + 990022$$

$$:= 30008 \times 11 + 11 \times 80003 = 330088 + 880033$$

$$:= 40007 \times 11 + 11 \times 70004 = 440077 + 770044$$

$$:= 50006 \times 11 + 11 \times 60005 = 550066 + 660055$$

$$1222221 := 10101 \times 29 + 92 \times 10101 = 292929 + 929292$$

$$:= 10101 \times 38 + 83 \times 10101 = 383838 + 838383$$

$$:= 10101 \times 47 + 74 \times 10101 = 474747 + 747474$$

$$:= 10101 \times 56 + 65 \times 10101 = 565656 + 656565$$

$$:= 31304 \times 12 + 21 \times 40313 = 375648 + 846573$$

$$:= 2009 \times 111 + 111 \times 9002 = 222999 + 999222$$

$$:= 3008 \times 111 + 111 \times 8003 = 333888 + 888333$$

$$:= 4007 \times 111 + 111 \times 7004 = 444777 + 777444$$

$$:= 5006 \times 111 + 111 \times 6005 = 555666 + 666555$$

$$2004002 := 1001 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1001 = 1002001 + 1002001$$

$$2020202 := 10001 \times 101 + 101 \times 10001 = 1010101 + 1010101$$

$$2040402 := 10101 \times 101 + 101 \times 10101 = 1020201 + 1020201$$

$$2060602 := 10201 \times 101 + 101 \times 10201 = 1030301 + 1030301$$

$$2080802 := 10301 \times 101 + 101 \times 10301 = 1040401 + 1040401$$

$$2114112 := 1011 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1101 = 1012011 + 1102101$$

$$2122212 := 10011 \times 101 + 101 \times 11001 = 1011111 + 1111101$$

$$2142412 := 10111 \times 101 + 101 \times 11101 = 1021211 + 1121201$$

$$2162612 := 10211 \times 101 + 101 \times 11201 = 1031311 + 1131301$$

$$2182812 := 10311 \times 101 + 101 \times 11301 = 1041411 + 1141401$$

$$2200022 := 100001 \times 11 + 11 \times 100001 = 1100011 + 1100011$$

$$2212122 := 100101 \times 11 + 11 \times 101001 = 1101111 + 1111011$$

$$2220222 := 10001 \times 111 + 111 \times 10001 = 1110111 + 1110111$$

$$2224222 := 100201 \times 11 + 11 \times 102001 = 1102211 + 1122011$$

$$:= 101101 \times 11 + 11 \times 101101 = 1112111 + 1121111$$

$$:= 10021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12001 = 1012121 + 1212101$$

$$:= 11011 \times 101 + 101 \times 11011 = 1112111 + 1121111$$

$$:= 1021 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1201 = 1022021 + 1202201$$

$$:= 1111 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1111 = 1112111 + 1121111$$

$$2226222 := 1101 \times 1011 + 1011 \times 1011 = 1113111 + 1131111$$

$$2234322 := 1011 \times 1011 + 1011 \times 1101 = 1022121 + 1212201$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2236322 &:= 100301 \times 11 + 11 \times 103001 = 1103311 + 1133011 & &:= 11121 \times 101 + 101 \times 12111 = 1123221 + 1223211 \\
&:= 101201 \times 11 + 11 \times 102101 = 1113211 + 1123111 & &:= 1111 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1111 = 1123221 + 1223211 \\
2242422 &:= 10101 \times 111 + 111 \times 10101 = 1121211 + 1121211 & &2354532 := 10111 \times 111 + 111 \times 11101 = 1122321 + 1232211 \\
& & & &:= 1021 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1201 = 1032231 + 1322301 \\
2244422 &:= 10121 \times 101 + 101 \times 12101 = 1022221 + 1222201 & &2358532 := 100411 \times 11 + 11 \times 114001 = 1104521 + 1254011 \\
&:= 11111 \times 101 + 101 \times 11111 = 1122211 + 1122211 & &:= 101311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113101 = 1114421 + 1244111 \\
2248422 &:= 100401 \times 11 + 11 \times 104001 = 1104411 + 1144011 & &:= 102211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112201 = 1124321 + 1234211 \\
&:= 101301 \times 11 + 11 \times 103101 = 1114311 + 1134111 & &:= 103111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111301 = 1134221 + 1224311 \\
&:= 102201 \times 11 + 11 \times 102201 = 1124211 + 1124211 & &:= 104011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110401 = 1144121 + 1214411 \\
2264622 &:= 10201 \times 111 + 111 \times 10201 = 1132311 + 1132311 & &2366632 := 10231 \times 101 + 101 \times 13201 = 1033331 + 1333301 \\
&:= 10221 \times 101 + 101 \times 12201 = 1032321 + 1232301 & &:= 11221 \times 101 + 101 \times 12211 = 1133321 + 1233311 \\
&:= 11211 \times 101 + 101 \times 11211 = 1132311 + 1132311 & &2376732 := 10211 \times 111 + 111 \times 11201 = 1133421 + 1243311 \\
2284822 &:= 10321 \times 101 + 101 \times 12301 = 1042421 + 1242401 & &2386832 := 10331 \times 101 + 101 \times 13301 = 1043431 + 1343401 \\
&:= 11311 \times 101 + 101 \times 11311 = 1142411 + 1142411 & &:= 11321 \times 101 + 101 \times 12311 = 1143421 + 1243411 \\
2286822 &:= 10301 \times 111 + 111 \times 10301 = 1143411 + 1143411 & &2398932 := 10311 \times 111 + 111 \times 11301 = 1144521 + 1254411 \\
2310132 &:= 100011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110001 = 1100121 + 1210011 & &2420242 := 100021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120001 = 1100231 + 1320011 \\
& & & &:= 110011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110011 = 1210121 + 1210121 \\
& & & &:= 10001 \times 121 + 121 \times 10001 = 1210121 + 1210121 \\
2322232 &:= 100111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111001 = 1101221 + 1221011 & &2428242 := 10041 \times 101 + 101 \times 14001 = 1014141 + 1414101 \\
&:= 101011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110101 = 1111121 + 1211111 & &:= 11031 \times 101 + 101 \times 13011 = 1114131 + 1314111 \\
& & & &:= 12021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12021 = 1214121 + 1214121 \\
2326232 &:= 10031 \times 101 + 101 \times 13001 = 1013131 + 1313101 & &2432342 := 100121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121001 = 1101331 + 1331011 \\
&:= 11021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12011 = 1113121 + 1213111 & &:= 101021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120101 = 1111231 + 1321111 \\
& & & &:= 110111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111011 = 1211221 + 1221121 \\
2332332 &:= 10011 \times 111 + 111 \times 11001 = 1111221 + 1221111 & &2444442 := 100221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122001 = 1102431 + 1342011 \\
& & & &:= 101121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121101 = 1112331 + 1332111 \\
& & & &:= 102021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120201 = 1122231 + 1322211 \\
& & & &:= 110211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112011 = 1212321 + 1232121 \\
& & & &:= 111111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111111 = 1222221 + 1222221 \\
& & & &:= 10021 \times 111 + 111 \times 12001 = 1112331 + 1332111 \\
& & & &:= 10101 \times 121 + 121 \times 10101 = 1222221 + 1222221 \\
& & & &:= 11011 \times 111 + 111 \times 11011 = 1222221 + 1222221 \\
& & & &:= 1041 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1401 = 1042041 + 1402401 \\
2338332 &:= 1101 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 1011 = 1124121 + 1214211 & & \\
2346432 &:= 100311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113001 = 1103421 + 1243011 & & \\
&:= 101211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112101 = 1113321 + 1233111 & & \\
&:= 102111 \times 11 + 11 \times 111201 = 1123221 + 1223211 & & \\
&:= 103011 \times 11 + 11 \times 110301 = 1133121 + 1213311 & & \\
&:= 10131 \times 101 + 101 \times 13101 = 1023231 + 1323201 & &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1131 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1311 = 1132131 + 1312311 \\ &:= 1221 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1221 = 1222221 + 1222221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2530352} &:= 100031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130001 = 1100341 + 1430011 \\ &:= 110021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120011 = 1210231 + 1320121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2448442} &:= 10141 \times 101 + 101 \times 14101 = 1024241 + 1424201 \\ &:= 11131 \times 101 + 101 \times 13111 = 1124231 + 1324211 \\ &:= 12121 \times 101 + 101 \times 12121 = 1224221 + 1224221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2542452} &:= 100131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131001 = 1101441 + 1441011 \\ &:= 101031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130101 = 1111341 + 1431111 \\ &:= 110121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121011 = 1211331 + 1331121 \\ &:= 111021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120111 = 1221231 + 1321221 \\ &:= 10011 \times 121 + 121 \times 11001 = 1211331 + 1331121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2456542} &:= 100321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123001 = 1103531 + 1353011 \\ &:= 101221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122101 = 1113431 + 1343111 \\ &:= 102121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121201 = 1123331 + 1333211 \\ &:= 103021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120301 = 1133231 + 1323311 \\ &:= 110311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113011 = 1213421 + 1243121 \\ &:= 111211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112111 = 1223321 + 1233221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2554552} &:= 100231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132001 = 1102541 + 1452011 \\ &:= 101131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131101 = 1112441 + 1442111 \\ &:= 102031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130201 = 1122341 + 1432211 \\ &:= 110221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122011 = 1212431 + 1342121 \\ &:= 111121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121111 = 1222331 + 1332221 \\ &:= 112021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120211 = 1232231 + 1322321 \\ &:= 1051 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1501 = 1052051 + 1502501 \\ &:= 1141 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1411 = 1142141 + 1412411 \\ &:= 1231 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1321 = 1232231 + 1322321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2458542} := 1121 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 1211 = 1234221 + 1224321$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2466642} &:= 10121 \times 111 + 111 \times 12101 = 1123431 + 1343211 \\ &:= 11111 \times 111 + 111 \times 11111 = 1233321 + 1233321 \\ &:= 1121 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1211 = 1133331 + 1333311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2556552} &:= 10031 \times 111 + 111 \times 13001 = 1113441 + 1443111 \\ &:= 11021 \times 111 + 111 \times 12011 = 1223331 + 1333221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2468642} &:= 100421 \times 11 + 11 \times 124001 = 1104631 + 1364011 \\ &:= 101321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123101 = 1114531 + 1354111 \\ &:= 102221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122201 = 1124431 + 1344211 \\ &:= 103121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121301 = 1134331 + 1334311 \\ &:= 104021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120401 = 1144231 + 1324411 \\ &:= 110411 \times 11 + 11 \times 114011 = 1214521 + 1254121 \\ &:= 111311 \times 11 + 11 \times 113111 = 1224421 + 1244221 \\ &:= 112211 \times 11 + 11 \times 112211 = 1234321 + 1234321 \\ &:= 10201 \times 121 + 121 \times 10201 = 1234321 + 1234321 \\ &:= 10241 \times 101 + 101 \times 14201 = 1034341 + 1434301 \\ &:= 11231 \times 101 + 101 \times 13211 = 1134331 + 1334311 \\ &:= 12221 \times 101 + 101 \times 12221 = 1234321 + 1234321 \\ &:= 1111 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 1111 = 1134331 + 1334311 \\ &:= 1111 \times 1111 + 1111 \times 1111 = 1234321 + 1234321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2566652} &:= 100331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133001 = 1103641 + 1463011 \\ &:= 101231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132101 = 1113541 + 1453111 \\ &:= 102131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131201 = 1123441 + 1443211 \\ &:= 103031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130301 = 1133341 + 1433311 \\ &:= 110321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123011 = 1213531 + 1353121 \\ &:= 111221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122111 = 1223431 + 1343221 \\ &:= 112121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121211 = 1233331 + 1333321 \\ &:= 113021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120311 = 1243231 + 1323421 \\ &:= 10111 \times 121 + 121 \times 11101 = 1223431 + 1343221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2474742} := 1031 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1301 = 1042341 + 1432401$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2578752} &:= 100431 \times 11 + 11 \times 134001 = 1104741 + 1474011 \\ &:= 101331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133101 = 1114641 + 1464111 \\ &:= 102231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132201 = 1124541 + 1454211 \\ &:= 103131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131301 = 1134441 + 1444311 \\ &:= 104031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130401 = 1144341 + 1434411 \\ &:= 110421 \times 11 + 11 \times 124011 = 1214631 + 1364121 \\ &:= 111321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123111 = 1224531 + 1354221 \\ &:= 112221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122211 = 1234431 + 1344321 \\ &:= 113121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121311 = 1244331 + 1334421 \\ &:= 114021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120411 = 1254231 + 1324521 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2484842} &:= 1021 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 1201 = 1042441 + 1442401 \\ &:= 10221 \times 111 + 111 \times 12201 = 1134531 + 1354311 \\ &:= 10341 \times 101 + 101 \times 14301 = 1044441 + 1444401 \\ &:= 11211 \times 111 + 111 \times 11211 = 1244421 + 1244421 \\ &:= 11331 \times 101 + 101 \times 13311 = 1144431 + 1344411 \\ &:= 12321 \times 101 + 101 \times 12321 = 1244421 + 1244421 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10131 \times 111 + 111 \times 13101 = 1124541 + 1454211 \\ &:= 11121 \times 111 + 111 \times 12111 = 1234431 + 1344321 \\ &:= 1221 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1221 = 1234431 + 1344321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2586852} &:= 1131 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1311 = 1143441 + 1443411 \\ \mathbf{2594952} &:= 1041 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1401 = 1052451 + 1542501 \\ \mathbf{2598952} &:= 1121 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 1211 = 1144541 + 1454411 \\ \mathbf{2620262} &:= 10001 \times 131 + 131 \times 10001 = 1310131 + 1310131 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2640462} &:= 100041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140001 = 1100451 + 1540011 \\ &:= 110031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130011 = 1210341 + 1430121 \\ &:= 120021 \times 11 + 11 \times 120021 = 1320231 + 1320231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2646462} := 10101 \times 131 + 131 \times 10101 = 1323231 + 1323231$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2652562} &:= 100141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141001 = 1101551 + 1551011 \\ &:= 101041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140101 = 1111451 + 1541111 \\ &:= 110131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131011 = 1211441 + 1441121 \\ &:= 111031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130111 = 1221341 + 1431221 \\ &:= 120121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121021 = 1321331 + 1331231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2664662} &:= 100241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142001 = 1102651 + 1562011 \\ &:= 101141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141101 = 1112551 + 1552111 \\ &:= 102041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140201 = 1122451 + 1542211 \\ &:= 110231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132011 = 1212541 + 1452121 \\ &:= 111131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131111 = 1222441 + 1442221 \\ &:= 112031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130211 = 1232341 + 1432321 \\ &:= 120221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122021 = 1322431 + 1342231 \\ &:= 121121 \times 11 + 11 \times 121121 = 1332331 + 1332331 \\ &:= 10021 \times 121 + 121 \times 12001 = 1212541 + 1452121 \\ &:= 11011 \times 121 + 121 \times 11011 = 1332331 + 1332331 \\ &:= 1061 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1601 = 1062061 + 1602601 \\ &:= 1151 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1511 = 1152151 + 1512511 \\ &:= 1241 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1421 = 1242241 + 1422421 \\ &:= 1331 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1331 = 1332331 + 1332331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2668662} &:= 10041 \times 111 + 111 \times 14001 = 1114551 + 1554111 \\ &:= 11031 \times 111 + 111 \times 13011 = 1224441 + 1444221 \\ &:= 12021 \times 111 + 111 \times 12021 = 1334331 + 1334331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2676762} &:= 100341 \times 11 + 11 \times 143001 = 1103751 + 1573011 \\ &:= 101241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142101 = 1113651 + 1563111 \\ &:= 102141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141201 = 1123551 + 1553211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 103041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140301 = 1133451 + 1543311 \\ &:= 110331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133011 = 1213641 + 1463121 \\ &:= 111231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132111 = 1223541 + 1453221 \\ &:= 112131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131211 = 1233441 + 1443321 \\ &:= 113031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130311 = 1243341 + 1433421 \\ &:= 120321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123021 = 1323531 + 1353231 \\ &:= 121221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122121 = 1333431 + 1343331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2688862} &:= 100441 \times 11 + 11 \times 144001 = 1104851 + 1584011 \\ &:= 101341 \times 11 + 11 \times 143101 = 1114751 + 1574111 \\ &:= 102241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142201 = 1124651 + 1564211 \\ &:= 103141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141301 = 1134551 + 1554311 \\ &:= 104041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140401 = 1144451 + 1544411 \\ &:= 110431 \times 11 + 11 \times 134011 = 1214741 + 1474121 \\ &:= 111331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133111 = 1224641 + 1464221 \\ &:= 112231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132211 = 1234541 + 1454321 \\ &:= 113131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131311 = 1244441 + 1444421 \\ &:= 114031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130411 = 1254341 + 1434521 \\ &:= 120421 \times 11 + 11 \times 124021 = 1324631 + 1364231 \\ &:= 121321 \times 11 + 11 \times 123121 = 1334531 + 1354331 \\ &:= 122221 \times 11 + 11 \times 122221 = 1344431 + 1344431 \\ &:= 10121 \times 121 + 121 \times 12101 = 1224641 + 1464221 \\ &:= 11111 \times 121 + 121 \times 11111 = 1344431 + 1344431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2698962} := 1231 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 1321 = 1244541 + 1454421$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2750572} &:= 100051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150001 = 1100561 + 1650011 \\ &:= 110041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140011 = 1210451 + 1540121 \\ &:= 120031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130021 = 1320341 + 1430231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2752572} := 10011 \times 131 + 131 \times 11001 = 1311441 + 1441131$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2762672} &:= 100151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151001 = 1101661 + 1661011 \\ &:= 101051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150101 = 1111561 + 1651111 \\ &:= 110141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141011 = 1211551 + 1551121 \\ &:= 111041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140111 = 1221451 + 1541221 \\ &:= 120131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131021 = 1321441 + 1441231 \\ &:= 121031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130121 = 1331341 + 1431331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2774772} &:= 100251 \times 11 + 11 \times 152001 = 1102761 + 1672011 \\ &:= 101151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151101 = 1112661 + 1662111 \\ &:= 102051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150201 = 1122561 + 1652211 \\ &:= 110241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142011 = 1212651 + 1562121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 111141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141111 = 1222551 + 1552221 \\
&:= 112041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140211 = 1232451 + 1542321 \\
&:= 120231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132021 = 1322541 + 1452231 \\
&:= 121131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131121 = 1332441 + 1442331 \\
&:= 122031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130221 = 1342341 + 1432431 \\
&:= 1071 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1701 = 1072071 + 1702701 \\
&:= 1161 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1611 = 1162161 + 1612611 \\
&:= 1251 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1521 = 1252251 + 1522521 \\
&:= 1341 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1431 = 1342341 + 1432431
\end{aligned}$$

$$2820282 := 10001 \times 141 + 141 \times 10001 = 1410141 + 1410141$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2848482 &:= 100061 \times 11 + 11 \times 160001 = 1100671 + 1760011 \\
&:= 110051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150011 = 1210561 + 1650121 \\
&:= 120041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140021 = 1320451 + 1540231 \\
&:= 130031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130031 = 1430341 + 1430341 \\
&:= 10101 \times 141 + 141 \times 10101 = 1424241 + 1424241
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2872782 &:= 100161 \times 11 + 11 \times 161001 = 1101771 + 1771011 \\
&:= 101061 \times 11 + 11 \times 160101 = 1111671 + 1761111 \\
&:= 110151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151011 = 1211661 + 1661121 \\
&:= 111051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150111 = 1221561 + 1651221 \\
&:= 120141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141021 = 1321551 + 1551231 \\
&:= 121041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140121 = 1331451 + 1541331 \\
&:= 130131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131031 = 1431441 + 1441341
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2884882 &:= 100261 \times 11 + 11 \times 162001 = 1102871 + 1782011 \\
&:= 101161 \times 11 + 11 \times 161101 = 1112771 + 1772111 \\
&:= 102061 \times 11 + 11 \times 160201 = 1122671 + 1762211 \\
&:= 110251 \times 11 + 11 \times 152011 = 1212761 + 1672121 \\
&:= 111151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151111 = 1222661 + 1662221 \\
&:= 112051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150211 = 1232561 + 1652321 \\
&:= 120241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142021 = 1322651 + 1562231 \\
&:= 121141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141121 = 1332551 + 1552331 \\
&:= 122041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140221 = 1342451 + 1542431 \\
&:= 130231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132031 = 1432541 + 1452341 \\
&:= 131131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131131 = 1442441 + 1442441 \\
&:= 10021 \times 131 + 131 \times 12001 = 1312751 + 1572131 \\
&:= 11011 \times 131 + 131 \times 11011 = 1442441 + 1442441 \\
&:= 1081 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1801 = 1082081 + 1802801 \\
&:= 1171 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1711 = 1172171 + 1712711 \\
&:= 1261 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1621 = 1262261 + 1622621 \\
&:= 1351 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1531 = 1352351 + 1532531 \\
&:= 1441 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1441 = 1442441 + 1442441
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2896982 &:= 100361 \times 11 + 11 \times 163001 = 1103971 + 1793011 \\
&:= 101261 \times 11 + 11 \times 162101 = 1113871 + 1783111 \\
&:= 102161 \times 11 + 11 \times 161201 = 1123771 + 1773211 \\
&:= 103061 \times 11 + 11 \times 160301 = 1133671 + 1763311 \\
&:= 110351 \times 11 + 11 \times 153011 = 1213861 + 1683121 \\
&:= 111251 \times 11 + 11 \times 152111 = 1223761 + 1673221 \\
&:= 112151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151211 = 1233661 + 1663321 \\
&:= 113051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150311 = 1243561 + 1653421
\end{aligned}$$

$$2778772 := 10111 \times 131 + 131 \times 11101 = 1324541 + 1454231$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2786872 &:= 100351 \times 11 + 11 \times 153001 = 1103861 + 1683011 \\
&:= 101251 \times 11 + 11 \times 152101 = 1113761 + 1673111 \\
&:= 102151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151201 = 1123661 + 1663211 \\
&:= 103051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150301 = 1133561 + 1653311 \\
&:= 110341 \times 11 + 11 \times 143011 = 1213751 + 1573121 \\
&:= 111241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142111 = 1223651 + 1563221 \\
&:= 112141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141211 = 1233551 + 1553321 \\
&:= 113041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140311 = 1243451 + 1543421 \\
&:= 120331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133021 = 1323641 + 1463231 \\
&:= 121231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132121 = 1333541 + 1453331 \\
&:= 122131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131221 = 1343441 + 1443431 \\
&:= 123031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130321 = 1353341 + 1433531 \\
&:= 10031 \times 121 + 121 \times 13001 = 1213751 + 1573121 \\
&:= 11021 \times 121 + 121 \times 12011 = 1333541 + 1453331
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2798972 &:= 100451 \times 11 + 11 \times 154001 = 1104961 + 1694011 \\
&:= 101351 \times 11 + 11 \times 153101 = 1114861 + 1684111 \\
&:= 102251 \times 11 + 11 \times 152201 = 1124761 + 1674211 \\
&:= 103151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151301 = 1134661 + 1664311 \\
&:= 104051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150401 = 1144561 + 1654411 \\
&:= 110441 \times 11 + 11 \times 144011 = 1214851 + 1584121 \\
&:= 111341 \times 11 + 11 \times 143111 = 1224751 + 1574221 \\
&:= 112241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142211 = 1234651 + 1564321 \\
&:= 113141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141311 = 1244551 + 1554421 \\
&:= 114041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140411 = 1254451 + 1544521 \\
&:= 120431 \times 11 + 11 \times 134021 = 1324741 + 1474231 \\
&:= 121331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133121 = 1334641 + 1464331 \\
&:= 122231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132221 = 1344541 + 1454431 \\
&:= 123131 \times 11 + 11 \times 131321 = 1354441 + 1444531 \\
&:= 124031 \times 11 + 11 \times 130421 = 1364341 + 1434631
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 120341 \times 11 + 11 \times 143021 = 1323751 + 1573231 \\ &:= 121241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142121 = 1333651 + 1563331 \\ &:= 122141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141221 = 1343551 + 1553431 \\ &:= 123041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140321 = 1353451 + 1543531 \\ &:= 130331 \times 11 + 11 \times 133031 = 1433641 + 1463341 \\ &:= 131231 \times 11 + 11 \times 132131 = 1443541 + 1453441 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030303} &:= 10001 \times 102 + 201 \times 10001 = 1020102 + 2010201 \\ &:= 10002 \times 101 + 101 \times 20001 = 1010202 + 2020101 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3050503} := 10102 \times 101 + 101 \times 20101 = 1020302 + 2030201$$

$$\mathbf{3060603} := 10101 \times 102 + 201 \times 10101 = 1030302 + 2030301$$

$$\mathbf{3070703} := 10202 \times 101 + 101 \times 20201 = 1030402 + 2040301$$

$$\mathbf{2962692} := 10011 \times 141 + 141 \times 11001 = 1411551 + 1551141$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3090903} &:= 10201 \times 102 + 201 \times 10201 = 1040502 + 2050401 \\ &:= 10302 \times 101 + 101 \times 20301 = 1040502 + 2050401 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2970792} := 100071 \times 11 + 11 \times 170001 = 1100781 + 1870011$$

$$:= 110061 \times 11 + 11 \times 160011 = 1210671 + 1760121$$

$$:= 120051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150021 = 1320561 + 1650231$$

$$:= 130041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140031 = 1430451 + 1540341$$

$$\mathbf{3116113} := 1012 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2101 = 1013012 + 2103101$$

$$:= 1102 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2011 = 1103102 + 2013011$$

$$\mathbf{3126213} := 1101 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1011 = 1103202 + 2023011$$

$$\mathbf{3132313} := 10012 \times 101 + 101 \times 21001 = 1011212 + 2121101$$

$$:= 11002 \times 101 + 101 \times 20011 = 1111202 + 2021111$$

$$\mathbf{3134313} := 10011 \times 201 + 102 \times 11001 = 2012211 + 1122102$$

$$\mathbf{3152513} := 10112 \times 101 + 101 \times 21101 = 1021312 + 2131201$$

$$:= 11102 \times 101 + 101 \times 20111 = 1121302 + 2031211$$

$$\mathbf{2994992} := 100271 \times 11 + 11 \times 172001 = 1102981 + 1892011$$

$$:= 101171 \times 11 + 11 \times 171101 = 1112881 + 1882111$$

$$:= 102071 \times 11 + 11 \times 170201 = 1122781 + 1872211$$

$$:= 110261 \times 11 + 11 \times 162011 = 1212871 + 1782121$$

$$:= 111161 \times 11 + 11 \times 161111 = 1222771 + 1772221$$

$$:= 112061 \times 11 + 11 \times 160211 = 1232671 + 1762321$$

$$:= 120251 \times 11 + 11 \times 152021 = 1322761 + 1672231$$

$$:= 121151 \times 11 + 11 \times 151121 = 1332661 + 1662331$$

$$:= 122051 \times 11 + 11 \times 150221 = 1342561 + 1652431$$

$$:= 130241 \times 11 + 11 \times 142031 = 1432651 + 1562341$$

$$:= 131141 \times 11 + 11 \times 141131 = 1442551 + 1552441$$

$$:= 132041 \times 11 + 11 \times 140231 = 1452451 + 1542541$$

$$:= 1091 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1901 = 1092091 + 1902901$$

$$:= 1181 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1811 = 1182181 + 1812811$$

$$:= 1271 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1721 = 1272271 + 1722721$$

$$:= 1361 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1631 = 1362361 + 1632631$$

$$:= 1451 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 1541 = 1452451 + 1542541$$

$$\mathbf{3164613} := 10111 \times 201 + 102 \times 11101 = 2032311 + 1132302$$

$$\mathbf{3172713} := 10212 \times 101 + 101 \times 21201 = 1031412 + 2141301$$

$$:= 11202 \times 101 + 101 \times 20211 = 1131402 + 2041311$$

$$\mathbf{3192913} := 10312 \times 101 + 101 \times 21301 = 1041512 + 2151401$$

$$:= 11302 \times 101 + 101 \times 20311 = 1141502 + 2051411$$

$$\mathbf{3194913} := 10211 \times 201 + 102 \times 11201 = 2052411 + 1142502$$

$$\mathbf{3216123} := 1011 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1101 = 1013022 + 2203101$$

$$\mathbf{3226223} := 1022 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2201 = 1023022 + 2203201$$

$$:= 1112 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2111 = 1113112 + 2113111$$

$$:= 1202 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2021 = 1203202 + 2023021$$

$$\mathbf{3230323} := 10001 \times 112 + 211 \times 10001 = 1120112 + 2110211$$

$$\mathbf{3232323} := 10011 \times 102 + 201 \times 11001 = 1021122 + 2211201$$

$$\mathbf{3006003} := 1002 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2001 = 1003002 + 2003001$$

$$\mathbf{3234323} := 10022 \times 101 + 101 \times 22001 = 1012222 + 2222101$$

$$:= 11012 \times 101 + 101 \times 21011 = 1112212 + 2122111$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& := 12002 \times 101 + 101 \times 20021 = 1212202 + 2022121 \\
\mathbf{3238323} & := 10021 \times 201 + 102 \times 12001 = 2014221 + 1224102 \\
& := 1101 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1011 = 1114212 + 2124111 \\
\mathbf{3246423} & := 1102 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 2011 = 1213302 + 2033121 \\
& := 1201 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1021 = 1203402 + 2043021 \\
\mathbf{3254523} & := 10122 \times 101 + 101 \times 22101 = 1022322 + 2232201 \\
& := 11112 \times 101 + 101 \times 21111 = 1122312 + 2132211 \\
& := 12102 \times 101 + 101 \times 20121 = 1222302 + 2032221 \\
\mathbf{3262623} & := 10101 \times 112 + 211 \times 10101 = 1131312 + 2131311 \\
& := 10111 \times 102 + 201 \times 11101 = 1031322 + 2231301 \\
\mathbf{3268623} & := 10121 \times 201 + 102 \times 12101 = 2034321 + 1234302 \\
\mathbf{3274723} & := 10222 \times 101 + 101 \times 22201 = 1032422 + 2242301 \\
& := 11212 \times 101 + 101 \times 21211 = 1132412 + 2142311 \\
& := 12202 \times 101 + 101 \times 20221 = 1232402 + 2042321 \\
\mathbf{3292923} & := 10211 \times 102 + 201 \times 11201 = 1041522 + 2251401 \\
\mathbf{3294923} & := 10201 \times 112 + 211 \times 10201 = 1142512 + 2152411 \\
& := 10322 \times 101 + 101 \times 22301 = 1042522 + 2252401 \\
& := 11312 \times 101 + 101 \times 21311 = 1142512 + 2152411 \\
& := 12302 \times 101 + 101 \times 20321 = 1242502 + 2052421 \\
\mathbf{3298923} & := 10221 \times 201 + 102 \times 12201 = 2054421 + 1244502 \\
\mathbf{3300033} & := 100001 \times 12 + 21 \times 100001 = 1200012 + 2100021 \\
& := 100002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200001 = 1100022 + 2200011 \\
\mathbf{3312133} & := 100102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201001 = 1101122 + 2211011 \\
& := 101002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200101 = 1111022 + 2201111 \\
\mathbf{3314133} & := 100101 \times 21 + 12 \times 101001 = 2102121 + 1212012 \\
\mathbf{3322233} & := 100101 \times 12 + 21 \times 101001 = 1201212 + 2121021 \\
\mathbf{3324233} & := 100202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202001 = 1102222 + 2222011 \\
& := 101102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201101 = 1112122 + 2212111 \\
& := 102002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200201 = 1122022 + 2202211 \\
\mathbf{3328233} & := 100201 \times 21 + 12 \times 102001 = 2104221 + 1224012 \\
& := 1102 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2011 = 1114122 + 2214111 \\
\mathbf{3330333} & := 10002 \times 111 + 111 \times 20001 = 1110222 + 2220111 \\
\mathbf{3336333} & := 100302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203001 = 1103322 + 2233011 \\
& := 101101 \times 12 + 21 \times 101101 = 1213212 + 2123121 \\
& := 101202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202101 = 1113222 + 2223111 \\
& := 102102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201201 = 1123122 + 2213211 \\
& := 103002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200301 = 1133022 + 2203311 \\
& := 10032 \times 101 + 101 \times 23001 = 1013232 + 2323101 \\
& := 11011 \times 102 + 201 \times 11011 = 1123122 + 2213211 \\
& := 11022 \times 101 + 101 \times 22011 = 1113222 + 2223111 \\
& := 12012 \times 101 + 101 \times 21021 = 1213212 + 2123121 \\
& := 13002 \times 101 + 101 \times 20031 = 1313202 + 2023131 \\
& := 1012 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2101 = 1023132 + 2313201 \\
& := 1032 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2301 = 1033032 + 2303301 \\
& := 1111 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1111 = 1113222 + 2223111 \\
& := 1122 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2211 = 1123122 + 2213211 \\
& := 1212 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2121 = 1213212 + 2123121 \\
& := 1302 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2031 = 1303302 + 2033031 \\
\mathbf{3344433} & := 100201 \times 12 + 21 \times 102001 = 1202412 + 2142021 \\
& := 10011 \times 211 + 112 \times 11001 = 2112321 + 1232112 \\
\mathbf{3348433} & := 100402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204001 = 1104422 + 2244011 \\
& := 101302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203101 = 1114322 + 2234111 \\
& := 102202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202201 = 1124222 + 2224211 \\
& := 103102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201301 = 1134122 + 2214311 \\
& := 104002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200401 = 1144022 + 2204411 \\
\mathbf{3352533} & := 10102 \times 111 + 111 \times 20101 = 1121322 + 2231211 \\
\mathbf{3356533} & := 10132 \times 101 + 101 \times 23101 = 1023332 + 2333201 \\
& := 11122 \times 101 + 101 \times 22111 = 1123322 + 2233211 \\
& := 12112 \times 101 + 101 \times 21121 = 1223312 + 2133221 \\
& := 13102 \times 101 + 101 \times 20131 = 1323302 + 2033231 \\
\mathbf{3358533} & := 101201 \times 12 + 21 \times 102101 = 1214412 + 2144121 \\
& := 1112 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 2111 = 1224312 + 2134221 \\
\mathbf{3366633} & := 100301 \times 12 + 21 \times 103001 = 1203612 + 2163021 \\
& := 11111 \times 102 + 201 \times 11111 = 1133322 + 2233311
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1202 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 2021 = 1323402 + 2043231 \\ &:= 1301 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1031 = 1303602 + 2063031 \\ &:= 2001 \times 1031 + 1301 \times 1002 = 2063031 + 1303602 \end{aligned}$$

$$3374733 := 10202 \times 111 + 111 \times 20201 = 1132422 + 2242311$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3376733 &:= 10111 \times 211 + 112 \times 11101 = 2133421 + 1243312 \\ &:= 10232 \times 101 + 101 \times 23201 = 1033432 + 2343301 \\ &:= 11222 \times 101 + 101 \times 22211 = 1133422 + 2243311 \\ &:= 12212 \times 101 + 101 \times 21221 = 1233412 + 2143321 \\ &:= 13202 \times 101 + 101 \times 20231 = 1333402 + 2043331 \\ &:= 1201 \times 1102 + 2011 \times 1021 = 1323502 + 2053231 \end{aligned}$$

$$3388833 := 100401 \times 12 + 21 \times 104001 = 1204812 + 2184021$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3396933 &:= 10302 \times 111 + 111 \times 20301 = 1143522 + 2253411 \\ &:= 10332 \times 101 + 101 \times 23301 = 1043532 + 2353401 \\ &:= 11211 \times 102 + 201 \times 11211 = 1143522 + 2253411 \\ &:= 11322 \times 101 + 101 \times 22311 = 1143522 + 2253411 \\ &:= 12312 \times 101 + 101 \times 21321 = 1243512 + 2153421 \\ &:= 13302 \times 101 + 101 \times 20331 = 1343502 + 2053431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3410143 &:= 100012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210001 = 1100132 + 2310011 \\ &:= 110002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200011 = 1210022 + 2200121 \end{aligned}$$

$$3420243 := 100011 \times 21 + 12 \times 110001 = 2100231 + 1320012$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3422243 &:= 100112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211001 = 1101232 + 2321011 \\ &:= 101012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210101 = 1111132 + 2311111 \\ &:= 110102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201011 = 1211122 + 2211121 \\ &:= 111002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200111 = 1221022 + 2201221 \end{aligned}$$

$$3426243 := 1021 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1201 = 1023042 + 2403201$$

$$3430343 := 10001 \times 122 + 221 \times 10001 = 1220122 + 2210221$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3434343 &:= 100111 \times 21 + 12 \times 111001 = 2102331 + 1332012 \\ &:= 100212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212001 = 1102332 + 2332011 \\ &:= 101112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211101 = 1112232 + 2322111 \\ &:= 102012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210201 = 1122132 + 2312211 \\ &:= 110202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202011 = 1212222 + 2222121 \\ &:= 111102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201111 = 1222122 + 2212221 \\ &:= 112002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200211 = 1232022 + 2202321 \\ &:= 10021 \times 102 + 201 \times 12001 = 1022142 + 2412201 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3438343 &:= 10042 \times 101 + 101 \times 24001 = 1014242 + 2424101 \\ &:= 11032 \times 101 + 101 \times 23011 = 1114232 + 2324111 \\ &:= 12022 \times 101 + 101 \times 22021 = 1214222 + 2224121 \\ &:= 13012 \times 101 + 101 \times 21031 = 1314212 + 2124131 \\ &:= 14002 \times 101 + 101 \times 20041 = 1414202 + 2024141 \\ &:= 20041 \times 101 + 101 \times 14002 = 2024141 + 1414202 \\ &:= 21031 \times 101 + 101 \times 13012 = 2124131 + 1314212 \\ &:= 22021 \times 101 + 101 \times 12022 = 2224121 + 1214222 \\ &:= 23011 \times 101 + 101 \times 11032 = 2324111 + 1114232 \\ &:= 24001 \times 101 + 101 \times 10042 = 2424101 + 1014242 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3442443 &:= 101011 \times 21 + 12 \times 110101 = 2121231 + 1321212 \\ &:= 100312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213001 = 1103432 + 2343011 \\ &:= 101212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212101 = 1113332 + 2333111 \\ &:= 102112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211201 = 1123232 + 2323211 \\ &:= 103012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210301 = 1133132 + 2313311 \\ &:= 110302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203011 = 1213322 + 2233121 \\ &:= 111202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202111 = 1223222 + 2223221 \\ &:= 112102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201211 = 1233122 + 2213321 \\ &:= 113002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200311 = 1243022 + 2203421 \\ &:= 10011 \times 112 + 211 \times 11001 = 1121232 + 2321211 \\ &:= 10012 \times 111 + 111 \times 21001 = 1111332 + 2331111 \\ &:= 11002 \times 111 + 111 \times 20011 = 1221222 + 2221221 \\ &:= 1042 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2401 = 1043042 + 2403401 \\ &:= 1132 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2311 = 1133132 + 2313311 \\ &:= 1222 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2221 = 1223222 + 2223221 \\ &:= 1312 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2131 = 1313312 + 2133131 \\ &:= 1402 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2041 = 1403402 + 2043041 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3448443 &:= 100211 \times 21 + 12 \times 112001 = 2104431 + 1344012 \\ &:= 1112 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2111 = 1124232 + 2324211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3456543 &:= 101111 \times 21 + 12 \times 111101 = 2123331 + 1333212 \\ &:= 1022 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2201 = 1033242 + 2423301 \\ &:= 1211 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1121 = 1213422 + 2243121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3458543 &:= 100412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214001 = 1104532 + 2354011 \\ &:= 101312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213101 = 1114432 + 2344111 \\ &:= 102212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212201 = 1124332 + 2334211 \\ &:= 103112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211301 = 1134232 + 2324311 \\ &:= 104012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210401 = 1144132 + 2314411 \\ &:= 110402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204011 = 1214422 + 2244121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 111302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203111 = 1224322 + 2234221 \\ &:= 112202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202211 = 1234222 + 2224321 \\ &:= 113102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201311 = 1244122 + 2214421 \\ &:= 114002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200411 = 1254022 + 2204521 \\ &:= 10021 \times 211 + 112 \times 12001 = 2114431 + 1344112 \\ &:= 10142 \times 101 + 101 \times 24101 = 1024342 + 2434201 \\ &:= 11132 \times 101 + 101 \times 23111 = 1124332 + 2334211 \\ &:= 12122 \times 101 + 101 \times 22121 = 1224322 + 2234221 \\ &:= 13112 \times 101 + 101 \times 21131 = 1324312 + 2134231 \\ &:= 14102 \times 101 + 101 \times 20141 = 1424302 + 2034241 \\ &:= 1111 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1111 = 1124332 + 2334211 \\ &:= 1111 \times 1102 + 2011 \times 1111 = 1224322 + 2234221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3464643} &:= 102011 \times 21 + 12 \times 110201 = 2142231 + 1322412 \\ &:= 10101 \times 122 + 221 \times 10101 = 1232322 + 2232321 \\ &:= 10112 \times 111 + 111 \times 21101 = 1122432 + 2342211 \\ &:= 10121 \times 102 + 201 \times 12101 = 1032342 + 2432301 \\ &:= 11102 \times 111 + 111 \times 20111 = 1232322 + 2232321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3474743} := 10111 \times 112 + 211 \times 11101 = 1132432 + 2342311$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3478743} &:= 102111 \times 21 + 12 \times 111201 = 2144331 + 1334412 \\ &:= 10242 \times 101 + 101 \times 24201 = 1034442 + 2444301 \\ &:= 11232 \times 101 + 101 \times 23211 = 1134432 + 2344311 \\ &:= 12222 \times 101 + 101 \times 22221 = 1234422 + 2244321 \\ &:= 13212 \times 101 + 101 \times 21231 = 1334412 + 2144331 \\ &:= 14202 \times 101 + 101 \times 20241 = 1434402 + 2044341 \\ &:= 1212 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 2121 = 1334412 + 2144331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3486843} &:= 103011 \times 21 + 12 \times 110301 = 2163231 + 1323612 \\ &:= 10212 \times 111 + 111 \times 21201 = 1133532 + 2353311 \\ &:= 11202 \times 111 + 111 \times 20211 = 1243422 + 2243421 \\ &:= 1302 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 2031 = 1433502 + 2053341 \\ &:= 1401 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1041 = 1403802 + 2083041 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3494943} := 10221 \times 102 + 201 \times 12201 = 1042542 + 2452401$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3498943} &:= 10201 \times 122 + 221 \times 10201 = 1244522 + 2254421 \\ &:= 10342 \times 101 + 101 \times 24301 = 1044542 + 2454401 \\ &:= 11332 \times 101 + 101 \times 23311 = 1144532 + 2354411 \\ &:= 12322 \times 101 + 101 \times 22321 = 1244522 + 2254421 \\ &:= 13312 \times 101 + 101 \times 21331 = 1344512 + 2154431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3498943} := 14302 \times 101 + 101 \times 20341 = 1444502 + 2054441$$

$$\mathbf{3510153} := 100011 \times 12 + 21 \times 110001 = 1200132 + 2310021$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3520253} &:= 100022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220001 = 1100242 + 2420011 \\ &:= 110012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210011 = 1210132 + 2310121 \\ &:= 120002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200021 = 1320022 + 2200231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3524253} := 101011 \times 12 + 21 \times 110101 = 1212132 + 2312121$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3532353} &:= 100111 \times 12 + 21 \times 111001 = 1201332 + 2331021 \\ &:= 100122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221001 = 1101342 + 2431011 \\ &:= 101022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220101 = 1111242 + 2421111 \\ &:= 110112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211011 = 1211232 + 2321121 \\ &:= 111012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210111 = 1221132 + 2311221 \\ &:= 120102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201021 = 1321122 + 2211231 \\ &:= 121002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200121 = 1331022 + 2201331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3538353} &:= 102011 \times 12 + 21 \times 110201 = 1224132 + 2314221 \\ &:= 11021 \times 102 + 201 \times 12011 = 1124142 + 2414211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3540453} := 100021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120001 = 2100441 + 1440012$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3544453} &:= 100222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222001 = 1102442 + 2442011 \\ &:= 101122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221101 = 1112342 + 2432111 \\ &:= 102022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220201 = 1122242 + 2422211 \\ &:= 110212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212011 = 1212332 + 2332121 \\ &:= 111112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211111 = 1222232 + 2322221 \\ &:= 112012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210211 = 1232132 + 2312321 \\ &:= 120202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202021 = 1322222 + 2222231 \\ &:= 121102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201121 = 1332122 + 2212331 \\ &:= 122002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200221 = 1342022 + 2202431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3546453} &:= 101111 \times 12 + 21 \times 111101 = 1213332 + 2333121 \\ &:= 1121 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1211 = 1123242 + 2423211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3554553} &:= 100121 \times 21 + 12 \times 121001 = 2102541 + 1452012 \\ &:= 100211 \times 12 + 21 \times 112001 = 1202532 + 2352021 \\ &:= 10011 \times 221 + 122 \times 11001 = 2212431 + 1342122 \\ &:= 10022 \times 111 + 111 \times 22001 = 1112442 + 2442111 \\ &:= 11012 \times 111 + 111 \times 21011 = 1222332 + 2332221 \\ &:= 12002 \times 111 + 111 \times 20021 = 1332222 + 2222331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3556553 &:= 100322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223001 = 1103542 + 2453011 \\
&:= 101222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222101 = 1113442 + 2443111 \\
&:= 102122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221201 = 1123342 + 2433211 \\
&:= 103022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220301 = 1133242 + 2423311 \\
&:= 110312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213011 = 1213432 + 2343121 \\
&:= 111212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212111 = 1223332 + 2333221 \\
&:= 112112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211211 = 1233232 + 2323321 \\
&:= 113012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210311 = 1243132 + 2313421 \\
&:= 120302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203021 = 1323322 + 2233231 \\
&:= 121202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202121 = 1333222 + 2223331 \\
&:= 122102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201221 = 1343122 + 2213431 \\
&:= 123002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200321 = 1353022 + 2203531 \\
&:= 11011 \times 112 + 211 \times 11011 = 1233232 + 2323321 \\
&:= 1021 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1201 = 1033252 + 2523301 \\
&:= 1052 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2501 = 1053052 + 2503501 \\
&:= 1142 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2411 = 1143142 + 2413411 \\
&:= 1232 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2321 = 1233232 + 2323321 \\
&:= 1322 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2231 = 1323322 + 2233231 \\
&:= 1412 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2141 = 1413412 + 2143141 \\
&:= 1502 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2051 = 1503502 + 2053051
\end{aligned}$$

$$3562653 := 101021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120101 = 2121441 + 1441212$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3568653 &:= 100221 \times 21 + 12 \times 122001 = 2104641 + 1464012 \\
&:= 100422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224001 = 1104642 + 2464011 \\
&:= 101211 \times 12 + 21 \times 112101 = 1214532 + 2354121 \\
&:= 101322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223101 = 1114542 + 2454111 \\
&:= 102222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222201 = 1124442 + 2444211 \\
&:= 103122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221301 = 1134342 + 2434311 \\
&:= 104022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220401 = 1144242 + 2424411 \\
&:= 110412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214011 = 1214532 + 2354121 \\
&:= 111312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213111 = 1224432 + 2344221 \\
&:= 112212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212211 = 1234332 + 2334321 \\
&:= 113112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211311 = 1244232 + 2324421 \\
&:= 114012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210411 = 1254132 + 2314521 \\
&:= 120402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204021 = 1324422 + 2244231 \\
&:= 121302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203121 = 1334322 + 2234331 \\
&:= 122202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202221 = 1344222 + 2224431 \\
&:= 123102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201321 = 1354122 + 2214531 \\
&:= 124002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200421 = 1364022 + 2204631 \\
&:= 11121 \times 102 + 201 \times 12111 = 1134342 + 2434311 \\
&:= 1122 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2211 = 1134342 + 2434311
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3576753 &:= 100311 \times 12 + 21 \times 113001 = 1203732 + 2373021 \\
&:= 101121 \times 21 + 12 \times 121101 = 2123541 + 1453212 \\
&:= 10122 \times 111 + 111 \times 22101 = 1123542 + 2453211 \\
&:= 11112 \times 111 + 111 \times 21111 = 1233432 + 2343321 \\
&:= 12102 \times 111 + 111 \times 20121 = 1343322 + 2233431 \\
&:= 1032 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2301 = 1043352 + 2533401 \\
&:= 1311 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1131 = 1313622 + 2263131
\end{aligned}$$

$$3584853 := 102021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120201 = 2142441 + 1442412$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3588853 &:= 10111 \times 221 + 122 \times 11101 = 2234531 + 1354322 \\
&:= 11111 \times 112 + 211 \times 11111 = 1244432 + 2344421 \\
&:= 1211 \times 1102 + 2011 \times 1121 = 1334522 + 2254331
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3598953 &:= 100411 \times 12 + 21 \times 114001 = 1204932 + 2394021 \\
&:= 102121 \times 21 + 12 \times 121201 = 2144541 + 1454412 \\
&:= 10222 \times 111 + 111 \times 22201 = 1134642 + 2464311 \\
&:= 11212 \times 111 + 111 \times 21211 = 1244532 + 2354421 \\
&:= 11221 \times 102 + 201 \times 12211 = 1144542 + 2454411 \\
&:= 12202 \times 111 + 111 \times 20221 = 1354422 + 2244531 \\
&:= 1312 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 2131 = 1444512 + 2154441
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3630363 &:= 100032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230001 = 1100352 + 2530011 \\
&:= 110011 \times 12 + 21 \times 110011 = 1320132 + 2310231 \\
&:= 110022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220011 = 1210242 + 2420121 \\
&:= 120012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210021 = 1320132 + 2310231 \\
&:= 130002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200031 = 1430022 + 2200341 \\
&:= 10001 \times 132 + 231 \times 10001 = 1320132 + 2310231 \\
&:= 10002 \times 121 + 121 \times 20001 = 1210242 + 2420121
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3636363 &:= 10031 \times 102 + 201 \times 13001 = 1023162 + 2613201 \\
&:= 1031 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1301 = 1033062 + 2603301
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3642463 &:= 100132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231001 = 1101452 + 2541011 \\
&:= 101032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230101 = 1111352 + 2531111 \\
&:= 110122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221011 = 1211342 + 2431121 \\
&:= 111022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220111 = 1221242 + 2421221 \\
&:= 120112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211021 = 1321232 + 2321231 \\
&:= 121012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210121 = 1331132 + 2311331 \\
&:= 130102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201031 = 1431122 + 2211341 \\
&:= 131002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200131 = 1441022 + 2201441
\end{aligned}$$

$$3644463 := 110111 \times 21 + 12 \times 111011 = 2312331 + 1332132$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3652563 &:= 110111 \times 12 + 21 \times 111011 = 1321332 + 2331231 \\
&:= 10011 \times 122 + 221 \times 11001 = 1221342 + 2431221 \\
3654563 &:= 100232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232001 = 1102552 + 2552011 \\
&:= 101132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231101 = 1112452 + 2542111 \\
&:= 102032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230201 = 1122352 + 2532211 \\
&:= 110222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222011 = 1212442 + 2442121 \\
&:= 111122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221111 = 1222342 + 2432221 \\
&:= 112022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220211 = 1232242 + 2422321 \\
&:= 120212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212021 = 1322332 + 2332231 \\
&:= 121112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211121 = 1332232 + 2322331 \\
&:= 122012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210221 = 1342132 + 2312431 \\
&:= 130202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202031 = 1432222 + 2222341 \\
&:= 131102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201131 = 1442122 + 2212441 \\
&:= 132002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200231 = 1452022 + 2202541 \\
&:= 10021 \times 112 + 211 \times 12001 = 1122352 + 2532211 \\
&:= 10102 \times 121 + 121 \times 20101 = 1222342 + 2432221 \\
3658563 &:= 110211 \times 21 + 12 \times 112011 = 2314431 + 1344132 \\
3660663 &:= 100031 \times 21 + 12 \times 130001 = 2100651 + 1560012 \\
3666663 &:= 10032 \times 111 + 111 \times 23001 = 1113552 + 2553111 \\
&:= 100332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233001 = 1103652 + 2563011 \\
&:= 101232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232101 = 1113552 + 2553111 \\
&:= 102132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231201 = 1123452 + 2543211 \\
&:= 103032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230301 = 1133352 + 2533311 \\
&:= 110322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223011 = 1213542 + 2453121 \\
&:= 111111 \times 12 + 21 \times 111111 = 1333332 + 2333331 \\
&:= 111222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222111 = 1223442 + 2443221 \\
&:= 112122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221211 = 1233342 + 2433321 \\
&:= 113022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220311 = 1243242 + 2423421 \\
&:= 120312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213021 = 1323432 + 2343231 \\
&:= 121212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212121 = 1333332 + 2333331 \\
&:= 122112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211221 = 1343232 + 2323431 \\
&:= 123012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210321 = 1353132 + 2313531 \\
&:= 130302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203031 = 1433322 + 2233341 \\
&:= 131202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202131 = 1443222 + 2223441 \\
&:= 132102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201231 = 1453122 + 2213541 \\
&:= 133002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200331 = 1463022 + 2203641 \\
&:= 10101 \times 132 + 231 \times 10101 = 1333332 + 2333331 \\
&:= 10131 \times 102 + 201 \times 13101 = 1033362 + 2633301 \\
&:= 11022 \times 111 + 111 \times 22011 = 1223442 + 2443221 \\
&:= 12012 \times 111 + 111 \times 21021 = 1333332 + 2333331 \\
&:= 13002 \times 111 + 111 \times 20031 = 1443222 + 2223441 \\
&:= 1062 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2601 = 1063062 + 2603601 \\
&:= 1152 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2511 = 1153152 + 2513511 \\
&:= 1221 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1221 = 1223442 + 2443221 \\
&:= 1242 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2421 = 1243242 + 2423421 \\
&:= 1332 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2331 = 1333332 + 2333331 \\
&:= 1422 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2241 = 1423422 + 2243241 \\
&:= 1512 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2151 = 1513512 + 2153151 \\
&:= 1602 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2061 = 1603602 + 2063061 \\
3674763 &:= 100131 \times 21 + 12 \times 131001 = 2102751 + 1572012 \\
&:= 110211 \times 12 + 21 \times 112011 = 1322532 + 2352231 \\
3678763 &:= 100432 \times 11 + 11 \times 234001 = 1104752 + 2574011 \\
&:= 101332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233101 = 1114652 + 2564111 \\
&:= 102232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232201 = 1124552 + 2554211 \\
&:= 103132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231301 = 1134452 + 2544311 \\
&:= 104032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230401 = 1144352 + 2534411 \\
&:= 110422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224011 = 1214642 + 2464121 \\
&:= 111322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223111 = 1224542 + 2454221 \\
&:= 112222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222211 = 1234442 + 2444321 \\
&:= 113122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221311 = 1244342 + 2434421 \\
&:= 114022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220411 = 1254242 + 2424521 \\
&:= 120412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214021 = 1324532 + 2354231 \\
&:= 121312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213121 = 1334432 + 2344331 \\
&:= 122212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212221 = 1344332 + 2334431 \\
&:= 123112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211321 = 1354232 + 2324531 \\
&:= 124012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210421 = 1364132 + 2314631 \\
&:= 130402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204031 = 1434422 + 2244341 \\
&:= 131302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203131 = 1444322 + 2234441 \\
&:= 132202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202231 = 1454222 + 2224541 \\
&:= 133102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201331 = 1464122 + 2214641 \\
&:= 134002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200431 = 1474022 + 2204741 \\
&:= 10021 \times 221 + 122 \times 12001 = 2214641 + 1464122 \\
&:= 10202 \times 121 + 121 \times 20201 = 1234442 + 2444321 \\
&:= 1121 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1211 = 1134452 + 2544311 \\
3682863 &:= 101031 \times 21 + 12 \times 130101 = 2121651 + 1561212 \\
3686863 &:= 10111 \times 122 + 221 \times 11101 = 1233542 + 2453321 \\
&:= 10121 \times 112 + 211 \times 12101 = 1133552 + 2553311
\end{aligned}$$

$$:= 1022 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 2201 = 1043462 + 2643401$$

$$:= 1131 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1311 = 1133262 + 2623311$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3688863} &:= 100231 \times 21 + 12 \times 132001 = 2104851 + 1584012 \\ &:= 111211 \times 12 + 21 \times 112111 = 1334532 + 2354331 \\ &:= 10132 \times 111 + 111 \times 23101 = 1124652 + 2564211 \\ &:= 11122 \times 111 + 111 \times 22111 = 1234542 + 2454321 \\ &:= 12112 \times 111 + 111 \times 21121 = 1344432 + 2344431 \\ &:= 13102 \times 111 + 111 \times 20131 = 1454322 + 2234541 \\ &:= 1132 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2311 = 1144452 + 2544411 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3764673} &:= 100221 \times 12 + 21 \times 122001 = 1202652 + 2562021 \\ &:= 100242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242001 = 1102662 + 2662011 \\ &:= 101142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241101 = 1112562 + 2652111 \\ &:= 102042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240201 = 1122462 + 2642211 \\ &:= 110121 \times 21 + 12 \times 121011 = 2312541 + 1452132 \\ &:= 110232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232011 = 1212552 + 2552121 \\ &:= 111132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231111 = 1222452 + 2542221 \\ &:= 112032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230211 = 1232352 + 2532321 \\ &:= 120222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222021 = 1322442 + 2442231 \\ &:= 121122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221121 = 1332342 + 2432331 \\ &:= 122022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220221 = 1342242 + 2422431 \\ &:= 130212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212031 = 1432332 + 2332341 \\ &:= 131112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211131 = 1442232 + 2322441 \\ &:= 132012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210231 = 1452132 + 2312541 \\ &:= 140202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202041 = 1542222 + 2222451 \\ &:= 141102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201141 = 1552122 + 2212551 \\ &:= 142002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200241 = 1562022 + 2202651 \\ &:= 10011 \times 231 + 132 \times 11001 = 2312541 + 1452132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3720273} := 100021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120001 = 1200252 + 2520021$$

$$\mathbf{3734373} := 101021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120101 = 1212252 + 2522121$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3740473} &:= 100042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240001 = 1100462 + 2640011 \\ &:= 110032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230011 = 1210352 + 2530121 \\ &:= 120022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220021 = 1320242 + 2420231 \\ &:= 130012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210031 = 1430132 + 2310341 \\ &:= 140002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200041 = 1540022 + 2200451 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3768673} &:= 11021 \times 112 + 211 \times 12011 = 1234352 + 2534321 \\ \mathbf{3772773} &:= 111021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120111 = 2331441 + 1441332 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3776773} &:= 100342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243001 = 1103762 + 2673011 \\ &:= 101242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242101 = 1113662 + 2663111 \\ &:= 102142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241201 = 1123562 + 2653211 \\ &:= 103042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240301 = 1133462 + 2643311 \\ &:= 110332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233011 = 1213652 + 2563121 \\ &:= 111232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232111 = 1223552 + 2553221 \\ &:= 112132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231211 = 1233452 + 2543321 \\ &:= 113032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230311 = 1243352 + 2533421 \\ &:= 120322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223021 = 1323542 + 2453231 \\ &:= 121222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222121 = 1333442 + 2443331 \\ &:= 122122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221221 = 1343342 + 2433431 \\ &:= 123022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220321 = 1353242 + 2423531 \\ &:= 130312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213031 = 1433432 + 2343341 \\ &:= 131212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212131 = 1443332 + 2333441 \\ &:= 132112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211231 = 1453232 + 2323541 \\ &:= 133012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210331 = 1463132 + 2313641 \\ &:= 140302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203041 = 1543322 + 2233451 \\ &:= 141202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202141 = 1553222 + 2223551 \\ &:= 142102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201241 = 1563122 + 2213651 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3742473} := 100121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121001 = 1201452 + 2541021$$

$$\mathbf{3748473} := 102021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120201 = 1224252 + 2524221$$

$$\mathbf{3750573} := 110021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120011 = 2310441 + 1440132$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3752573} &:= 100142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241001 = 1101562 + 2651011 \\ &:= 101042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240101 = 1111462 + 2641111 \\ &:= 110132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231011 = 1211452 + 2541121 \\ &:= 111032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230111 = 1221352 + 2531221 \\ &:= 120122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221021 = 1321342 + 2431231 \\ &:= 121022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220121 = 1331242 + 2421331 \\ &:= 130112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211031 = 1431232 + 2321341 \\ &:= 131012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210131 = 1441132 + 2311441 \\ &:= 140102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201041 = 1541122 + 2211451 \\ &:= 141002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200141 = 1551022 + 2201551 \\ &:= 10012 \times 121 + 121 \times 21001 = 1211452 + 2541121 \\ &:= 11002 \times 121 + 121 \times 20011 = 1331242 + 2421331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3756573} := 101121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121101 = 1213452 + 2543121$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 143002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200341 = 1573022 + 2203751 \\
&:= 10112 \times 121 + 121 \times 21101 = 1223552 + 2553221 \\
&:= 11011 \times 122 + 221 \times 11011 = 1343342 + 2433431 \\
&:= 11102 \times 121 + 121 \times 20111 = 1343342 + 2433431 \\
&:= 1031 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1301 = 1043372 + 2733401 \\
&:= 1072 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2701 = 1073072 + 2703701 \\
&:= 1162 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2611 = 1163162 + 2613611 \\
&:= 1252 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2521 = 1253252 + 2523521 \\
&:= 1342 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2431 = 1343342 + 2433431 \\
&:= 1432 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2341 = 1433432 + 2343341 \\
&:= 1522 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2251 = 1523522 + 2253251 \\
&:= 1612 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2161 = 1613612 + 2163161 \\
&:= 1702 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2071 = 1703702 + 2073071
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3778773} &:= 101221 \times 12 + 21 \times 122101 = 1214652 + 2564121 \\
&:= 110221 \times 21 + 12 \times 122011 = 2314641 + 1464132 \\
&:= 10042 \times 111 + 111 \times 24001 = 1114662 + 2664111 \\
&:= 11032 \times 111 + 111 \times 23011 = 1224552 + 2554221 \\
&:= 12022 \times 111 + 111 \times 22021 = 1334442 + 2444331 \\
&:= 13012 \times 111 + 111 \times 21031 = 1444332 + 2334441 \\
&:= 14002 \times 111 + 111 \times 20041 = 1554222 + 2224551
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3780873} := 100041 \times 21 + 12 \times 140001 = 2100861 + 1680012$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3786873} &:= 100321 \times 12 + 21 \times 123001 = 1203852 + 2583021 \\
&:= 111121 \times 21 + 12 \times 121111 = 2333541 + 1453332 \\
&:= 1321 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1231 = 1323642 + 2463231
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3788873} &:= 100442 \times 11 + 11 \times 244001 = 1104862 + 2684011 \\
&:= 101342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243101 = 1114762 + 2674111 \\
&:= 102242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242201 = 1124662 + 2664211 \\
&:= 103142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241301 = 1134562 + 2654311 \\
&:= 104042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240401 = 1144462 + 2644411 \\
&:= 110432 \times 11 + 11 \times 234011 = 1214752 + 2574121 \\
&:= 111332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233111 = 1224652 + 2564221 \\
&:= 112232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232211 = 1234552 + 2554321 \\
&:= 113132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231311 = 1244452 + 2544421 \\
&:= 114032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230411 = 1254352 + 2534521 \\
&:= 120422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224021 = 1324642 + 2464231 \\
&:= 121322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223121 = 1334542 + 2454331 \\
&:= 122222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222221 = 1344442 + 2444431 \\
&:= 123122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221321 = 1354342 + 2434531 \\
&:= 124022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220421 = 1364242 + 2424631
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 130412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214031 = 1434532 + 2354341 \\
&:= 131312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213131 = 1444432 + 2344441 \\
&:= 132212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212231 = 1454332 + 2334541 \\
&:= 133112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211331 = 1464232 + 2324641 \\
&:= 134012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210431 = 1474132 + 2314741 \\
&:= 140402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204041 = 1544422 + 2244451 \\
&:= 141302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203141 = 1554322 + 2234551 \\
&:= 142202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202241 = 1564222 + 2224651 \\
&:= 143102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201341 = 1574122 + 2214751 \\
&:= 144002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200441 = 1584022 + 2204851
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3794973} &:= 100141 \times 21 + 12 \times 141001 = 2102961 + 1692012 \\
&:= 112021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120211 = 2352441 + 1442532
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3830383} &:= 10001 \times 142 + 241 \times 10001 = 1420142 + 2410241 \\
\mathbf{3838383} &:= 10041 \times 102 + 201 \times 14001 = 1024182 + 2814201 \\
\mathbf{3840483} &:= 110021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120011 = 1320252 + 2520231 \\
\mathbf{3846483} &:= 1041 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1401 = 1043082 + 2803401
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3850583} &:= 100052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250001 = 1100572 + 2750011 \\
&:= 110042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240011 = 1210462 + 2640121 \\
&:= 120032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230021 = 1320352 + 2530231 \\
&:= 130022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220031 = 1430242 + 2420341 \\
&:= 140012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210041 = 1540132 + 2310451 \\
&:= 150002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200051 = 1650022 + 2200561
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3854583} := 111021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120111 = 1332252 + 2522331$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3862683} &:= 100152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251001 = 1101672 + 2761011 \\
&:= 101052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250101 = 1111572 + 2751111 \\
&:= 110121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121011 = 1321452 + 2541231 \\
&:= 110142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241011 = 1211562 + 2651121 \\
&:= 111042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240111 = 1221462 + 2641221 \\
&:= 120132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231021 = 1321452 + 2541231 \\
&:= 121032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230121 = 1331352 + 2531331 \\
&:= 130122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221031 = 1431342 + 2431341 \\
&:= 131022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220131 = 1441242 + 2421441 \\
&:= 140112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211041 = 1541232 + 2321451 \\
&:= 141012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210141 = 1551132 + 2311551 \\
&:= 150102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201051 = 1651122 + 2211561 \\
&:= 151002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200151 = 1661022 + 2201661 \\
&:= 10011 \times 132 + 231 \times 11001 = 1321452 + 2541231
\end{aligned}$$

$$3866683 := 10031 \times 112 + 211 \times 13001 = 1123472 + 2743211$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3868683 &:= 112021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120211 = 1344252 + 2524431 \\ &:= 10101 \times 142 + 241 \times 10101 = 1434342 + 2434341 \\ &:= 10141 \times 102 + 201 \times 14101 = 1034382 + 2834301 \end{aligned}$$

$$3870783 := 110031 \times 21 + 12 \times 130011 = 2310651 + 1560132$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3874783 &:= 100252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252001 = 1102772 + 2772011 \\ &:= 101152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251101 = 1112672 + 2762111 \\ &:= 102052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250201 = 1122572 + 2752211 \\ &:= 110242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242011 = 1212662 + 2662121 \\ &:= 111142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241111 = 1222562 + 2652221 \\ &:= 112042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240211 = 1232462 + 2642321 \\ &:= 120232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232021 = 1322552 + 2552231 \\ &:= 121132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231121 = 1332452 + 2542331 \\ &:= 122032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230221 = 1342352 + 2532431 \\ &:= 130222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222031 = 1432442 + 2442341 \\ &:= 131122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221131 = 1442342 + 2432441 \\ &:= 132022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220231 = 1452242 + 2422541 \\ &:= 140212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212041 = 1542332 + 2332451 \\ &:= 141112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211141 = 1552232 + 2322551 \\ &:= 142012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210241 = 1562132 + 2312651 \\ &:= 150202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202051 = 1652222 + 2222561 \\ &:= 151102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201151 = 1662122 + 2212661 \\ &:= 152002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200251 = 1672022 + 2202761 \\ &:= 10021 \times 122 + 221 \times 12001 = 1222562 + 2652221 \\ &:= 10022 \times 121 + 121 \times 22001 = 1212662 + 2662121 \\ &:= 11012 \times 121 + 121 \times 21011 = 1332452 + 2542331 \\ &:= 12002 \times 121 + 121 \times 20021 = 1452242 + 2422541 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3876783 &:= 111121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121111 = 1333452 + 2543331 \\ &:= 1231 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1321 = 1233462 + 2643321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3884883 &:= 110131 \times 21 + 12 \times 131011 = 2312751 + 1572132 \\ &:= 110221 \times 12 + 21 \times 122011 = 1322652 + 2562231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3886883 &:= 100352 \times 11 + 11 \times 253001 = 1103872 + 2783011 \\ &:= 101252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252101 = 1113772 + 2773111 \\ &:= 102152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251201 = 1123672 + 2763211 \\ &:= 103052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250301 = 1133572 + 2753311 \\ &:= 110342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243011 = 1213762 + 2673121 \\ &:= 111242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242111 = 1223662 + 2663221 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 112142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241211 = 1233562 + 2653321$$

$$:= 113042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240311 = 1243462 + 2643421$$

$$:= 120332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233021 = 1323652 + 2563231$$

$$:= 121232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232121 = 1333552 + 2553331$$

$$:= 122132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231221 = 1343452 + 2543431$$

$$:= 123032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230321 = 1353352 + 2533531$$

$$:= 130322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223031 = 1433542 + 2453341$$

$$:= 131222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222131 = 1443442 + 2443441$$

$$:= 132122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221231 = 1453342 + 2433541$$

$$:= 133022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220331 = 1463242 + 2423641$$

$$:= 140312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213041 = 1543432 + 2343451$$

$$:= 141212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212141 = 1553332 + 2333551$$

$$:= 142112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211241 = 1563232 + 2323651$$

$$:= 143012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210341 = 1573132 + 2313751$$

$$:= 150302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203051 = 1653322 + 2233561$$

$$:= 151202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202151 = 1663222 + 2223661$$

$$:= 152102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201251 = 1673122 + 2213761$$

$$:= 153002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200351 = 1683022 + 2203861$$

$$:= 1442 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2441 = 1443442 + 2443441$$

$$:= 1082 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2801 = 1083082 + 2803801$$

$$:= 1172 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2711 = 1173172 + 2713711$$

$$:= 1262 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2621 = 1263262 + 2623621$$

$$:= 1352 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2531 = 1353352 + 2533531$$

$$:= 1532 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2351 = 1533532 + 2353351$$

$$:= 1622 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2261 = 1623622 + 2263261$$

$$:= 1712 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2171 = 1713712 + 2173171$$

$$:= 1802 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2081 = 1803802 + 2083081$$

$$3892983 := 111031 \times 21 + 12 \times 130111 = 2331651 + 1561332$$

$$3898983 := 100452 \times 11 + 11 \times 254001 = 1104972 + 2794011$$

$$:= 101352 \times 11 + 11 \times 253101 = 1114872 + 2784111$$

$$:= 102252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252201 = 1124772 + 2774211$$

$$:= 103152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251301 = 1134672 + 2764311$$

$$:= 104052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250401 = 1144572 + 2754411$$

$$:= 110231 \times 21 + 12 \times 132011 = 2314851 + 1584132$$

$$:= 110442 \times 11 + 11 \times 244011 = 1214862 + 2684121$$

$$:= 111221 \times 12 + 21 \times 122111 = 1334652 + 2564331$$

$$:= 111342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243111 = 1224762 + 2674221$$

$$:= 112242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242211 = 1234662 + 2664321$$

$$:= 113142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241311 = 1244562 + 2654421$$

$$:= 114042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240411 = 1254462 + 2644521$$

$$:= 120432 \times 11 + 11 \times 234021 = 1324752 + 2574231$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 121332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233121 = 1334652 + 2564331 \\
&:= 122232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232221 = 1344552 + 2554431 \\
&:= 123132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231321 = 1354452 + 2544531 \\
&:= 124032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230421 = 1364352 + 2534631 \\
&:= 130422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224031 = 1434642 + 2464341 \\
&:= 131322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223131 = 1444542 + 2454441 \\
&:= 132222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222231 = 1454442 + 2444541 \\
&:= 133122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221331 = 1464342 + 2434641 \\
&:= 134022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220431 = 1474242 + 2424741 \\
&:= 140412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214041 = 1544532 + 2354451 \\
&:= 141312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213141 = 1554432 + 2344551 \\
&:= 142212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212241 = 1564332 + 2334651 \\
&:= 143112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211341 = 1574232 + 2324751 \\
&:= 144012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210441 = 1584132 + 2314851 \\
&:= 150402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204051 = 1654422 + 2244561 \\
&:= 151302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203151 = 1664322 + 2234661 \\
&:= 152202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202251 = 1674222 + 2224761 \\
&:= 153102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201351 = 1684122 + 2214861 \\
&:= 154002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200451 = 1694022 + 2204961 \\
&:= 10021 \times 231 + 132 \times 12001 = 2314851 + 1584132 \\
&:= 10111 \times 132 + 231 \times 11101 = 1334652 + 2564331 \\
&:= 10122 \times 121 + 121 \times 22101 = 1224762 + 2674221 \\
&:= 10131 \times 112 + 211 \times 13101 = 1134672 + 2764311 \\
&:= 10241 \times 102 + 201 \times 14201 = 1044582 + 2854401 \\
&:= 11112 \times 121 + 121 \times 21111 = 1344552 + 2554431 \\
&:= 12102 \times 121 + 121 \times 20121 = 1464342 + 2434641 \\
&:= 1131 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1311 = 1144572 + 2754411
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3930393} &:= 130001 \times 21 + 12 \times 100031 = 2730021 + 1200372 \\
&:= 10002 \times 131 + 131 \times 20001 = 1310262 + 2620131
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3944493} := 101031 \times 12 + 21 \times 130101 = 1212372 + 2732121$$

$$\mathbf{3952593} := 100131 \times 12 + 21 \times 131001 = 1201572 + 2751021$$

$$\mathbf{3956593} := 10102 \times 131 + 131 \times 20101 = 1323362 + 2633231$$

$$\mathbf{3958593} := 102031 \times 12 + 21 \times 130201 = 1224372 + 2734221$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3960693} &:= 100062 \times 11 + 11 \times 260001 = 1100682 + 2860011 \\
&:= 110052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250011 = 1210572 + 2750121 \\
&:= 120021 \times 12 + 21 \times 120021 = 1440252 + 2520441 \\
&:= 120021 \times 21 + 12 \times 120021 = 2520441 + 1440252 \\
&:= 120042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240021 = 1320462 + 2640231 \\
&:= 130032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230031 = 1430352 + 2530341 \\
&:= 140022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220041 = 1540242 + 2420451
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 150012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210051 = 1650132 + 2310561 \\
&:= 160002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200061 = 1760022 + 2200671
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3966693} &:= 101131 \times 12 + 21 \times 131101 = 1213572 + 2753121 \\
&:= 1141 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1411 = 1143282 + 2823411
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3972793} &:= 100162 \times 11 + 11 \times 261001 = 1101782 + 2871011 \\
&:= 101062 \times 11 + 11 \times 260101 = 1111682 + 2861111 \\
&:= 110152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251011 = 1211672 + 2761121 \\
&:= 111052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250111 = 1221572 + 2751221 \\
&:= 120142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241021 = 1321562 + 2651231 \\
&:= 121042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240121 = 1331462 + 2641331 \\
&:= 130132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231031 = 1431452 + 2541341 \\
&:= 131032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230131 = 1441352 + 2531441 \\
&:= 140122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221041 = 1541342 + 2431451 \\
&:= 141022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220141 = 1551242 + 2421551 \\
&:= 150112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211051 = 1651232 + 2321561 \\
&:= 151012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210151 = 1661132 + 2311661 \\
&:= 160102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201061 = 1761122 + 2211671 \\
&:= 161002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200161 = 1771022 + 2201771
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3974793} &:= 100231 \times 12 + 21 \times 132001 = 1202772 + 2772021 \\
&:= 120121 \times 21 + 12 \times 121021 = 2522541 + 1452252 \\
&:= 10011 \times 241 + 142 \times 11001 = 2412651 + 1562142
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3982893} := 120121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121021 = 1441452 + 2541441$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{3984893} &:= 100262 \times 11 + 11 \times 262001 = 1102882 + 2882011 \\
&:= 101162 \times 11 + 11 \times 261101 = 1112782 + 2872111 \\
&:= 102062 \times 11 + 11 \times 260201 = 1122682 + 2862211 \\
&:= 110252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252011 = 1212772 + 2772121 \\
&:= 111152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251111 = 1222672 + 2762221 \\
&:= 112052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250211 = 1232572 + 2752321 \\
&:= 120242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242021 = 1322662 + 2662231 \\
&:= 121142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241121 = 1332562 + 2652331 \\
&:= 122042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240221 = 1342462 + 2642431 \\
&:= 130232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232031 = 1432552 + 2552341 \\
&:= 131132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231131 = 1442452 + 2542441 \\
&:= 132032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230231 = 1452352 + 2532541 \\
&:= 140222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222041 = 1542442 + 2442451 \\
&:= 141122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221141 = 1552342 + 2432551 \\
&:= 142022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220241 = 1562242 + 2422651 \\
&:= 150212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212051 = 1652332 + 2332561
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 151112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211151 = 1662232 + 2322661 \\ &:= 152012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210251 = 1672132 + 2312761 \\ &:= 160202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202061 = 1762222 + 2222671 \\ &:= 161102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201161 = 1772122 + 2212771 \\ &:= 162002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200261 = 1782022 + 2202871 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3988893} &:= 101231 \times 12 + 21 \times 132101 = 1214772 + 2774121 \\ &:= 120221 \times 21 + 12 \times 122021 = 2524641 + 1464252 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3990993} := 110041 \times 21 + 12 \times 140011 = 2310861 + 1680132$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3996993} &:= 100331 \times 12 + 21 \times 133001 = 1203972 + 2793021 \\ &:= 100362 \times 11 + 11 \times 263001 = 1103982 + 2893011 \\ &:= 101262 \times 11 + 11 \times 262101 = 1113882 + 2883111 \\ &:= 102162 \times 11 + 11 \times 261201 = 1123782 + 2873211 \\ &:= 103062 \times 11 + 11 \times 260301 = 1133682 + 2863311 \\ &:= 110352 \times 11 + 11 \times 253011 = 1213872 + 2783121 \\ &:= 111252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252111 = 1223772 + 2773221 \\ &:= 112152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251211 = 1233672 + 2763321 \\ &:= 113052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250311 = 1243572 + 2753421 \\ &:= 120342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243021 = 1323762 + 2673231 \\ &:= 121121 \times 12 + 21 \times 121121 = 1453452 + 2543541 \\ &:= 121242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242121 = 1333662 + 2663331 \\ &:= 122142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241221 = 1343562 + 2653431 \\ &:= 123042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240321 = 1353462 + 2643531 \\ &:= 130332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233031 = 1433652 + 2563341 \\ &:= 131232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232131 = 1443552 + 2553441 \\ &:= 132132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231231 = 1453452 + 2543541 \\ &:= 133032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230331 = 1463352 + 2533641 \\ &:= 140322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223041 = 1543542 + 2453451 \\ &:= 141222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222141 = 1553442 + 2443551 \\ &:= 142122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221241 = 1563342 + 2433651 \\ &:= 143022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220341 = 1573242 + 2423751 \\ &:= 150312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213051 = 1653432 + 2343561 \\ &:= 151212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212151 = 1663332 + 2333661 \\ &:= 152112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211251 = 1673232 + 2323761 \\ &:= 153012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210351 = 1683132 + 2313861 \\ &:= 160302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203061 = 1763322 + 2233671 \\ &:= 161202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202161 = 1773222 + 2223771 \\ &:= 162102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201261 = 1783122 + 2213871 \\ &:= 163002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200361 = 1793022 + 2203971 \\ &:= 10032 \times 121 + 121 \times 23001 = 1213872 + 2783121 \\ &:= 11011 \times 132 + 231 \times 11011 = 1453452 + 2543541 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 11022 \times 121 + 121 \times 22011 = 1333662 + 2663331 \\ &:= 12012 \times 121 + 121 \times 21021 = 1453452 + 2543541 \\ &:= 13002 \times 121 + 121 \times 20031 = 1573242 + 2423751 \\ &:= 1041 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 1401 = 1053492 + 2943501 \\ &:= 1092 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2901 = 1093092 + 2903901 \\ &:= 1182 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2811 = 1183182 + 2813811 \\ &:= 1272 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2721 = 1273272 + 2723721 \\ &:= 1331 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 1331 = 1333662 + 2663331 \\ &:= 1362 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2631 = 1363362 + 2633631 \\ &:= 1452 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2541 = 1453452 + 2543541 \\ &:= 1542 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2451 = 1543542 + 2453451 \\ &:= 1632 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2361 = 1633632 + 2363361 \\ &:= 1722 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2271 = 1723722 + 2273271 \\ &:= 1812 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2181 = 1813812 + 2183181 \\ &:= 1902 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2091 = 1903902 + 2093091 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{3998993} := 11021 \times 122 + 221 \times 12011 = 1344562 + 2654431$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4008004} &:= 1003 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3001 = 1004003 + 3004001 \\ &:= 2002 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2002 = 2004002 + 2004002 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4040404} &:= 10001 \times 103 + 301 \times 10001 = 1030103 + 3010301 \\ &:= 10001 \times 202 + 202 \times 10001 = 2020202 + 2020202 \\ &:= 10003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30001 = 1010303 + 3030101 \\ &:= 20002 \times 101 + 101 \times 20002 = 2020202 + 2020202 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4050504} := 10002 \times 201 + 102 \times 20001 = 2010402 + 2040102$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4060604} &:= 10103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30101 = 1020403 + 3040201 \\ &:= 20102 \times 101 + 101 \times 20102 = 2030302 + 2030302 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4080804} &:= 10101 \times 103 + 301 \times 10101 = 1040403 + 3040401 \\ &:= 10101 \times 202 + 202 \times 10101 = 2040402 + 2040402 \\ &:= 10102 \times 201 + 102 \times 20101 = 2030502 + 2050302 \\ &:= 10203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30201 = 1030503 + 3050301 \\ &:= 20202 \times 101 + 101 \times 20202 = 2040402 + 2040402 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4118114} &:= 1013 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3101 = 1014013 + 3104101 \\ &:= 1103 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3011 = 1104103 + 3014011 \\ &:= 2012 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2102 = 2014012 + 2104102 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4138314} := 1101 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1011 = 1104303 + 3034011$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4142414 &:= 10013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31001 = 1011313 + 3131101 \\ &:= 11003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30011 = 1111303 + 3031111 \\ &:= 20012 \times 101 + 101 \times 21002 = 2021212 + 2121202 \end{aligned}$$

$$4146414 := 10011 \times 301 + 103 \times 11001 = 3013311 + 1133103$$

$$4154514 := 10012 \times 201 + 102 \times 21001 = 2012412 + 2142102$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4162614 &:= 10113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31101 = 1021413 + 3141201 \\ &:= 11103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30111 = 1121403 + 3041211 \\ &:= 20112 \times 101 + 101 \times 21102 = 2031312 + 2131302 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4182814 &:= 10213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31201 = 1031513 + 3151301 \\ &:= 11203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30211 = 1131503 + 3051311 \\ &:= 20212 \times 101 + 101 \times 21202 = 2041412 + 2141402 \end{aligned}$$

$$4184814 := 10112 \times 201 + 102 \times 21101 = 2032512 + 2152302$$

$$4186814 := 10111 \times 301 + 103 \times 11101 = 3043411 + 1143403$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4228224 &:= 1023 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3201 = 1024023 + 3204201 \\ &:= 1113 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3111 = 1114113 + 3114111 \\ &:= 1203 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3021 = 1204203 + 3024021 \\ &:= 2002 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2002 = 2024022 + 2204202 \\ &:= 2022 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2202 = 2024022 + 2204202 \\ &:= 2112 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2112 = 2114112 + 2114112 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4240424 &:= 10001 \times 113 + 311 \times 10001 = 1130113 + 3110311 \\ &:= 10001 \times 212 + 212 \times 10001 = 2120212 + 2120212 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4244424 &:= 10011 \times 202 + 202 \times 11001 = 2022222 + 2222202 \\ &:= 10023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32001 = 1012323 + 3232101 \\ &:= 11013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31011 = 1112313 + 3132111 \\ &:= 12003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30021 = 1212303 + 3032121 \\ &:= 20022 \times 101 + 101 \times 22002 = 2022222 + 2222202 \\ &:= 21012 \times 101 + 101 \times 21012 = 2122212 + 2122212 \end{aligned}$$

$$4252524 := 11002 \times 201 + 102 \times 20011 = 2211402 + 2041122$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4258524 &:= 10022 \times 201 + 102 \times 22001 = 2014422 + 2244102 \\ &:= 1103 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 3011 = 1214403 + 3044121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4264624 &:= 10123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32101 = 1022423 + 3242201 \\ &:= 11113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31111 = 1122413 + 3142211 \\ &:= 12103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30121 = 1222403 + 3042221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 20122 \times 101 + 101 \times 22102 = 2032322 + 2232302 \\ &:= 21112 \times 101 + 101 \times 21112 = 2132312 + 2132312 \end{aligned}$$

$$4268624 := 1201 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1021 = 1204603 + 3064021$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4282824 &:= 10101 \times 113 + 311 \times 10101 = 1141413 + 3141411 \\ &:= 10101 \times 212 + 212 \times 10101 = 2141412 + 2141412 \\ &:= 11102 \times 201 + 102 \times 20111 = 2231502 + 2051322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4284824 &:= 10111 \times 202 + 202 \times 11101 = 2042422 + 2242402 \\ &:= 10223 \times 101 + 101 \times 32201 = 1032523 + 3252301 \\ &:= 11213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31211 = 1132513 + 3152311 \\ &:= 12203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30221 = 1232503 + 3052321 \\ &:= 20222 \times 101 + 101 \times 22202 = 2042422 + 2242402 \\ &:= 21212 \times 101 + 101 \times 21212 = 2142412 + 2142412 \end{aligned}$$

$$4288824 := 10122 \times 201 + 102 \times 22101 = 2034522 + 2254302$$

$$4318134 := 1011 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1101 = 1014033 + 3304101$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4338334 &:= 1033 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3301 = 1034033 + 3304301 \\ &:= 1123 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3211 = 1124123 + 3214211 \\ &:= 1213 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3121 = 1214213 + 3124121 \\ &:= 1303 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3031 = 1304303 + 3034031 \\ &:= 2032 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2302 = 2034032 + 2304302 \\ &:= 2122 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2212 = 2124122 + 2214212 \end{aligned}$$

$$4342434 := 10011 \times 103 + 301 \times 11001 = 1031133 + 3311301$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4346434 &:= 10033 \times 101 + 101 \times 33001 = 1013333 + 3333101 \\ &:= 11023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32011 = 1113323 + 3233111 \\ &:= 12013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31021 = 1213313 + 3133121 \\ &:= 13003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30031 = 1313303 + 3033131 \\ &:= 20032 \times 101 + 101 \times 23002 = 2023322 + 2323202 \\ &:= 21022 \times 101 + 101 \times 22012 = 2123222 + 2223212 \end{aligned}$$

$$4348434 := 2012 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2102 = 2034132 + 2314302$$

$$4350534 := 10002 \times 211 + 112 \times 20001 = 2110422 + 2240112$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4356534 &:= 10011 \times 311 + 113 \times 11001 = 3113421 + 1243113 \\ &:= 11012 \times 201 + 102 \times 21011 = 2213412 + 2143122 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4366634 &:= 10133 \times 101 + 101 \times 33101 = 1023433 + 3343201 \\ &:= 11123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32111 = 1123423 + 3243211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 12113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31121 = 1223413 + 3143221 \\ &:= 13103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30131 = 1323403 + 3043231 \\ &:= 20132 \times 101 + 101 \times 23102 = 2033332 + 2333302 \\ &:= 21122 \times 101 + 101 \times 22112 = 2133322 + 2233312 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 101203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302101 = 1113233 + 3323111 \\ &:= 102103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301201 = 1123133 + 3313211 \\ &:= 103003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300301 = 1133033 + 3303311 \\ &:= 200302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203002 = 2203322 + 2233022 \\ &:= 201202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202102 = 2213222 + 2223122 \end{aligned}$$

$$4378734 := 1203 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 3021 = 1324503 + 3054231$$

$$4438344 := 1013 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 3101 = 1024143 + 3414201$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4382834 &:= 10102 \times 211 + 112 \times 20101 = 2131522 + 2251312 \\ &:= 10111 \times 103 + 301 \times 11101 = 1041433 + 3341401 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4440444 &:= 10001 \times 123 + 321 \times 10001 = 1230123 + 3210321 \\ &:= 10001 \times 222 + 222 \times 10001 = 2220222 + 2220222 \\ &:= 10003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30001 = 1110333 + 3330111 \\ &:= 20002 \times 111 + 111 \times 20002 = 2220222 + 2220222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4386834 &:= 10233 \times 101 + 101 \times 33201 = 1033533 + 3353301 \\ &:= 11112 \times 201 + 102 \times 21111 = 2233512 + 2153322 \\ &:= 11223 \times 101 + 101 \times 32211 = 1133523 + 3253311 \\ &:= 12213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31221 = 1233513 + 3153321 \\ &:= 13203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30231 = 1333503 + 3053331 \\ &:= 20232 \times 101 + 101 \times 23202 = 2043432 + 2343402 \\ &:= 21222 \times 101 + 101 \times 22212 = 2143422 + 2243412 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4448444 &:= 100201 \times 22 + 22 \times 102001 = 2204422 + 2244022 \\ &:= 100403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304001 = 1104433 + 3344011 \\ &:= 101101 \times 13 + 31 \times 101101 = 1314313 + 3134131 \\ &:= 101101 \times 22 + 22 \times 101101 = 2224222 + 2224222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4398934 &:= 10111 \times 311 + 113 \times 11101 = 3144521 + 1254413 \\ &:= 1201 \times 1103 + 3011 \times 1021 = 1324703 + 3074231 \\ &:= 1301 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1031 = 1304903 + 3094031 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 102203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302201 = 1124233 + 3324211 \\ &:= 103103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301301 = 1134133 + 3314311 \\ &:= 104003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300401 = 1144033 + 3304411 \\ &:= 200402 \times 11 + 11 \times 204002 = 2204422 + 2244022 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4400044 &:= 100001 \times 13 + 31 \times 100001 = 1300013 + 3100031 \\ &:= 100001 \times 22 + 22 \times 100001 = 2200022 + 2200022 \\ &:= 100003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300001 = 1100033 + 3300011 \\ &:= 200002 \times 11 + 11 \times 200002 = 2200022 + 2200022 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 201302 \times 11 + 11 \times 203102 = 2214322 + 2234122 \\ &:= 202202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202202 = 2224222 + 2224222 \\ &:= 10021 \times 202 + 202 \times 12001 = 2024242 + 2424202 \\ &:= 10043 \times 101 + 101 \times 34001 = 1014343 + 3434101 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4412144 &:= 100103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301001 = 1101133 + 3311011 \\ &:= 101003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300101 = 1111033 + 3301111 \\ &:= 200102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201002 = 2201122 + 2211022 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 11011 \times 103 + 301 \times 11011 = 1134133 + 3314311 \\ &:= 11011 \times 202 + 202 \times 11011 = 2224222 + 2224222 \\ &:= 11033 \times 101 + 101 \times 33011 = 1114333 + 3334111 \\ &:= 12023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32021 = 1214323 + 3234121 \end{aligned}$$

$$4416144 := 100101 \times 31 + 13 \times 101001 = 3103131 + 1313013$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 13013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31031 = 1314313 + 3134131 \\ &:= 20042 \times 101 + 101 \times 24002 = 2024242 + 2424202 \\ &:= 21032 \times 101 + 101 \times 23012 = 2124232 + 2324212 \\ &:= 22022 \times 101 + 101 \times 22022 = 2224222 + 2224222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4424244 &:= 100101 \times 22 + 22 \times 101001 = 2202222 + 2222022 \\ &:= 100203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302001 = 1102233 + 3322011 \\ &:= 101103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301101 = 1112133 + 3312111 \\ &:= 102003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300201 = 1122033 + 3302211 \\ &:= 200202 \times 11 + 11 \times 202002 = 2202222 + 2222022 \\ &:= 201102 \times 11 + 11 \times 201102 = 2212122 + 2212122 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 14003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30041 = 1414303 + 3034141 \\ &:= 1043 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3401 = 1044043 + 3404401 \\ &:= 1111 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1111 = 1114333 + 3334111 \\ &:= 1133 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3311 = 1134133 + 3314311 \end{aligned}$$

$$4432344 := 100101 \times 13 + 31 \times 101001 = 1301313 + 3131031$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1223 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3221 = 1224223 + 3224221 \\ &:= 1313 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3131 = 1314313 + 3134131 \\ &:= 1403 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3041 = 1404403 + 3044041 \\ &:= 2002 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 2002 = 2044042 + 2404402 \end{aligned}$$

$$4436344 := 100303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303001 = 1103333 + 3333011$$

$$:= 2002 \times 1111 + 1111 \times 2002 = 2224222 + 2224222$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 2042 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2402 = 2044042 + 2404402 \\ &:= 2132 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2312 = 2134132 + 2314312 \\ &:= 2222 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2222 = 2224222 + 2224222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4454544} &:= 10011 \times 212 + 212 \times 11001 = 2122332 + 2332212 \\ &:= 12002 \times 201 + 102 \times 20021 = 2412402 + 2042142 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4462644} &:= 10103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30101 = 1121433 + 3341211 \\ &:= 20102 \times 111 + 111 \times 20102 = 2231322 + 2231322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4464644} &:= 100201 \times 13 + 31 \times 102001 = 1302613 + 3162031 \\ &:= 10012 \times 211 + 112 \times 21001 = 2112532 + 2352112 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4468644} &:= 10143 \times 101 + 101 \times 34101 = 1024443 + 3444201 \\ &:= 11133 \times 101 + 101 \times 33111 = 1124433 + 3344211 \\ &:= 12123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32121 = 1224423 + 3244221 \\ &:= 13113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31131 = 1324413 + 3144231 \\ &:= 14103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30141 = 1424403 + 3044241 \\ &:= 20142 \times 101 + 101 \times 24102 = 2034342 + 2434302 \\ &:= 2022 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2202 = 2044242 + 2424402 \\ &:= 21132 \times 101 + 101 \times 23112 = 2134332 + 2334312 \\ &:= 22122 \times 101 + 101 \times 22122 = 2234322 + 2234322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4484844} &:= 10101 \times 123 + 321 \times 10101 = 1242423 + 3242421 \\ &:= 10101 \times 222 + 222 \times 10101 = 2242422 + 2242422 \\ &:= 10203 \times 111 + 111 \times 30201 = 1132533 + 3352311 \\ &:= 12102 \times 201 + 102 \times 20121 = 2432502 + 2052342 \\ &:= 20202 \times 111 + 111 \times 20202 = 2242422 + 2242422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4488844} &:= 10121 \times 202 + 202 \times 12101 = 2044442 + 2444402 \\ &:= 10243 \times 101 + 101 \times 34201 = 1034543 + 3454301 \\ &:= 11111 \times 103 + 301 \times 11111 = 1144433 + 3344411 \\ &:= 11111 \times 202 + 202 \times 11111 = 2244422 + 2244422 \\ &:= 11233 \times 101 + 101 \times 33211 = 1134533 + 3354311 \\ &:= 12223 \times 101 + 101 \times 32221 = 1234523 + 3254321 \\ &:= 13213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31231 = 1334513 + 3154331 \\ &:= 14203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30241 = 1434503 + 3054341 \\ &:= 20242 \times 101 + 101 \times 24202 = 2044442 + 2444402 \\ &:= 21232 \times 101 + 101 \times 23212 = 2144432 + 2344412 \\ &:= 22222 \times 101 + 101 \times 22222 = 2244422 + 2244422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4496944} &:= 100301 \times 13 + 31 \times 103001 = 1303913 + 3193031 \\ &:= 10111 \times 212 + 212 \times 11101 = 2143532 + 2353412 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10112 \times 211 + 112 \times 21101 = 2133632 + 2363312 \\ &:= 11101 \times 212 + 212 \times 10111 = 2353412 + 2143532 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4498944} &:= 1303 \times 1101 + 1011 \times 3031 = 1434603 + 3064341 \\ \mathbf{4500054} &:= 100002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200001 = 2100042 + 2400012 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4510154} &:= 100013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310001 = 1100143 + 3410011 \\ &:= 110003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300011 = 1210033 + 3300121 \\ &:= 200012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210002 = 2200132 + 2310022 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4514154} := 100102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201001 = 2102142 + 2412012$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4522254} &:= 100113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311001 = 1101243 + 3421011 \\ &:= 101002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200101 = 2121042 + 2401212 \\ &:= 101013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310101 = 1111143 + 3411111 \\ &:= 110103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301011 = 1211133 + 3311121 \\ &:= 111003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300111 = 1221033 + 3301221 \\ &:= 200112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211002 = 2201232 + 2321022 \\ &:= 201012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210102 = 2211132 + 2311122 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4528254} := 100202 \times 21 + 12 \times 202001 = 2104242 + 2424012$$

$$\mathbf{4530354} := 100011 \times 31 + 13 \times 110001 = 3100341 + 1430013$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4534354} &:= 100213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312001 = 1102343 + 3432011 \\ &:= 101113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311101 = 1112243 + 3422111 \\ &:= 102013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310201 = 1122143 + 3412211 \\ &:= 110203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302011 = 1212233 + 3322121 \\ &:= 111103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301111 = 1222133 + 3312221 \\ &:= 112003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300211 = 1232033 + 3302321 \\ &:= 200212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212002 = 2202332 + 2332022 \\ &:= 201112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211102 = 2212232 + 2322122 \\ &:= 202012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210202 = 2222132 + 2312222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4536354} := 101102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201101 = 2123142 + 2413212$$

$$\mathbf{4544454} := 102002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200201 = 2142042 + 2402412$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4546454} &:= 100111 \times 31 + 13 \times 111001 = 3103441 + 1443013 \\ &:= 100313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313001 = 1103443 + 3443011 \\ &:= 101213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312101 = 1113343 + 3433111 \\ &:= 102113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311201 = 1123243 + 3423211 \\ &:= 103013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310301 = 1133143 + 3413311 \\ &:= 110303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303011 = 1213333 + 3333121 \\ &:= 111203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302111 = 1223233 + 3323221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 112103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301211 = 1233133 + 3313321 \\ &:= 113003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300311 = 1243033 + 3303421 \\ &:= 200312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213002 = 2203432 + 2343022 \\ &:= 201212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212102 = 2213332 + 2333122 \\ &:= 202112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211202 = 2223232 + 2323222 \\ &:= 203012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210302 = 2233132 + 2313322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4566654} &:= 103002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200301 = 2163042 + 2403612 \\ &:= 10011 \times 321 + 123 \times 11001 = 3213531 + 1353123 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4574754} &:= 10113 \times 111 + 111 \times 31101 = 1122543 + 3452211 \\ &:= 11103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30111 = 1232433 + 3342321 \\ &:= 20112 \times 111 + 111 \times 21102 = 2232432 + 2342322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4552554} &:= 10011 \times 113 + 311 \times 11001 = 1131243 + 3421311 \\ &:= 10013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31001 = 1111443 + 3441111 \\ &:= 11003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30011 = 1221333 + 3331221 \\ &:= 20012 \times 111 + 111 \times 21002 = 2221332 + 2331222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4578754} &:= 101111 \times 31 + 13 \times 111101 = 3134441 + 1444313 \\ &:= 10022 \times 211 + 112 \times 22001 = 2114642 + 2464112 \\ &:= 1211 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1121 = 1214633 + 3364121 \\ &:= 2012 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 2102 = 2054252 + 2524502 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4558554} &:= 100413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314001 = 1104543 + 3454011 \\ &:= 101313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313101 = 1114443 + 3444111 \\ &:= 102102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201201 = 2144142 + 2414412 \\ &:= 102213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312201 = 1124343 + 3434211 \\ &:= 103113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311301 = 1134243 + 3424311 \\ &:= 104013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310401 = 1144143 + 3414411 \\ &:= 110403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304011 = 1214433 + 3344121 \\ &:= 111303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303111 = 1224333 + 3334221 \\ &:= 112203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302211 = 1234233 + 3324321 \\ &:= 113103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301311 = 1244133 + 3314421 \\ &:= 114003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300411 = 1254033 + 3304521 \\ &:= 200412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214002 = 2204532 + 2354022 \\ &:= 201312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213102 = 2214432 + 2344122 \\ &:= 202212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212202 = 2224332 + 2334222 \\ &:= 203112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211302 = 2234232 + 2324322 \\ &:= 204012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210402 = 2244132 + 2314422 \\ &:= 12012 \times 201 + 102 \times 21021 = 2414412 + 2144142 \\ &:= 1023 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 3201 = 1034253 + 3524301 \\ &:= 1053 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3501 = 1054053 + 3504501 \\ &:= 1143 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3411 = 1144143 + 3414411 \\ &:= 1233 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3321 = 1234233 + 3324321 \\ &:= 1323 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3231 = 1324323 + 3234231 \\ &:= 1413 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3141 = 1414413 + 3144141 \\ &:= 1503 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3051 = 1504503 + 3054051 \\ &:= 2052 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2502 = 2054052 + 2504502 \\ &:= 2142 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2412 = 2144142 + 2414412 \\ &:= 2232 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2322 = 2234232 + 2324322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4588854} &:= 104002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200401 = 2184042 + 2404812 \\ &:= 12112 \times 201 + 102 \times 21121 = 2434512 + 2154342 \\ &:= 2032 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 2302 = 2054352 + 2534502 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4594954} &:= 102011 \times 31 + 13 \times 110201 = 3162341 + 1432613 \\ &:= 10111 \times 113 + 311 \times 11101 = 1142543 + 3452411 \\ &:= 11102 \times 211 + 112 \times 20111 = 2342522 + 2252432 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4596954} &:= 10213 \times 111 + 111 \times 31201 = 1133643 + 3463311 \\ &:= 11203 \times 111 + 111 \times 30211 = 1243533 + 3353421 \\ &:= 20212 \times 111 + 111 \times 21202 = 2243532 + 2353422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4620264} &:= 100011 \times 22 + 22 \times 110001 = 2200242 + 2420022 \\ &:= 100012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210001 = 2100252 + 2520012 \\ &:= 100023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320001 = 1100253 + 3520011 \\ &:= 110013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310011 = 1210143 + 3410121 \\ &:= 120003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300021 = 1320033 + 3300231 \\ &:= 200022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220002 = 2200242 + 2420022 \\ &:= 210012 \times 11 + 11 \times 210012 = 2310132 + 2310132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4628264} := 1021 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1201 = 1024063 + 3604201$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4632364} &:= 100123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321001 = 1101353 + 3531011 \\ &:= 101023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320101 = 1111253 + 3521111 \\ &:= 110113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311011 = 1211243 + 3421121 \\ &:= 111013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310111 = 1221143 + 3411221 \\ &:= 120103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301021 = 1321133 + 3311231 \\ &:= 121003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300121 = 1331033 + 3301331 \\ &:= 200122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221002 = 2201342 + 2431022 \\ &:= 201022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220102 = 2211242 + 2421122 \\ &:= 210112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211012 = 2311232 + 2321132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4562654} &:= 101011 \times 31 + 13 \times 110101 = 3131341 + 1431313 \\ &:= 11002 \times 211 + 112 \times 20011 = 2321422 + 2241232 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4634364 &:= 100112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211001 = 2102352 + 2532012 \\
4640464 &:= 10001 \times 133 + 331 \times 10001 = 1330133 + 3310331 \\
&:= 10001 \times 232 + 232 \times 10001 = 2320232 + 2320232 \\
4642464 &:= 101012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210101 = 2121252 + 2521212 \\
4644464 &:= 100111 \times 22 + 22 \times 111001 = 2202442 + 2442022 \\
&:= 100223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322001 = 1102453 + 3542011 \\
&:= 101011 \times 22 + 22 \times 110101 = 2222242 + 2422222 \\
&:= 101123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321101 = 1112353 + 3532111 \\
&:= 102023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320201 = 1122253 + 3522211 \\
&:= 110213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312011 = 1212343 + 3432121 \\
&:= 111113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311111 = 1222243 + 3422221 \\
&:= 112013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310211 = 1232143 + 3412321 \\
&:= 120203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302021 = 1322233 + 3322231 \\
&:= 121103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301121 = 1332133 + 3312331 \\
&:= 122003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300221 = 1342033 + 3302431 \\
&:= 200222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222002 = 2202442 + 2442022 \\
&:= 201122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221102 = 2212342 + 2432122 \\
&:= 202022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220202 = 2222242 + 2422222 \\
&:= 210212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212012 = 2312332 + 2332132 \\
&:= 211112 \times 11 + 11 \times 211112 = 2322232 + 2322232 \\
&:= 10021 \times 103 + 301 \times 12001 = 1032163 + 3612301 \\
4648464 &:= 100212 \times 21 + 12 \times 212001 = 2104452 + 2544012 \\
4650564 &:= 10002 \times 221 + 122 \times 20001 = 2210442 + 2440122 \\
4656564 &:= 100323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323001 = 1103553 + 3553011 \\
&:= 101112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211101 = 2123352 + 2533212 \\
&:= 101223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322101 = 1113453 + 3543111 \\
&:= 102123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321201 = 1123353 + 3533211 \\
&:= 103023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320301 = 1133253 + 3523311 \\
&:= 110313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313011 = 1213443 + 3443121 \\
&:= 111213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312111 = 1223343 + 3433221 \\
&:= 112113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311211 = 1233243 + 3423321 \\
&:= 113013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310311 = 1243143 + 3413421 \\
&:= 120303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303021 = 1323333 + 3333231 \\
&:= 121203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302121 = 1333233 + 3323331 \\
&:= 122103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301221 = 1343133 + 3313431 \\
&:= 123003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300321 = 1353033 + 3303531 \\
&:= 200322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223002 = 2203542 + 2453022 \\
&:= 201222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222102 = 2213442 + 2443122 \\
&:= 202122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221202 = 2223342 + 2433222 \\
&:= 203022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220302 = 2233242 + 2423322 \\
&:= 210312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213012 = 2313432 + 2343132 \\
&:= 211212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212112 = 2323332 + 2333232 \\
&:= 13002 \times 201 + 102 \times 20031 = 2613402 + 2043162 \\
4660664 &:= 100021 \times 31 + 13 \times 120001 = 3100651 + 1560013 \\
4664664 &:= 102012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210201 = 2142252 + 2522412 \\
&:= 10011 \times 222 + 222 \times 11001 = 2222442 + 2442222 \\
&:= 10023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32001 = 1112553 + 3552111 \\
&:= 11013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31011 = 1222443 + 3442221 \\
&:= 12003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30021 = 1332333 + 3332331 \\
&:= 20022 \times 111 + 111 \times 22002 = 2222442 + 2442222 \\
&:= 21012 \times 111 + 111 \times 21012 = 2332332 + 2332332 \\
4668664 &:= 100211 \times 22 + 22 \times 112001 = 2204642 + 2464022 \\
&:= 100423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324001 = 1104653 + 3564011 \\
&:= 101111 \times 22 + 22 \times 111101 = 2224442 + 2444222 \\
&:= 101323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323101 = 1114553 + 3554111 \\
&:= 102011 \times 22 + 22 \times 110201 = 2244242 + 2424422 \\
&:= 102223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322201 = 1124453 + 3544211 \\
&:= 103123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321301 = 1134353 + 3534311 \\
&:= 104023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320401 = 1144253 + 3524411 \\
&:= 110413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314011 = 1214543 + 3454121 \\
&:= 111313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313111 = 1224443 + 3444221 \\
&:= 112213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312211 = 1234343 + 3434321 \\
&:= 113113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311311 = 1244243 + 3424421 \\
&:= 114013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310411 = 1254143 + 3414521 \\
&:= 120403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304021 = 1324433 + 3344231 \\
&:= 121303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303121 = 1334333 + 3334331 \\
&:= 122203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302221 = 1344233 + 3324431 \\
&:= 123103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301321 = 1354133 + 3314531 \\
&:= 124003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300421 = 1364033 + 3304631 \\
&:= 200422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224002 = 2204642 + 2464022 \\
&:= 201322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223102 = 2214542 + 2454122 \\
&:= 202222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222202 = 2224442 + 2444222 \\
&:= 203122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221302 = 2234342 + 2434322 \\
&:= 204022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220402 = 2244242 + 2424422 \\
&:= 210412 \times 11 + 11 \times 214012 = 2314532 + 2354132 \\
&:= 211312 \times 11 + 11 \times 213112 = 2324432 + 2344232 \\
&:= 212212 \times 11 + 11 \times 212212 = 2334332 + 2334332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 10021 \times 212 + 212 \times 12001 = 2124452 + 2544212 \\
&:= 11011 \times 113 + 311 \times 11011 = 1244243 + 3424421 \\
&:= 11011 \times 212 + 212 \times 11011 = 2334332 + 2334332 \\
&:= 1063 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3601 = 1064063 + 3604601 \\
&:= 1153 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3511 = 1154153 + 3514511 \\
&:= 1243 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3421 = 1244243 + 3424421 \\
&:= 1333 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3331 = 1334333 + 3334331 \\
&:= 1423 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3241 = 1424423 + 3244241 \\
&:= 1513 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3151 = 1514513 + 3154151 \\
&:= 1603 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3061 = 1604603 + 3064061 \\
&:= 2002 \times 1031 + 1301 \times 2002 = 2064062 + 2604602 \\
&:= 2002 \times 1121 + 1211 \times 2002 = 2244242 + 2424422 \\
&:= 2062 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2602 = 2064062 + 2604602 \\
&:= 2152 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2512 = 2154152 + 2514512 \\
&:= 2242 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2422 = 2244242 + 2424422 \\
&:= 2332 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2332 = 2334332 + 2334332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4676764} &:= 100121 \times 31 + 13 \times 121001 = 3103751 + 1573013 \\
&:= 11012 \times 211 + 112 \times 21011 = 2323532 + 2353232
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4678764} &:= 102112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211201 = 2144352 + 2534412 \\
&:= 1033 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 3301 = 1044363 + 3634401
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4684864} &:= 10102 \times 221 + 122 \times 20101 = 2232542 + 2452322 \\
&:= 10121 \times 103 + 301 \times 12101 = 1042463 + 3642401
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4686864} &:= 103012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210301 = 2163252 + 2523612 \\
&:= 10101 \times 133 + 331 \times 10101 = 1343433 + 3343431 \\
&:= 10101 \times 232 + 232 \times 10101 = 2343432 + 2343432 \\
&:= 10123 \times 111 + 111 \times 32101 = 1123653 + 3563211 \\
&:= 11113 \times 111 + 111 \times 31111 = 1233543 + 3453321 \\
&:= 12103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30121 = 1343433 + 3343431 \\
&:= 13102 \times 201 + 102 \times 20131 = 2633502 + 2053362 \\
&:= 20122 \times 111 + 111 \times 22102 = 2233542 + 2453322 \\
&:= 21112 \times 111 + 111 \times 21112 = 2343432 + 2343432
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4692964} := 101021 \times 31 + 13 \times 120101 = 3131651 + 1561313$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4710174} &:= 100011 \times 13 + 31 \times 110001 = 1300143 + 3410031 \\
&:= 110002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200011 = 2310042 + 2400132
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4724274} := 110102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201011 = 2312142 + 2412132$$

$$\mathbf{4726274} := 101011 \times 13 + 31 \times 110101 = 1313143 + 3413131$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4730374} &:= 100033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330001 = 1100363 + 3630011 \\
&:= 110023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320011 = 1210253 + 3520121 \\
&:= 120013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310021 = 1320143 + 3410231 \\
&:= 130003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300031 = 1430033 + 3300341 \\
&:= 200032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230002 = 2200352 + 2530022 \\
&:= 210022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220012 = 2310242 + 2420132
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4732374} := 111002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200111 = 2331042 + 2401332$$

$$\mathbf{4738374} := 110202 \times 21 + 12 \times 202011 = 2314242 + 2424132$$

$$\mathbf{4740474} := 100022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220001 = 2100462 + 2640012$$

$$\mathbf{4742474} := 100111 \times 13 + 31 \times 111001 = 1301443 + 3441031$$

$$:= 100133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331001 = 1101463 + 3641011$$

$$:= 101033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330101 = 1111363 + 3631111$$

$$:= 110123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321011 = 1211353 + 3531121$$

$$:= 111023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320111 = 1221253 + 3521221$$

$$:= 120113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311021 = 1321243 + 3421231$$

$$:= 121013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310121 = 1331143 + 3411331$$

$$:= 130103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301031 = 1431133 + 3311341$$

$$:= 131003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300131 = 1441033 + 3301441$$

$$:= 200132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231002 = 2201452 + 2541022$$

$$:= 201032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230102 = 2211352 + 2531122$$

$$:= 210122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221012 = 2311342 + 2431132$$

$$:= 211022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220112 = 2321242 + 2421232$$

$$\mathbf{4746474} := 111102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201111 = 2333142 + 2413332$$

$$\mathbf{4754574} := 100122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221001 = 2102562 + 2652012$$

$$:= 100233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332001 = 1102563 + 3652011$$

$$:= 101133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331101 = 1112463 + 3642111$$

$$:= 102033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330201 = 1122363 + 3632211$$

$$:= 110223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322011 = 1212453 + 3542121$$

$$:= 111123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321111 = 1222353 + 3532221$$

$$:= 112002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200211 = 2352042 + 2402532$$

$$:= 112023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320211 = 1232253 + 3522321$$

$$:= 120213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312021 = 1322343 + 3432231$$

$$:= 121113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311121 = 1332243 + 3422331$$

$$:= 122013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310221 = 1342143 + 3412431$$

$$:= 130203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302031 = 1432233 + 3322341$$

$$:= 131103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301131 = 1442133 + 3312441$$

$$:= 132003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300231 = 1452033 + 3302541$$

$$:= 200232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232002 = 2202552 + 2552022$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 201132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231102 = 2212452 + 2542122 \\ &:= 202032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230202 = 2222352 + 2532222 \\ &:= 210222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222012 = 2312442 + 2442132 \\ &:= 211122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221112 = 2322342 + 2432232 \\ &:= 212022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220212 = 2332242 + 2422332 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4758574} &:= 101111 \times 13 + 31 \times 111101 = 1314443 + 3444131 \\ &:= 1021 \times 1013 + 3101 \times 1201 = 1034273 + 3724301 \\ &:= 1121 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1211 = 1124363 + 3634211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4762674} &:= 101022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220101 = 2121462 + 2641212 \\ &:= 10011 \times 123 + 321 \times 11001 = 1231353 + 3531321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4766674} &:= 100333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333001 = 1103663 + 3663011 \\ &:= 101233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332101 = 1113563 + 3653111 \\ &:= 102133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331201 = 1123463 + 3643211 \\ &:= 103033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330301 = 1133363 + 3633311 \\ &:= 110323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323011 = 1213553 + 3553121 \\ &:= 111223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322111 = 1223453 + 3543221 \\ &:= 112123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321211 = 1233353 + 3533321 \\ &:= 113023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320311 = 1243253 + 3523421 \\ &:= 120313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313021 = 1323443 + 3443231 \\ &:= 121213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312121 = 1333343 + 3433331 \\ &:= 122113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311221 = 1343243 + 3423431 \\ &:= 123013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310321 = 1353143 + 3413531 \\ &:= 130303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303031 = 1433333 + 3333341 \\ &:= 131203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302131 = 1443233 + 3323441 \\ &:= 132103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301231 = 1453133 + 3313541 \\ &:= 133003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300331 = 1463033 + 3303641 \\ &:= 200332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233002 = 2203652 + 2563022 \\ &:= 201232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232102 = 2213552 + 2553122 \\ &:= 202132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231202 = 2223452 + 2543222 \\ &:= 203032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230302 = 2233352 + 2533322 \\ &:= 210322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223012 = 2313542 + 2453132 \\ &:= 211222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222112 = 2323442 + 2443232 \\ &:= 212122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221212 = 2333342 + 2433332 \\ &:= 213022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220312 = 2343242 + 2423432 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4768674} &:= 100222 \times 21 + 12 \times 222001 = 2104662 + 2664012 \\ &:= 112102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201211 = 2354142 + 2414532 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4774774} &:= 100211 \times 13 + 31 \times 112001 = 1302743 + 3472031 \\ &:= 10012 \times 221 + 122 \times 21001 = 2212652 + 2562122 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 12002 \times 211 + 112 \times 20021 = 2532422 + 2242352$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4776774} &:= 101122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221101 = 2123562 + 2653212 \\ &:= 113002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200311 = 2373042 + 2403732 \\ &:= 10011 \times 331 + 133 \times 11001 = 3313641 + 1463133 \\ &:= 10033 \times 111 + 111 \times 33001 = 1113663 + 3663111 \\ &:= 11023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32011 = 1223553 + 3553221 \\ &:= 12013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31021 = 1333443 + 3443331 \\ &:= 13003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30031 = 1443333 + 3333441 \\ &:= 20032 \times 111 + 111 \times 23002 = 2223552 + 2553222 \\ &:= 21022 \times 111 + 111 \times 22012 = 2333442 + 2443332 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4778774} &:= 100433 \times 11 + 11 \times 334001 = 1104763 + 3674011 \\ &:= 101333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333101 = 1114663 + 3664111 \\ &:= 102233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332201 = 1124563 + 3654211 \\ &:= 103133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331301 = 1134463 + 3644311 \\ &:= 104033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330401 = 1144363 + 3634411 \\ &:= 110423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324011 = 1214653 + 3564121 \\ &:= 111323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323111 = 1224553 + 3554221 \\ &:= 112223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322211 = 1234453 + 3544321 \\ &:= 113123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321311 = 1244353 + 3534421 \\ &:= 114023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320411 = 1254253 + 3524521 \\ &:= 120413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314021 = 1324543 + 3454231 \\ &:= 121313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313121 = 1334443 + 3444331 \\ &:= 122213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312221 = 1344343 + 3434431 \\ &:= 123113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311321 = 1354243 + 3424531 \\ &:= 124013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310421 = 1364143 + 3414631 \\ &:= 130403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304031 = 1434433 + 3344341 \\ &:= 131303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303131 = 1444333 + 3334441 \\ &:= 132203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302231 = 1454233 + 3324541 \\ &:= 133103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301331 = 1464133 + 3314641 \\ &:= 134003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300431 = 1474033 + 3304741 \\ &:= 200432 \times 11 + 11 \times 234002 = 2204752 + 2574022 \\ &:= 201332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233102 = 2214652 + 2564122 \\ &:= 202232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232202 = 2224552 + 2554222 \\ &:= 203132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231302 = 2234452 + 2544322 \\ &:= 204032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230402 = 2244352 + 2534422 \\ &:= 210422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224012 = 2314642 + 2464132 \\ &:= 211322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223112 = 2324542 + 2454232 \\ &:= 212222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222212 = 2334442 + 2444332 \\ &:= 213122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221312 = 2344342 + 2434432 \\ &:= 214022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220412 = 2354242 + 2424532 \\ &:= 1073 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3701 = 1074073 + 3704701 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 1163 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3611 = 1164163 + 3614611 \\
&:= 1253 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3521 = 1254253 + 3524521 \\
&:= 1343 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3431 = 1344343 + 3434431 \\
&:= 1433 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3341 = 1434433 + 3344341 \\
&:= 1523 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3251 = 1524523 + 3254251 \\
&:= 1613 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3161 = 1614613 + 3164161 \\
&:= 1703 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3071 = 1704703 + 3074071 \\
&:= 2072 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2702 = 2074072 + 2704702 \\
&:= 2162 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2612 = 2164162 + 2614612 \\
&:= 2252 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2522 = 2254252 + 2524522 \\
&:= 2342 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2432 = 2344342 + 2434432
\end{aligned}$$

$$4844484 := 110112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211011 = 2312352 + 2532132$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4852584 &:= 100143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341001 = 1101573 + 3751011 \\
&:= 101043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340101 = 1111473 + 3741111 \\
&:= 110133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331011 = 1211463 + 3641121 \\
&:= 111012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210111 = 2331252 + 2521332 \\
&:= 111033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330111 = 1221363 + 3631221 \\
&:= 120123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321021 = 1321353 + 3531231 \\
&:= 121023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320121 = 1331253 + 3521331 \\
&:= 130113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311031 = 1431243 + 3421341 \\
&:= 131013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310131 = 1441143 + 3411441 \\
&:= 140103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301041 = 1541133 + 3311451 \\
&:= 141003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300141 = 1551033 + 3301551 \\
&:= 200142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241002 = 2201562 + 2651022 \\
&:= 201042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240102 = 2211462 + 2641122 \\
&:= 210132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231012 = 2311452 + 2541132 \\
&:= 211032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230112 = 2321352 + 2531232 \\
&:= 220122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221022 = 2421342 + 2431242
\end{aligned}$$

$$4784874 := 102022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220201 = 2142462 + 2642412$$

$$4790974 := 100031 \times 31 + 13 \times 130001 = 3100961 + 1690013$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4798974 &:= 102122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221201 = 2144562 + 2654412 \\
&:= 114002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200411 = 2394042 + 2404932 \\
&:= 10133 \times 111 + 111 \times 33101 = 1124763 + 3674211 \\
&:= 11123 \times 111 + 111 \times 32111 = 1234653 + 3564321 \\
&:= 12113 \times 111 + 111 \times 31121 = 1344543 + 3454431 \\
&:= 13103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30131 = 1454433 + 3344541 \\
&:= 20132 \times 111 + 111 \times 23102 = 2234652 + 2564322 \\
&:= 21122 \times 111 + 111 \times 22112 = 2344542 + 2454432 \\
&:= 1043 \times 1011 + 1101 \times 3401 = 1054473 + 3744501
\end{aligned}$$

$$4856584 := 110111 \times 31 + 13 \times 111011 = 3413441 + 1443143$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4858584 &:= 110212 \times 21 + 12 \times 212011 = 2314452 + 2544132 \\
&:= 14002 \times 201 + 102 \times 20041 = 2814402 + 2044182
\end{aligned}$$

$$4860684 := 100032 \times 21 + 12 \times 230001 = 2100672 + 2760012$$

$$4830384 := 110012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210011 = 2310252 + 2520132$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4864684 &:= 100121 \times 22 + 22 \times 121001 = 2202662 + 2662022 \\
&:= 100243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342001 = 1102673 + 3762011 \\
&:= 101021 \times 22 + 22 \times 120101 = 2222462 + 2642222 \\
&:= 101143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341101 = 1112573 + 3752111 \\
&:= 102043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340201 = 1122473 + 3742211 \\
&:= 110111 \times 22 + 22 \times 111011 = 2422442 + 2442242 \\
&:= 110233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332011 = 1212563 + 3652121 \\
&:= 111133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331111 = 1222463 + 3642221 \\
&:= 112033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330211 = 1232363 + 3632321 \\
&:= 120223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322021 = 1322453 + 3542231 \\
&:= 121123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321121 = 1332353 + 3532331 \\
&:= 122023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320221 = 1342253 + 3522431 \\
&:= 130213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312031 = 1432343 + 3432341 \\
&:= 131113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311131 = 1442243 + 3422441 \\
&:= 132013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310231 = 1452143 + 3412541 \\
&:= 140203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302041 = 1542233 + 3322451 \\
&:= 141103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301141 = 1552133 + 3312551
\end{aligned}$$

$$4840484 := 100021 \times 22 + 22 \times 120001 = 2200462 + 2640022$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 100043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340001 = 1100473 + 3740011 \\
&:= 110011 \times 13 + 31 \times 110011 = 1430143 + 3410341 \\
&:= 110011 \times 22 + 22 \times 110011 = 2420242 + 2420242 \\
&:= 110033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330011 = 1210363 + 3630121 \\
&:= 120023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320021 = 1320253 + 3520231 \\
&:= 130013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310031 = 1430143 + 3410341 \\
&:= 140003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300041 = 1540033 + 3300451 \\
&:= 200042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240002 = 2200462 + 2640022 \\
&:= 210032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230012 = 2310352 + 2530132 \\
&:= 220022 \times 11 + 11 \times 220022 = 2420242 + 2420242 \\
&:= 10001 \times 143 + 341 \times 10001 = 1430143 + 3410341 \\
&:= 10001 \times 242 + 242 \times 10001 = 2420242 + 2420242 \\
&:= 10003 \times 121 + 121 \times 30001 = 1210363 + 3630121 \\
&:= 20002 \times 121 + 121 \times 20002 = 2420242 + 2420242
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 142003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300241 = 1562033 + 3302651 \\
&:= 200242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242002 = 2202662 + 2662022 \\
&:= 201142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241102 = 2212562 + 2652122 \\
&:= 202042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240202 = 2222462 + 2642222 \\
&:= 210232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232012 = 2312552 + 2552132 \\
&:= 211132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231112 = 2322452 + 2542232 \\
&:= 212032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230212 = 2332352 + 2532332 \\
&:= 220222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222022 = 2422442 + 2442242 \\
&:= 221122 \times 11 + 11 \times 221122 = 2432342 + 2432342 \\
&:= 10021 \times 113 + 311 \times 12001 = 1132373 + 3732311 \\
&:= 10103 \times 121 + 121 \times 30101 = 1222463 + 3642221 \\
&:= 20102 \times 121 + 121 \times 20102 = 2432342 + 2432342
\end{aligned}$$

$$4866684 := 111112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211111 = 2333352 + 2533332$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4872784 &:= 110111 \times 13 + 31 \times 111011 = 1431443 + 3441341 \\
&:= 11002 \times 221 + 122 \times 20011 = 2431442 + 2441342
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4874784 &:= 100132 \times 21 + 12 \times 231001 = 2102772 + 2772012 \\
&:= 112012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210211 = 2352252 + 2522532 \\
&:= 10011 \times 232 + 232 \times 11001 = 2322552 + 2522232
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4876784 &:= 100343 \times 11 + 11 \times 343001 = 1103773 + 3773011 \\
&:= 101243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342101 = 1113673 + 3763111 \\
&:= 102143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341201 = 1123573 + 3753211 \\
&:= 103043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340301 = 1133473 + 3743311 \\
&:= 110333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333011 = 1213663 + 3663121 \\
&:= 111233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332111 = 1223563 + 3653221 \\
&:= 112133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331211 = 1233463 + 3643321 \\
&:= 113033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330311 = 1243363 + 3633421 \\
&:= 120323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323021 = 1323553 + 3553231 \\
&:= 121223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322121 = 1333453 + 3543331 \\
&:= 122123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321221 = 1343353 + 3533431 \\
&:= 123023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320321 = 1353253 + 3523531 \\
&:= 130313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313031 = 1433443 + 3443341 \\
&:= 131213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312131 = 1443343 + 3433441 \\
&:= 132113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311231 = 1453243 + 3423541 \\
&:= 133013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310331 = 1463143 + 3413641 \\
&:= 140303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303041 = 1543333 + 3333451 \\
&:= 141203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302141 = 1553233 + 3323551 \\
&:= 142103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301241 = 1563133 + 3313651 \\
&:= 143003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300341 = 1573033 + 3303751 \\
&:= 200342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243002 = 2203762 + 2673022
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 201242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242102 = 2213662 + 2663122 \\
&:= 202142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241202 = 2223562 + 2653222 \\
&:= 203042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240302 = 2233462 + 2643322 \\
&:= 210332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233012 = 2313652 + 2563132 \\
&:= 211232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232112 = 2323552 + 2553232 \\
&:= 212132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231212 = 2333452 + 2543332 \\
&:= 213032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230312 = 2343352 + 2533432 \\
&:= 220322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223022 = 2423542 + 2453242 \\
&:= 221222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222122 = 2433442 + 2443342
\end{aligned}$$

$$4882884 := 101032 \times 21 + 12 \times 230101 = 2121672 + 2761212$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4888884 &:= 100221 \times 22 + 22 \times 122001 = 2204862 + 2684022 \\
&:= 100232 \times 21 + 12 \times 232001 = 2104872 + 2784012 \\
&:= 100443 \times 11 + 11 \times 344001 = 1104873 + 3784011 \\
&:= 101121 \times 22 + 22 \times 121101 = 2224662 + 2664222 \\
&:= 101343 \times 11 + 11 \times 343101 = 1114773 + 3774111 \\
&:= 102243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342201 = 1124673 + 3764211 \\
&:= 102021 \times 22 + 22 \times 120201 = 2244462 + 2644422 \\
&:= 103143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341301 = 1134573 + 3754311 \\
&:= 104043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340401 = 1144473 + 3744411 \\
&:= 110211 \times 22 + 22 \times 112011 = 2424642 + 2464242 \\
&:= 110433 \times 11 + 11 \times 334011 = 1214763 + 3674121 \\
&:= 111111 \times 13 + 31 \times 111111 = 1444443 + 3444441 \\
&:= 111111 \times 22 + 22 \times 111111 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 111333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333111 = 1224663 + 3664221 \\
&:= 112112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211211 = 2354352 + 2534532 \\
&:= 112233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332211 = 1234563 + 3654321 \\
&:= 113133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331311 = 1244463 + 3644421 \\
&:= 114033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330411 = 1254363 + 3634521 \\
&:= 120423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324021 = 1324653 + 3564231 \\
&:= 121323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323121 = 1334553 + 3554331 \\
&:= 122223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322221 = 1344453 + 3544431 \\
&:= 123123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321321 = 1354353 + 3534531 \\
&:= 124023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320421 = 1364253 + 3524631 \\
&:= 130413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314031 = 1434543 + 3454341 \\
&:= 131313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313131 = 1444443 + 3444441 \\
&:= 132213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312231 = 1454343 + 3434541 \\
&:= 133113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311331 = 1464243 + 3424641 \\
&:= 134013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310431 = 1474143 + 3414741 \\
&:= 141303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303141 = 1554333 + 3334551 \\
&:= 142203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302241 = 1564233 + 3324651 \\
&:= 143103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301341 = 1574133 + 3314751
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 144003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300441 = 1584033 + 3304851 \\
&:= 140403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304041 = 1544433 + 3344451 \\
&:= 200442 \times 11 + 11 \times 244002 = 2204862 + 2684022 \\
&:= 201342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243102 = 2214762 + 2674122 \\
&:= 202242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242202 = 2224662 + 2664222 \\
&:= 203142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241302 = 2234562 + 2654322 \\
&:= 204042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240402 = 2244462 + 2644422 \\
&:= 210432 \times 11 + 11 \times 234012 = 2314752 + 2574132 \\
&:= 211332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233112 = 2324652 + 2564232 \\
&:= 212232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232212 = 2334552 + 2554332 \\
&:= 213132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231312 = 2344452 + 2544432 \\
&:= 214032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230412 = 2354352 + 2534532 \\
&:= 220422 \times 11 + 11 \times 224022 = 2424642 + 2464242 \\
&:= 221322 \times 11 + 11 \times 223122 = 2434542 + 2454342 \\
&:= 222222 \times 11 + 11 \times 222222 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 10021 \times 222 + 222 \times 12001 = 2224662 + 2664222 \\
&:= 10043 \times 111 + 111 \times 34001 = 1114773 + 3774111 \\
&:= 10101 \times 143 + 341 \times 10101 = 1444443 + 3444441 \\
&:= 10101 \times 242 + 242 \times 10101 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 10203 \times 121 + 121 \times 30201 = 1234563 + 3654321 \\
&:= 11011 \times 123 + 321 \times 11011 = 1354353 + 3534531 \\
&:= 11011 \times 222 + 222 \times 11011 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 11033 \times 111 + 111 \times 33011 = 1224663 + 3664221 \\
&:= 12012 \times 211 + 112 \times 21021 = 2534532 + 2354352 \\
&:= 12023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32021 = 1334553 + 3554331 \\
&:= 13013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31031 = 1444443 + 3444441 \\
&:= 14003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30041 = 1554333 + 3334551 \\
&:= 20042 \times 111 + 111 \times 24002 = 2224662 + 2664222 \\
&:= 20202 \times 121 + 121 \times 20202 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 21032 \times 111 + 111 \times 23012 = 2334552 + 2554332 \\
&:= 22022 \times 111 + 111 \times 22022 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 14102 \times 201 + 102 \times 20141 = 2834502 + 2054382 \\
&:= 1023 \times 1021 + 1201 \times 3201 = 1044483 + 3844401 \\
&:= 1083 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3801 = 1084083 + 3804801 \\
&:= 1173 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3711 = 1174173 + 3714711 \\
&:= 1221 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1221 = 1224663 + 3664221 \\
&:= 1263 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3621 = 1264263 + 3624621 \\
&:= 1353 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3531 = 1354353 + 3534531 \\
&:= 1443 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3441 = 1444443 + 3444441 \\
&:= 1533 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3351 = 1534533 + 3354351 \\
&:= 1623 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3261 = 1624623 + 3264261 \\
&:= 1713 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3171 = 1714713 + 3174171 \\
&:= 1803 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3081 = 1804803 + 3084081
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 2002 \times 1041 + 1401 \times 2002 = 2084082 + 2804802 \\
&:= 2002 \times 1131 + 1311 \times 2002 = 2264262 + 2624622 \\
&:= 2002 \times 1221 + 1221 \times 2002 = 2444442 + 2444442 \\
&:= 2082 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2802 = 2084082 + 2804802 \\
&:= 2172 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2712 = 2174172 + 2714712 \\
&:= 2262 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2622 = 2264262 + 2624622 \\
&:= 2352 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2532 = 2354352 + 2534532 \\
&:= 2442 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2442 = 2444442 + 2444442
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4896984} &:= 101132 \times 21 + 12 \times 231101 = 2123772 + 2773212 \\
&:= 113012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210311 = 2373252 + 2523732
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4898984} &:= 10022 \times 221 + 122 \times 22001 = 2214862 + 2684122 \\
\mathbf{4920294} &:= 120002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200021 = 2520042 + 2400252 \\
\mathbf{4934394} &:= 120102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201021 = 2522142 + 2412252 \\
\mathbf{4938394} &:= 1031 \times 1003 + 3001 \times 1301 = 1034093 + 3904301 \\
\mathbf{4942494} &:= 121002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200121 = 2541042 + 2401452 \\
\mathbf{4946494} &:= 10031 \times 103 + 301 \times 13001 = 1033193 + 3913301 \\
\mathbf{4948494} &:= 120202 \times 21 + 12 \times 202021 = 2524242 + 2424252
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4950594} &:= 100053 \times 11 + 11 \times 350001 = 1100583 + 3850011 \\
&:= 110022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220011 = 2310462 + 2640132 \\
&:= 110043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340011 = 1210473 + 3740121 \\
&:= 120033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330021 = 1320363 + 3630231 \\
&:= 130023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320031 = 1430253 + 3520341 \\
&:= 140013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310041 = 1540143 + 3410451 \\
&:= 150003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300051 = 1650033 + 3300561 \\
&:= 200052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250002 = 2200572 + 2750022 \\
&:= 210042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240012 = 2310462 + 2640132 \\
&:= 220032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230022 = 2420352 + 2530242 \\
&:= 10002 \times 231 + 132 \times 20001 = 2310462 + 2640132
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4956594} := 121102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201121 = 2543142 + 2413452$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{4962694} &:= 100153 \times 11 + 11 \times 351001 = 1101683 + 3861011 \\
&:= 101053 \times 11 + 11 \times 350101 = 1111583 + 3851111 \\
&:= 110143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341011 = 1211573 + 3751121 \\
&:= 111043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340111 = 1221473 + 3741221 \\
&:= 120133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331021 = 1321463 + 3641231 \\
&:= 121033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330121 = 1331363 + 3631331 \\
&:= 130123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321031 = 1431353 + 3531341 \\
&:= 131023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320131 = 1441253 + 3521441 \\
&:= 140113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311041 = 1541243 + 3421451
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 141013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310141 = 1551143 + 3411551 \\ &:= 150103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301051 = 1651133 + 3311561 \\ &:= 151003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300151 = 1661033 + 3301661 \\ &:= 200152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251002 = 2201672 + 2761022 \\ &:= 201052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250102 = 2211572 + 2751122 \\ &:= 210142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241012 = 2311562 + 2651132 \\ &:= 211042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240112 = 2321462 + 2641232 \\ &:= 220132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231022 = 2421452 + 2541242 \\ &:= 221032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230122 = 2431352 + 2531342 \\ &:= 10013 \times 121 + 121 \times 31001 = 1211573 + 3751121 \\ &:= 11003 \times 121 + 121 \times 30011 = 1331363 + 3631331 \\ &:= 20012 \times 121 + 121 \times 21002 = 2421452 + 2541242 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4964694} &:= 110122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221011 = 2312562 + 2652132 \\ &:= 122002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200221 = 2562042 + 2402652 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4970794} := 110021 \times 31 + 13 \times 120011 = 3410651 + 1560143$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4972794} &:= 111022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220111 = 2331462 + 2641332 \\ &:= 10011 \times 133 + 331 \times 11001 = 1331463 + 3641331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4974794} &:= 100253 \times 11 + 11 \times 352001 = 1102783 + 3872011 \\ &:= 101153 \times 11 + 11 \times 351101 = 1112683 + 3862111 \\ &:= 102053 \times 11 + 11 \times 350201 = 1122583 + 3852211 \\ &:= 110243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342011 = 1212673 + 3762121 \\ &:= 111143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341111 = 1222573 + 3752221 \\ &:= 112043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340211 = 1232473 + 3742321 \\ &:= 120233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332021 = 1322563 + 3652231 \\ &:= 121133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331121 = 1332463 + 3642331 \\ &:= 122033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330221 = 1342363 + 3632431 \\ &:= 130223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322031 = 1432453 + 3542341 \\ &:= 131123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321131 = 1442353 + 3532441 \\ &:= 132023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320231 = 1452253 + 3522541 \\ &:= 140213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312041 = 1542343 + 3432451 \\ &:= 141113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311141 = 1552243 + 3422551 \\ &:= 142013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310241 = 1562143 + 3412651 \\ &:= 150203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302051 = 1652233 + 3322561 \\ &:= 151103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301151 = 1662133 + 3312661 \\ &:= 152003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300251 = 1672033 + 3302761 \\ &:= 200252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252002 = 2202772 + 2772022 \\ &:= 201152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251102 = 2212672 + 2762122 \\ &:= 202052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250202 = 2222572 + 2752222 \\ &:= 210242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242012 = 2312662 + 2662132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 211142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241112 = 2322562 + 2652232 \\ &:= 212042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240212 = 2332462 + 2642332 \\ &:= 220232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232022 = 2422552 + 2552242 \\ &:= 221132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231122 = 2432452 + 2542342 \\ &:= 222032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230222 = 2442352 + 2532442 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4978794} &:= 110222 \times 21 + 12 \times 222011 = 2314662 + 2664132 \\ &:= 122102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201221 = 2564142 + 2414652 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4980894} := 100042 \times 21 + 12 \times 240001 = 2100882 + 2880012$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4986894} &:= 100353 \times 11 + 11 \times 353001 = 1103883 + 3883011 \\ &:= 101253 \times 11 + 11 \times 352101 = 1113783 + 3873111 \\ &:= 102153 \times 11 + 11 \times 351201 = 1123683 + 3863211 \\ &:= 103053 \times 11 + 11 \times 350301 = 1133583 + 3853311 \\ &:= 110121 \times 31 + 13 \times 121011 = 3413751 + 1573143 \\ &:= 110343 \times 11 + 11 \times 343011 = 1213773 + 3773121 \\ &:= 111122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221111 = 2333562 + 2653332 \\ &:= 111243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342111 = 1223673 + 3763221 \\ &:= 112143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341211 = 1233573 + 3753321 \\ &:= 113043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340311 = 1243473 + 3743421 \\ &:= 120333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333021 = 1323663 + 3663231 \\ &:= 121233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332121 = 1333563 + 3653331 \\ &:= 122133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331221 = 1343463 + 3643431 \\ &:= 123002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200321 = 2583042 + 2403852 \\ &:= 123033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330321 = 1353363 + 3633531 \\ &:= 130323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323031 = 1433553 + 3553341 \\ &:= 131223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322131 = 1443453 + 3543441 \\ &:= 132123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321231 = 1453353 + 3533541 \\ &:= 133023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320331 = 1463253 + 3523641 \\ &:= 140313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313041 = 1543443 + 3443451 \\ &:= 141213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312141 = 1553343 + 3433551 \\ &:= 142113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311241 = 1563243 + 3423651 \\ &:= 143013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310341 = 1573143 + 3413751 \\ &:= 150303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303051 = 1653333 + 3333561 \\ &:= 151203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302151 = 1663233 + 3323661 \\ &:= 152103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301251 = 1673133 + 3313761 \\ &:= 153003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300351 = 1683033 + 3303861 \\ &:= 200352 \times 11 + 11 \times 253002 = 2203872 + 2783022 \\ &:= 201252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252102 = 2213772 + 2773122 \\ &:= 202152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251202 = 2223672 + 2763222 \\ &:= 203052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250302 = 2233572 + 2753322 \\ &:= 210342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243012 = 2313762 + 2673132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 211242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242112 = 2323662 + 2663232 \\ &:= 212142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241212 = 2333562 + 2653332 \\ &:= 213042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240312 = 2343462 + 2643432 \\ &:= 220332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233022 = 2423652 + 2563242 \\ &:= 221232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232122 = 2433552 + 2553342 \\ &:= 222132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231222 = 2443452 + 2543442 \\ &:= 223032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230322 = 2453352 + 2533542 \\ &:= 10011 \times 341 + 143 \times 11001 = 3413751 + 1573143 \\ &:= 10102 \times 231 + 132 \times 20101 = 2333562 + 2653332 \\ &:= 10113 \times 121 + 121 \times 31101 = 1223673 + 3763221 \\ &:= 10131 \times 103 + 301 \times 13101 = 1043493 + 3943401 \\ &:= 11103 \times 121 + 121 \times 30111 = 1343463 + 3643431 \\ &:= 13002 \times 211 + 112 \times 20031 = 2743422 + 2243472 \\ &:= 20112 \times 121 + 121 \times 21102 = 2433552 + 2553342 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4994994} &:= 100142 \times 21 + 12 \times 241001 = 2102982 + 2892012 \\ &:= 112022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220211 = 2352462 + 2642532 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4996994} := 11012 \times 221 + 122 \times 21011 = 2433652 + 2563342$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4998994} &:= 100453 \times 11 + 11 \times 354001 = 1104983 + 3894011 \\ &:= 101353 \times 11 + 11 \times 353101 = 1114883 + 3884111 \\ &:= 102253 \times 11 + 11 \times 352201 = 1124783 + 3874211 \\ &:= 103153 \times 11 + 11 \times 351301 = 1134683 + 3864311 \\ &:= 104053 \times 11 + 11 \times 350401 = 1144583 + 3854411 \\ &:= 110443 \times 11 + 11 \times 344011 = 1214873 + 3784121 \\ &:= 111343 \times 11 + 11 \times 343111 = 1224773 + 3774221 \\ &:= 112243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342211 = 1234673 + 3764321 \\ &:= 113143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341311 = 1244573 + 3754421 \\ &:= 114043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340411 = 1254473 + 3744521 \\ &:= 120433 \times 11 + 11 \times 334021 = 1324763 + 3674231 \\ &:= 121333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333121 = 1334663 + 3664331 \\ &:= 122233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332221 = 1344563 + 3654431 \\ &:= 123133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331321 = 1354463 + 3644531 \\ &:= 124033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330421 = 1364363 + 3634631 \\ &:= 130423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324031 = 1434653 + 3564341 \\ &:= 131323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323131 = 1444553 + 3554441 \\ &:= 132223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322231 = 1454453 + 3544541 \\ &:= 133123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321331 = 1464353 + 3534641 \\ &:= 134023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320431 = 1474253 + 3524741 \\ &:= 140413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314041 = 1544543 + 3454451 \\ &:= 141313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313141 = 1554443 + 3444551 \\ &:= 142213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312241 = 1564343 + 3434651 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 143113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311341 = 1574243 + 3424751 \\ &:= 144013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310441 = 1584143 + 3414851 \\ &:= 150403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304051 = 1654433 + 3344561 \\ &:= 151303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303151 = 1664333 + 3334661 \\ &:= 152203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302251 = 1674233 + 3324761 \\ &:= 153103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301351 = 1684133 + 3314861 \\ &:= 154003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300451 = 1694033 + 3304961 \\ &:= 200452 \times 11 + 11 \times 254002 = 2204972 + 2794022 \\ &:= 201352 \times 11 + 11 \times 253102 = 2214872 + 2784122 \\ &:= 202252 \times 11 + 11 \times 252202 = 2224772 + 2774222 \\ &:= 203152 \times 11 + 11 \times 251302 = 2234672 + 2764322 \\ &:= 204052 \times 11 + 11 \times 250402 = 2244572 + 2754422 \\ &:= 210442 \times 11 + 11 \times 244012 = 2314862 + 2684132 \\ &:= 211342 \times 11 + 11 \times 243112 = 2324762 + 2674232 \\ &:= 212242 \times 11 + 11 \times 242212 = 2334662 + 2664332 \\ &:= 213142 \times 11 + 11 \times 241312 = 2344562 + 2654432 \\ &:= 214042 \times 11 + 11 \times 240412 = 2354462 + 2644532 \\ &:= 220432 \times 11 + 11 \times 234022 = 2424752 + 2574242 \\ &:= 221332 \times 11 + 11 \times 233122 = 2434652 + 2564342 \\ &:= 222232 \times 11 + 11 \times 232222 = 2444552 + 2554442 \\ &:= 223132 \times 11 + 11 \times 231322 = 2454452 + 2544542 \\ &:= 224032 \times 11 + 11 \times 230422 = 2464352 + 2534642 \\ &:= 1093 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3901 = 1094093 + 3904901 \\ &:= 1183 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3811 = 1184183 + 3814811 \\ &:= 1273 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3721 = 1274273 + 3724721 \\ &:= 1363 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3631 = 1364363 + 3634631 \\ &:= 1453 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3541 = 1454453 + 3544541 \\ &:= 1543 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3451 = 1544543 + 3454451 \\ &:= 1633 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3361 = 1634633 + 3364361 \\ &:= 1723 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3271 = 1724723 + 3274271 \\ &:= 1813 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3181 = 1814813 + 3184181 \\ &:= 1903 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 3091 = 1904903 + 3094091 \\ &:= 2092 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2902 = 2094092 + 2904902 \\ &:= 2182 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2812 = 2184182 + 2814812 \\ &:= 2272 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2722 = 2274272 + 2724722 \\ &:= 2362 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2632 = 2364362 + 2634632 \\ &:= 2452 \times 1001 + 1001 \times 2542 = 2454452 + 2544542 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5008005} := 1002 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2001 = 1004004 + 4004001$$

$$\mathbf{5040405} := 10002 \times 102 + 201 \times 20001 = 1020204 + 4020201$$

$$\mathbf{5050505} := 10001 \times 104 + 401 \times 10001 = 1040104 + 4010401$$

$$:= 10001 \times 203 + 302 \times 10001 = 2030203 + 3020302$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40001 = 1010404 + 4040101 \\ &:= 20003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30002 = 2020303 + 3030202 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5250525} &:= 10001 \times 114 + 411 \times 10001 = 1140114 + 4110411 \\ &:= 10001 \times 213 + 312 \times 10001 = 2130213 + 3120312 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5070705} &:= 10002 \times 301 + 103 \times 20001 = 3010602 + 2060103 \\ &:= 10003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30001 = 2010603 + 3060102 \\ &:= 10102 \times 102 + 201 \times 20101 = 1030404 + 4040301 \\ &:= 10104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40101 = 1020504 + 4050201 \\ &:= 20103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30102 = 2030403 + 3040302 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5254525} &:= 10024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42001 = 1012424 + 4242101 \\ &:= 11014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41011 = 1112414 + 4142111 \\ &:= 12004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40021 = 1212404 + 4042121 \\ &:= 20023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32002 = 2022323 + 3232202 \\ &:= 21013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31012 = 2122313 + 3132212 \\ &:= 22003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30022 = 2222303 + 3032222 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5090905} &:= 10204 \times 101 + 101 \times 40201 = 1030604 + 4060301 \\ &:= 20203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30202 = 2040503 + 3050402 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5256525} &:= 10011 \times 302 + 203 \times 11001 = 3023322 + 2233203 \\ \mathbf{5258525} &:= 1102 \times 1102 + 2011 \times 2011 = 1214404 + 4044121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5128215} := 1102 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2011 = 1104204 + 4024011$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5272725} &:= 10112 \times 102 + 201 \times 21101 = 1031424 + 4241301 \\ &:= 11003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30011 = 2211603 + 3061122 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5144415} := 11002 \times 102 + 201 \times 20011 = 1122204 + 4022211$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5152515} &:= 10014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41001 = 1011414 + 4141101 \\ &:= 11004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40011 = 1111404 + 4041111 \\ &:= 20013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31002 = 2021313 + 3131202 \\ &:= 21003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30012 = 2121303 + 3031212 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5274725} &:= 10124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42101 = 1022524 + 4252201 \\ &:= 11114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41111 = 1122514 + 4152211 \\ &:= 12104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40121 = 1222504 + 4052221 \\ &:= 20123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32102 = 2032423 + 3242302 \\ &:= 21113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31112 = 2132413 + 3142312 \\ &:= 22103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30122 = 2232403 + 3042322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5158515} := 10011 \times 401 + 104 \times 11001 = 4014411 + 1144104$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5278725} &:= 10023 \times 201 + 102 \times 32001 = 2014623 + 3264102 \\ &:= 12102 \times 102 + 201 \times 20121 = 1234404 + 4044321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5172715} &:= 10114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41101 = 1021514 + 4151201 \\ &:= 11104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40111 = 1121504 + 4051211 \\ &:= 20113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31102 = 2031413 + 3141302 \\ &:= 21103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30112 = 2131403 + 3041312 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5174715} &:= 10013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31001 = 2012613 + 3162102 \\ &:= 11102 \times 102 + 201 \times 20111 = 1132404 + 4042311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5294925} &:= 10224 \times 101 + 101 \times 42201 = 1032624 + 4262301 \\ &:= 11214 \times 101 + 101 \times 41211 = 1132614 + 4162311 \\ &:= 12204 \times 101 + 101 \times 40221 = 1232604 + 4062321 \\ &:= 20223 \times 101 + 101 \times 32202 = 2042523 + 3252402 \\ &:= 21213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31212 = 2142513 + 3152412 \\ &:= 22203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30222 = 2242503 + 3052422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5176715} := 10012 \times 301 + 103 \times 21001 = 3013612 + 2163103$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5192915} &:= 10214 \times 101 + 101 \times 41201 = 1031614 + 4161301 \\ &:= 11204 \times 101 + 101 \times 40211 = 1131604 + 4061311 \\ &:= 20213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31202 = 2041513 + 3151402 \\ &:= 21203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30212 = 2141503 + 3051412 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5338335} &:= 1112 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2111 = 1114224 + 4224111 \\ \mathbf{5340435} &:= 10002 \times 112 + 211 \times 20001 = 1120224 + 4220211 \\ \mathbf{5346435} &:= 11012 \times 102 + 201 \times 21011 = 1123224 + 4223211 \\ \mathbf{5354535} &:= 10011 \times 203 + 302 \times 11001 = 2032233 + 3322302 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5218125} := 1012 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2101 = 1014024 + 4204101$$

$$\mathbf{5242425} := 10012 \times 102 + 201 \times 21001 = 1021224 + 4221201$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5356535} &:= 10034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43001 = 1013434 + 4343101 \\ &:= 11024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42011 = 1113424 + 4243111 \\ &:= 12014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41021 = 1213414 + 4143121 \\ &:= 13004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40031 = 1313404 + 4043131 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5248425} &:= 12002 \times 102 + 201 \times 20021 = 1224204 + 4024221 \\ &:= 1202 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2021 = 1204404 + 4044021 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 20033 \times 101 + 101 \times 33002 = 2023333 + 3333202 \\ &:= 21023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32012 = 2123323 + 3233212 \\ &:= 22013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31022 = 2223313 + 3133222 \\ &:= 23003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30032 = 2323303 + 3033232 \end{aligned}$$

$$5438345 := 1012 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 2101 = 1024144 + 4414201$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5444445 &:= 100202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202001 = 1202424 + 4242021 \\ &:= 10022 \times 102 + 201 \times 22001 = 1022244 + 4422201 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5368635 &:= 10011 \times 411 + 114 \times 11001 = 4114521 + 1254114 \\ &:= 1302 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2031 = 1304604 + 4064031 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5450545 &:= 10001 \times 124 + 421 \times 10001 = 1240124 + 4210421 \\ &:= 10001 \times 223 + 322 \times 10001 = 2230223 + 3220322 \end{aligned}$$

$$5370735 := 10002 \times 311 + 113 \times 20001 = 3110622 + 2260113$$

$$5452545 := 10011 \times 104 + 401 \times 11001 = 1041144 + 4411401$$

$$5454545 := 11002 \times 112 + 211 \times 20011 = 1232224 + 4222321$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5372735 &:= 10102 \times 112 + 211 \times 20101 = 1131424 + 4241311 \\ &:= 11002 \times 301 + 103 \times 20011 = 3311602 + 2061133 \end{aligned}$$

$$5458545 := 101202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202101 = 1214424 + 4244121$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5376735 &:= 10134 \times 101 + 101 \times 43101 = 1023534 + 4353201 \\ &:= 11013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31011 = 2213613 + 3163122 \\ &:= 11112 \times 102 + 201 \times 21111 = 1133424 + 4243311 \\ &:= 11124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42111 = 1123524 + 4253211 \\ &:= 12114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41121 = 1223514 + 4153221 \\ &:= 13104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40131 = 1323504 + 4053231 \\ &:= 20133 \times 101 + 101 \times 33102 = 2033433 + 3343302 \\ &:= 21123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32112 = 2133423 + 3243312 \\ &:= 22113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31122 = 2233413 + 3143322 \\ &:= 23103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30132 = 2333403 + 3043332 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 10044 \times 101 + 101 \times 44001 = 1014444 + 4444101$$

$$:= 11034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43011 = 1114434 + 4344111$$

$$:= 12024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42021 = 1214424 + 4244121$$

$$:= 13014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41031 = 1314414 + 4144131$$

$$:= 14004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40041 = 1414404 + 4044141$$

$$:= 20043 \times 101 + 101 \times 34002 = 2024343 + 3434202$$

$$:= 21033 \times 101 + 101 \times 33012 = 2124333 + 3334212$$

$$:= 22023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32022 = 2224323 + 3234222$$

$$:= 23013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31032 = 2324313 + 3134232$$

$$:= 24003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30042 = 2424303 + 3034242$$

$$:= 1212 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2121 = 1214424 + 4244121$$

$$5388835 := 1202 \times 1102 + 2011 \times 2021 = 1324604 + 4064231$$

$$5466645 := 100302 \times 12 + 21 \times 203001 = 1203624 + 4263021$$

$$:= 10011 \times 312 + 213 \times 11001 = 3123432 + 2343213$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5396935 &:= 10234 \times 101 + 101 \times 43201 = 1033634 + 4363301 \\ &:= 11224 \times 101 + 101 \times 42211 = 1133624 + 4263311 \\ &:= 12214 \times 101 + 101 \times 41221 = 1233614 + 4163321 \\ &:= 13204 \times 101 + 101 \times 40231 = 1333604 + 4063331 \\ &:= 20233 \times 101 + 101 \times 33202 = 2043533 + 3353402 \\ &:= 21223 \times 101 + 101 \times 32212 = 2143523 + 3253412 \\ &:= 22213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31222 = 2243513 + 3153422 \\ &:= 23203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30232 = 2343503 + 3053432 \end{aligned}$$

$$5470745 := 10003 \times 211 + 112 \times 30001 = 2110633 + 3360112$$

$$5474745 := 10122 \times 102 + 201 \times 22101 = 1032444 + 4442301$$

$$:= 12003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30021 = 2412603 + 3062142$$

$$5478745 := 10144 \times 101 + 101 \times 44101 = 1024544 + 4454201$$

$$:= 11012 \times 301 + 103 \times 21011 = 3314612 + 2164133$$

$$:= 11134 \times 101 + 101 \times 43111 = 1124534 + 4354211$$

$$:= 12124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42121 = 1224524 + 4254221$$

$$:= 13114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41131 = 1324514 + 4154231$$

$$:= 14104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40141 = 1424504 + 4054241$$

$$:= 20143 \times 101 + 101 \times 34102 = 2034443 + 3444302$$

$$:= 21133 \times 101 + 101 \times 33112 = 2134433 + 3344312$$

$$:= 22123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32122 = 2234423 + 3244322$$

$$:= 23113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31132 = 2334413 + 3144332$$

$$:= 24103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30142 = 2434403 + 3044342$$

$$5400045 := 100002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200001 = 1200024 + 4200021$$

$$5414145 := 101002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200101 = 1212024 + 4202121$$

$$5422245 := 100102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201001 = 1201224 + 4221021$$

$$5428245 := 102002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200201 = 1224024 + 4204221$$

$$:= 1022 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2201 = 1024044 + 4404201$$

$$5436345 := 101102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201101 = 1213224 + 4223121$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5486845 &:= 10012 \times 311 + 113 \times 21001 = 3113732 + 2373113 \\ &:= 11102 \times 112 + 211 \times 20111 = 1243424 + 4243421 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5488845 &:= 100402 \times 12 + 21 \times 204001 = 1204824 + 4284021 \\ &:= 1402 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2041 = 1404804 + 4084041 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5498945 &:= 10244 \times 101 + 101 \times 44201 = 1034644 + 4464301 \\ &:= 11234 \times 101 + 101 \times 43211 = 1134634 + 4364311 \\ &:= 12224 \times 101 + 101 \times 42221 = 1234624 + 4264321 \\ &:= 13214 \times 101 + 101 \times 41231 = 1334614 + 4164331 \\ &:= 14204 \times 101 + 101 \times 40241 = 1434604 + 4064341 \\ &:= 20243 \times 101 + 101 \times 34202 = 2044543 + 3454402 \\ &:= 21233 \times 101 + 101 \times 33212 = 2144533 + 3354412 \\ &:= 22223 \times 101 + 101 \times 32222 = 2244523 + 3254422 \\ &:= 23213 \times 101 + 101 \times 31232 = 2344513 + 3154432 \\ &:= 24203 \times 101 + 101 \times 30242 = 2444503 + 3054442 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5500055 &:= 100001 \times 14 + 41 \times 100001 = 1400014 + 4100041 \\ &:= 100001 \times 23 + 32 \times 100001 = 2300023 + 3200032 \\ &:= 100004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400001 = 1100044 + 4400011 \\ &:= 200003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300002 = 2200033 + 3300022 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5512155 &:= 100104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401001 = 1101144 + 4411011 \\ &:= 101004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400101 = 1111044 + 4401111 \\ &:= 200103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301002 = 2201133 + 3311022 \\ &:= 201003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300102 = 2211033 + 3301122 \end{aligned}$$

$$5518155 := 100101 \times 41 + 14 \times 101001 = 4104141 + 1414014$$

$$5520255 := 110002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200011 = 1320024 + 4200231$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5524255 &:= 100204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402001 = 1102244 + 4422011 \\ &:= 101104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401101 = 1112144 + 4412111 \\ &:= 102004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400201 = 1122044 + 4402211 \\ &:= 200203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302002 = 2202233 + 3322022 \\ &:= 201103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301102 = 2212133 + 3312122 \\ &:= 202003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300202 = 2222033 + 3302222 \end{aligned}$$

$$5526255 := 100101 \times 32 + 23 \times 101001 = 3203232 + 2323023$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5534355 &:= 100101 \times 23 + 32 \times 101001 = 2302323 + 3232032 \\ &:= 111002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200111 = 1332024 + 4202331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5536355 &:= 100304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403001 = 1103344 + 4433011 \\ &:= 101204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402101 = 1113244 + 4423111 \\ &:= 102104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401201 = 1123144 + 4413211 \\ &:= 103004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400301 = 1133044 + 4403311 \\ &:= 200303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303002 = 2203333 + 3333022 \\ &:= 201203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302102 = 2213233 + 3323122 \\ &:= 202103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301202 = 2223133 + 3313222 \\ &:= 203003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300302 = 2233033 + 3303322 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5542455 &:= 100101 \times 14 + 41 \times 101001 = 1401414 + 4141041 \\ &:= 110102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201011 = 1321224 + 4221231 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5548455 &:= 100404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404001 = 1104444 + 4444011 \\ &:= 101304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403101 = 1114344 + 4434111 \\ &:= 102204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402201 = 1124244 + 4424211 \\ &:= 103104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401301 = 1134144 + 4414311 \\ &:= 104004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400401 = 1144044 + 4404411 \\ &:= 112002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200211 = 1344024 + 4204431 \\ &:= 200403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304002 = 2204433 + 3344022 \\ &:= 201303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303102 = 2214333 + 3334122 \\ &:= 202203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302202 = 2224233 + 3324222 \\ &:= 203103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301302 = 2234133 + 3314322 \\ &:= 204003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300402 = 2244033 + 3304422 \\ &:= 11022 \times 102 + 201 \times 22011 = 1124244 + 4424211 \\ &:= 1122 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2211 = 1124244 + 4424211 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5550555 &:= 10004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40001 = 1110444 + 4440111 \\ &:= 20003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30002 = 2220333 + 3330222 \end{aligned}$$

$$5552555 := 10012 \times 112 + 211 \times 21001 = 1121344 + 4431211$$

$$5556555 := 111102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201111 = 1333224 + 4223331$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5564655 &:= 110202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202011 = 1322424 + 4242231 \\ &:= 10011 \times 213 + 312 \times 11001 = 2132343 + 3432312 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5568655 &:= 100201 \times 23 + 32 \times 102001 = 2304623 + 3264032 \\ &:= 12002 \times 112 + 211 \times 20021 = 1344224 + 4224431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5572755 &:= 10104 \times 111 + 111 \times 40101 = 1121544 + 4451211 \\ &:= 20103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30102 = 2231433 + 3341322 \end{aligned}$$

$$5578755 := 111202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202111 = 1334424 + 4244331$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10011 \times 421 + 124 \times 11001 = 4214631 + 1364124 \\ &:= 11122 \times 102 + 201 \times 22111 = 1134444 + 4444311 \\ &:= 12013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31021 = 2414613 + 3164142 \\ &:= 1312 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2131 = 1314624 + 4264131 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 212003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300212 = 2332033 + 3302332$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5638365} &:= 102012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210201 = 1224144 + 4414221 \\ &:= 1032 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2301 = 1034064 + 4604301 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5584855} &:= 100201 \times 14 + 41 \times 102001 = 1402814 + 4182041 \\ &:= 10013 \times 211 + 112 \times 31001 = 2112743 + 3472112 \\ &:= 10112 \times 112 + 211 \times 21101 = 1132544 + 4452311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5640465} &:= 100011 \times 41 + 14 \times 110001 = 4100451 + 1540014 \\ &:= 120002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200021 = 1440024 + 4200441 \\ &:= 10002 \times 122 + 221 \times 20001 = 1220244 + 4420221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5586855} := 110302 \times 12 + 21 \times 203011 = 1323624 + 4263231$$

$$\mathbf{5646465} := 100314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413001 = 1103454 + 4543011$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5594955} &:= 10204 \times 111 + 111 \times 40201 = 1132644 + 4462311 \\ &:= 20203 \times 111 + 111 \times 30202 = 2242533 + 3352422 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 101112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211101 = 1213344 + 4433121$$

$$:= 101214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412101 = 1113354 + 4533111$$

$$:= 102114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411201 = 1123254 + 4523211$$

$$:= 103014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410301 = 1133154 + 4513311$$

$$:= 110304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403011 = 1213344 + 4433121$$

$$:= 111204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402111 = 1223244 + 4423221$$

$$:= 112104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401211 = 1233144 + 4413321$$

$$:= 113004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400311 = 1243044 + 4403421$$

$$:= 200313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313002 = 2203443 + 3443022$$

$$:= 201213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312102 = 2213343 + 3433122$$

$$:= 202113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311202 = 2223243 + 3423222$$

$$:= 203013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310302 = 2233143 + 3413322$$

$$:= 210303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303012 = 2313333 + 3333132$$

$$:= 211203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302112 = 2323233 + 3323232$$

$$:= 212103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301212 = 2333133 + 3313332$$

$$:= 213003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300312 = 2343033 + 3303432$$

$$:= 10032 \times 102 + 201 \times 23001 = 1023264 + 4623201$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5622265} &:= 100114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411001 = 1101254 + 4521011 \\ &:= 101014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410101 = 1111154 + 4511111 \\ &:= 110104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401011 = 1211144 + 4411121 \\ &:= 111004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400111 = 1221044 + 4401221 \\ &:= 200113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311002 = 2201243 + 3421022 \\ &:= 201013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310102 = 2211143 + 3411122 \\ &:= 210103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301012 = 2311133 + 3311132 \\ &:= 211003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300112 = 2321033 + 3301232 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5650565} := 10001 \times 134 + 431 \times 10001 = 1340134 + 4310431$$

$$:= 10001 \times 233 + 332 \times 10001 = 2330233 + 3320332$$

$$\mathbf{5624265} := 101012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210101 = 1212144 + 4412121$$

$$\mathbf{5632365} := 100112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211001 = 1201344 + 4431021$$

$$\mathbf{5654565} := 100212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212001 = 1202544 + 4452021$$

$$:= 121002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200121 = 1452024 + 4202541$$

$$\mathbf{5634365} := 100214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412001 = 1102354 + 4532011$$

$$:= 101114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411101 = 1112254 + 4522111$$

$$:= 102014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410201 = 1122154 + 4512211$$

$$:= 110204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402011 = 1212244 + 4422121$$

$$:= 111104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401111 = 1222144 + 4412221$$

$$:= 112004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400211 = 1232044 + 4402321$$

$$:= 200213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312002 = 2202343 + 3432022$$

$$:= 201113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311102 = 2212243 + 3422122$$

$$:= 202013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310202 = 2222143 + 3412222$$

$$:= 210203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302012 = 2312233 + 3322132$$

$$:= 211103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301112 = 2322133 + 3312232$$

$$\mathbf{5658565} := 100111 \times 41 + 14 \times 111001 = 4104551 + 1554014$$

$$:= 100414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414001 = 1104554 + 4554011$$

$$:= 101314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413101 = 1114454 + 4544111$$

$$:= 102214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412201 = 1124354 + 4534211$$

$$:= 103114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411301 = 1134254 + 4524311$$

$$:= 104014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410401 = 1144154 + 4514411$$

$$:= 110404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404011 = 1214444 + 4444121$$

$$:= 111304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403111 = 1224344 + 4434221$$

$$:= 112204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402211 = 1234244 + 4424321$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 113104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401311 = 1244144 + 4414421 \\
&:= 114004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400411 = 1254044 + 4404521 \\
&:= 200413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314002 = 2204543 + 3454022 \\
&:= 201313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313102 = 2214443 + 3444122 \\
&:= 202213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312202 = 2224343 + 3434222 \\
&:= 203113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311302 = 2234243 + 3424322 \\
&:= 204013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310402 = 2244143 + 3414422 \\
&:= 210403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304012 = 2314433 + 3344132 \\
&:= 211303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303112 = 2324333 + 3334232 \\
&:= 212203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302212 = 2334233 + 3324332 \\
&:= 213103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301312 = 2344133 + 3314432 \\
&:= 214003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300412 = 2354033 + 3304532 \\
&:= 10021 \times 203 + 302 \times 12001 = 2034263 + 3624302 \\
&:= 1022 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 2201 = 1034264 + 4624301
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5684865 &:= 120202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202021 = 1442424 + 4242441 \\
&:= 10114 \times 111 + 111 \times 41101 = 1122654 + 4562211 \\
&:= 11104 \times 111 + 111 \times 40111 = 1232544 + 4452321 \\
&:= 20113 \times 111 + 111 \times 31102 = 2232543 + 3452322 \\
&:= 21103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30112 = 2342433 + 3342432
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5698965 &:= 100412 \times 12 + 21 \times 214001 = 1204944 + 4494021 \\
&:= 121202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202121 = 1454424 + 4244541 \\
&:= 10023 \times 211 + 112 \times 32001 = 2114853 + 3584112 \\
&:= 11112 \times 112 + 211 \times 21111 = 1244544 + 4454421 \\
&:= 1412 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2141 = 1414824 + 4284141
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5700075 &:= 100002 \times 31 + 13 \times 200001 = 3100062 + 2600013 \\
&:= 100003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300001 = 2100063 + 3600012
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5662665 &:= 120102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201021 = 1441224 + 4221441 \\
&:= 10011 \times 114 + 411 \times 11001 = 1141254 + 4521411 \\
&:= 10014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41001 = 1111554 + 4551111 \\
&:= 11004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40011 = 1221444 + 4441221 \\
&:= 20013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31002 = 2221443 + 3441222 \\
&:= 21003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30012 = 2331333 + 3331332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5714175 &:= 100103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301001 = 2102163 + 3612012 \\
5716175 &:= 100102 \times 31 + 13 \times 201001 = 3103162 + 2613013
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5720275 &:= 100024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420001 = 1100264 + 4620011 \\
&:= 110014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410011 = 1210154 + 4510121 \\
&:= 120004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400021 = 1320044 + 4400231 \\
&:= 200023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320002 = 2200253 + 3520022 \\
&:= 210013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310012 = 2310143 + 3410132 \\
&:= 220003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300022 = 2420033 + 3300242
\end{aligned}$$

$$**5666665** := 11012 \times 112 + 211 \times 21011 = 1233344 + 4433321$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5668665 &:= 101212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212101 = 1214544 + 4454121 \\
&:= 122002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200221 = 1464024 + 4204641 \\
&:= 1222 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2221 = 1224444 + 4444221
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5722275 &:= 101003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300101 = 2121063 + 3601212 \\
5728275 &:= 100203 \times 21 + 12 \times 302001 = 2104263 + 3624012
\end{aligned}$$

$$**5670765** := 10002 \times 321 + 123 \times 20001 = 3210642 + 2460123$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5730375 &:= 100011 \times 32 + 23 \times 110001 = 3200352 + 2530023 \\
&:= 110012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210011 = 1320144 + 4410231
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5674765 &:= 10102 \times 122 + 221 \times 20101 = 1232444 + 4442321 \\
&:= 12002 \times 301 + 103 \times 20021 = 3612602 + 2062163
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5732375 &:= 100124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421001 = 1101364 + 4631011 \\
&:= 101002 \times 31 + 13 \times 200101 = 3131062 + 2601313 \\
&:= 101024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420101 = 1111264 + 4621111 \\
&:= 110114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411011 = 1211254 + 4521121 \\
&:= 111014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410111 = 1221154 + 4511221 \\
&:= 120104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401021 = 1321144 + 4411231 \\
&:= 121004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400121 = 1331044 + 4401331 \\
&:= 200123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321002 = 2201353 + 3531022 \\
&:= 201023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320102 = 2211253 + 3521122 \\
&:= 210113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311012 = 2311243 + 3421132 \\
&:= 211013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310112 = 2321143 + 3411232 \\
&:= 220103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301022 = 2421133 + 3311242
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5676765 &:= 100312 \times 12 + 21 \times 213001 = 1203744 + 4473021 \\
&:= 121102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201121 = 1453224 + 4223541 \\
&:= 10011 \times 322 + 223 \times 11001 = 3223542 + 2453223 \\
&:= 10132 \times 102 + 201 \times 23101 = 1033464 + 4643301 \\
&:= 13003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30031 = 2613603 + 3063162
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5682865 &:= 101011 \times 41 + 14 \times 110101 = 4141451 + 1541414 \\
&:= 11002 \times 311 + 113 \times 20011 = 3421622 + 2261243 \\
&:= 11003 \times 211 + 112 \times 30011 = 2321633 + 3361232
\end{aligned}$$

$$:= 221003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300122 = 2431033 + 3301342$$

$$\mathbf{5736375} := 101103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301101 = 2123163 + 3613212$$

$$\mathbf{5744475} := 100224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422001 = 1102464 + 4642011$$

$$:= 101124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421101 = 1112364 + 4632111$$

$$:= 102003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300201 = 2142063 + 3602412$$

$$:= 102024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420201 = 1122264 + 4622211$$

$$:= 110214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412011 = 1212354 + 4532121$$

$$:= 111012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210111 = 1332144 + 4412331$$

$$:= 111114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411111 = 1222254 + 4522221$$

$$:= 112014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410211 = 1232154 + 4512321$$

$$:= 120204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402021 = 1322244 + 4422231$$

$$:= 121104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401121 = 1332144 + 4412331$$

$$:= 122004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400221 = 1342044 + 4402431$$

$$:= 200223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322002 = 2202453 + 3542022$$

$$:= 201123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321102 = 2212353 + 3532122$$

$$:= 202023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320202 = 2222253 + 3522222$$

$$:= 210213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312012 = 2312343 + 3432132$$

$$:= 211113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311112 = 2322243 + 3422232$$

$$:= 212013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310212 = 2332143 + 3412332$$

$$:= 220203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302022 = 2422233 + 3322242$$

$$:= 221103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301122 = 2432133 + 3312342$$

$$:= 222003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300222 = 2442033 + 3302442$$

$$\mathbf{5748475} := 101102 \times 31 + 13 \times 201101 = 3134162 + 2614313$$

$$\mathbf{5752575} := 110112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211011 = 1321344 + 4431231$$

$$\mathbf{5756575} := 100111 \times 32 + 23 \times 111001 = 3203552 + 2553023$$

$$:= 100324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423001 = 1103564 + 4653011$$

$$:= 101224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422101 = 1113464 + 4643111$$

$$:= 102124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421201 = 1123364 + 4633211$$

$$:= 103024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420301 = 1133264 + 4623311$$

$$:= 110314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413011 = 1213454 + 4543121$$

$$:= 111214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412111 = 1223354 + 4533221$$

$$:= 112114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411211 = 1233254 + 4523321$$

$$:= 113014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410311 = 1243154 + 4513421$$

$$:= 120304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403021 = 1323344 + 4433231$$

$$:= 121204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402121 = 1333244 + 4423331$$

$$:= 122104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401221 = 1343144 + 4413431$$

$$:= 123004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400321 = 1353044 + 4403531$$

$$:= 200323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323002 = 2203553 + 3553022$$

$$:= 201223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322102 = 2213453 + 3543122$$

$$:= 202123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321202 = 2223353 + 3533222$$

$$:= 203023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320302 = 2233253 + 3523322$$

$$:= 210313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313012 = 2313443 + 3443132$$

$$:= 211213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312112 = 2323343 + 3433232$$

$$:= 212113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311212 = 2333243 + 3423332$$

$$:= 213013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310312 = 2343143 + 3413432$$

$$:= 220303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303022 = 2423333 + 3333242$$

$$:= 221203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302122 = 2433233 + 3323342$$

$$:= 222103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301222 = 2443133 + 3313442$$

$$:= 223003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300322 = 2453033 + 3303542$$

$$\mathbf{5758575} := 102103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301201 = 2144163 + 3614412$$

$$:= 112012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210211 = 1344144 + 4414431$$

$$:= 1132 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2311 = 1134264 + 4624311$$

$$\mathbf{5760675} := 130002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200031 = 1560024 + 4200651$$

$$\mathbf{5764675} := 101011 \times 32 + 23 \times 110101 = 3232352 + 2532323$$

$$:= 102002 \times 31 + 13 \times 200201 = 3162062 + 2602613$$

$$:= 10022 \times 112 + 211 \times 22001 = 1122464 + 4642211$$

$$:= 11002 \times 122 + 221 \times 20011 = 1342244 + 4422431$$

$$\mathbf{5766675} := 103003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300301 = 2163063 + 3603612$$

$$:= 111112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211111 = 1333344 + 4433331$$

$$\mathbf{5768675} := 100424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424001 = 1104664 + 4664011$$

$$:= 100424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424001 = 1104664 + 4664011$$

$$:= 101324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423101 = 1114564 + 4654111$$

$$:= 101324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423101 = 1114564 + 4654111$$

$$:= 102224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422201 = 1124464 + 4644211$$

$$:= 102224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422201 = 1124464 + 4644211$$

$$:= 103124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421301 = 1134364 + 4634311$$

$$:= 103124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421301 = 1134364 + 4634311$$

$$:= 104024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420401 = 1144264 + 4624411$$

$$:= 104024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420401 = 1144264 + 4624411$$

$$:= 110414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414011 = 1214554 + 4554121$$

$$:= 110414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414011 = 1214554 + 4554121$$

$$:= 111314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413111 = 1224454 + 4544221$$

$$:= 111314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413111 = 1224454 + 4544221$$

$$:= 112214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412211 = 1234354 + 4534321$$

$$:= 112214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412211 = 1234354 + 4534321$$

$$:= 113114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411311 = 1244254 + 4524421$$

$$:= 113114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411311 = 1244254 + 4524421$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 114014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410411 = 1254154 + 4514521 \\
&:= 114014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410411 = 1254154 + 4514521 \\
&:= 120404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404021 = 1324444 + 4444231 \\
&:= 120404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404021 = 1324444 + 4444231 \\
&:= 121304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403121 = 1334344 + 4434331 \\
&:= 121304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403121 = 1334344 + 4434331 \\
&:= 122204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402221 = 1344244 + 4424431 \\
&:= 122204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402221 = 1344244 + 4424431 \\
&:= 123104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401321 = 1354144 + 4414531 \\
&:= 123104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401321 = 1354144 + 4414531 \\
&:= 124004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400421 = 1364044 + 4404631 \\
&:= 124004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400421 = 1364044 + 4404631 \\
&:= 200423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324002 = 2204653 + 3564022 \\
&:= 200423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324002 = 2204653 + 3564022 \\
&:= 201323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323102 = 2214553 + 3554122 \\
&:= 201323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323102 = 2214553 + 3554122 \\
&:= 202223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322202 = 2224453 + 3544222 \\
&:= 202223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322202 = 2224453 + 3544222 \\
&:= 203123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321302 = 2234353 + 3534322 \\
&:= 203123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321302 = 2234353 + 3534322 \\
&:= 204023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320402 = 2244253 + 3524422 \\
&:= 204023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320402 = 2244253 + 3524422 \\
&:= 210413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314012 = 2314543 + 3454132 \\
&:= 210413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314012 = 2314543 + 3454132 \\
&:= 211313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313112 = 2324443 + 3444232 \\
&:= 211313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313112 = 2324443 + 3444232 \\
&:= 212213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312212 = 2334343 + 3434332 \\
&:= 212213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312212 = 2334343 + 3434332 \\
&:= 213113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311312 = 2344243 + 3424432 \\
&:= 213113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311312 = 2344243 + 3424432 \\
&:= 214013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310412 = 2354143 + 3414532 \\
&:= 214013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310412 = 2354143 + 3414532 \\
&:= 220403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304022 = 2424433 + 3344242 \\
&:= 220403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304022 = 2424433 + 3344242 \\
&:= 221303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303122 = 2434333 + 3334342 \\
&:= 221303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303122 = 2434333 + 3334342 \\
&:= 222203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302222 = 2444233 + 3324442 \\
&:= 222203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302222 = 2444233 + 3324442 \\
&:= 223103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301322 = 2454133 + 3314542 \\
&:= 223103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301322 = 2454133 + 3314542 \\
&:= 224003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300422 = 2464033 + 3304642 \\
&:= 224003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300422 = 2464033 + 3304642
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5774775 &:= 110212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212011 = 1322544 + 4452231 \\
&:= 131002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200131 = 1572024 + 4202751 \\
&:= 10011 \times 223 + 322 \times 11001 = 2232453 + 3542322 \\
&:= 10024 \times 111 + 111 \times 42001 = 1112664 + 4662111 \\
&:= 11014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41011 = 1222554 + 4552221 \\
&:= 12004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40021 = 1332444 + 4442331 \\
&:= 20023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32002 = 2222553 + 3552222 \\
&:= 21013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31012 = 2332443 + 3442332 \\
&:= 22003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30022 = 2442333 + 3332442
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5780875 &:= 100021 \times 41 + 14 \times 120001 = 4100861 + 1680014 \\
5782875 &:= 130102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201031 = 1561224 + 4221651
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5788875 &:= 104003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300401 = 2184063 + 3604812 \\
&:= 111212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212111 = 1334544 + 4454331 \\
&:= 132002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200231 = 1584024 + 4204851 \\
&:= 10011 \times 431 + 134 \times 11001 = 4314741 + 1474134 \\
&:= 1322 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2231 = 1324644 + 4464231
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5796975 &:= 103002 \times 31 + 13 \times 200301 = 3193062 + 2603913 \\
&:= 110312 \times 12 + 21 \times 213011 = 1323744 + 4473231 \\
&:= 131102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201131 = 1573224 + 4223751 \\
&:= 10012 \times 321 + 123 \times 21001 = 3213852 + 2583123 \\
&:= 10122 \times 112 + 211 \times 22101 = 1133664 + 4663311 \\
&:= 10124 \times 111 + 111 \times 42101 = 1123764 + 4673211 \\
&:= 11013 \times 211 + 112 \times 31011 = 2323743 + 3473232 \\
&:= 11114 \times 111 + 111 \times 41111 = 1233654 + 4563321 \\
&:= 12104 \times 111 + 111 \times 40121 = 1343544 + 4453431 \\
&:= 20123 \times 111 + 111 \times 32102 = 2233653 + 3563322 \\
&:= 21113 \times 111 + 111 \times 31112 = 2343543 + 3453432 \\
&:= 22103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30122 = 2453433 + 3343542
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5798975 &:= 100121 \times 41 + 14 \times 121001 = 4104961 + 1694014 \\
&:= 102011 \times 32 + 23 \times 110201 = 3264352 + 2534623 \\
&:= 11012 \times 311 + 113 \times 21011 = 3424732 + 2374243 \\
&:= 11102 \times 122 + 221 \times 20111 = 1354444 + 4444531
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5820285 &:= 100011 \times 23 + 32 \times 110001 = 2300253 + 3520032 \\
&:= 100013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310001 = 2100273 + 3720012 \\
&:= 100022 \times 12 + 21 \times 220001 = 1200264 + 4620021
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5830385 &:= 100012 \times 31 + 13 \times 210001 = 3100372 + 2730013 \\
&:= 100034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430001 = 1100374 + 4730011
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 110024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420011 = 1210264 + 4620121 \\ &:= 120014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410021 = 1320154 + 4510231 \\ &:= 130004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400031 = 1430044 + 4400341 \\ &:= 200033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330002 = 2200363 + 3630022 \\ &:= 210023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320012 = 2310253 + 3520132 \\ &:= 220013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310022 = 2420143 + 3410242 \\ &:= 230003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300032 = 2530033 + 3300352 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5834385} &:= 100113 \times 21 + 12 \times 311001 = 2102373 + 3732012 \\ &:= 101022 \times 12 + 21 \times 220101 = 1212264 + 4622121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5842485} &:= 100122 \times 12 + 21 \times 221001 = 1201464 + 4641021 \\ &:= 100134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431001 = 1101474 + 4741011 \\ &:= 101013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310101 = 2121273 + 3721212 \\ &:= 101034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430101 = 1111374 + 4731111 \\ &:= 110124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421011 = 1211364 + 4631121 \\ &:= 111024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420111 = 1221264 + 4621221 \\ &:= 120114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411021 = 1321254 + 4521231 \\ &:= 121014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410121 = 1331154 + 4511331 \\ &:= 130104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401031 = 1431144 + 4411341 \\ &:= 131004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400131 = 1441044 + 4401441 \\ &:= 200133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331002 = 2201463 + 3641022 \\ &:= 201033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330102 = 2211363 + 3631122 \\ &:= 210123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321012 = 2311353 + 3531132 \\ &:= 211023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320112 = 2321253 + 3521232 \\ &:= 220113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311022 = 2421243 + 3421242 \\ &:= 221013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310122 = 2431143 + 3411342 \\ &:= 230103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301032 = 2531133 + 3311352 \\ &:= 231003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300132 = 2541033 + 3301452 \\ &:= 431001 \times 11 + 11 \times 100134 = 4741011 + 1101474 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5846485} &:= 100112 \times 31 + 13 \times 211001 = 3103472 + 2743013 \\ &:= 101011 \times 23 + 32 \times 110101 = 2323253 + 3523232 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5848485} &:= 100213 \times 21 + 12 \times 312001 = 2104473 + 3744012 \\ &:= 102022 \times 12 + 21 \times 220201 = 1224264 + 4624221 \\ &:= 10042 \times 102 + 201 \times 24001 = 1024284 + 4824201 \\ &:= 1042 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2401 = 1044084 + 4804401 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5850585} &:= 10001 \times 144 + 441 \times 10001 = 1440144 + 4410441 \\ &:= 10001 \times 243 + 342 \times 10001 = 2430243 + 3420342 \\ &:= 120012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210021 = 1440144 + 4410441 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5854585} &:= 100111 \times 23 + 32 \times 111001 = 2302553 + 3552032 \\ &:= 10021 \times 104 + 401 \times 12001 = 1042184 + 4812401 \\ &:= 100234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432001 = 1102574 + 4752011 \\ &:= 101134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431101 = 1112474 + 4742111 \\ &:= 102034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430201 = 1122374 + 4732211 \\ &:= 110224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422011 = 1212464 + 4642121 \\ &:= 111124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421111 = 1222364 + 4632221 \\ &:= 112024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420211 = 1232264 + 4622321 \\ &:= 120214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412021 = 1322354 + 4532231 \\ &:= 121114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411121 = 1332254 + 4522331 \\ &:= 122014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410221 = 1342154 + 4512431 \\ &:= 130204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402031 = 1432244 + 4422341 \\ &:= 131104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401131 = 1442144 + 4412441 \\ &:= 132004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400231 = 1452044 + 4402541 \\ &:= 200233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332002 = 2202563 + 3652022 \\ &:= 201133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331102 = 2212463 + 3642122 \\ &:= 202033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330202 = 2222363 + 3632222 \\ &:= 210223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322012 = 2312453 + 3542132 \\ &:= 211123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321112 = 2322353 + 3532232 \\ &:= 212023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320212 = 2332253 + 3522332 \\ &:= 220213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312022 = 2422343 + 3432242 \\ &:= 221113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311122 = 2432243 + 3422342 \\ &:= 222013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310222 = 2442143 + 3412442 \\ &:= 230203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302032 = 2532233 + 3322352 \\ &:= 231103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301132 = 2542133 + 3312452 \\ &:= 232003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300232 = 2552033 + 3302552 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5856585} &:= 101113 \times 21 + 12 \times 311101 = 2123373 + 3733212 \\ &:= 101122 \times 12 + 21 \times 221101 = 1213464 + 4643121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5862685} &:= 101012 \times 31 + 13 \times 210101 = 3131372 + 2731313 \\ &:= 10012 \times 122 + 221 \times 21001 = 1221464 + 4641221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5864685} &:= 100222 \times 12 + 21 \times 222001 = 1202664 + 4662021 \\ &:= 102013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310201 = 2142273 + 3722412 \\ &:= 121012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210121 = 1452144 + 4412541 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5866685} &:= 100334 \times 11 + 11 \times 433001 = 1103674 + 4763011 \\ &:= 101234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432101 = 1113574 + 4753111 \\ &:= 102134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431201 = 1123474 + 4743211 \\ &:= 103034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430301 = 1133374 + 4733311 \\ &:= 110324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423011 = 1213564 + 4653121 \\ &:= 111224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422111 = 1223464 + 4643221 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 112124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421211 = 1233364 + 4633321 \\
&:= 113024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420311 = 1243264 + 4623421 \\
&:= 120314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413021 = 1323454 + 4543231 \\
&:= 121214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412121 = 1333354 + 4533331 \\
&:= 122114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411221 = 1343254 + 4523431 \\
&:= 123014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410321 = 1353154 + 4513531 \\
&:= 130304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403031 = 1433344 + 4433341 \\
&:= 131204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402131 = 1443244 + 4423441 \\
&:= 132104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401231 = 1453144 + 4413541 \\
&:= 133004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400331 = 1463044 + 4403641 \\
&:= 200333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333002 = 2203663 + 3663022 \\
&:= 201233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332102 = 2213563 + 3653122 \\
&:= 202133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331202 = 2223463 + 3643222 \\
&:= 203033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330302 = 2233363 + 3633322 \\
&:= 210323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323012 = 2313553 + 3553132 \\
&:= 211223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322112 = 2323453 + 3543232 \\
&:= 212123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321212 = 2333353 + 3533332 \\
&:= 213023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320312 = 2343253 + 3523432 \\
&:= 220313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313022 = 2423443 + 3443242 \\
&:= 221213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312122 = 2433343 + 3433342 \\
&:= 222113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311222 = 2443243 + 3423442 \\
&:= 223013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310322 = 2453143 + 3413542 \\
&:= 230303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303032 = 2533333 + 3333352 \\
&:= 231203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302132 = 2543233 + 3323452 \\
&:= 232103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301232 = 2553133 + 3313552 \\
&:= 233003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300332 = 2563033 + 3303652
\end{aligned}$$

$$5870785 := 10003 \times 221 + 122 \times 30001 = 2210663 + 3660122$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5872785 &:= 120112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211021 = 1441344 + 4431441 \\
&:= 10011 \times 124 + 421 \times 11001 = 1241364 + 4631421
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5878785 &:= 100434 \times 11 + 11 \times 434001 = 1104774 + 4774011 \\
&:= 101112 \times 31 + 13 \times 211101 = 3134472 + 2744313 \\
&:= 101222 \times 12 + 21 \times 222101 = 1214664 + 4664121 \\
&:= 101334 \times 11 + 11 \times 433101 = 1114674 + 4764111 \\
&:= 102113 \times 21 + 12 \times 311201 = 2144373 + 3734412 \\
&:= 102234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432201 = 1124574 + 4754211 \\
&:= 103134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431301 = 1134474 + 4744311 \\
&:= 104034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430401 = 1144374 + 4734411 \\
&:= 110424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424011 = 1214664 + 4664121 \\
&:= 111324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423111 = 1224564 + 4654221 \\
&:= 112224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422211 = 1234464 + 4644321
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 113124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421311 = 1244364 + 4634421 \\
&:= 114024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420411 = 1254264 + 4624521 \\
&:= 120414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414021 = 1324554 + 4554231 \\
&:= 121314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413121 = 1334454 + 4544331 \\
&:= 122012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210221 = 1464144 + 4414641 \\
&:= 122214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412221 = 1344354 + 4534431 \\
&:= 123114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411321 = 1354254 + 4524531 \\
&:= 124014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410421 = 1364154 + 4514631 \\
&:= 130404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404031 = 1434444 + 4444341 \\
&:= 131304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403131 = 1444344 + 4434441 \\
&:= 132204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402231 = 1454244 + 4424541 \\
&:= 133104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401331 = 1464144 + 4414641 \\
&:= 134004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400431 = 1474044 + 4404741 \\
&:= 200433 \times 11 + 11 \times 334002 = 2204763 + 3674022 \\
&:= 201333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333102 = 2214663 + 3664122 \\
&:= 202233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332202 = 2224563 + 3654222 \\
&:= 203133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331302 = 2234463 + 3644322 \\
&:= 204033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330402 = 2244363 + 3634422 \\
&:= 210423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324012 = 2314653 + 3564132 \\
&:= 211323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323112 = 2324553 + 3554232 \\
&:= 212223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322212 = 2334453 + 3544332 \\
&:= 213123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321312 = 2344353 + 3534432 \\
&:= 214023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320412 = 2354253 + 3524532 \\
&:= 220413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314022 = 2424543 + 3454242 \\
&:= 221313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313122 = 2434443 + 3444342 \\
&:= 222213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312222 = 2444343 + 3434442 \\
&:= 223113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311322 = 2454243 + 3424542 \\
&:= 224013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310422 = 2464143 + 3414642 \\
&:= 230403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304032 = 2534433 + 3344352 \\
&:= 231303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303132 = 2544333 + 3334452 \\
&:= 232203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302232 = 2554233 + 3324552 \\
&:= 233103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301332 = 2564133 + 3314652 \\
&:= 234003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300432 = 2574033 + 3304752 \\
&:= 10021 \times 213 + 312 \times 12001 = 2134473 + 3744312 \\
&:= 10142 \times 102 + 201 \times 24101 = 1034484 + 4844301 \\
&:= 11022 \times 112 + 211 \times 22011 = 1234464 + 4644321 \\
&:= 14003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30041 = 2814603 + 3064182 \\
&:= 1032 \times 1012 + 2101 \times 2301 = 1044384 + 4834401 \\
&:= 1232 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2321 = 1234464 + 4644321
\end{aligned}$$

$$5880885 := 140002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200041 = 1680024 + 4200861$$

$$5886885 := 100322 \times 12 + 21 \times 223001 = 1203864 + 4683021$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 103013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310301 = 2163273 + 3723612 \\ &:= 121112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211121 = 1453344 + 4433541 \\ &:= 10011 \times 332 + 233 \times 11001 = 3323652 + 2563233 \\ &:= 10034 \times 111 + 111 \times 43001 = 1113774 + 4773111 \\ &:= 11024 \times 111 + 111 \times 42011 = 1223664 + 4663221 \\ &:= 12014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41021 = 1333554 + 4553331 \\ &:= 13004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40031 = 1443444 + 4443441 \\ &:= 20033 \times 111 + 111 \times 33002 = 2223663 + 3663222 \\ &:= 21023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32012 = 2333553 + 3553332 \\ &:= 22013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31022 = 2443443 + 3443442 \\ &:= 23003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30032 = 2553333 + 3333552 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5888885} &:= 100211 \times 23 + 32 \times 112001 = 2304853 + 3584032 \\ &:= 12002 \times 122 + 221 \times 20021 = 1464244 + 4424641 \\ &:= 1022 \times 1022 + 2201 \times 2201 = 1044484 + 4844401 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5894985} &:= 102012 \times 31 + 13 \times 210201 = 3162372 + 2732613 \\ &:= 120212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212021 = 1442544 + 4452441 \\ &:= 141002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200141 = 1692024 + 4202961 \\ &:= 12003 \times 211 + 112 \times 30021 = 2532633 + 3362352 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5896985} := 10112 \times 122 + 221 \times 21101 = 1233664 + 4663321$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5910195} &:= 100011 \times 14 + 41 \times 110001 = 1400154 + 4510041 \\ &:= 110003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300011 = 2310063 + 3600132 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5924295} := 110103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301011 = 2312163 + 3612132$$

$$\mathbf{5928295} := 101011 \times 14 + 41 \times 110101 = 1414154 + 4514141$$

$$\mathbf{5932395} := 111003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300111 = 2331063 + 3601332$$

$$\mathbf{5938395} := 110203 \times 21 + 12 \times 302011 = 2314263 + 3624132$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5940495} &:= 100023 \times 21 + 12 \times 320001 = 2100483 + 3840012 \\ &:= 100044 \times 11 + 11 \times 440001 = 1100484 + 4840011 \\ &:= 110022 \times 12 + 21 \times 220011 = 1320264 + 4620231 \\ &:= 110034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430011 = 1210374 + 4730121 \\ &:= 120024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420021 = 1320264 + 4620231 \\ &:= 130014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410031 = 1430154 + 4510341 \\ &:= 140004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400041 = 1540044 + 4400451 \\ &:= 200043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340002 = 2200473 + 3740022 \\ &:= 210033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330012 = 2310363 + 3630132 \\ &:= 220023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320022 = 2420253 + 3520242 \\ &:= 230013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310032 = 2530143 + 3410352 \\ &:= 240003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300042 = 2640033 + 3300462 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 10002 \times 132 + 231 \times 20001 = 1320264 + 4620231$$

$$\mathbf{5946495} := 111103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301111 = 2333163 + 3613332$$

$$\mathbf{5952595} := 100111 \times 14 + 41 \times 111001 = 1401554 + 4551041$$

$$:= 100144 \times 11 + 11 \times 441001 = 1101584 + 4851011$$

$$:= 101044 \times 11 + 11 \times 440101 = 1111484 + 4841111$$

$$:= 110134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431011 = 1211474 + 4741121$$

$$:= 111034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430111 = 1221374 + 4731221$$

$$:= 120124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421021 = 1321364 + 4631231$$

$$:= 121024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420121 = 1331264 + 4621331$$

$$:= 130114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411031 = 1431254 + 4521341$$

$$:= 131014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410131 = 1441154 + 4511441$$

$$:= 140104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401041 = 1541144 + 4411451$$

$$:= 141004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400141 = 1551044 + 4401551$$

$$:= 200143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341002 = 2201573 + 3751022$$

$$:= 201043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340102 = 2211473 + 3741122$$

$$:= 210133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331012 = 2311463 + 3641132$$

$$:= 211033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330112 = 2321363 + 3631232$$

$$:= 220123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321022 = 2421353 + 3531242$$

$$:= 221023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320122 = 2431253 + 3521342$$

$$:= 230113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311032 = 2531243 + 3421352$$

$$:= 231013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310132 = 2541143 + 3411452$$

$$:= 240103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301042 = 2641133 + 3311462$$

$$:= 241003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300142 = 2651033 + 3301562$$

$$\mathbf{5954595} := 100123 \times 21 + 12 \times 321001 = 2102583 + 3852012$$

$$:= 111022 \times 12 + 21 \times 220111 = 1332264 + 4622331$$

$$:= 112003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300211 = 2352063 + 3602532$$

$$\mathbf{5960695} := 100021 \times 32 + 23 \times 120001 = 3200672 + 2760023$$

$$:= 100022 \times 31 + 13 \times 220001 = 3100682 + 2860013$$

$$\mathbf{5962695} := 101023 \times 21 + 12 \times 320101 = 2121483 + 3841212$$

$$:= 110122 \times 12 + 21 \times 221011 = 1321464 + 4641231$$

$$\mathbf{5964695} := 100244 \times 11 + 11 \times 442001 = 1102684 + 4862011$$

$$:= 101144 \times 11 + 11 \times 441101 = 1112584 + 4852111$$

$$:= 102044 \times 11 + 11 \times 440201 = 1122484 + 4842211$$

$$:= 110234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432011 = 1212574 + 4752121$$

$$:= 111134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431111 = 1222474 + 4742221$$

$$:= 112034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430211 = 1232374 + 4732321$$

$$:= 120224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422021 = 1322464 + 4642231$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 121124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421121 = 1332364 + 4632331 \\
&:= 122024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420221 = 1342264 + 4622431 \\
&:= 130214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412031 = 1432354 + 4532341 \\
&:= 131114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411131 = 1442254 + 4522441 \\
&:= 132014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410231 = 1452154 + 4512541 \\
&:= 140204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402041 = 1542244 + 4422451 \\
&:= 141104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401141 = 1552144 + 4412551 \\
&:= 142004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400241 = 1562044 + 4402651 \\
&:= 200243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342002 = 2202673 + 3762022 \\
&:= 201143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341102 = 2212573 + 3752122 \\
&:= 202043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340202 = 2222473 + 3742222 \\
&:= 210233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332012 = 2312563 + 3652132 \\
&:= 211133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331112 = 2322463 + 3642232 \\
&:= 212033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330212 = 2332363 + 3632332 \\
&:= 220223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322022 = 2422453 + 3542242 \\
&:= 221123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321122 = 2432353 + 3532342 \\
&:= 222023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320222 = 2442253 + 3522442 \\
&:= 230213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312032 = 2532343 + 3432352 \\
&:= 231113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311132 = 2542243 + 3422452 \\
&:= 232013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310232 = 2552143 + 3412552 \\
&:= 240203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302042 = 2642233 + 3322462 \\
&:= 241103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301142 = 2652133 + 3312562 \\
&:= 242003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300242 = 2662033 + 3302662
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{5968695} &:= 100223 \times 21 + 12 \times 322001 = 2104683 + 3864012 \\
&:= 112022 \times 12 + 21 \times 220211 = 1344264 + 4624431 \\
&:= 112103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301211 = 2354163 + 3614532 \\
&:= 1142 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2411 = 1144284 + 4824411
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{5970795} &:= 130012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210031 = 1560144 + 4410651 \\
&:= 10002 \times 331 + 133 \times 20001 = 3310662 + 2660133
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{5976795} &:= 100122 \times 31 + 13 \times 221001 = 3103782 + 2873013 \\
&:= 100344 \times 11 + 11 \times 443001 = 1103784 + 4873011 \\
&:= 101123 \times 21 + 12 \times 321101 = 2123583 + 3853212 \\
&:= 101244 \times 11 + 11 \times 442101 = 1113684 + 4863111 \\
&:= 102144 \times 11 + 11 \times 441201 = 1123584 + 4853211 \\
&:= 103044 \times 11 + 11 \times 440301 = 1133484 + 4843311 \\
&:= 110334 \times 11 + 11 \times 433011 = 1213674 + 4763121 \\
&:= 111122 \times 12 + 21 \times 221111 = 1333464 + 4643331 \\
&:= 111234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432111 = 1223574 + 4753221 \\
&:= 112134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431211 = 1233474 + 4743321 \\
&:= 113003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300311 = 2373063 + 3603732
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 113034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430311 = 1243374 + 4733421 \\
&:= 120324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423021 = 1323564 + 4653231 \\
&:= 121224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422121 = 1333464 + 4643331 \\
&:= 122124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421221 = 1343364 + 4633431 \\
&:= 123024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420321 = 1353264 + 4623531 \\
&:= 130314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413031 = 1433454 + 4543341 \\
&:= 131214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412131 = 1443354 + 4533441 \\
&:= 132114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411231 = 1453254 + 4523541 \\
&:= 133014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410331 = 1463154 + 4513641 \\
&:= 140304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403041 = 1543344 + 4433451 \\
&:= 141204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402141 = 1553244 + 4423551 \\
&:= 142104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401241 = 1563144 + 4413651 \\
&:= 143004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400341 = 1573044 + 4403751 \\
&:= 200343 \times 11 + 11 \times 343002 = 2203773 + 3773022 \\
&:= 201243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342102 = 2213673 + 3763122 \\
&:= 202143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341202 = 2223573 + 3753222 \\
&:= 203043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340302 = 2233473 + 3743322 \\
&:= 210333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333012 = 2313663 + 3663132 \\
&:= 211233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332112 = 2323563 + 3653232 \\
&:= 212133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331212 = 2333463 + 3643332 \\
&:= 213033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330312 = 2343363 + 3633432 \\
&:= 220323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323022 = 2423553 + 3553242 \\
&:= 221223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322122 = 2433453 + 3543342 \\
&:= 222123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321222 = 2443353 + 3533442 \\
&:= 223023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320322 = 2453253 + 3523542 \\
&:= 230313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313032 = 2533443 + 3443352 \\
&:= 231213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312132 = 2543343 + 3433452 \\
&:= 232113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311232 = 2553243 + 3423552 \\
&:= 233013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310332 = 2563143 + 3413652 \\
&:= 240303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303042 = 2643333 + 3333462 \\
&:= 241203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302142 = 2653233 + 3323562 \\
&:= 242103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301242 = 2663133 + 3313662 \\
&:= 243003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300342 = 2673033 + 3303762 \\
&:= 10032 \times 112 + 211 \times 23001 = 1123584 + 4853211 \\
&:= 10102 \times 132 + 231 \times 20101 = 1333464 + 4643331 \\
&:= 13002 \times 301 + 103 \times 20031 = 3913602 + 2063193
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{5984895} &:= 102023 \times 21 + 12 \times 320201 = 2142483 + 3842412 \\
&:= 110222 \times 12 + 21 \times 222011 = 1322664 + 4662231 \\
&:= 131012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210131 = 1572144 + 4412751 \\
&:= 10011 \times 233 + 332 \times 11001 = 2332563 + 3652332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5986895} := 100121 \times 32 + 23 \times 121001 = 3203872 + 2783023$$

$$:= 11012 \times 122 + 221 \times 21011 = 1343464 + 4643431$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5988895 &:= 100444 \times 11 + 11 \times 444001 = 1104884 + 4884011 \\ &:= 101344 \times 11 + 11 \times 443101 = 1114784 + 4874111 \\ &:= 102244 \times 11 + 11 \times 442201 = 1124684 + 4864211 \\ &:= 103144 \times 11 + 11 \times 441301 = 1134584 + 4854311 \\ &:= 104044 \times 11 + 11 \times 440401 = 1144484 + 4844411 \\ &:= 110434 \times 11 + 11 \times 434011 = 1214774 + 4774121 \\ &:= 111334 \times 11 + 11 \times 433111 = 1224674 + 4764221 \\ &:= 112234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432211 = 1234574 + 4754321 \\ &:= 113134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431311 = 1244474 + 4744421 \\ &:= 114034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430411 = 1254374 + 4734521 \\ &:= 120424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424021 = 1324664 + 4664231 \\ &:= 121324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423121 = 1334564 + 4654331 \\ &:= 122224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422221 = 1344464 + 4644431 \\ &:= 123124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421321 = 1354364 + 4634531 \\ &:= 124024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420421 = 1364264 + 4624631 \\ &:= 130414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414031 = 1434554 + 4554341 \\ &:= 131314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413131 = 1444454 + 4544441 \\ &:= 132214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412231 = 1454354 + 4534541 \\ &:= 133114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411331 = 1464254 + 4524641 \\ &:= 134014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410431 = 1474154 + 4514741 \\ &:= 140404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404041 = 1544444 + 4444451 \\ &:= 141304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403141 = 1554344 + 4434551 \\ &:= 142204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402241 = 1564244 + 4424651 \\ &:= 143104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401341 = 1574144 + 4414751 \\ &:= 144004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400441 = 1584044 + 4404851 \\ &:= 200443 \times 11 + 11 \times 344002 = 2204873 + 3784022 \\ &:= 201343 \times 11 + 11 \times 343102 = 2214773 + 3774122 \\ &:= 202243 \times 11 + 11 \times 342202 = 2224673 + 3764222 \\ &:= 203143 \times 11 + 11 \times 341302 = 2234573 + 3754322 \\ &:= 204043 \times 11 + 11 \times 340402 = 2244473 + 3744422 \\ &:= 210433 \times 11 + 11 \times 334012 = 2314763 + 3674132 \\ &:= 211333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333112 = 2324663 + 3664232 \\ &:= 212233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332212 = 2334563 + 3654332 \\ &:= 213133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331312 = 2344463 + 3644432 \\ &:= 214033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330412 = 2354363 + 3634532 \\ &:= 220423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324022 = 2424653 + 3564242 \\ &:= 221323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323122 = 2434553 + 3554342 \\ &:= 222223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322222 = 2444453 + 3544442 \\ &:= 223123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321322 = 2454353 + 3534542 \\ &:= 224023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320422 = 2464253 + 3524642 \\ &:= 230413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314032 = 2534543 + 3454352 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 231313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313132 = 2544443 + 3444452$$

$$:= 232213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312232 = 2554343 + 3434552$$

$$:= 233113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311332 = 2564243 + 3424652$$

$$:= 234013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310432 = 2574143 + 3414752$$

$$:= 240403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304042 = 2644433 + 3344462$$

$$:= 241303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303142 = 2654333 + 3334562$$

$$:= 242203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302242 = 2664233 + 3324662$$

$$:= 243103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301342 = 2674133 + 3314762$$

$$:= 244003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300442 = 2684033 + 3304862$$

$$5992995 := 101022 \times 31 + 13 \times 220101 = 3131682 + 2861313$$

$$:= 130112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211031 = 1561344 + 4431651$$

$$:= 11002 \times 321 + 123 \times 20011 = 3531642 + 2461353$$

$$5994995 := 10013 \times 221 + 122 \times 31001 = 2212873 + 3782122$$

$$:= 100211 \times 14 + 41 \times 112001 = 1402954 + 4592041$$

$$:= 101021 \times 32 + 23 \times 120101 = 3232672 + 2762323$$

$$:= 12002 \times 311 + 113 \times 20021 = 3732622 + 2262373$$

$$5998995 := 10011 \times 441 + 144 \times 11001 = 4414851 + 1584144$$

$$:= 102123 \times 21 + 12 \times 321201 = 2144583 + 3854412$$

$$:= 111222 \times 12 + 21 \times 222111 = 1334664 + 4664331$$

$$:= 114003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300411 = 2394063 + 3604932$$

$$:= 132012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210231 = 1584144 + 4414851$$

$$:= 10044 \times 111 + 111 \times 44001 = 1114884 + 4884111$$

$$:= 11034 \times 111 + 111 \times 43011 = 1224774 + 4774221$$

$$:= 12024 \times 111 + 111 \times 42021 = 1334664 + 4664331$$

$$:= 13014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41031 = 1444554 + 4554441$$

$$:= 14004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40041 = 1554444 + 4444551$$

$$:= 20043 \times 111 + 111 \times 34002 = 2224773 + 3774222$$

$$:= 21033 \times 111 + 111 \times 33012 = 2334663 + 3664332$$

$$:= 22023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32022 = 2444553 + 3554442$$

$$:= 23013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31032 = 2554443 + 3444552$$

$$:= 24003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30042 = 2664333 + 3334662$$

$$:= 1332 \times 1002 + 2001 \times 2331 = 1334664 + 4664331$$

$$6060606 := 10001 \times 105 + 501 \times 10001 = 1050105 + 5010501$$

$$:= 10001 \times 204 + 402 \times 10001 = 2040204 + 4020402$$

$$:= 10001 \times 303 + 303 \times 10001 = 3030303 + 3030303$$

$$:= 10002 \times 202 + 202 \times 20001 = 2020404 + 4040202$$

$$:= 10005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50001 = 1010505 + 5050101$$

$$:= 20002 \times 102 + 201 \times 20002 = 2040204 + 4020402$$

$$:= 20004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40002 = 2020404 + 4040202$$

$$:= 30003 \times 101 + 101 \times 30003 = 3030303 + 3030303$$

$$:= 30023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32003 = 3032323 + 3232303$$

$$:= 31013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31013 = 3132313 + 3132313$$

$$\mathbf{6080806} := 10105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50101 = 1020605 + 5060201$$

$$:= 20104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40102 = 2030504 + 4050302$$

$$:= 30103 \times 101 + 101 \times 30103 = 3040403 + 3040403$$

$$\mathbf{6268626} := 10011 \times 402 + 204 \times 11001 = 4024422 + 2244204$$

$$:= 20022 \times 201 + 102 \times 22002 = 4024422 + 2244204$$

$$\mathbf{6090906} := 10002 \times 401 + 104 \times 20001 = 4010802 + 2080104$$

$$:= 10004 \times 201 + 102 \times 40001 = 2010804 + 4080102$$

$$:= 20102 \times 102 + 201 \times 20102 = 2050404 + 4040502$$

$$\mathbf{6284826} := 10125 \times 101 + 101 \times 52101 = 1022625 + 5262201$$

$$:= 11115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51111 = 1122615 + 5162211$$

$$:= 12105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50121 = 1222605 + 5062221$$

$$:= 20124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42102 = 2032524 + 4252302$$

$$:= 21114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41112 = 2132514 + 4152312$$

$$:= 22104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40122 = 2232504 + 4052322$$

$$:= 30123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32103 = 3042423 + 3242403$$

$$:= 31113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31113 = 3142413 + 3142413$$

$$\mathbf{6162616} := 10015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51001 = 1011515 + 5151101$$

$$:= 11005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50011 = 1111505 + 5051111$$

$$:= 20014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41002 = 2021414 + 4141202$$

$$:= 21004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40012 = 2121404 + 4041212$$

$$:= 30013 \times 101 + 101 \times 31003 = 3031313 + 3131303$$

$$\mathbf{6292926} := 11004 \times 201 + 102 \times 40011 = 2211804 + 4081122$$

$$:= 20112 \times 102 + 201 \times 21102 = 2051424 + 4241502$$

$$\mathbf{6164616} := 20012 \times 201 + 102 \times 21002 = 4022412 + 2142204$$

$$\mathbf{6298926} := 10024 \times 201 + 102 \times 42001 = 2014824 + 4284102$$

$$:= 20122 \times 201 + 102 \times 22102 = 4044522 + 2254404$$

$$\mathbf{6182816} := 10115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51101 = 1021615 + 5161201$$

$$:= 11105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50111 = 1121605 + 5061211$$

$$:= 20114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41102 = 2031514 + 4151302$$

$$:= 21104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40112 = 2131504 + 4051312$$

$$:= 30113 \times 101 + 101 \times 31103 = 3041413 + 3141403$$

$$\mathbf{6360636} := 10002 \times 212 + 212 \times 20001 = 2120424 + 4240212$$

$$\mathbf{6366636} := 10011 \times 303 + 303 \times 11001 = 3033333 + 3333303$$

$$:= 10035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53001 = 1013535 + 5353101$$

$$:= 11025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52011 = 1113525 + 5253111$$

$$:= 12015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51021 = 1213515 + 5153121$$

$$:= 13005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50031 = 1313505 + 5053131$$

$$:= 20034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43002 = 2023434 + 4343202$$

$$:= 21012 \times 102 + 201 \times 21012 = 2143224 + 4223412$$

$$:= 21024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42012 = 2123424 + 4243212$$

$$:= 22014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41022 = 2223414 + 4143222$$

$$:= 23004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40032 = 2323404 + 4043232$$

$$:= 30033 \times 101 + 101 \times 33003 = 3033333 + 3333303$$

$$:= 31023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32013 = 3133323 + 3233313$$

$$\mathbf{6194916} := 10014 \times 201 + 102 \times 41001 = 2012814 + 4182102$$

$$:= 20112 \times 201 + 102 \times 21102 = 4042512 + 2152404$$

$$\mathbf{6198916} := 10012 \times 401 + 104 \times 21001 = 4014812 + 2184104$$

$$\mathbf{6260626} := 10001 \times 115 + 511 \times 10001 = 1150115 + 5110511$$

$$:= 10001 \times 214 + 412 \times 10001 = 2140214 + 4120412$$

$$:= 10001 \times 313 + 313 \times 10001 = 3130313 + 3130313$$

$$\mathbf{6262626} := 20012 \times 102 + 201 \times 21002 = 2041224 + 4221402$$

$$\mathbf{6264626} := 10012 \times 202 + 202 \times 21001 = 2022424 + 4242202$$

$$:= 10025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52001 = 1012525 + 5252101$$

$$:= 11002 \times 202 + 202 \times 20011 = 2222404 + 4042222$$

$$:= 11015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51011 = 1112515 + 5152111$$

$$:= 12005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50021 = 1212505 + 5052121$$

$$:= 20024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42002 = 2022424 + 4242202$$

$$:= 21014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41012 = 2122414 + 4142212$$

$$:= 22004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40022 = 2222404 + 4042222$$

$$\mathbf{6386836} := 10135 \times 101 + 101 \times 53101 = 1023635 + 5363201$$

$$:= 11125 \times 101 + 101 \times 52111 = 1123625 + 5263211$$

$$:= 12115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51121 = 1223615 + 5163221$$

$$:= 13105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50131 = 1323605 + 5063231$$

$$:= 20134 \times 101 + 101 \times 43102 = 2033534 + 4353302$$

$$:= 21124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42112 = 2133524 + 4253312$$

$$:= 22114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41122 = 2233514 + 4153322$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 23104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40132 = 2333504 + 4053332 \\ &:= 30133 \times 101 + 101 \times 33103 = 3043433 + 3343403 \\ &:= 31123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32113 = 3143423 + 3243413 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6390936} := 10002 \times 411 + 114 \times 20001 = 4110822 + 2280114$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6396936} &:= 11014 \times 201 + 102 \times 41011 = 2213814 + 4183122 \\ &:= 21112 \times 102 + 201 \times 21112 = 2153424 + 4243512 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6460646} &:= 10001 \times 125 + 521 \times 10001 = 1250125 + 5210521 \\ &:= 10001 \times 224 + 422 \times 10001 = 2240224 + 4220422 \\ &:= 10001 \times 323 + 323 \times 10001 = 3230323 + 3230323 \\ &:= 20002 \times 112 + 211 \times 20002 = 2240224 + 4220422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6464646} &:= 10011 \times 204 + 402 \times 11001 = 2042244 + 4422402 \\ &:= 20022 \times 102 + 201 \times 22002 = 2042244 + 4422402 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6468646} &:= 10022 \times 202 + 202 \times 22001 = 2024444 + 4444202 \\ &:= 10045 \times 101 + 101 \times 54001 = 1014545 + 5454101 \\ &:= 11012 \times 202 + 202 \times 21011 = 2224424 + 4244222 \\ &:= 11035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53011 = 1114535 + 5354111 \\ &:= 12002 \times 202 + 202 \times 20021 = 2424404 + 4044242 \\ &:= 12025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52021 = 1214525 + 5254121 \\ &:= 13015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51031 = 1314515 + 5154131 \\ &:= 14005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50041 = 1414505 + 5054141 \\ &:= 20044 \times 101 + 101 \times 44002 = 2024444 + 4444202 \\ &:= 21034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43012 = 2124434 + 4344212 \\ &:= 22024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42022 = 2224424 + 4244222 \\ &:= 23014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41032 = 2324414 + 4144232 \\ &:= 24004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40042 = 2424404 + 4044242 \\ &:= 30043 \times 101 + 101 \times 34003 = 3034343 + 3434303 \\ &:= 31033 \times 101 + 101 \times 33013 = 3134333 + 3334313 \\ &:= 32023 \times 101 + 101 \times 32023 = 3234323 + 3234323 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6478746} := 10011 \times 412 + 214 \times 11001 = 4124532 + 2354214$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6488846} &:= 10145 \times 101 + 101 \times 54101 = 1024645 + 5464201 \\ &:= 11135 \times 101 + 101 \times 53111 = 1124635 + 5364211 \\ &:= 12125 \times 101 + 101 \times 52121 = 1224625 + 5264221 \\ &:= 13115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51131 = 1324615 + 5164231 \\ &:= 14105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50141 = 1424605 + 5064241 \\ &:= 20144 \times 101 + 101 \times 44102 = 2034544 + 4454302 \\ &:= 21134 \times 101 + 101 \times 43112 = 2134534 + 4354312 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 22124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42122 = 2234524 + 4254322 \\ &:= 23114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41132 = 2334514 + 4154332 \\ &:= 24104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40142 = 2434504 + 4054342 \\ &:= 30143 \times 101 + 101 \times 34103 = 3044443 + 3444403 \\ &:= 31133 \times 101 + 101 \times 33113 = 3144433 + 3344413 \\ &:= 32123 \times 101 + 101 \times 32123 = 3244423 + 3244423 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6492946} &:= 11002 \times 401 + 104 \times 20011 = 4411802 + 2081144 \\ &:= 20102 \times 112 + 211 \times 20102 = 2251424 + 4241522 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6494946} &:= 12004 \times 201 + 102 \times 40021 = 2412804 + 4082142 \\ &:= 20122 \times 102 + 201 \times 22102 = 2052444 + 4442502 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6562656} := 10011 \times 105 + 501 \times 11001 = 1051155 + 5511501$$

$$\mathbf{6568656} := 21022 \times 102 + 201 \times 22012 = 2144244 + 4424412$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6574756} &:= 10012 \times 212 + 212 \times 21001 = 2122544 + 4452212 \\ &:= 11002 \times 212 + 212 \times 20011 = 2332424 + 4242332 \\ &:= 20012 \times 211 + 112 \times 21002 = 4222532 + 2352224 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6576756} := 10011 \times 313 + 313 \times 11001 = 3133443 + 3443313$$

$$\mathbf{6590956} := 10004 \times 211 + 112 \times 40001 = 2110844 + 4480112$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6598956} &:= 12014 \times 201 + 102 \times 41021 = 2414814 + 4184142 \\ &:= 21122 \times 102 + 201 \times 22112 = 2154444 + 4444512 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6600066} &:= 100001 \times 15 + 51 \times 100001 = 1500015 + 5100051 \\ &:= 100001 \times 24 + 42 \times 100001 = 2400024 + 4200042 \\ &:= 100001 \times 33 + 33 \times 100001 = 3300033 + 3300033 \\ &:= 100002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200001 = 2200044 + 4400022 \\ &:= 100005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500001 = 1100055 + 5500011 \\ &:= 200002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200002 = 2400024 + 4200042 \\ &:= 200004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400002 = 2200044 + 4400022 \\ &:= 300003 \times 11 + 11 \times 300003 = 3300033 + 3300033 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6612166} &:= 100105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501001 = 1101155 + 5511011 \\ &:= 101005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500101 = 1111055 + 5501111 \\ &:= 200104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401002 = 2201144 + 4411022 \\ &:= 201004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400102 = 2211044 + 4401122 \\ &:= 300103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301003 = 3301133 + 3311033 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6614166} := 200102 \times 21 + 12 \times 201002 = 4202142 + 2412024$$

$$\mathbf{6622266} := 200102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201002 = 2401224 + 4221042$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6624266 &:= 100102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201001 = 2202244 + 4422022 \\
&:= 100205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502001 = 1102255 + 5522011 \\
&:= 101002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200101 = 2222044 + 4402222 \\
&:= 101105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501101 = 1112155 + 5512111 \\
&:= 102005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500201 = 1122055 + 5502211 \\
&:= 200204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402002 = 2202244 + 4422022 \\
&:= 201104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401102 = 2212144 + 4412122 \\
&:= 202004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400202 = 2222044 + 4402222 \\
&:= 300203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302003 = 3302233 + 3322033 \\
&:= 301103 \times 11 + 11 \times 301103 = 3312133 + 3312133 \\
6628266 &:= 100101 \times 42 + 24 \times 101001 = 4204242 + 2424024 \\
6628266 &:= 200202 \times 21 + 12 \times 202002 = 4204242 + 2424024 \\
6636366 &:= 100101 \times 33 + 33 \times 101001 = 3303333 + 3333033 \\
&:= 100305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503001 = 1103355 + 5533011 \\
&:= 101205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502101 = 1113255 + 5523111 \\
&:= 102105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501201 = 1123155 + 5513211 \\
&:= 103005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500301 = 1133055 + 5503311 \\
&:= 200304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403002 = 2203344 + 4433022 \\
&:= 201102 \times 12 + 21 \times 201102 = 2413224 + 4223142 \\
&:= 201204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402102 = 2213244 + 4423122 \\
&:= 202104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401202 = 2223144 + 4413222 \\
&:= 203004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400302 = 2233044 + 4403322 \\
&:= 300303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303003 = 3303333 + 3333033 \\
&:= 301203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302103 = 3313233 + 3323133 \\
6644466 &:= 100101 \times 24 + 42 \times 101001 = 2402424 + 4242042 \\
&:= 200202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202002 = 2402424 + 4242042 \\
6648466 &:= 100202 \times 22 + 22 \times 202001 = 2204444 + 4444022 \\
&:= 100405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504001 = 1104455 + 5544011 \\
&:= 101102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201101 = 2224244 + 4424222 \\
&:= 101305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503101 = 1114355 + 5534111 \\
&:= 102002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200201 = 2244044 + 4404422 \\
&:= 102205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502201 = 1124255 + 5524211 \\
&:= 103105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501301 = 1134155 + 5514311 \\
&:= 104005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500401 = 1144055 + 5504411 \\
&:= 200404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404002 = 2204444 + 4444022 \\
&:= 201304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403102 = 2214344 + 4434122 \\
&:= 202204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402202 = 2224244 + 4424222 \\
&:= 203104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401302 = 2234144 + 4414322 \\
&:= 204004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400402 = 2244044 + 4404422 \\
&:= 300403 \times 11 + 11 \times 304003 = 3304433 + 3344033 \\
&:= 301303 \times 11 + 11 \times 303103 = 3314333 + 3334133 \\
&:= 302203 \times 11 + 11 \times 302203 = 3324233 + 3324233 \\
6652566 &:= 100101 \times 15 + 51 \times 101001 = 1501515 + 5151051 \\
6658566 &:= 201202 \times 12 + 21 \times 202102 = 2414424 + 4244142 \\
6660666 &:= 10001 \times 135 + 531 \times 10001 = 1350135 + 5310531 \\
&:= 10001 \times 234 + 432 \times 10001 = 2340234 + 4320432 \\
&:= 10001 \times 333 + 333 \times 10001 = 3330333 + 3330333 \\
&:= 10002 \times 222 + 222 \times 20001 = 2220444 + 4440222 \\
&:= 10005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50001 = 1110555 + 5550111 \\
&:= 20004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40002 = 2220444 + 4440222 \\
&:= 30003 \times 111 + 111 \times 30003 = 3330333 + 3330333 \\
6666666 &:= 200302 \times 12 + 21 \times 203002 = 2403624 + 4263042 \\
&:= 20032 \times 102 + 201 \times 23002 = 2043264 + 4623402 \\
6672766 &:= 20012 \times 112 + 211 \times 21002 = 2241344 + 4431422 \\
6674766 &:= 10011 \times 214 + 412 \times 11001 = 2142354 + 4532412 \\
6682866 &:= 10105 \times 111 + 111 \times 50101 = 1121655 + 5561211 \\
&:= 20104 \times 111 + 111 \times 40102 = 2231544 + 4451322 \\
&:= 30103 \times 111 + 111 \times 30103 = 3341433 + 3341433 \\
6688866 &:= 100201 \times 24 + 42 \times 102001 = 2404824 + 4284042 \\
&:= 200402 \times 12 + 21 \times 204002 = 2404824 + 4284042 \\
&:= 10011 \times 422 + 224 \times 11001 = 4224642 + 2464224 \\
&:= 20022 \times 211 + 112 \times 22002 = 4224642 + 2464224 \\
6690966 &:= 10002 \times 421 + 124 \times 20001 = 4210842 + 2480124 \\
6696966 &:= 13004 \times 201 + 102 \times 40031 = 2613804 + 4083162 \\
&:= 20132 \times 102 + 201 \times 23102 = 2053464 + 4643502 \\
6710176 &:= 100015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510001 = 1100165 + 5610011 \\
&:= 110005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500011 = 1210055 + 5500121 \\
&:= 200014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410002 = 2200154 + 4510022 \\
&:= 210004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400012 = 2310044 + 4400132 \\
&:= 300013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310003 = 3300143 + 3410033 \\
6720276 &:= 200012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210002 = 4200252 + 2520024
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6722276 &:= 100115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511001 = 1101265 + 5621011 \\
&:= 101015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510101 = 1111165 + 5611111 \\
&:= 110105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501011 = 1211155 + 5511121 \\
&:= 111005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500111 = 1221055 + 5501221 \\
&:= 200114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411002 = 2201254 + 4521022 \\
&:= 201014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410102 = 2211154 + 4511122 \\
&:= 210104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401012 = 2311144 + 4411132 \\
&:= 211004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400112 = 2321044 + 4401232 \\
&:= 300113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311003 = 3301243 + 3421033 \\
&:= 301013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310103 = 3311143 + 3411133 \\
6734376 &:= 100215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512001 = 1102365 + 5632011 \\
&:= 101115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511101 = 1112265 + 5622111 \\
&:= 102015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510201 = 1122165 + 5612211 \\
&:= 110205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502011 = 1212255 + 5522121 \\
&:= 111105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501111 = 1222155 + 5512221 \\
&:= 112005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500211 = 1232055 + 5502321 \\
&:= 200112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211002 = 4202352 + 2532024 \\
&:= 200214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412002 = 2202354 + 4532022 \\
&:= 201114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411102 = 2212254 + 4522122 \\
&:= 202014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410202 = 2222154 + 4512222 \\
&:= 210204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402012 = 2312244 + 4422132 \\
&:= 211104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401112 = 2322144 + 4412232 \\
&:= 212004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400212 = 2332044 + 4402332 \\
&:= 300213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312003 = 3302343 + 3432033 \\
&:= 301113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311103 = 3312243 + 3422133 \\
&:= 302013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310203 = 3322143 + 3412233 \\
6742476 &:= 201012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210102 = 4221252 + 2521224 \\
6746476 &:= 100315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513001 = 1103465 + 5643011 \\
&:= 101215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512101 = 1113365 + 5633111 \\
&:= 102115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511201 = 1123265 + 5623211 \\
&:= 103015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510301 = 1133165 + 5613311 \\
&:= 110305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503011 = 1213355 + 5533121 \\
&:= 111205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502111 = 1223255 + 5523221 \\
&:= 112105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501211 = 1233155 + 5513321 \\
&:= 113005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500311 = 1243055 + 5503421 \\
&:= 200314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413002 = 2203454 + 4543022 \\
&:= 201214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412102 = 2213354 + 4533122 \\
&:= 202114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411202 = 2223254 + 4523222 \\
&:= 203014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410302 = 2233154 + 4513322 \\
&:= 210304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403012 = 2313344 + 4433132 \\
&:= 211204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402112 = 2323244 + 4423232 \\
&:= 212104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401212 = 2333144 + 4413332 \\
&:= 213004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400312 = 2343044 + 4403432 \\
&:= 300313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313003 = 3303443 + 3443033 \\
&:= 301213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312103 = 3313343 + 3433133 \\
&:= 302113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311203 = 3323243 + 3423233 \\
&:= 303013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310303 = 3333143 + 3413333 \\
6748476 &:= 200212 \times 21 + 12 \times 212002 = 4204452 + 2544024 \\
6750576 &:= 100011 \times 51 + 15 \times 110001 = 5100561 + 1650015 \\
6756576 &:= 201112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211102 = 4223352 + 2533224 \\
6758576 &:= 100415 \times 11 + 11 \times 514001 = 1104565 + 5654011 \\
&:= 101315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513101 = 1114465 + 5644111 \\
&:= 102215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512201 = 1124365 + 5634211 \\
&:= 103115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511301 = 1134265 + 5624311 \\
&:= 104015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510401 = 1144165 + 5614411 \\
&:= 110405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504011 = 1214455 + 5544121 \\
&:= 111305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503111 = 1224355 + 5534221 \\
&:= 112205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502211 = 1234255 + 5524321 \\
&:= 113105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501311 = 1244155 + 5514421 \\
&:= 114005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500411 = 1254055 + 5504521 \\
&:= 200414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414002 = 2204554 + 4554022 \\
&:= 201314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413102 = 2214454 + 4544122 \\
&:= 202214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412202 = 2224354 + 4534222 \\
&:= 203114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411302 = 2234254 + 4524322 \\
&:= 204014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410402 = 2244154 + 4514422 \\
&:= 210404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404012 = 2314444 + 4444132 \\
&:= 211304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403112 = 2324344 + 4434232 \\
&:= 212204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402212 = 2334244 + 4424332 \\
&:= 213104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401312 = 2344144 + 4414432 \\
&:= 214004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400412 = 2354044 + 4404532 \\
&:= 300413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314003 = 3304543 + 3454033 \\
&:= 301313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313103 = 3314443 + 3444133 \\
&:= 302213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312203 = 3324343 + 3434233 \\
&:= 303113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311303 = 3334243 + 3424333 \\
&:= 304013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310403 = 3344143 + 3414433 \\
6764676 &:= 202012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210202 = 4242252 + 2522424 \\
6772776 &:= 10011 \times 115 + 511 \times 11001 = 1151265 + 5621511 \\
&:= 10015 \times 111 + 111 \times 51001 = 1111665 + 5661111
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 11005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50011 = 1221555 + 5551221 \\ &:= 20014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41002 = 2221554 + 4551222 \\ &:= 21004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40012 = 2331444 + 4441332 \\ &:= 30013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31003 = 3331443 + 3441333 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6778776} := 202112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211202 = 4244352 + 2534424$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6786876} &:= 203012 \times 21 + 12 \times 210302 = 4263252 + 2523624 \\ &:= 10011 \times 323 + 323 \times 11001 = 3233553 + 3553323 \\ &:= 21012 \times 112 + 211 \times 21012 = 2353344 + 4433532 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6788876} &:= 10022 \times 212 + 212 \times 22001 = 2124664 + 4664212 \\ &:= 11012 \times 212 + 212 \times 21011 = 2334544 + 4454332 \\ &:= 12002 \times 212 + 212 \times 20021 = 2544424 + 4244452 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6794976} &:= 10115 \times 111 + 111 \times 51101 = 1122765 + 5672211 \\ &:= 11105 \times 111 + 111 \times 50111 = 1232655 + 5562321 \\ &:= 20114 \times 111 + 111 \times 41102 = 2232654 + 4562322 \\ &:= 21104 \times 111 + 111 \times 40112 = 2342544 + 4452432 \\ &:= 30113 \times 111 + 111 \times 31103 = 3342543 + 3452433 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6810186} := 200012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210002 = 2400144 + 4410042$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6820286} &:= 100012 \times 22 + 22 \times 210001 = 2200264 + 4620022 \\ &:= 100025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520001 = 1100275 + 5720011 \\ &:= 110002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200011 = 2420044 + 4400242 \\ &:= 110015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510011 = 1210165 + 5610121 \\ &:= 120005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500021 = 1320055 + 5500231 \\ &:= 200024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420002 = 2200264 + 4620022 \\ &:= 210014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410012 = 2310154 + 4510132 \\ &:= 220004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400022 = 2420044 + 4400242 \\ &:= 300023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320003 = 3300253 + 3520033 \\ &:= 310013 \times 11 + 11 \times 310013 = 3410143 + 3410143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6824286} := 201012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210102 = 2412144 + 4412142$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6832386} &:= 100125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521001 = 1101375 + 5731011 \\ &:= 101025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520101 = 1111275 + 5721111 \\ &:= 110115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511011 = 1211265 + 5621121 \\ &:= 111015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510111 = 1221165 + 5611221 \\ &:= 120105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501021 = 1321155 + 5511231 \\ &:= 121005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500121 = 1331055 + 5501331 \\ &:= 200112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211002 = 2401344 + 4431042 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 200124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421002 = 2201364 + 4631022 \\ &:= 201024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420102 = 2211264 + 4621122 \\ &:= 210114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411012 = 2311254 + 4521132 \\ &:= 211014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410112 = 2321154 + 4511232 \\ &:= 220104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401022 = 2421144 + 4411242 \\ &:= 221004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400122 = 2431044 + 4401342 \\ &:= 300123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321003 = 3301353 + 3531033 \\ &:= 301023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320103 = 3311253 + 3521133 \\ &:= 310113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311013 = 3411243 + 3421143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6838386} := 202012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210202 = 2424144 + 4414242$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6840486} &:= 100011 \times 42 + 24 \times 110001 = 4200462 + 2640024 \\ &:= 200022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220002 = 4200462 + 2640024 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6844486} &:= 100112 \times 22 + 22 \times 211001 = 2202464 + 4642022 \\ &:= 100225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522001 = 1102475 + 5742011 \\ &:= 101012 \times 22 + 22 \times 210101 = 2222264 + 4622222 \\ &:= 101125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521101 = 1112375 + 5732111 \\ &:= 102025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520201 = 1122275 + 5722211 \\ &:= 110102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201011 = 2422244 + 4422242 \\ &:= 110215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512011 = 1212365 + 5632121 \\ &:= 111002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200111 = 2442044 + 4402442 \\ &:= 111115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511111 = 1222265 + 5622221 \\ &:= 112015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510211 = 1232165 + 5612321 \\ &:= 120205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502021 = 1322255 + 5522231 \\ &:= 121105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501121 = 1332155 + 5512331 \\ &:= 122005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500221 = 1342055 + 5502431 \\ &:= 200224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422002 = 2202464 + 4642022 \\ &:= 201124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421102 = 2212364 + 4632122 \\ &:= 202024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420202 = 2222264 + 4622222 \\ &:= 210214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412012 = 2312354 + 4532132 \\ &:= 211114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411112 = 2322254 + 4522232 \\ &:= 212014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410212 = 2332154 + 4512332 \\ &:= 220204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402022 = 2422244 + 4422242 \\ &:= 221104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401122 = 2432144 + 4412342 \\ &:= 222004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400222 = 2442044 + 4402442 \\ &:= 300223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322003 = 3302453 + 3542033 \\ &:= 301123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321103 = 3312353 + 3532133 \\ &:= 302023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320203 = 3322253 + 3522233 \\ &:= 310213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312013 = 3412343 + 3432143 \\ &:= 311113 \times 11 + 11 \times 311113 = 3422243 + 3422243 \end{aligned}$$

$$6846486 := 201112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211102 = 2413344 + 4433142$$

$$6854586 := 200122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221002 = 4202562 + 2652024 \\ := 212002 \times 21 + 12 \times 200212 = 4452042 + 2402544$$

$$6856586 := 100325 \times 11 + 11 \times 523001 = 1103575 + 5753011 \\ := 101225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522101 = 1113475 + 5743111 \\ := 102125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521201 = 1123375 + 5733211 \\ := 103025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520301 = 1133275 + 5723311 \\ := 110315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513011 = 1213465 + 5643121 \\ := 111215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512111 = 1223365 + 5633221 \\ := 112115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511211 = 1233265 + 5623321 \\ := 113015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510311 = 1243165 + 5613421 \\ := 120305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503021 = 1323355 + 5533231 \\ := 121205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502121 = 1333255 + 5523331 \\ := 122105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501221 = 1343155 + 5513431 \\ := 123005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500321 = 1353055 + 5503531 \\ := 200324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423002 = 2203564 + 4653022 \\ := 201224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422102 = 2213464 + 4643122 \\ := 202124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421202 = 2223364 + 4633222 \\ := 203024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420302 = 2233264 + 4623322 \\ := 210314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413012 = 2313454 + 4543132 \\ := 211214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412112 = 2323354 + 4533232 \\ := 212114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411212 = 2333254 + 4523332 \\ := 213014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410312 = 2343154 + 4513432 \\ := 220304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403022 = 2423344 + 4433242 \\ := 221204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402122 = 2433244 + 4423342 \\ := 222104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401222 = 2443144 + 4413442 \\ := 223004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400322 = 2453044 + 4403542 \\ := 300323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323003 = 3303553 + 3553033 \\ := 301223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322103 = 3313453 + 3543133 \\ := 302123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321203 = 3323353 + 3533233 \\ := 303023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320303 = 3333253 + 3523333 \\ := 310313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313013 = 3413443 + 3443143 \\ := 311213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312113 = 3423343 + 3433243$$

$$6860686 := 10001 \times 145 + 541 \times 10001 = 1450145 + 5410541 \\ := 10001 \times 244 + 442 \times 10001 = 2440244 + 4420442 \\ := 10001 \times 343 + 343 \times 10001 = 3430343 + 3430343 \\ := 20002 \times 122 + 221 \times 20002 = 2440244 + 4420442$$

$$6862686 := 201022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220102 = 4221462 + 2641224$$

$$6868686 := 100111 \times 42 + 24 \times 111001 = 4204662 + 2664024 \\ := 100212 \times 22 + 22 \times 212001 = 2204664 + 4664022 \\ := 100425 \times 11 + 11 \times 524001 = 1104675 + 5764011 \\ := 101112 \times 22 + 22 \times 211101 = 2224464 + 4644222 \\ := 101325 \times 11 + 11 \times 523101 = 1114575 + 5754111 \\ := 102012 \times 22 + 22 \times 210201 = 2244264 + 4624422 \\ := 102225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522201 = 1124475 + 5744211 \\ := 103125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521301 = 1134375 + 5734311 \\ := 104025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520401 = 1144275 + 5724411 \\ := 110202 \times 22 + 22 \times 202011 = 2424444 + 4444242 \\ := 110415 \times 11 + 11 \times 514011 = 1214565 + 5654121 \\ := 111102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201111 = 2444244 + 4424442 \\ := 111315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513111 = 1224465 + 5644221 \\ := 112002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200211 = 2464044 + 4404642 \\ := 112215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512211 = 1234365 + 5634321 \\ := 113115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511311 = 1244265 + 5624421 \\ := 114015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510411 = 1254165 + 5614521 \\ := 120405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504021 = 1324455 + 5544231 \\ := 121305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503121 = 1334355 + 5534331 \\ := 122205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502221 = 1344255 + 5524431 \\ := 123105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501321 = 1354155 + 5514531 \\ := 124005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500421 = 1364055 + 5504631 \\ := 200222 \times 21 + 12 \times 222002 = 4204662 + 2664024 \\ := 200424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424002 = 2204664 + 4664022 \\ := 201111 \times 22 + 22 \times 111102 = 4424442 + 2444244 \\ := 201212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212102 = 2414544 + 4454142 \\ := 201324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423102 = 2214564 + 4654122 \\ := 202224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422202 = 2224464 + 4644222 \\ := 203124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421302 = 2234364 + 4634322 \\ := 204024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420402 = 2244264 + 4624422 \\ := 210414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414012 = 2314554 + 4554132 \\ := 211314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413112 = 2324454 + 4544232 \\ := 212214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412212 = 2334354 + 4534332 \\ := 213114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411312 = 2344254 + 4524432 \\ := 214014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410412 = 2354154 + 4514532 \\ := 220404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404022 = 2424444 + 4444242 \\ := 221304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403122 = 2434344 + 4434342 \\ := 222002 \times 12 + 21 \times 200222 = 2664024 + 4204662 \\ := 222204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402222 = 2444244 + 4424442 \\ := 223104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401322 = 2454144 + 4414542 \\ := 224004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400422 = 2464044 + 4404642 \\ := 300423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324003 = 3304653 + 3564033 \\ := 301323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323103 = 3314553 + 3554133$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 302223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322203 = 3324453 + 3544233 \\ &:= 303123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321303 = 3334353 + 3534333 \\ &:= 304023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320403 = 3344253 + 3524433 \\ &:= 310413 \times 11 + 11 \times 314013 = 3414543 + 3454143 \\ &:= 311313 \times 11 + 11 \times 313113 = 3424443 + 3444243 \\ &:= 312213 \times 11 + 11 \times 312213 = 3434343 + 3434343 \\ &:= 10021 \times 204 + 402 \times 12001 = 2044284 + 4824402 \\ &:= 20042 \times 102 + 201 \times 24002 = 2044284 + 4824402 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6876786} &:= 200312 \times 12 + 21 \times 213002 = 2403744 + 4473042 \\ &:= 201122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221102 = 4223562 + 2653224 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6884886} &:= 101011 \times 42 + 24 \times 110101 = 4242462 + 2642424 \\ &:= 202022 \times 21 + 12 \times 220202 = 4242462 + 2642424 \\ &:= 10011 \times 224 + 422 \times 11001 = 2242464 + 4642422 \\ &:= 10012 \times 222 + 222 \times 21001 = 2222664 + 4662222 \\ &:= 10025 \times 111 + 111 \times 52001 = 1112775 + 5772111 \\ &:= 11002 \times 222 + 222 \times 20011 = 2442444 + 4442442 \\ &:= 11015 \times 111 + 111 \times 51011 = 1222665 + 5662221 \\ &:= 12005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50021 = 1332555 + 5552331 \\ &:= 20022 \times 112 + 211 \times 22002 = 2242464 + 4642422 \\ &:= 20024 \times 111 + 111 \times 42002 = 2222664 + 4662222 \\ &:= 21014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41012 = 2332554 + 4552332 \\ &:= 22004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40022 = 2442444 + 4442442 \\ &:= 30023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32003 = 3332553 + 3552333 \\ &:= 31013 \times 111 + 111 \times 31013 = 3442443 + 3442443 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6894986} &:= 12002 \times 401 + 104 \times 20021 = 4812802 + 2082184 \\ &:= 20102 \times 122 + 221 \times 20102 = 2452444 + 4442542 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6898986} &:= 200412 \times 12 + 21 \times 214002 = 2404944 + 4494042 \\ &:= 202122 \times 21 + 12 \times 221202 = 4244562 + 2654424 \\ &:= 10011 \times 432 + 234 \times 11001 = 4324752 + 2574234 \\ &:= 14004 \times 201 + 102 \times 40041 = 2814804 + 4084182 \\ &:= 20142 \times 102 + 201 \times 24102 = 2054484 + 4844502 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6900096} &:= 100002 \times 41 + 14 \times 200001 = 4100082 + 2800014 \\ &:= 100004 \times 21 + 12 \times 400001 = 2100084 + 4800012 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6914196} := 100104 \times 21 + 12 \times 401001 = 2102184 + 4812012$$

$$\mathbf{6918196} := 100102 \times 41 + 14 \times 201001 = 4104182 + 2814014$$

$$\mathbf{6922296} := 101004 \times 21 + 12 \times 400101 = 2121084 + 4801212$$

$$\mathbf{6928296} := 100204 \times 21 + 12 \times 402001 = 2104284 + 4824012$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6930396} &:= 100011 \times 33 + 33 \times 110001 = 3300363 + 3630033 \\ &:= 100035 \times 11 + 11 \times 530001 = 1100385 + 5830011 \\ &:= 110025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520011 = 1210275 + 5720121 \\ &:= 120015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510021 = 1320165 + 5610231 \\ &:= 130005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500031 = 1430055 + 5500341 \\ &:= 200034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430002 = 2200374 + 4730022 \\ &:= 210012 \times 12 + 21 \times 210012 = 2520144 + 4410252 \\ &:= 210024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420012 = 2310264 + 4620132 \\ &:= 220014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410022 = 2420154 + 4510242 \\ &:= 230004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400032 = 2530044 + 4400352 \\ &:= 300033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330003 = 3300363 + 3630033 \\ &:= 310023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320013 = 3410253 + 3520143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6936396} := 101104 \times 21 + 12 \times 401101 = 2123184 + 4813212$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6942496} &:= 100135 \times 11 + 11 \times 531001 = 1101485 + 5841011 \\ &:= 101002 \times 41 + 14 \times 200101 = 4141082 + 2801414 \\ &:= 101035 \times 11 + 11 \times 530101 = 1111385 + 5831111 \\ &:= 110125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521011 = 1211375 + 5731121 \\ &:= 111025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520111 = 1221275 + 5721221 \\ &:= 120115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511021 = 1321265 + 5621231 \\ &:= 121015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510121 = 1331165 + 5611331 \\ &:= 130105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501031 = 1431155 + 5511341 \\ &:= 131005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500131 = 1441055 + 5501441 \\ &:= 200134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431002 = 2201474 + 4741022 \\ &:= 201034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430102 = 2211374 + 4731122 \\ &:= 210124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421012 = 2311364 + 4631132 \\ &:= 211024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420112 = 2321264 + 4621232 \\ &:= 220114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411022 = 2421254 + 4521242 \\ &:= 221014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410122 = 2431154 + 4511342 \\ &:= 230104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401032 = 2531144 + 4411352 \\ &:= 231004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400132 = 2541044 + 4401452 \\ &:= 300133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331003 = 3301463 + 3641033 \\ &:= 301033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330103 = 3311363 + 3631133 \\ &:= 310123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321013 = 3411353 + 3531143 \\ &:= 311023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320113 = 3421253 + 3521243 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6944496} &:= 102004 \times 21 + 12 \times 400201 = 2142084 + 4802412 \\ &:= 210112 \times 21 + 12 \times 211012 = 4412352 + 2532144 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6952596} := 210112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211012 = 2521344 + 4431252$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6954596 &:= 100235 \times 11 + 11 \times 532001 = 1102585 + 5852011 \\
&:= 101135 \times 11 + 11 \times 531101 = 1112485 + 5842111 \\
&:= 102035 \times 11 + 11 \times 530201 = 1122385 + 5832211 \\
&:= 110225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522011 = 1212475 + 5742121 \\
&:= 111125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521111 = 1222375 + 5732221 \\
&:= 112025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520211 = 1232275 + 5722321 \\
&:= 120215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512021 = 1322365 + 5632231 \\
&:= 121115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511121 = 1332265 + 5622331 \\
&:= 122015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510221 = 1342165 + 5612431 \\
&:= 130205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502031 = 1432255 + 5522341 \\
&:= 131105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501131 = 1442155 + 5512441 \\
&:= 132005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500231 = 1452055 + 5502541 \\
&:= 200234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432002 = 2202574 + 4752022 \\
&:= 201134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431102 = 2212474 + 4742122 \\
&:= 202034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430202 = 2222374 + 4732222 \\
&:= 210224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422012 = 2312464 + 4642132 \\
&:= 211124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421112 = 2322364 + 4632232 \\
&:= 212024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420212 = 2332264 + 4622332 \\
&:= 220214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412022 = 2422354 + 4532242 \\
&:= 221114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411122 = 2432254 + 4522342 \\
&:= 222014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410222 = 2442154 + 4512442 \\
&:= 230204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402032 = 2532244 + 4422352 \\
&:= 231104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401132 = 2542144 + 4412452 \\
&:= 232004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400232 = 2552044 + 4402552 \\
&:= 300233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332003 = 3302563 + 3652033 \\
&:= 301133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331103 = 3312463 + 3642133 \\
&:= 302033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330203 = 3322363 + 3632233 \\
&:= 310223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322013 = 3412453 + 3542143 \\
&:= 311123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321113 = 3422353 + 3532243 \\
&:= 312023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320213 = 3432253 + 3522343
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6958596 &:= 102104 \times 21 + 12 \times 401201 = 2144184 + 4814412 \\
&:= 210212 \times 21 + 12 \times 212012 = 4414452 + 2544144
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6960696 &:= 200032 \times 21 + 12 \times 230002 = 4200672 + 2760024 \\
&:= 10002 \times 232 + 232 \times 20001 = 2320464 + 4640232
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6966696 &:= 100111 \times 33 + 33 \times 111001 = 3303663 + 3663033 \\
&:= 100335 \times 11 + 11 \times 533001 = 1103685 + 5863011 \\
&:= 101011 \times 33 + 33 \times 110101 = 3333363 + 3633333 \\
&:= 101235 \times 11 + 11 \times 532101 = 1113585 + 5853111 \\
&:= 102135 \times 11 + 11 \times 531201 = 1123485 + 5843211 \\
&:= 103004 \times 21 + 12 \times 400301 = 2163084 + 4803612
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 103035 \times 11 + 11 \times 530301 = 1133385 + 5833311 \\
&:= 110325 \times 11 + 11 \times 523011 = 1213575 + 5753121 \\
&:= 111225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522111 = 1223475 + 5743221 \\
&:= 112125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521211 = 1233375 + 5733321 \\
&:= 113025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520311 = 1243275 + 5723421 \\
&:= 120315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513021 = 1323465 + 5643231 \\
&:= 121215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512121 = 1333365 + 5633331 \\
&:= 122115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511221 = 1343265 + 5623431 \\
&:= 123015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510321 = 1353165 + 5613531 \\
&:= 130305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503031 = 1433355 + 5533341 \\
&:= 131205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502131 = 1443255 + 5523441 \\
&:= 132105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501231 = 1453155 + 5513541 \\
&:= 133005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500331 = 1463055 + 5503641 \\
&:= 200334 \times 11 + 11 \times 433002 = 2203674 + 4763022 \\
&:= 201234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432102 = 2213574 + 4753122 \\
&:= 202134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431202 = 2223474 + 4743222 \\
&:= 203034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430302 = 2233374 + 4733322 \\
&:= 210324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423012 = 2313564 + 4653132 \\
&:= 211112 \times 12 + 21 \times 211112 = 2533344 + 4433352 \\
&:= 211224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422112 = 2323464 + 4643232 \\
&:= 212124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421212 = 2333364 + 4633332 \\
&:= 213024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420312 = 2343264 + 4623432 \\
&:= 220314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413022 = 2423454 + 4543242 \\
&:= 221214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412122 = 2433354 + 4533342 \\
&:= 222114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411222 = 2443254 + 4523442 \\
&:= 223014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410322 = 2453154 + 4513542 \\
&:= 230304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403032 = 2533344 + 4433352 \\
&:= 231204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402132 = 2543244 + 4423452 \\
&:= 232104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401232 = 2553144 + 4413552 \\
&:= 233004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400332 = 2563044 + 4403652 \\
&:= 300333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333003 = 3303663 + 3663033 \\
&:= 301233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332103 = 3313563 + 3653133 \\
&:= 302133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331203 = 3323463 + 3643233 \\
&:= 303033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330303 = 3333363 + 3633333 \\
&:= 310323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323013 = 3413553 + 3553143 \\
&:= 311223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322113 = 3423453 + 3543243 \\
&:= 312123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321213 = 3433353 + 3533343 \\
&:= 313023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320313 = 3443253 + 3523443
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6974796 &:= 200132 \times 21 + 12 \times 231002 = 4202772 + 2772024 \\
&:= 210212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212012 = 2522544 + 4452252
\end{aligned}$$

$$6978796 := 100435 \times 11 + 11 \times 534001 = 1104785 + 5874011$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 101335 \times 11 + 11 \times 533101 = 1114685 + 5864111 \\
&:= 102235 \times 11 + 11 \times 532201 = 1124585 + 5854211 \\
&:= 103135 \times 11 + 11 \times 531301 = 1134485 + 5844311 \\
&:= 104035 \times 11 + 11 \times 530401 = 1144385 + 5834411 \\
&:= 110425 \times 11 + 11 \times 524011 = 1214675 + 5764121 \\
&:= 111325 \times 11 + 11 \times 523111 = 1224575 + 5754221 \\
&:= 112225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522211 = 1234475 + 5744321 \\
&:= 113125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521311 = 1244375 + 5734421 \\
&:= 114025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520411 = 1254275 + 5724521 \\
&:= 120415 \times 11 + 11 \times 514021 = 1324565 + 5654231 \\
&:= 121315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513121 = 1334465 + 5644331 \\
&:= 122215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512221 = 1344365 + 5634431 \\
&:= 123115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511321 = 1354265 + 5624531 \\
&:= 124015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510421 = 1364165 + 5614631 \\
&:= 130405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504031 = 1434455 + 5544341 \\
&:= 131305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503131 = 1444355 + 5534441 \\
&:= 132205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502231 = 1454255 + 5524541 \\
&:= 133105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501331 = 1464155 + 5514641 \\
&:= 134005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500431 = 1474055 + 5504741 \\
&:= 200434 \times 11 + 11 \times 434002 = 2204774 + 4774022 \\
&:= 201334 \times 11 + 11 \times 433102 = 2214674 + 4764122 \\
&:= 202234 \times 11 + 11 \times 432202 = 2224574 + 4754222 \\
&:= 203134 \times 11 + 11 \times 431302 = 2234474 + 4744322 \\
&:= 204034 \times 11 + 11 \times 430402 = 2244374 + 4734422 \\
&:= 210424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424012 = 2314664 + 4664132 \\
&:= 211324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423112 = 2324564 + 4654232 \\
&:= 212224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422212 = 2334464 + 4644332 \\
&:= 213124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421312 = 2344364 + 4634432 \\
&:= 214024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420412 = 2354264 + 4624532 \\
&:= 220414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414022 = 2424554 + 4554242 \\
&:= 221314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413122 = 2434454 + 4544342 \\
&:= 222214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412222 = 2444354 + 4534442 \\
&:= 223114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411322 = 2454254 + 4524542 \\
&:= 224014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410422 = 2464154 + 4514642 \\
&:= 230404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404032 = 2534444 + 4444352 \\
&:= 231304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403132 = 2544344 + 4434452 \\
&:= 232204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402232 = 2554244 + 4424552 \\
&:= 233104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401332 = 2564144 + 4414652 \\
&:= 234004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400432 = 2574044 + 4404752 \\
&:= 300433 \times 11 + 11 \times 334003 = 3304763 + 3674033 \\
&:= 301333 \times 11 + 11 \times 333103 = 3314663 + 3664133 \\
&:= 302233 \times 11 + 11 \times 332203 = 3324563 + 3654233 \\
&:= 303133 \times 11 + 11 \times 331303 = 3334463 + 3644333
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 304033 \times 11 + 11 \times 330403 = 3344363 + 3634433 \\
&:= 310423 \times 11 + 11 \times 324013 = 3414653 + 3564143 \\
&:= 311323 \times 11 + 11 \times 323113 = 3424553 + 3554243 \\
&:= 312223 \times 11 + 11 \times 322213 = 3434453 + 3544343 \\
&:= 313123 \times 11 + 11 \times 321313 = 3444353 + 3534443 \\
&:= 314023 \times 11 + 11 \times 320413 = 3454253 + 3524543
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{6982896} &:= 10011 \times 125 + 521 \times 11001 = 1251375 + 5731521 \\
&:= 201032 \times 21 + 12 \times 230102 = 4221672 + 2761224
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{6984896} &:= 102002 \times 41 + 14 \times 200201 = 4182082 + 2802814 \\
&:= 200201 \times 14 + 41 \times 102002 = 2802814 + 4182082
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{6988896} &:= 104004 \times 21 + 12 \times 400401 = 2184084 + 4804812 \\
&:= 200232 \times 21 + 12 \times 232002 = 4204872 + 2784024 \\
&:= 211212 \times 12 + 21 \times 212112 = 2534544 + 4454352
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6990996} := 10002 \times 431 + 134 \times 20001 = 4310862 + 2680134$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{6996996} &:= 201132 \times 21 + 12 \times 231102 = 4223772 + 2773224 \\
&:= 210312 \times 12 + 21 \times 213012 = 2523744 + 4473252 \\
&:= 10011 \times 333 + 333 \times 11001 = 3333663 + 3663333 \\
&:= 10035 \times 111 + 111 \times 53001 = 1113885 + 5883111 \\
&:= 11025 \times 111 + 111 \times 52011 = 1223775 + 5773221 \\
&:= 12015 \times 111 + 111 \times 51021 = 1333665 + 5663331 \\
&:= 13005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50031 = 1443555 + 5553441 \\
&:= 20034 \times 111 + 111 \times 43002 = 2223774 + 4773222 \\
&:= 21024 \times 111 + 111 \times 42012 = 2333664 + 4663332 \\
&:= 22014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41022 = 2443554 + 4553442 \\
&:= 23004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40032 = 2553444 + 4443552 \\
&:= 30033 \times 111 + 111 \times 33003 = 3333663 + 3663333 \\
&:= 31023 \times 111 + 111 \times 32013 = 3443553 + 3553443
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6998996} := 21022 \times 112 + 211 \times 22012 = 2354464 + 4644532$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7050507} &:= 10002 \times 103 + 301 \times 20001 = 1030206 + 6020301 \\
&:= 10003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30001 = 1020306 + 6030201
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7070707} &:= 10001 \times 106 + 601 \times 10001 = 1060106 + 6010601 \\
&:= 10001 \times 205 + 502 \times 10001 = 2050205 + 5020502 \\
&:= 10001 \times 304 + 403 \times 10001 = 3040304 + 4030403 \\
&:= 10006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60001 = 1010606 + 6060101 \\
&:= 20005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50002 = 2020505 + 5050202
\end{aligned}$$

$$:= 30004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40003 = 3030404 + 4040303$$

$$:= 21015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51012 = 2122515 + 5152212$$

$$:= 22005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50022 = 2222505 + 5052222$$

$$\mathbf{7080807} := 10002 \times 302 + 203 \times 20001 = 3020604 + 4060203$$

$$:= 30024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42003 = 3032424 + 4242303$$

$$:= 10103 \times 102 + 201 \times 30101 = 1030506 + 6050301$$

$$:= 31014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41013 = 3132414 + 4142313$$

$$:= 20003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30002 = 4020603 + 3060204$$

$$:= 32004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40023 = 3232404 + 4042323$$

$$\mathbf{7090907} := 10102 \times 103 + 301 \times 20101 = 1040506 + 6050401$$

$$\mathbf{7282827} := 10113 \times 102 + 201 \times 31101 = 1031526 + 6251301$$

$$:= 10106 \times 101 + 101 \times 60101 = 1020706 + 6070201$$

$$:= 21003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30012 = 4221603 + 3061224$$

$$:= 20105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50102 = 2030605 + 5060302$$

$$\mathbf{7286827} := 10012 \times 302 + 203 \times 21001 = 3023624 + 4263203$$

$$:= 30104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40103 = 3040504 + 4050403$$

$$\mathbf{7154517} := 11003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30011 = 1122306 + 6032211$$

$$\mathbf{7288827} := 12103 \times 102 + 201 \times 30121 = 1234506 + 6054321$$

$$\mathbf{7156517} := 11002 \times 103 + 301 \times 20011 = 1133206 + 6023311$$

$$:= 20023 \times 201 + 102 \times 32002 = 4024623 + 3264204$$

$$\mathbf{7172717} := 10016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61001 = 1011616 + 6161101$$

$$\mathbf{7294927} := 10126 \times 101 + 101 \times 62101 = 1022726 + 6272201$$

$$:= 11006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60011 = 1111606 + 6061111$$

$$:= 11116 \times 101 + 101 \times 61111 = 1122716 + 6172211$$

$$:= 20015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51002 = 2021515 + 5151202$$

$$:= 12106 \times 101 + 101 \times 60121 = 1222706 + 6072221$$

$$:= 21005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50012 = 2121505 + 5051212$$

$$:= 20125 \times 101 + 101 \times 52102 = 2032625 + 5262302$$

$$:= 30014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41003 = 3031414 + 4141303$$

$$:= 21115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51112 = 2132615 + 5162312$$

$$:= 31004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40013 = 3131404 + 4041313$$

$$:= 22105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50122 = 2232605 + 5062322$$

$$\mathbf{7184817} := 11103 \times 102 + 201 \times 30111 = 1132506 + 6052311$$

$$:= 31114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41113 = 3142514 + 4152413$$

$$:= 20013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31002 = 4022613 + 3162204$$

$$:= 32104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40123 = 3242504 + 4052423$$

$$\mathbf{7192917} := 10116 \times 101 + 101 \times 61101 = 1021716 + 6171201$$

$$\mathbf{7350537} := 10002 \times 113 + 311 \times 20001 = 1130226 + 6220311$$

$$:= 11106 \times 101 + 101 \times 60111 = 1121706 + 6071211$$

$$\mathbf{7352537} := 10012 \times 103 + 301 \times 21001 = 1031236 + 6321301$$

$$:= 20115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51102 = 2031615 + 5161302$$

$$\mathbf{7356537} := 11013 \times 102 + 201 \times 31011 = 1123326 + 6233211$$

$$:= 21105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50112 = 2131605 + 5061312$$

$$\mathbf{7376737} := 10036 \times 101 + 101 \times 63001 = 1013636 + 6363101$$

$$:= 30114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41103 = 3041514 + 4151403$$

$$:= 11026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62011 = 1113626 + 6263111$$

$$:= 31104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40113 = 3141504 + 4051413$$

$$:= 12016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61021 = 1213616 + 6163121$$

$$\mathbf{7196917} := 11102 \times 103 + 301 \times 20111 = 1143506 + 6053411$$

$$:= 13006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60031 = 1313606 + 6063131$$

$$\mathbf{7252527} := 10013 \times 102 + 201 \times 31001 = 1021326 + 6231201$$

$$:= 20035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53002 = 2023535 + 5353202$$

$$\mathbf{7258527} := 12003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30021 = 1224306 + 6034221$$

$$:= 21025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52012 = 2123525 + 5253212$$

$$\mathbf{7270727} := 10001 \times 116 + 611 \times 10001 = 1160116 + 6110611$$

$$:= 22015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51022 = 2223515 + 5153222$$

$$:= 10001 \times 215 + 512 \times 10001 = 2150215 + 5120512$$

$$:= 23005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50032 = 2323505 + 5053232$$

$$:= 10001 \times 314 + 413 \times 10001 = 3140314 + 4130413$$

$$:= 30034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43003 = 3033434 + 4343303$$

$$\mathbf{7274727} := 10026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62001 = 1012626 + 6262101$$

$$:= 31024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42013 = 3133424 + 4243313$$

$$:= 11016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61011 = 1112616 + 6162111$$

$$:= 32014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41023 = 3233414 + 4143323$$

$$:= 12006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60021 = 1212606 + 6062121$$

$$\mathbf{7378737} := 10011 \times 403 + 304 \times 11001 = 4034433 + 3344304$$

$$:= 20025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52002 = 2022525 + 5252202$$

$$\mathbf{7380837} := 10002 \times 312 + 213 \times 20001 = 3120624 + 4260213$$

$$7384837 := 11002 \times 302 + 203 \times 20011 = 3322604 + 4062233$$

$$:= 31034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43013 = 3134434 + 4344313$$

$$7386837 := 11113 \times 102 + 201 \times 31111 = 1133526 + 6253311$$

$$:= 21013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31012 = 4223613 + 3163224$$

$$:= 32024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42023 = 3234424 + 4244323$$

$$:= 33014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41033 = 3334414 + 4144333$$

$$:= 34004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40043 = 3434404 + 4044343$$

$$7392937 := 10102 \times 113 + 311 \times 20101 = 1141526 + 6251411$$

$$:= 10112 \times 103 + 301 \times 21101 = 1041536 + 6351401$$

$$7482847 := 10103 \times 112 + 211 \times 30101 = 1131536 + 6351311$$

$$7396937 := 10136 \times 101 + 101 \times 63101 = 1023736 + 6373201$$

$$:= 11126 \times 101 + 101 \times 62111 = 1123726 + 6273211$$

$$:= 12116 \times 101 + 101 \times 61121 = 1223716 + 6173221$$

$$:= 13106 \times 101 + 101 \times 60131 = 1323706 + 6073231$$

$$:= 20135 \times 101 + 101 \times 53102 = 2033635 + 5363302$$

$$:= 21125 \times 101 + 101 \times 52112 = 2133625 + 5263312$$

$$:= 22115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51122 = 2233615 + 5163322$$

$$:= 23105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50132 = 2333605 + 5063332$$

$$:= 30134 \times 101 + 101 \times 43103 = 3043534 + 4353403$$

$$:= 31124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42113 = 3143524 + 4253413$$

$$:= 32114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41123 = 3243514 + 4153423$$

$$:= 33104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40133 = 3343504 + 4053433$$

$$7484847 := 10123 \times 102 + 201 \times 32101 = 1032546 + 6452301$$

$$:= 22003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30022 = 4422603 + 3062244$$

$$7498947 := 10146 \times 101 + 101 \times 64101 = 1024746 + 6474201$$

$$:= 11112 \times 103 + 301 \times 21111 = 1144536 + 6354411$$

$$:= 11136 \times 101 + 101 \times 63111 = 1124736 + 6374211$$

$$:= 12126 \times 101 + 101 \times 62121 = 1224726 + 6274221$$

$$:= 13116 \times 101 + 101 \times 61131 = 1324716 + 6174231$$

$$:= 14106 \times 101 + 101 \times 60141 = 1424706 + 6074241$$

$$:= 20145 \times 101 + 101 \times 54102 = 2034645 + 5464302$$

$$:= 21135 \times 101 + 101 \times 53112 = 2134635 + 5364312$$

$$:= 22125 \times 101 + 101 \times 52122 = 2234625 + 5264322$$

$$:= 23115 \times 101 + 101 \times 51132 = 2334615 + 5164332$$

$$:= 24105 \times 101 + 101 \times 50142 = 2434605 + 5064342$$

$$:= 30144 \times 101 + 101 \times 44103 = 3044544 + 4454403$$

$$:= 31134 \times 101 + 101 \times 43113 = 3144534 + 4354413$$

$$:= 32124 \times 101 + 101 \times 42123 = 3244524 + 4254423$$

$$:= 33114 \times 101 + 101 \times 41133 = 3344514 + 4154433$$

$$:= 34104 \times 101 + 101 \times 40143 = 3444504 + 4054443$$

$$7450547 := 10003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30001 = 1120336 + 6330211$$

$$7454547 := 10023 \times 102 + 201 \times 32001 = 1022346 + 6432201$$

$$7458547 := 11012 \times 103 + 301 \times 21011 = 1134236 + 6324311$$

$$7466647 := 11002 \times 113 + 311 \times 20011 = 1243226 + 6223421$$

$$7500057 := 100002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200001 = 1300026 + 6200031$$

$$:= 100003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300001 = 1200036 + 6300021$$

$$7470747 := 10001 \times 126 + 621 \times 10001 = 1260126 + 6210621$$

$$:= 10001 \times 225 + 522 \times 10001 = 2250225 + 5220522$$

$$:= 10001 \times 324 + 423 \times 10001 = 3240324 + 4230423$$

$$7476747 := 10011 \times 304 + 403 \times 11001 = 3043344 + 4433403$$

$$7514157 := 101003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300101 = 1212036 + 6302121$$

$$7516157 := 101002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200101 = 1313026 + 6203131$$

$$7522257 := 100103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301001 = 1201236 + 6321021$$

$$7528257 := 102003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300201 = 1224036 + 6304221$$

$$7532357 := 100102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201001 = 1301326 + 6231031$$

$$7536357 := 101103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301101 = 1213236 + 6323121$$

$$7544457 := 100203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302001 = 1202436 + 6342021$$

$$7548457 := 101102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201101 = 1314326 + 6234131$$

$$7558557 := 101203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302101 = 1214436 + 6344121$$

$$:= 11023 \times 102 + 201 \times 32011 = 1124346 + 6434211$$

$$7564657 := 100202 \times 13 + 31 \times 202001 = 1302626 + 6262031$$

$$7478747 := 10046 \times 101 + 101 \times 64001 = 1014646 + 6464101$$

$$:= 11036 \times 101 + 101 \times 63011 = 1114636 + 6364111$$

$$:= 12026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62021 = 1214626 + 6264121$$

$$:= 13016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61031 = 1314616 + 6164131$$

$$:= 14006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60041 = 1414606 + 6064141$$

$$:= 20045 \times 101 + 101 \times 54002 = 2024545 + 5454202$$

$$:= 21035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53012 = 2124535 + 5354212$$

$$:= 22025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52022 = 2224525 + 5254222$$

$$:= 23015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51032 = 2324515 + 5154232$$

$$:= 24005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50042 = 2424505 + 5054242$$

$$:= 30044 \times 101 + 101 \times 44003 = 3034444 + 4444303$$

$$:= 11003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30011 = 1232336 + 6332321$$

$$**7680867** := 10002 \times 322 + 223 \times 20001 = 3220644 + 4460223$$

$$**7566657** := 100303 \times 12 + 21 \times 303001 = 1203636 + 6363021$$

$$**7686867** := 110303 \times 12 + 21 \times 303011 = 1323636 + 6363231$$

$$**7574757** := 10011 \times 205 + 502 \times 11001 = 2052255 + 5522502$$

$$:= 10011 \times 314 + 413 \times 11001 = 3143454 + 4543413$$

$$**7580857** := 20003 \times 211 + 112 \times 30002 = 4220633 + 3360224$$

$$:= 10133 \times 102 + 201 \times 33101 = 1033566 + 6653301$$

$$:= 23003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30032 = 4623603 + 3063264$$

$$**7588857** := 100403 \times 12 + 21 \times 304001 = 1204836 + 6384021$$

$$:= 10011 \times 413 + 314 \times 11001 = 4134543 + 3454314$$

$$:= 11123 \times 102 + 201 \times 32111 = 1134546 + 6454311$$

$$:= 22013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31022 = 4424613 + 3164244$$

$$**7688867** := 12002 \times 302 + 203 \times 20021 = 3624604 + 4064263$$

$$**7694967** := 110202 \times 13 + 31 \times 202011 = 1432626 + 6262341$$

$$:= 10102 \times 123 + 321 \times 20101 = 1242546 + 6452421$$

$$:= 10113 \times 112 + 211 \times 31101 = 1132656 + 6562311$$

$$:= 10122 \times 103 + 301 \times 22101 = 1042566 + 6652401$$

$$:= 11002 \times 312 + 213 \times 20011 = 3432624 + 4262343$$

$$:= 20013 \times 211 + 112 \times 31002 = 4222743 + 3472224$$

$$**7596957** := 100302 \times 13 + 31 \times 203001 = 1303926 + 6293031$$

$$:= 10012 \times 312 + 213 \times 21001 = 3123744 + 4473213$$

$$:= 11103 \times 112 + 211 \times 30111 = 1243536 + 6353421$$

$$**7620267** := 110003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300011 = 1320036 + 6300231$$

$$**7700077** := 100001 \times 16 + 61 \times 100001 = 1600016 + 6100061$$

$$**7630367** := 110002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200011 = 1430026 + 6200341$$

$$:= 100001 \times 25 + 52 \times 100001 = 2500025 + 5200052$$

$$**7634367** := 111003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300111 = 1332036 + 6302331$$

$$:= 100001 \times 34 + 43 \times 100001 = 3400034 + 4300043$$

$$**7642467** := 110103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301011 = 1321236 + 6321231$$

$$:= 100006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600001 = 1100066 + 6600011$$

$$**7646467** := 111002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200111 = 1443026 + 6203441$$

$$:= 200005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500002 = 2200055 + 5500022$$

$$**7648467** := 112003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300211 = 1344036 + 6304431$$

$$:= 300004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400003 = 3300044 + 4400033$$

$$**7650567** := 10002 \times 123 + 321 \times 20001 = 1230246 + 6420321$$

$$**7654567** := 10022 \times 103 + 301 \times 22001 = 1032266 + 6622301$$

$$**7710177** := 100013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310001 = 1200156 + 6510021$$

$$**7656567** := 111103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301111 = 1333236 + 6323331$$

$$:= 10033 \times 102 + 201 \times 33001 = 1023366 + 6633201$$

$$**7712177** := 100106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601001 = 1101166 + 6611011$$

$$:= 101006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600101 = 1111066 + 6601111$$

$$**7662667** := 110102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201011 = 1431326 + 6231341$$

$$:= 10012 \times 113 + 311 \times 21001 = 1131356 + 6531311$$

$$:= 10013 \times 112 + 211 \times 31001 = 1121456 + 6541211$$

$$:= 200105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501002 = 2201155 + 5511022$$

$$:= 201005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500102 = 2211055 + 5501122$$

$$:= 300104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401003 = 3301144 + 4411033$$

$$:= 301004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400103 = 3311044 + 4401133$$

$$**7664667** := 110203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302011 = 1322436 + 6342231$$

$$**7724277** := 100206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602001 = 1102266 + 6622011$$

$$:= 101013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310101 = 1212156 + 6512121$$

$$:= 101106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601101 = 1112166 + 6612111$$

$$:= 102006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600201 = 1122066 + 6602211$$

$$:= 200205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502002 = 2202255 + 5522022$$

$$:= 201105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501102 = 2212155 + 5512122$$

$$:= 202005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500202 = 2222055 + 5502222$$

$$:= 300204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402003 = 3302244 + 4422033$$

$$:= 301104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401103 = 3312144 + 4412133$$

$$:= 302004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400203 = 3322044 + 4402233$$

$$**7670767** := 10001 \times 136 + 631 \times 10001 = 1360136 + 6310631$$

$$:= 10001 \times 235 + 532 \times 10001 = 2350235 + 5320532$$

$$:= 10001 \times 334 + 433 \times 10001 = 3340334 + 4330433$$

$$**7672767** := 10011 \times 106 + 601 \times 11001 = 1061166 + 6611601$$

$$**7678767** := 111102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201111 = 1444326 + 6234441$$

$$:= 111203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302111 = 1334436 + 6344331$$

$$:= 12003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30021 = 1344336 + 6334431$$

$$7732377 := 100113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311001 = 1201356 + 6531021$$

$$7760677 := 120002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200021 = 1560026 + 6200651$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7736377 &:= 100306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603001 = 1103366 + 6633011 \\ &:= 101206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602101 = 1113266 + 6623111 \\ &:= 102106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601201 = 1123166 + 6613211 \\ &:= 103006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600301 = 1133066 + 6603311 \\ &:= 200305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503002 = 2203355 + 5533022 \\ &:= 201205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502102 = 2213255 + 5523122 \\ &:= 202105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501202 = 2223155 + 5513222 \\ &:= 203005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500302 = 2233055 + 5503322 \\ &:= 300304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403003 = 3303344 + 4433033 \\ &:= 301204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402103 = 3313244 + 4423133 \\ &:= 302104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401203 = 3323144 + 4413233 \\ &:= 303004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400303 = 3333044 + 4403333 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7762677 &:= 100101 \times 16 + 61 \times 101001 = 1601616 + 6161061 \\ &:= 120103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301021 = 1441236 + 6321441 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7768677 &:= 101213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312101 = 1214556 + 6554121 \\ &:= 122003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300221 = 1464036 + 6304641 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7770777 &:= 10006 \times 111 + 111 \times 60001 = 1110666 + 6660111 \\ &:= 20005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50002 = 2220555 + 5550222 \\ &:= 30004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40003 = 3330444 + 4440333 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7776777 &:= 100313 \times 12 + 21 \times 313001 = 1203756 + 6573021 \\ &:= 121002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200121 = 1573026 + 6203751 \\ &:= 121103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301121 = 1453236 + 6323541 \\ &:= 11002 \times 123 + 321 \times 20011 = 1353246 + 6423531 \\ &:= 11013 \times 112 + 211 \times 31011 = 1233456 + 6543321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7738377 &:= 100101 \times 43 + 34 \times 101001 = 4304343 + 3434034 \\ &:= 102013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310201 = 1224156 + 6514221 \end{aligned}$$

$$7778777 := 11012 \times 113 + 311 \times 21011 = 1244356 + 6534421$$

$$7740477 := 120003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300021 = 1440036 + 6300441$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7784877 &:= 120203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302021 = 1442436 + 6342441 \\ &:= 10011 \times 215 + 512 \times 11001 = 2152365 + 5632512 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7746477 &:= 100101 \times 34 + 43 \times 101001 = 3403434 + 4343043 \\ &:= 101113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311101 = 1213356 + 6533121 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7792977 &:= 120102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201021 = 1561326 + 6231651 \\ &:= 10106 \times 111 + 111 \times 60101 = 1121766 + 6671211 \\ &:= 20105 \times 111 + 111 \times 50102 = 2231655 + 5561322 \\ &:= 21003 \times 211 + 112 \times 30012 = 4431633 + 3361344 \\ &:= 30104 \times 111 + 111 \times 40103 = 3341544 + 4451433 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7798977 &:= 100413 \times 12 + 21 \times 314001 = 1204956 + 6594021 \\ &:= 121203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302121 = 1454436 + 6344541 \\ &:= 10011 \times 423 + 324 \times 11001 = 4234653 + 3564324 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7800087 &:= 100002 \times 32 + 23 \times 200001 = 3200064 + 4600023 \\ &:= 200003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300002 = 4200063 + 3600024 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7810187 &:= 100012 \times 13 + 31 \times 210001 = 1300156 + 6510031 \\ &:= 100016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610001 = 1100176 + 6710011 \\ &:= 110006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600011 = 1210066 + 6600121 \\ &:= 200015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510002 = 2200165 + 5610022 \\ &:= 210005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500012 = 2310055 + 5500132 \\ &:= 300014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410003 = 3300154 + 4510033 \\ &:= 310004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400013 = 3410044 + 4400143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7754577 &:= 100101 \times 25 + 52 \times 101001 = 2502525 + 5252052 \\ &:= 100213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312001 = 1202556 + 6552021 \\ &:= 121003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300121 = 1452036 + 6302541 \end{aligned}$$

$$7814187 := 200103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301002 = 4202163 + 3612024$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7822287 &:= 100116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611001 = 1101276 + 6721011 \\ &:= 101016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610101 = 1111176 + 6711111 \\ &:= 110106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601011 = 1211166 + 6611121 \\ &:= 111006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600111 = 1221066 + 6601221 \\ &:= 200115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511002 = 2201265 + 5621022 \\ &:= 201003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300102 = 4221063 + 3601224 \\ &:= 201015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510102 = 2211165 + 5611122 \\ &:= 210105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501012 = 2311155 + 5511132 \\ &:= 211005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500112 = 2321055 + 5501232 \\ &:= 300114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411003 = 3301254 + 4521033 \\ &:= 301014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410103 = 3311154 + 4511133 \\ &:= 310104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401013 = 3411144 + 4411143 \\ &:= 311004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400113 = 3421044 + 4401243 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7826287 &:= 100102 \times 32 + 23 \times 201001 = 3203264 + 4623023 \\ &:= 101012 \times 13 + 31 \times 210101 = 1313156 + 6513131 \end{aligned}$$

$$7828287 := 200203 \times 21 + 12 \times 302002 = 4204263 + 3624024$$

$$7830387 := 110013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310011 = 1320156 + 6510231$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7834387 &:= 100216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612001 = 1102376 + 6732011 \\ &:= 101002 \times 32 + 23 \times 200101 = 3232064 + 4602323 \\ &:= 101116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611101 = 1112276 + 6722111 \\ &:= 102016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610201 = 1122176 + 6712211 \\ &:= 110206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602011 = 1212266 + 6622121 \\ &:= 111106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601111 = 1222166 + 6612221 \\ &:= 112006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600211 = 1232066 + 6602321 \\ &:= 200215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512002 = 2202365 + 5632022 \\ &:= 201115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511102 = 2212265 + 5622122 \\ &:= 202015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510202 = 2222165 + 5612222 \\ &:= 210205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502012 = 2312255 + 5522132 \\ &:= 211105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501112 = 2322155 + 5512232 \\ &:= 212005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500212 = 2332055 + 5502332 \\ &:= 300214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412003 = 3302354 + 4532033 \\ &:= 301114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411103 = 3312254 + 4522133 \\ &:= 302014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410203 = 3322154 + 4512233 \\ &:= 310204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402013 = 3412244 + 4422143 \\ &:= 311104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401113 = 3422144 + 4412243 \\ &:= 312004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400213 = 3432044 + 4402343 \end{aligned}$$

$$7836387 := 201103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301102 = 4223163 + 3613224$$

$$7842487 := 100112 \times 13 + 31 \times 211001 = 1301456 + 6541031$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7844487 &:= 111013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310111 = 1332156 + 6512331 \\ &:= 202003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300202 = 4242063 + 3602424 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7846487 &:= 100316 \times 11 + 11 \times 613001 = 1103476 + 6743011 \\ &:= 101216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612101 = 1113376 + 6733111 \\ &:= 102116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611201 = 1123276 + 6723211 \\ &:= 103016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610301 = 1133176 + 6713311 \\ &:= 110306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603011 = 1213366 + 6633121 \\ &:= 111206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602111 = 1223266 + 6623221 \\ &:= 112106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601211 = 1233166 + 6613321 \\ &:= 113006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600311 = 1243066 + 6603421 \\ &:= 200315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513002 = 2203465 + 5643022 \\ &:= 201215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512102 = 2213365 + 5633122 \\ &:= 202115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511202 = 2223265 + 5623222 \\ &:= 203015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510302 = 2233165 + 5613322 \\ &:= 210305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503012 = 2313355 + 5533132 \\ &:= 211205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502112 = 2323255 + 5523232 \\ &:= 212105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501212 = 2333155 + 5513332 \\ &:= 213005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500312 = 2343055 + 5503432 \\ &:= 300314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413003 = 3303454 + 4543033 \\ &:= 301214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412103 = 3313354 + 4533133 \\ &:= 302114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411203 = 3323254 + 4523233 \\ &:= 303014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410303 = 3333154 + 4513333 \\ &:= 310304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403013 = 3413344 + 4433143 \\ &:= 311204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402113 = 3423244 + 4423243 \\ &:= 312104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401213 = 3433144 + 4413343 \\ &:= 313004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400313 = 3443044 + 4403443 \end{aligned}$$

$$7850587 := 10003 \times 122 + 221 \times 30001 = 1220366 + 6630221$$

$$7852587 := 110113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311011 = 1321356 + 6531231$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7858587 &:= 100416 \times 11 + 11 \times 614001 = 1104576 + 6754011 \\ &:= 101112 \times 13 + 31 \times 211101 = 1314456 + 6544131 \\ &:= 101316 \times 11 + 11 \times 613101 = 1114476 + 6744111 \\ &:= 102216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612201 = 1124376 + 6734211 \\ &:= 103116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611301 = 1134276 + 6724311 \\ &:= 104016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610401 = 1144176 + 6714411 \\ &:= 110406 \times 11 + 11 \times 604011 = 1214466 + 6644121 \\ &:= 111306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603111 = 1224366 + 6634221 \\ &:= 112013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310211 = 1344156 + 6514431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 112206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602211 = 1234266 + 6624321 \\
&:= 113106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601311 = 1244166 + 6614421 \\
&:= 114006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600411 = 1254066 + 6604521 \\
&:= 200415 \times 11 + 11 \times 514002 = 2204565 + 5654022 \\
&:= 201315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513102 = 2214465 + 5644122 \\
&:= 202103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301202 = 4244163 + 3614424 \\
&:= 202215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512202 = 2224365 + 5634222 \\
&:= 203115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511302 = 2234265 + 5624322 \\
&:= 204015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510402 = 2244165 + 5614422 \\
&:= 210405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504012 = 2314455 + 5544132 \\
&:= 211305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503112 = 2324355 + 5534232 \\
&:= 212205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502212 = 2334255 + 5524332 \\
&:= 213105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501312 = 2344155 + 5514432 \\
&:= 214005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500412 = 2354055 + 5504532 \\
&:= 300414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414003 = 3304554 + 4554033 \\
&:= 301314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413103 = 3314454 + 4544133 \\
&:= 302214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412203 = 3324354 + 4534233 \\
&:= 303114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411303 = 3334254 + 4524333 \\
&:= 304014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410403 = 3344154 + 4514433 \\
&:= 310404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404013 = 3414444 + 4444143 \\
&:= 311304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403113 = 3424344 + 4434243 \\
&:= 312204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402213 = 3434244 + 4424343 \\
&:= 313104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401313 = 3444144 + 4414443 \\
&:= 314004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400413 = 3454044 + 4404543 \\
&:= 10043 \times 102 + 201 \times 34001 = 1024386 + 6834201
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7860687} &:= 100011 \times 61 + 16 \times 110001 = 6100671 + 1760016 \\
&:= 130003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300031 = 1560036 + 6300651
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7866687} &:= 111113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311111 = 1333356 + 6533331 \\
&:= 203003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300302 = 4263063 + 3603624
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7868687} := 102002 \times 32 + 23 \times 200201 = 3264064 + 4604623$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7870787} &:= 10001 \times 146 + 641 \times 10001 = 1460146 + 6410641 \\
&:= 10001 \times 245 + 542 \times 10001 = 2450245 + 5420542 \\
&:= 10001 \times 344 + 443 \times 10001 = 3440344 + 4430443
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7874787} &:= 100212 \times 13 + 31 \times 212001 = 1302756 + 6572031 \\
&:= 110213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312011 = 1322556 + 6552231 \\
&:= 131003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300131 = 1572036 + 6302751 \\
&:= 10023 \times 112 + 211 \times 32001 = 1122576 + 6752211
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7882887} &:= 130103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301031 = 1561236 + 6321651 \\
&:= 10011 \times 116 + 611 \times 11001 = 1161276 + 6721611 \\
&:= 10016 \times 111 + 111 \times 61001 = 1111776 + 6771111 \\
&:= 11006 \times 111 + 111 \times 60011 = 1221666 + 6661221 \\
&:= 20015 \times 111 + 111 \times 51002 = 2221665 + 5661222 \\
&:= 21005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50012 = 2331555 + 5551332 \\
&:= 30014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41003 = 3331554 + 4551333 \\
&:= 31004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40013 = 3441444 + 4441443
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7884887} := 10103 \times 122 + 221 \times 30101 = 1232566 + 6652321$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7888887} &:= 111213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312111 = 1334556 + 6554331 \\
&:= 132003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300231 = 1584036 + 6304851 \\
&:= 204003 \times 21 + 12 \times 300402 = 4284063 + 3604824 \\
&:= 10143 \times 102 + 201 \times 34101 = 1034586 + 6854301 \\
&:= 24003 \times 201 + 102 \times 30042 = 4824603 + 3064284
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7890987} := 130002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200031 = 1690026 + 6200961$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7896987} &:= 110313 \times 12 + 21 \times 313011 = 1323756 + 6573231 \\
&:= 131103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301131 = 1573236 + 6323751 \\
&:= 10011 \times 324 + 423 \times 11001 = 3243564 + 4653423
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7920297} &:= 100023 \times 12 + 21 \times 320001 = 1200276 + 6720021 \\
&:= 100026 \times 11 + 11 \times 620001 = 1100286 + 6820011 \\
&:= 110016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610011 = 1210176 + 6710121 \\
&:= 120006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600021 = 1320066 + 6600231 \\
&:= 200013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310002 = 4200273 + 3720024 \\
&:= 200025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520002 = 2200275 + 5720022 \\
&:= 210015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510012 = 2310165 + 5610132 \\
&:= 220005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500022 = 2420055 + 5500242 \\
&:= 300024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420003 = 3300264 + 4620033 \\
&:= 310014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410013 = 3410154 + 4510143 \\
&:= 320004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400023 = 3520044 + 4400253
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{7932397} &:= 100126 \times 11 + 11 \times 621001 = 1101386 + 6831011 \\
&:= 101026 \times 11 + 11 \times 620101 = 1111286 + 6821111 \\
&:= 110116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611011 = 1211276 + 6721121 \\
&:= 111016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610111 = 1221176 + 6711221 \\
&:= 120106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601021 = 1321166 + 6611231 \\
&:= 121006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600121 = 1331066 + 6601331 \\
&:= 200125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521002 = 2201375 + 5731022 \\
&:= 201025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520102 = 2211275 + 5721122
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 210115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511012 = 2311265 + 5621132 \\ &:= 211015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510112 = 2321165 + 5611232 \\ &:= 220105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501022 = 2421155 + 5511242 \\ &:= 221005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500122 = 2431055 + 5501342 \\ &:= 300124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421003 = 3301364 + 4631033 \\ &:= 301024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420103 = 3311264 + 4621133 \\ &:= 310114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411013 = 3411254 + 4521143 \\ &:= 311014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410113 = 3421154 + 4511243 \\ &:= 320104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401023 = 3521144 + 4411253 \\ &:= 321004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400123 = 3531044 + 4401353 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7934397} &:= 101023 \times 12 + 21 \times 320101 = 1212276 + 6722121 \\ &:= 200113 \times 21 + 12 \times 311002 = 4202373 + 3732024 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7940497} := 110012 \times 13 + 31 \times 210011 = 1430156 + 6510341$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7942497} &:= 100123 \times 12 + 21 \times 321001 = 1201476 + 6741021 \\ &:= 201013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310102 = 4221273 + 3721224 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7944497} &:= 100226 \times 11 + 11 \times 622001 = 1102486 + 6842011 \\ &:= 101126 \times 11 + 11 \times 621101 = 1112386 + 6832111 \\ &:= 102026 \times 11 + 11 \times 620201 = 1122286 + 6822211 \\ &:= 110216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612011 = 1212376 + 6732121 \\ &:= 111116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611111 = 1222276 + 6722221 \\ &:= 112016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610211 = 1232176 + 6712321 \\ &:= 120206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602021 = 1322266 + 6622231 \\ &:= 121106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601121 = 1332166 + 6612331 \\ &:= 122006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600221 = 1342066 + 6602431 \\ &:= 200225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522002 = 2202475 + 5742022 \\ &:= 201125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521102 = 2212375 + 5732122 \\ &:= 202025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520202 = 2222275 + 5722222 \\ &:= 210215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512012 = 2312365 + 5632132 \\ &:= 211115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511112 = 2322265 + 5622232 \\ &:= 212015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510212 = 2332165 + 5612332 \\ &:= 220205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502022 = 2422255 + 5522242 \\ &:= 221105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501122 = 2432155 + 5512342 \\ &:= 222005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500222 = 2442055 + 5502442 \\ &:= 300224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422003 = 3302464 + 4642033 \\ &:= 301124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421103 = 3312364 + 4632133 \\ &:= 302024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420203 = 3322264 + 4622233 \\ &:= 310214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412013 = 3412354 + 4532143 \\ &:= 311114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411113 = 3422254 + 4522243 \\ &:= 312014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410213 = 3432154 + 4512343 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 320204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402023 = 3522244 + 4422253 \\ &:= 321104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401123 = 3532144 + 4412353 \\ &:= 322004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400223 = 3542044 + 4402453 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7948497} &:= 102023 \times 12 + 21 \times 320201 = 1224276 + 6724221 \\ &:= 200213 \times 21 + 12 \times 312002 = 4204473 + 3744024 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7950597} &:= 100011 \times 52 + 25 \times 110001 = 5200572 + 2750025 \\ &:= 120013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310021 = 1440156 + 6510441 \\ &:= 10002 \times 133 + 331 \times 20001 = 1330266 + 6620331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7956597} &:= 100326 \times 11 + 11 \times 623001 = 1103586 + 6853011 \\ &:= 101123 \times 12 + 21 \times 321101 = 1213476 + 6743121 \\ &:= 101226 \times 11 + 11 \times 622101 = 1113486 + 6843111 \\ &:= 102126 \times 11 + 11 \times 621201 = 1123386 + 6833211 \\ &:= 103026 \times 11 + 11 \times 620301 = 1133286 + 6823311 \\ &:= 110316 \times 11 + 11 \times 613011 = 1213476 + 6743121 \\ &:= 111012 \times 13 + 31 \times 210111 = 1443156 + 6513441 \\ &:= 111216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612111 = 1223376 + 6733221 \\ &:= 112116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611211 = 1233276 + 6723321 \\ &:= 113016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610311 = 1243176 + 6713421 \\ &:= 120306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603021 = 1323366 + 6633231 \\ &:= 121206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602121 = 1333266 + 6623331 \\ &:= 122106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601221 = 1343166 + 6613431 \\ &:= 123006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600321 = 1353066 + 6603531 \\ &:= 200325 \times 11 + 11 \times 523002 = 2203575 + 5753022 \\ &:= 201113 \times 21 + 12 \times 311102 = 4223373 + 3733224 \\ &:= 201225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522102 = 2213475 + 5743122 \\ &:= 202125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521202 = 2223375 + 5733222 \\ &:= 203025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520302 = 2233275 + 5723322 \\ &:= 210315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513012 = 2313465 + 5643132 \\ &:= 211215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512112 = 2323365 + 5633232 \\ &:= 212115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511212 = 2333265 + 5623332 \\ &:= 213015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510312 = 2343165 + 5613432 \\ &:= 220305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503022 = 2423355 + 5533242 \\ &:= 221205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502122 = 2433255 + 5523342 \\ &:= 222105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501222 = 2443155 + 5513442 \\ &:= 223005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500322 = 2453055 + 5503542 \\ &:= 300324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423003 = 3303564 + 4653033 \\ &:= 301224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422103 = 3313464 + 4643133 \\ &:= 302124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421203 = 3323364 + 4633233 \\ &:= 303024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420303 = 3333264 + 4623333 \\ &:= 310314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413013 = 3413454 + 4543143 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 311214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412113 = 3423354 + 4533243 \\ &:= 312114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411213 = 3433254 + 4523343 \\ &:= 313014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410313 = 3443154 + 4513443 \\ &:= 320304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403023 = 3523344 + 4433253 \\ &:= 321204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402123 = 3533244 + 4423353 \\ &:= 322104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401223 = 3543144 + 4413453 \\ &:= 323004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400323 = 3553044 + 4403553 \\ &:= 10032 \times 103 + 301 \times 23001 = 1033296 + 6923301 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7964697} &:= 100223 \times 12 + 21 \times 322001 = 1202676 + 6762021 \\ &:= 121013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310121 = 1452156 + 6512541 \\ &:= 202013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310202 = 4242273 + 3722424 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7968697} &:= 100426 \times 11 + 11 \times 624001 = 1104686 + 6864011 \\ &:= 101326 \times 11 + 11 \times 623101 = 1114586 + 6854111 \\ &:= 102226 \times 11 + 11 \times 622201 = 1124486 + 6844211 \\ &:= 103126 \times 11 + 11 \times 621301 = 1134386 + 6834311 \\ &:= 104026 \times 11 + 11 \times 620401 = 1144286 + 6824411 \\ &:= 110416 \times 11 + 11 \times 614011 = 1214576 + 6754121 \\ &:= 111316 \times 11 + 11 \times 613111 = 1224476 + 6744221 \\ &:= 112216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612211 = 1234376 + 6734321 \\ &:= 113116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611311 = 1244276 + 6724421 \\ &:= 114016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610411 = 1254176 + 6714521 \\ &:= 120406 \times 11 + 11 \times 604021 = 1324466 + 6644231 \\ &:= 121306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603121 = 1334366 + 6634331 \\ &:= 122206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602221 = 1344266 + 6624431 \\ &:= 123106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601321 = 1354166 + 6614531 \\ &:= 124006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600421 = 1364066 + 6604631 \\ &:= 200425 \times 11 + 11 \times 524002 = 2204675 + 5764022 \\ &:= 201325 \times 11 + 11 \times 523102 = 2214575 + 5754122 \\ &:= 202225 \times 11 + 11 \times 522202 = 2224475 + 5744222 \\ &:= 203125 \times 11 + 11 \times 521302 = 2234375 + 5734322 \\ &:= 204025 \times 11 + 11 \times 520402 = 2244275 + 5724422 \\ &:= 210415 \times 11 + 11 \times 514012 = 2314565 + 5654132 \\ &:= 211315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513112 = 2324465 + 5644232 \\ &:= 212215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512212 = 2334365 + 5634332 \\ &:= 213115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511312 = 2344265 + 5624432 \\ &:= 214015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510412 = 2354165 + 5614532 \\ &:= 220405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504022 = 2424455 + 5544242 \\ &:= 221305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503122 = 2434355 + 5534342 \\ &:= 222205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502222 = 2444255 + 5524442 \\ &:= 223105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501322 = 2454155 + 5514542 \\ &:= 224005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500422 = 2464055 + 5504642 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 300424 \times 11 + 11 \times 424003 = 3304664 + 4664033 \\ &:= 301324 \times 11 + 11 \times 423103 = 3314564 + 4654133 \\ &:= 302224 \times 11 + 11 \times 422203 = 3324464 + 4644233 \\ &:= 303124 \times 11 + 11 \times 421303 = 3334364 + 4634333 \\ &:= 304024 \times 11 + 11 \times 420403 = 3344264 + 4624433 \\ &:= 310414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414013 = 3414554 + 4554143 \\ &:= 311314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413113 = 3424454 + 4544243 \\ &:= 312214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412213 = 3434354 + 4534343 \\ &:= 313114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411313 = 3444254 + 4524443 \\ &:= 314014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410413 = 3454154 + 4514543 \\ &:= 320404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404023 = 3524444 + 4444253 \\ &:= 321304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403123 = 3534344 + 4434353 \\ &:= 322204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402223 = 3544244 + 4424453 \\ &:= 323104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401323 = 3554144 + 4414553 \\ &:= 324004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400423 = 3564044 + 4404653 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7972797} &:= 110112 \times 13 + 31 \times 211011 = 1431456 + 6541341 \\ &:= 120113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311021 = 1441356 + 6531441 \\ &:= 10012 \times 123 + 321 \times 21001 = 1231476 + 6741321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7974797} &:= 10022 \times 113 + 311 \times 22001 = 1132486 + 6842311 \\ &:= 11003 \times 122 + 221 \times 30011 = 1342366 + 6632431 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7978797} &:= 101223 \times 12 + 21 \times 322101 = 1214676 + 6764121 \\ &:= 122013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310221 = 1464156 + 6514641 \\ &:= 202113 \times 21 + 12 \times 311202 = 4244373 + 3734424 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7980897} &:= 140003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300041 = 1680036 + 6300861 \\ &:= 10002 \times 332 + 233 \times 20001 = 3320664 + 4660233 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7986897} &:= 100323 \times 12 + 21 \times 323001 = 1203876 + 6783021 \\ &:= 121113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311121 = 1453356 + 6533541 \\ &:= 203013 \times 21 + 12 \times 310302 = 4263273 + 3723624 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7988897} &:= 111112 \times 13 + 31 \times 211111 = 1444456 + 6544441 \\ &:= 11023 \times 112 + 211 \times 32011 = 1234576 + 6754321 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7994997} &:= 120213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312021 = 1442556 + 6552441 \\ &:= 141003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300141 = 1692036 + 6302961 \\ &:= 10011 \times 225 + 522 \times 11001 = 2252475 + 5742522 \\ &:= 10026 \times 111 + 111 \times 62001 = 1112886 + 6882111 \\ &:= 11016 \times 111 + 111 \times 61011 = 1222776 + 6772221 \\ &:= 12006 \times 111 + 111 \times 60021 = 1332666 + 6662331 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 20025 \times 111 + 111 \times 52002 = 2222775 + 5772222 \\ &:= 21015 \times 111 + 111 \times 51012 = 2332665 + 5662332 \\ &:= 22005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50022 = 2442555 + 5552442 \\ &:= 30024 \times 111 + 111 \times 42003 = 3332664 + 4662333 \\ &:= 31014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41013 = 3442554 + 4552443 \\ &:= 32004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40023 = 3552444 + 4442553 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7996997} &:= 10102 \times 133 + 331 \times 20101 = 1343566 + 6653431 \\ &:= 10132 \times 103 + 301 \times 23101 = 1043596 + 6953401 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8070708} &:= 10002 \times 203 + 302 \times 20001 = 2030406 + 6040302 \\ &:= 20003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30002 = 2040306 + 6030402 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080808} &:= 10001 \times 107 + 701 \times 10001 = 1070107 + 7010701 \\ &:= 10001 \times 206 + 602 \times 10001 = 2060206 + 6020602 \\ &:= 10001 \times 305 + 503 \times 10001 = 3050305 + 5030503 \\ &:= 10001 \times 404 + 404 \times 10001 = 4040404 + 4040404 \\ &:= 10003 \times 202 + 202 \times 30001 = 2020606 + 6060202 \\ &:= 10007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70001 = 1010707 + 7070101 \\ &:= 20002 \times 103 + 301 \times 20002 = 2060206 + 6020602 \\ &:= 20002 \times 202 + 202 \times 20002 = 4040404 + 4040404 \\ &:= 20006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60002 = 2020606 + 6060202 \\ &:= 30005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50003 = 3030505 + 5050303 \\ &:= 40004 \times 101 + 101 \times 40004 = 4040404 + 4040404 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8174718} := 21003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30012 = 2142306 + 6032412$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8182818} &:= 10017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71001 = 1011717 + 7171101 \\ &:= 11007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70011 = 1111707 + 7071111 \\ &:= 20016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61002 = 2021616 + 6161202 \\ &:= 21006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60012 = 2121606 + 6061212 \\ &:= 30015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51003 = 3031515 + 5151303 \\ &:= 31005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50013 = 3131505 + 5051313 \\ &:= 40014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41004 = 4041414 + 4141404 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8186818} := 20012 \times 301 + 103 \times 21002 = 6023612 + 2163206$$

$$\mathbf{8272728} := 20013 \times 102 + 201 \times 31002 = 2041326 + 6231402$$

$$\mathbf{8276728} := 11002 \times 203 + 302 \times 20011 = 2233406 + 6043322$$

$$\mathbf{8278728} := 22003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30022 = 2244306 + 6034422$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8280828} &:= 10001 \times 117 + 711 \times 10001 = 1170117 + 7110711 \\ &:= 10001 \times 216 + 612 \times 10001 = 2160216 + 6120612 \\ &:= 10001 \times 315 + 513 \times 10001 = 3150315 + 5130513 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 10001 \times 414 + 414 \times 10001 = 4140414 + 4140414$$

$$\mathbf{8284828} := 10013 \times 202 + 202 \times 31001 = 2022626 + 6262202$$

$$:= 10027 \times 101 + 101 \times 72001 = 1012727 + 7272101$$

$$:= 11003 \times 202 + 202 \times 30011 = 2222606 + 6062222$$

$$:= 11017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71011 = 1112717 + 7172111$$

$$:= 12007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70021 = 1212707 + 7072121$$

$$:= 20012 \times 202 + 202 \times 21002 = 4042424 + 4242404$$

$$:= 20026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62002 = 2022626 + 6262202$$

$$:= 21016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61012 = 2122616 + 6162212$$

$$:= 22006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60022 = 2222606 + 6062222$$

$$:= 30025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52003 = 3032525 + 5252303$$

$$:= 31015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51013 = 3132515 + 5152313$$

$$:= 32005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50023 = 3232505 + 5052323$$

$$:= 40024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42004 = 4042424 + 4242404$$

$$:= 41014 \times 101 + 101 \times 41014 = 4142414 + 4142414$$

$$\mathbf{8370738} := 10002 \times 213 + 312 \times 20001 = 2130426 + 6240312$$

$$\mathbf{8374738} := 10012 \times 203 + 302 \times 21001 = 2032436 + 6342302$$

$$\mathbf{8376738} := 21013 \times 102 + 201 \times 31012 = 2143326 + 6233412$$

$$\mathbf{8382838} := 20012 \times 103 + 301 \times 21002 = 2061236 + 6321602$$

$$\mathbf{8386838} := 10037 \times 101 + 101 \times 73001 = 1013737 + 7373101$$

$$:= 11027 \times 101 + 101 \times 72011 = 1113727 + 7273111$$

$$:= 12017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71021 = 1213717 + 7173121$$

$$:= 13007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70031 = 1313707 + 7073131$$

$$:= 20036 \times 101 + 101 \times 63002 = 2023636 + 6363202$$

$$:= 21026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62012 = 2123626 + 6263212$$

$$:= 22016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61022 = 2223616 + 6163222$$

$$:= 23006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60032 = 2323606 + 6063232$$

$$:= 30035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53003 = 3033535 + 5353303$$

$$:= 31025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52013 = 3133525 + 5253313$$

$$:= 32015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51023 = 3233515 + 5153323$$

$$:= 33005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50033 = 3333505 + 5053333$$

$$:= 40034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43004 = 4043434 + 4343404$$

$$:= 41024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42014 = 4143424 + 4243414$$

$$\mathbf{8474748} := 20023 \times 102 + 201 \times 32002 = 2042346 + 6432402$$

$$\mathbf{8480848} := 10001 \times 127 + 721 \times 10001 = 1270127 + 7210721$$

$$:= 10001 \times 226 + 622 \times 10001 = 2260226 + 6220622$$

$$:= 10001 \times 325 + 523 \times 10001 = 3250325 + 5230523$$

$$:= 10001 \times 424 + 424 \times 10001 = 4240424 + 4240424$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10003 \times 212 + 212 \times 30001 = 2120636 + 6360212 \\ &:= 20002 \times 113 + 311 \times 20002 = 2260226 + 6220622 \\ &:= 20002 \times 212 + 212 \times 20002 = 4240424 + 4240424 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8488848} &:= 10011 \times 404 + 404 \times 11001 = 4044444 + 4444404 \\ &:= 10023 \times 202 + 202 \times 32001 = 2024646 + 6464202 \\ &:= 10047 \times 101 + 101 \times 74001 = 1014747 + 7474101 \\ &:= 11013 \times 202 + 202 \times 31011 = 2224626 + 6264222 \\ &:= 11037 \times 101 + 101 \times 73011 = 1114737 + 7374111 \\ &:= 12003 \times 202 + 202 \times 30021 = 2424606 + 6064242 \\ &:= 12027 \times 101 + 101 \times 72021 = 1214727 + 7274121 \\ &:= 13017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71031 = 1314717 + 7174131 \\ &:= 14007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70041 = 1414707 + 7074141 \\ &:= 20022 \times 202 + 202 \times 22002 = 4044444 + 4444404 \\ &:= 20046 \times 101 + 101 \times 64002 = 2024646 + 6464202 \\ &:= 21012 \times 103 + 301 \times 21012 = 2164236 + 6324612 \\ &:= 21012 \times 202 + 202 \times 21012 = 4244424 + 4244424 \\ &:= 21036 \times 101 + 101 \times 63012 = 2124636 + 6364212 \\ &:= 22026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62022 = 2224626 + 6264222 \\ &:= 23016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61032 = 2324616 + 6164232 \\ &:= 24006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60042 = 2424606 + 6064242 \\ &:= 30045 \times 101 + 101 \times 54003 = 3034545 + 5454303 \\ &:= 31035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53013 = 3134535 + 5354313 \\ &:= 32025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52023 = 3234525 + 5254323 \\ &:= 33015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51033 = 3334515 + 5154333 \\ &:= 34005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50043 = 3434505 + 5054343 \\ &:= 40044 \times 101 + 101 \times 44004 = 4044444 + 4444404 \\ &:= 41034 \times 101 + 101 \times 43014 = 4144434 + 4344414 \\ &:= 42024 \times 101 + 101 \times 42024 = 4244424 + 4244424 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8570758} := 20003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30002 = 2240336 + 6330422$$

$$\mathbf{8578758} := 21023 \times 102 + 201 \times 32012 = 2144346 + 6434412$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8586858} &:= 10011 \times 305 + 503 \times 11001 = 3053355 + 5533503 \\ &:= 11002 \times 213 + 312 \times 20011 = 2343426 + 6243432 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8596958} := 20012 \times 311 + 113 \times 21002 = 6223732 + 2373226$$

$$\mathbf{8670768} := 10002 \times 223 + 322 \times 20001 = 2230446 + 6440322$$

$$\mathbf{8676768} := 20033 \times 102 + 201 \times 33002 = 2043366 + 6633402$$

$$\mathbf{8678768} := 10022 \times 203 + 302 \times 22001 = 2034466 + 6644302$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8680868} &:= 10001 \times 137 + 731 \times 10001 = 1370137 + 7310731 \\ &:= 10001 \times 236 + 632 \times 10001 = 2360236 + 6320632 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 10001 \times 335 + 533 \times 10001 = 3350335 + 5330533 \\ &:= 10001 \times 434 + 434 \times 10001 = 4340434 + 4340434 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8684868} := 10011 \times 206 + 602 \times 11001 = 2062266 + 6622602$$

$$:= 10012 \times 213 + 312 \times 21001 = 2132556 + 6552312$$

$$:= 20022 \times 103 + 301 \times 22002 = 2062266 + 6622602$$

$$:= 21003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30012 = 2352336 + 6332532$$

$$\mathbf{8694968} := 10013 \times 212 + 212 \times 31001 = 2122756 + 6572212$$

$$:= 11003 \times 212 + 212 \times 30011 = 2332636 + 6362332$$

$$:= 20012 \times 212 + 212 \times 21002 = 4242544 + 4452424$$

$$\mathbf{8698968} := 10011 \times 414 + 414 \times 11001 = 4144554 + 4554414$$

$$\mathbf{8700078} := 100002 \times 23 + 32 \times 200001 = 2300046 + 6400032$$

$$:= 200003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300002 = 2400036 + 6300042$$

$$\mathbf{8714178} := 201003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300102 = 2412036 + 6302142$$

$$\mathbf{8722278} := 200103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301002 = 2401236 + 6321042$$

$$\mathbf{8726278} := 101002 \times 23 + 32 \times 200101 = 2323046 + 6403232$$

$$\mathbf{8728278} := 202003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300202 = 2424036 + 6304242$$

$$\mathbf{8734378} := 100102 \times 23 + 32 \times 201001 = 2302346 + 6432032$$

$$\mathbf{8736378} := 201103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301102 = 2413236 + 6323142$$

$$\mathbf{8744478} := 200203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302002 = 2402436 + 6342042$$

$$\mathbf{8758578} := 201203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302102 = 2414436 + 6344142$$

$$\mathbf{8766678} := 200303 \times 12 + 21 \times 303002 = 2403636 + 6363042$$

$$\mathbf{8768678} := 100202 \times 23 + 32 \times 202001 = 2304646 + 6464032$$

$$\mathbf{8782878} := 10011 \times 107 + 701 \times 11001 = 1071177 + 7711701$$

$$:= 20013 \times 112 + 211 \times 31002 = 2241456 + 6541422$$

$$\mathbf{8788878} := 200403 \times 12 + 21 \times 304002 = 2404836 + 6384042$$

$$\mathbf{8792978} := 20012 \times 113 + 311 \times 21002 = 2261356 + 6531622$$

$$\mathbf{8796978} := 10011 \times 315 + 513 \times 11001 = 3153465 + 5643513$$

$$\mathbf{8798978} := 22003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30022 = 2464336 + 6334642$$

$$\mathbf{8800088} := 100001 \times 17 + 71 \times 100001 = 1700017 + 7100071$$

$$:= 100001 \times 26 + 62 \times 100001 = 2600026 + 6200062$$

$$:= 100001 \times 35 + 53 \times 100001 = 3500035 + 5300053$$

$$:= 100001 \times 44 + 44 \times 100001 = 4400044 + 4400044$$

$$:= 100003 \times 22 + 22 \times 300001 = 2200066 + 6600022$$

$$:= 100007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700001 = 1100077 + 7700011$$

$$:= 200002 \times 13 + 31 \times 200002 = 2600026 + 6200062$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 200002 \times 22 + 22 \times 200002 = 4400044 + 4400044 \\ &:= 200006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600002 = 2200066 + 6600022 \\ &:= 300005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500003 = 3300055 + 5500033 \\ &:= 400004 \times 11 + 11 \times 400004 = 4400044 + 4400044 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 301205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502103 = 3313255 + 5523133 \\ &:= 302105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501203 = 3323155 + 5513233 \\ &:= 303005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500303 = 3333055 + 5503333 \\ &:= 400304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403004 = 4403344 + 4433044 \\ &:= 401204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402104 = 4413244 + 4423144 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8812188} &:= 100107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701001 = 1101177 + 7711011 \\ &:= 101007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700101 = 1111077 + 7701111 \\ &:= 200106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601002 = 2201166 + 6611022 \\ &:= 201006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600102 = 2211066 + 6601122 \\ &:= 300105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501003 = 3301155 + 5511033 \\ &:= 301005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500103 = 3311055 + 5501133 \\ &:= 400104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401004 = 4401144 + 4411044 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8842488} := 210103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301012 = 2521236 + 6321252$$

$$\mathbf{8848488} := 100101 \times 44 + 44 \times 101001 = 4404444 + 4444044$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 100203 \times 22 + 22 \times 302001 = 2204466 + 6644022 \\ &:= 100407 \times 11 + 11 \times 704001 = 1104477 + 7744011 \\ &:= 101103 \times 22 + 22 \times 301101 = 2224266 + 6624222 \\ &:= 101307 \times 11 + 11 \times 703101 = 1114377 + 7734111 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 102003 \times 22 + 22 \times 300201 = 2244066 + 6604422$$

$$:= 102207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702201 = 1124277 + 7724211$$

$$:= 103107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701301 = 1134177 + 7714311$$

$$:= 104007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700401 = 1144077 + 7704411$$

$$:= 200202 \times 22 + 22 \times 202002 = 4404444 + 4444044$$

$$:= 200406 \times 11 + 11 \times 604002 = 2204466 + 6644022$$

$$:= 201102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201102 = 2614326 + 6234162$$

$$:= 201102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201102 = 4424244 + 4424244$$

$$:= 201306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603102 = 2214366 + 6634122$$

$$:= 202206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602202 = 2224266 + 6624222$$

$$:= 203106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601302 = 2234166 + 6614322$$

$$:= 204006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600402 = 2244066 + 6604422$$

$$:= 212003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300212 = 2544036 + 6304452$$

$$:= 300212 \times 21 + 21 \times 212003 = 6304452 + 2544036$$

$$:= 300405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504003 = 3304455 + 5544033$$

$$:= 301305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503103 = 3314355 + 5534133$$

$$:= 302205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502203 = 3324255 + 5524233$$

$$:= 303105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501303 = 3334155 + 5514333$$

$$:= 304005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500403 = 3344055 + 5504433$$

$$:= 400404 \times 11 + 11 \times 404004 = 4404444 + 4444044$$

$$:= 401304 \times 11 + 11 \times 403104 = 4414344 + 4434144$$

$$:= 402204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402204 = 4424244 + 4424244$$

$$\mathbf{8856588} := 100101 \times 35 + 53 \times 101001 = 3503535 + 5353053$$

$$:= 211103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301112 = 2533236 + 6323352$$

$$\mathbf{8864688} := 100101 \times 26 + 62 \times 101001 = 2602626 + 6262062$$

$$:= 200202 \times 13 + 31 \times 202002 = 2602626 + 6262062$$

$$:= 210203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302012 = 2522436 + 6342252$$

$$\mathbf{8816188} := 200102 \times 31 + 13 \times 201002 = 6203162 + 2613026$$

$$\mathbf{8820288} := 210003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300012 = 2520036 + 6300252$$

$$\mathbf{8824288} := 100103 \times 22 + 22 \times 301001 = 2202266 + 6622022$$

$$:= 100207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702001 = 1102277 + 7722011$$

$$:= 101003 \times 22 + 22 \times 300101 = 2222066 + 6602222$$

$$:= 101107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701101 = 1112177 + 7712111$$

$$:= 102007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700201 = 1122077 + 7702211$$

$$:= 200102 \times 22 + 22 \times 201002 = 4402244 + 4422044$$

$$:= 200206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602002 = 2202266 + 6622022$$

$$:= 201106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601102 = 2212166 + 6612122$$

$$:= 202006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600202 = 2222066 + 6602222$$

$$:= 300205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502003 = 3302255 + 5522033$$

$$:= 301105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501103 = 3312155 + 5512133$$

$$:= 302005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500203 = 3322055 + 5502233$$

$$:= 400204 \times 11 + 11 \times 402004 = 4402244 + 4422044$$

$$:= 401104 \times 11 + 11 \times 401104 = 4412144 + 4412144$$

$$\mathbf{8832388} := 200102 \times 13 + 31 \times 201002 = 2601326 + 6231062$$

$$\mathbf{8834388} := 211003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300112 = 2532036 + 6302352$$

$$\mathbf{8836388} := 100307 \times 11 + 11 \times 703001 = 1103377 + 7733011$$

$$:= 101207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702101 = 1113277 + 7723111$$

$$:= 102107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701201 = 1123177 + 7713211$$

$$:= 103007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700301 = 1133077 + 7703311$$

$$:= 200306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603002 = 2203366 + 6633022$$

$$:= 201206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602102 = 2213266 + 6623122$$

$$:= 202106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601202 = 2223166 + 6613222$$

$$:= 203006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600302 = 2233066 + 6603322$$

$$:= 300305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503003 = 3303355 + 5533033$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8872788 &:= 100101 \times 17 + 71 \times 101001 = 1701717 + 7171071 & := 310105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501013 = 3411155 + 5511143 \\
& & := 311005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500113 = 3421055 + 5501243 \\
8878788 &:= 211203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302112 = 2534436 + 6344352 & := 400114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411004 = 4401254 + 4521044 \\
& := 20043 \times 102 + 201 \times 34002 = 2044386 + 6834402 & := 401014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410104 = 4411154 + 4511144 \\
8880888 &:= 10001 \times 147 + 741 \times 10001 = 1470147 + 7410741 & 8924298 := 201013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310102 = 2412156 + 6512142 \\
& := 10001 \times 246 + 642 \times 10001 = 2460246 + 6420642 & 8930398 := 110002 \times 23 + 32 \times 200011 = 2530046 + 6400352 \\
& := 10001 \times 345 + 543 \times 10001 = 3450345 + 5430543 & := 200012 \times 31 + 13 \times 210002 = 6200372 + 2730026 \\
& := 10001 \times 444 + 444 \times 10001 = 4440444 + 4440444 & 8932398 := 200113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311002 = 2401356 + 6531042 \\
& := 10003 \times 222 + 222 \times 30001 = 2220666 + 6660222 & 8934398 := 100217 \times 11 + 11 \times 712001 = 1102387 + 7832011 \\
& := 10007 \times 111 + 111 \times 70001 = 1110777 + 7770111 & := 101117 \times 11 + 11 \times 711101 = 1112287 + 7822111 \\
& := 20002 \times 123 + 321 \times 20002 = 2460246 + 6420642 & := 102017 \times 11 + 11 \times 710201 = 1122187 + 7812211 \\
& := 20002 \times 222 + 222 \times 20002 = 4440444 + 4440444 & := 110207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702011 = 1212277 + 7722121 \\
& := 20006 \times 111 + 111 \times 60002 = 2220666 + 6660222 & := 111107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701111 = 1222177 + 7712221 \\
& := 30005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50003 = 3330555 + 5550333 & := 112007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700211 = 1232077 + 7702321 \\
& := 40004 \times 111 + 111 \times 40004 = 4440444 + 4440444 & := 200216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612002 = 2202376 + 6732022 \\
8886888 &:= 210303 \times 12 + 21 \times 303012 = 2523636 + 6363252 & := 201116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611102 = 2212276 + 6722122 \\
8894988 &:= 10011 \times 216 + 612 \times 11001 = 2162376 + 6732612 & := 202016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610202 = 2222176 + 6712222 \\
8896988 &:= 200302 \times 13 + 31 \times 203002 = 2603926 + 6293062 & := 210206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602012 = 2312266 + 6622132 \\
& := 11002 \times 223 + 322 \times 20011 = 2453446 + 6443542 & := 211106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601112 = 2322166 + 6612232 \\
& := 21013 \times 112 + 211 \times 31012 = 2353456 + 6543532 & := 212006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600212 = 2332066 + 6602332 \\
8910198 &:= 100017 \times 11 + 11 \times 710001 = 1100187 + 7810011 & := 300215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512003 = 3302365 + 5632033 \\
& := 110007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700011 = 1210077 + 7700121 & := 301115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511103 = 3312265 + 5622133 \\
& := 200013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310002 = 2400156 + 6510042 & := 302015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510203 = 3322165 + 5612233 \\
& := 200016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610002 = 2200176 + 6710022 & := 310205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502013 = 3412255 + 5522143 \\
& := 210006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600012 = 2310066 + 6600132 & := 311105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501113 = 3422155 + 5512243 \\
& := 300015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510003 = 3300165 + 5610033 & := 312005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500213 = 3432055 + 5502343 \\
& := 310005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500013 = 3410055 + 5500143 & := 400214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412004 = 4402354 + 4532044 \\
& := 400014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410004 = 4400154 + 4510044 & := 401114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411104 = 4412254 + 4522144 \\
& & := 402014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410204 = 4422154 + 4512244 \\
8922298 &:= 100117 \times 11 + 11 \times 711001 = 1101287 + 7821011 & 8938398 := 202013 \times 12 + 21 \times 310202 = 2424156 + 6514242 \\
& := 101017 \times 11 + 11 \times 710101 = 1111187 + 7811111 & 8940498 := 220003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300022 = 2640036 + 6300462 \\
& := 110107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701011 = 1211177 + 7711121 & 8946498 := 100317 \times 11 + 11 \times 713001 = 1103487 + 7843011 \\
& := 111007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700111 = 1221077 + 7701221 & := 101217 \times 11 + 11 \times 712101 = 1113387 + 7833111 \\
& := 200116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611002 = 2201276 + 6721022 & := 102117 \times 11 + 11 \times 711201 = 1123287 + 7823211 \\
& := 201016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610102 = 2211176 + 6711122 & := 103017 \times 11 + 11 \times 710301 = 1133187 + 7813311 \\
& := 210106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601012 = 2311166 + 6611132 & := 110307 \times 11 + 11 \times 703011 = 1213377 + 7733121 \\
& := 211006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600112 = 2321066 + 6601232 & := 111207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702111 = 1223277 + 7723221 \\
& := 300115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511003 = 3301265 + 5621033 \\
& := 301015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510103 = 3311165 + 5611133
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 112107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701211 = 1233177 + 7713321 \\
&:= 113007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700311 = 1243077 + 7703421 \\
&:= 200112 \times 31 + 13 \times 211002 = 6203472 + 2743026 \\
&:= 200316 \times 11 + 11 \times 613002 = 2203476 + 6743022 \\
&:= 201113 \times 12 + 21 \times 311102 = 2413356 + 6533142 \\
&:= 201216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612102 = 2213376 + 6733122 \\
&:= 202116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611202 = 2223276 + 6723222 \\
&:= 203016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610302 = 2233176 + 6713322 \\
&:= 210306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603012 = 2313366 + 6633132 \\
&:= 211206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602112 = 2323266 + 6623232 \\
&:= 212106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601212 = 2333166 + 6613332 \\
&:= 213006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600312 = 2343066 + 6603432 \\
&:= 300315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513003 = 3303465 + 5643033 \\
&:= 301215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512103 = 3313365 + 5633133 \\
&:= 302115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511203 = 3323265 + 5623233 \\
&:= 303015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510303 = 3333165 + 5613333 \\
&:= 310305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503013 = 3413355 + 5533143 \\
&:= 311205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502113 = 3423255 + 5523243 \\
&:= 312105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501213 = 3433155 + 5513343 \\
&:= 313005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500313 = 3443055 + 5503443 \\
&:= 400314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413004 = 4403454 + 4543044 \\
&:= 401214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412104 = 4413354 + 4533144 \\
&:= 402114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411204 = 4423254 + 4523244 \\
&:= 403014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410304 = 4433154 + 4513344
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&:= 204016 \times 11 + 11 \times 610402 = 2244176 + 6714422 \\
&:= 210406 \times 11 + 11 \times 604012 = 2314466 + 6644132 \\
&:= 211306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603112 = 2324366 + 6634232 \\
&:= 212206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602212 = 2334266 + 6624332 \\
&:= 213106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601312 = 2344166 + 6614432 \\
&:= 214006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600412 = 2354066 + 6604532 \\
&:= 300415 \times 11 + 11 \times 514003 = 3304565 + 5654033 \\
&:= 301315 \times 11 + 11 \times 513103 = 3314465 + 5644133 \\
&:= 302215 \times 11 + 11 \times 512203 = 3324365 + 5634233 \\
&:= 303115 \times 11 + 11 \times 511303 = 3334265 + 5624333 \\
&:= 304015 \times 11 + 11 \times 510403 = 3344165 + 5614433 \\
&:= 310405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504013 = 3414455 + 5544143 \\
&:= 311305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503113 = 3424355 + 5534243 \\
&:= 312205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502213 = 3434255 + 5524343 \\
&:= 313105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501313 = 3444155 + 5514443 \\
&:= 314005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500413 = 3454055 + 5504543 \\
&:= 400414 \times 11 + 11 \times 414004 = 4404554 + 4554044 \\
&:= 401314 \times 11 + 11 \times 413104 = 4414454 + 4544144 \\
&:= 402214 \times 11 + 11 \times 412204 = 4424354 + 4534244 \\
&:= 403114 \times 11 + 11 \times 411304 = 4434254 + 4524344 \\
&:= 404014 \times 11 + 11 \times 410404 = 4444154 + 4514444
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8962698 &:= 201012 \times 31 + 13 \times 210102 = 6231372 + 2731326 \\
&:= 220103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301022 = 2641236 + 6321462
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8954598 &:= 200213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312002 = 2402556 + 6552042 \\
8954598 &:= 221003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300122 = 2652036 + 6302562 \\
8956598 &:= 111002 \times 23 + 32 \times 200111 = 2553046 + 6403552
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8964698 &:= 110102 \times 23 + 32 \times 201011 = 2532346 + 6432352 \\
8968698 &:= 201213 \times 12 + 21 \times 312102 = 2414556 + 6554142 \\
&:= 222003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300222 = 2664036 + 6304662
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8958598 &:= 100417 \times 11 + 11 \times 714001 = 1104587 + 7854011 \\
&:= 101317 \times 11 + 11 \times 713101 = 1114487 + 7844111 \\
&:= 102217 \times 11 + 11 \times 712201 = 1124387 + 7834211 \\
&:= 103117 \times 11 + 11 \times 711301 = 1134287 + 7824311 \\
&:= 104017 \times 11 + 11 \times 710401 = 1144187 + 7814411 \\
&:= 110407 \times 11 + 11 \times 704011 = 1214477 + 7744121 \\
&:= 111307 \times 11 + 11 \times 703111 = 1224377 + 7734221 \\
&:= 112207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702211 = 1234277 + 7724321 \\
&:= 113107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701311 = 1244177 + 7714421 \\
&:= 114007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700411 = 1254077 + 7704521 \\
&:= 200416 \times 11 + 11 \times 614002 = 2204576 + 6754022 \\
&:= 201316 \times 11 + 11 \times 613102 = 2214476 + 6744122 \\
&:= 202216 \times 11 + 11 \times 612202 = 2224376 + 6734222 \\
&:= 203116 \times 11 + 11 \times 611302 = 2234276 + 6724322
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8970798 &:= 100011 \times 71 + 17 \times 110001 = 7100781 + 1870017 \\
&:= 10002 \times 233 + 332 \times 20001 = 2330466 + 6640332
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8976798 &:= 200313 \times 12 + 21 \times 313002 = 2403756 + 6573042 \\
&:= 221103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301122 = 2653236 + 6323562
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8978798 &:= 201112 \times 31 + 13 \times 211102 = 6234472 + 2744326 \\
8984898 &:= 220203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302022 = 2642436 + 6342462 \\
8986898 &:= 20032 \times 103 + 301 \times 23002 = 2063296 + 6923602
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8992998 &:= 10011 \times 117 + 711 \times 11001 = 1171287 + 7821711 \\
&:= 10017 \times 111 + 111 \times 71001 = 1111887 + 7881111 \\
&:= 11007 \times 111 + 111 \times 70011 = 1221777 + 7771221
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 20016 \times 111 + 111 \times 61002 = 2221776 + 6771222 \\ &:= 21006 \times 111 + 111 \times 60012 = 2331666 + 6661332 \\ &:= 30015 \times 111 + 111 \times 51003 = 3331665 + 5661333 \\ &:= 31005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50013 = 3441555 + 5551443 \\ &:= 40014 \times 111 + 111 \times 41004 = 4441554 + 4551444 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8994998} &:= 202012 \times 31 + 13 \times 210202 = 6262372 + 2732626 \\ &:= 10012 \times 223 + 322 \times 21001 = 2232676 + 6762322 \\ &:= 20023 \times 112 + 211 \times 32002 = 2242576 + 6752422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8998998} &:= 110202 \times 23 + 32 \times 202011 = 2534646 + 6464352 \\ &:= 200413 \times 12 + 21 \times 314002 = 2404956 + 6594042 \\ &:= 221203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302122 = 2654436 + 6344562 \\ &:= 10022 \times 213 + 312 \times 22001 = 2134686 + 6864312 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9060609} &:= 10002 \times 104 + 401 \times 20001 = 1040208 + 8020401 \\ &:= 10004 \times 102 + 201 \times 40001 = 1020408 + 8040201 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090909} &:= 10001 \times 108 + 801 \times 10001 = 1080108 + 8010801 \\ &:= 10001 \times 207 + 702 \times 10001 = 2070207 + 7020702 \\ &:= 10001 \times 306 + 603 \times 10001 = 3060306 + 6030603 \\ &:= 10001 \times 405 + 504 \times 10001 = 4050405 + 5040504 \\ &:= 10002 \times 303 + 303 \times 20001 = 3030606 + 6060303 \\ &:= 10008 \times 101 + 101 \times 80001 = 1010808 + 8080101 \\ &:= 10104 \times 102 + 201 \times 40101 = 1030608 + 8060301 \\ &:= 20007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70002 = 2020707 + 7070202 \\ &:= 30003 \times 102 + 201 \times 30003 = 3060306 + 6030603 \\ &:= 30006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60003 = 3030606 + 6060303 \\ &:= 40005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50004 = 4040505 + 5050404 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9164619} := 11004 \times 102 + 201 \times 40011 = 1122408 + 8042211$$

$$\mathbf{9168619} := 11002 \times 104 + 401 \times 20011 = 1144208 + 8024411$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9192919} &:= 10018 \times 101 + 101 \times 81001 = 1011818 + 8181101 \\ &:= 11008 \times 101 + 101 \times 80011 = 1111808 + 8081111 \\ &:= 20017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71002 = 2021717 + 7171202 \\ &:= 21007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70012 = 2121707 + 7071212 \\ &:= 30016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61003 = 3031616 + 6161303 \\ &:= 31006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60013 = 3131606 + 6061313 \\ &:= 40015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51004 = 4041515 + 5151404 \\ &:= 41005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50014 = 4141505 + 5051414 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9194919} := 11104 \times 102 + 201 \times 40111 = 1132608 + 8062311$$

$$:= 30013 \times 201 + 102 \times 31003 = 6032613 + 3162306$$

$$\mathbf{9262629} := 10014 \times 102 + 201 \times 41001 = 1021428 + 8241201$$

$$\mathbf{9268629} := 12004 \times 102 + 201 \times 40021 = 1224408 + 8044221$$

$$\mathbf{9290929} := 10001 \times 118 + 811 \times 10001 = 1180118 + 8110811$$

$$:= 10001 \times 217 + 712 \times 10001 = 2170217 + 7120712$$

$$:= 10001 \times 316 + 613 \times 10001 = 3160316 + 6130613$$

$$:= 10001 \times 415 + 514 \times 10001 = 4150415 + 5140514$$

$$\mathbf{9292929} := 10114 \times 102 + 201 \times 41101 = 1031628 + 8261301$$

$$:= 30013 \times 102 + 201 \times 31003 = 3061326 + 6231603$$

$$\mathbf{9294929} := 10028 \times 101 + 101 \times 82001 = 1012828 + 8282101$$

$$:= 11018 \times 101 + 101 \times 81011 = 1112818 + 8182111$$

$$:= 12008 \times 101 + 101 \times 80021 = 1212808 + 8082121$$

$$:= 20027 \times 101 + 101 \times 72002 = 2022727 + 7272202$$

$$:= 21017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71012 = 2122717 + 7172212$$

$$:= 22007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70022 = 2222707 + 7072222$$

$$:= 30026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62003 = 3032626 + 6262303$$

$$:= 31016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61013 = 3132616 + 6162313$$

$$:= 32006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60023 = 3232606 + 6062323$$

$$:= 40025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52004 = 4042525 + 5252404$$

$$:= 41015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51014 = 4142515 + 5152414$$

$$:= 42005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50024 = 4242505 + 5052424$$

$$\mathbf{9298929} := 12104 \times 102 + 201 \times 40121 = 1234608 + 8064321$$

$$:= 30023 \times 201 + 102 \times 32003 = 6034623 + 3264306$$

$$\mathbf{9360639} := 10002 \times 114 + 411 \times 20001 = 1140228 + 8220411$$

$$\mathbf{9366639} := 11014 \times 102 + 201 \times 41011 = 1123428 + 8243211$$

$$\mathbf{9390939} := 10002 \times 313 + 313 \times 20001 = 3130626 + 6260313$$

$$\mathbf{9396939} := 10012 \times 303 + 303 \times 21001 = 3033636 + 6363303$$

$$:= 10038 \times 101 + 101 \times 83001 = 1013838 + 8383101$$

$$:= 11002 \times 303 + 303 \times 20011 = 3333606 + 6063333$$

$$:= 11028 \times 101 + 101 \times 82011 = 1113828 + 8283111$$

$$:= 11114 \times 102 + 201 \times 41111 = 1133628 + 8263311$$

$$:= 12018 \times 101 + 101 \times 81021 = 1213818 + 8183121$$

$$:= 13008 \times 101 + 101 \times 80031 = 1313808 + 8083131$$

$$:= 20037 \times 101 + 101 \times 73002 = 2023737 + 7373202$$

$$:= 21027 \times 101 + 101 \times 72012 = 2123727 + 7273212$$

$$:= 22017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71022 = 2223717 + 7173222$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 23007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70032 = 2323707 + 7073232 \\ &:= 30036 \times 101 + 101 \times 63003 = 3033636 + 6363303 \\ &:= 31013 \times 102 + 201 \times 31013 = 3163326 + 6233613 \\ &:= 31026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62013 = 3133626 + 6263313 \\ &:= 32016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61023 = 3233616 + 6163323 \\ &:= 33006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60033 = 3333606 + 6063333 \\ &:= 40035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53004 = 4043535 + 5353404 \\ &:= 41025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52014 = 4143525 + 5253414 \\ &:= 42015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51024 = 4243515 + 5153424 \\ &:= 43005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50034 = 4343505 + 5053434 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9560659} &:= 10004 \times 112 + 211 \times 40001 = 1120448 + 8440211 \\ \mathbf{9568659} &:= 11024 \times 102 + 201 \times 42011 = 1124448 + 8444211 \\ \mathbf{9592959} &:= 10104 \times 112 + 211 \times 40101 = 1131648 + 8461311 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9598959} &:= 10011 \times 405 + 504 \times 11001 = 4054455 + 5544504 \\ &:= 11124 \times 102 + 201 \times 42111 = 1134648 + 8464311 \\ &:= 31023 \times 102 + 201 \times 32013 = 3164346 + 6434613 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9600069} &:= 100002 \times 14 + 41 \times 200001 = 1400028 + 8200041 \\ &:= 100004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400001 = 1200048 + 8400021 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9462649} := 10012 \times 104 + 401 \times 21001 = 1041248 + 8421401$$

$$\mathbf{9464649} := 10024 \times 102 + 201 \times 42001 = 1022448 + 8442201$$

$$\mathbf{9478749} := 11002 \times 114 + 411 \times 20011 = 1254228 + 8224521$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9490949} &:= 10001 \times 128 + 821 \times 10001 = 1280128 + 8210821 \\ &:= 10001 \times 227 + 722 \times 10001 = 2270227 + 7220722 \\ &:= 10001 \times 326 + 623 \times 10001 = 3260326 + 6230623 \\ &:= 10001 \times 425 + 524 \times 10001 = 4250425 + 5240524 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9494949} &:= 10124 \times 102 + 201 \times 42101 = 1032648 + 8462301 \\ &:= 30023 \times 102 + 201 \times 32003 = 3062346 + 6432603 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9498949} &:= 10048 \times 101 + 101 \times 84001 = 1014848 + 8484101 \\ &:= 11038 \times 101 + 101 \times 83011 = 1114838 + 8384111 \\ &:= 12028 \times 101 + 101 \times 82021 = 1214828 + 8284121 \\ &:= 13018 \times 101 + 101 \times 81031 = 1314818 + 8184131 \\ &:= 14008 \times 101 + 101 \times 80041 = 1414808 + 8084141 \\ &:= 20047 \times 101 + 101 \times 74002 = 2024747 + 7474202 \\ &:= 21037 \times 101 + 101 \times 73012 = 2124737 + 7374212 \\ &:= 22027 \times 101 + 101 \times 72022 = 2224727 + 7274222 \\ &:= 23017 \times 101 + 101 \times 71032 = 2324717 + 7174232 \\ &:= 24007 \times 101 + 101 \times 70042 = 2424707 + 7074242 \\ &:= 30046 \times 101 + 101 \times 64003 = 3034646 + 6464303 \\ &:= 31036 \times 101 + 101 \times 63013 = 3134636 + 6364313 \\ &:= 32026 \times 101 + 101 \times 62023 = 3234626 + 6264323 \\ &:= 33016 \times 101 + 101 \times 61033 = 3334616 + 6164333 \\ &:= 34006 \times 101 + 101 \times 60043 = 3434606 + 6064343 \\ &:= 40045 \times 101 + 101 \times 54004 = 4044545 + 5454404 \\ &:= 41035 \times 101 + 101 \times 53014 = 4144535 + 5354414 \\ &:= 42025 \times 101 + 101 \times 52024 = 4244525 + 5254424 \\ &:= 43015 \times 101 + 101 \times 51034 = 4344515 + 5154434 \\ &:= 44005 \times 101 + 101 \times 50044 = 4444505 + 5054444 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9614169} := 101004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400101 = 1212048 + 8402121$$

$$\mathbf{9618169} := 101002 \times 14 + 41 \times 200101 = 1414028 + 8204141$$

$$\mathbf{9622269} := 100104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401001 = 1201248 + 8421021$$

$$\mathbf{9628269} := 102004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400201 = 1224048 + 8404221$$

$$\mathbf{9636369} := 101104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401101 = 1213248 + 8423121$$

$$\mathbf{9642469} := 100102 \times 14 + 41 \times 201001 = 1401428 + 8241041$$

$$\mathbf{9644469} := 100204 \times 12 + 21 \times 402001 = 1202448 + 8442021$$

$$\mathbf{9658569} := 101204 \times 12 + 21 \times 402101 = 1214448 + 8444121$$

$$\mathbf{9660669} := 10002 \times 124 + 421 \times 20001 = 1240248 + 8420421$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9666669} &:= 100304 \times 12 + 21 \times 403001 = 1203648 + 8463021 \\ &:= 10034 \times 102 + 201 \times 43001 = 1023468 + 8643201 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9674769} := 11004 \times 112 + 211 \times 40011 = 1232448 + 8442321$$

$$\mathbf{9684869} := 100202 \times 14 + 41 \times 202001 = 1402828 + 8282041$$

$$\mathbf{9688869} := 100404 \times 12 + 21 \times 404001 = 1204848 + 8484021$$

$$\mathbf{9690969} := 10001 \times 138 + 831 \times 10001 = 1380138 + 8310831$$

$$:= 10001 \times 237 + 732 \times 10001 = 2370237 + 7320732$$

$$:= 10001 \times 336 + 633 \times 10001 = 3360336 + 6330633$$

$$:= 10001 \times 435 + 534 \times 10001 = 4350435 + 5340534$$

$$:= 10002 \times 323 + 323 \times 20001 = 3230646 + 6460323$$

$$:= 30003 \times 112 + 211 \times 30003 = 3360336 + 6330633$$

$$\mathbf{9696969} := 10011 \times 306 + 603 \times 11001 = 3063366 + 6633603$$

$$:= 10134 \times 102 + 201 \times 43101 = 1033668 + 8663301$$

$$:= 30033 \times 102 + 201 \times 33003 = 3063366 + 6633603$$

$$\mathbf{9720279} := 110004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400011 = 1320048 + 8400231$$

$$\mathbf{9734379} := 111004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400111 = 1332048 + 8402331$$

$$\mathbf{9740479} := 110002 \times 14 + 41 \times 200011 = 1540028 + 8200451$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9742479 &:= 110104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401011 = 1321248 + 8421231 & := 10001 \times 346 + 643 \times 10001 = 3460346 + 6430643 \\
9748479 &:= 112004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400211 = 1344048 + 8404431 & := 10001 \times 445 + 544 \times 10001 = 4450445 + 5440544 \\
9756579 &:= 111104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401111 = 1333248 + 8423331 \\
9758579 &:= 111002 \times 14 + 41 \times 200111 = 1554028 + 8204551 \\
9764679 &:= 110204 \times 12 + 21 \times 402011 = 1322448 + 8442231 \\
9772779 &:= 10012 \times 114 + 411 \times 21001 = 1141368 + 8631411 \\
&:= 10014 \times 112 + 211 \times 41001 = 1121568 + 8651211 \\
9778779 &:= 111204 \times 12 + 21 \times 402111 = 1334448 + 8444331 \\
9782879 &:= 110102 \times 14 + 41 \times 201011 = 1541428 + 8241451 \\
9786879 &:= 110304 \times 12 + 21 \times 403011 = 1323648 + 8463231 \\
9788879 &:= 11002 \times 124 + 421 \times 20011 = 1364248 + 8424631 \\
&:= 12004 \times 112 + 211 \times 40021 = 1344448 + 8444431 \\
9794979 &:= 10011 \times 207 + 702 \times 11001 = 2072277 + 7722702 \\
9810189 &:= 100014 \times 12 + 21 \times 410001 = 1200168 + 8610021 \\
9824289 &:= 101014 \times 12 + 21 \times 410101 = 1212168 + 8612121 \\
9832389 &:= 100114 \times 12 + 21 \times 411001 = 1201368 + 8631021 \\
9838389 &:= 102014 \times 12 + 21 \times 410201 = 1224168 + 8614221 \\
9840489 &:= 120004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400021 = 1440048 + 8400441 \\
9846489 &:= 101114 \times 12 + 21 \times 411101 = 1213368 + 8633121 \\
9854589 &:= 100214 \times 12 + 21 \times 412001 = 1202568 + 8652021 \\
&:= 121004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400121 = 1452048 + 8402541 \\
9862689 &:= 120104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401021 = 1441248 + 8421441 \\
9864689 &:= 10022 \times 104 + 401 \times 22001 = 1042288 + 8822401 \\
9868689 &:= 101214 \times 12 + 21 \times 412101 = 1214568 + 8654121 \\
&:= 122004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400221 = 1464048 + 8404641 \\
&:= 10044 \times 102 + 201 \times 44001 = 1024488 + 8844201 \\
9876789 &:= 100314 \times 12 + 21 \times 413001 = 1203768 + 8673021 \\
&:= 121104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401121 = 1453248 + 8423541 \\
9880889 &:= 120002 \times 14 + 41 \times 200021 = 1680028 + 8200861 \\
9884889 &:= 120204 \times 12 + 21 \times 402021 = 1442448 + 8442441 \\
9886889 &:= 11014 \times 112 + 211 \times 41011 = 1233568 + 8653321 \\
9890989 &:= 10001 \times 148 + 841 \times 10001 = 1480148 + 8410841 \\
&:= 10001 \times 247 + 742 \times 10001 = 2470247 + 7420742 \\
9892989 &:= 10011 \times 108 + 801 \times 11001 = 1081188 + 8811801 \\
9898989 &:= 100414 \times 12 + 21 \times 414001 = 1204968 + 8694021 \\
&:= 121002 \times 14 + 41 \times 200121 = 1694028 + 8204961 \\
&:= 121204 \times 12 + 21 \times 402121 = 1454448 + 8444541 \\
&:= 10144 \times 102 + 201 \times 44101 = 1034688 + 8864301 \\
&:= 30043 \times 102 + 201 \times 34003 = 3064386 + 6834603 \\
9900099 &:= 100001 \times 18 + 81 \times 100001 = 1800018 + 8100081 \\
&:= 100001 \times 27 + 72 \times 100001 = 2700027 + 7200072 \\
&:= 100001 \times 36 + 63 \times 100001 = 3600036 + 6300063 \\
&:= 100001 \times 45 + 54 \times 100001 = 4500045 + 5400054 \\
&:= 100002 \times 33 + 33 \times 200001 = 3300066 + 6600033 \\
&:= 100008 \times 11 + 11 \times 800001 = 1100088 + 8800011 \\
&:= 200007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700002 = 2200077 + 7700022 \\
&:= 300003 \times 12 + 21 \times 300003 = 3600036 + 6300063 \\
&:= 300006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600003 = 3300066 + 6600033 \\
&:= 400005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500004 = 4400055 + 5500044 \\
9912199 &:= 100108 \times 11 + 11 \times 801001 = 1101188 + 8811011 \\
&:= 101008 \times 11 + 11 \times 800101 = 1111088 + 8801111 \\
&:= 200107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701002 = 2201177 + 7711022 \\
&:= 201007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700102 = 2211077 + 7701122 \\
&:= 300106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601003 = 3301166 + 6611033 \\
&:= 301006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600103 = 3311066 + 6601133 \\
&:= 400105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501004 = 4401155 + 5511044 \\
&:= 401005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500104 = 4411055 + 5501144 \\
9914199 &:= 300103 \times 21 + 12 \times 301003 = 6302163 + 3612036 \\
9922299 &:= 300103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301003 = 3601236 + 6321063 \\
9924299 &:= 100208 \times 11 + 11 \times 802001 = 1102288 + 8822011 \\
&:= 101108 \times 11 + 11 \times 801101 = 1112188 + 8812111 \\
&:= 102008 \times 11 + 11 \times 800201 = 1122088 + 8802211 \\
&:= 200207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702002 = 2202277 + 7722022 \\
&:= 201107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701102 = 2212177 + 7712122 \\
&:= 202007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700202 = 2222077 + 7702222 \\
&:= 300206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602003 = 3302266 + 6622033 \\
&:= 301106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601103 = 3312166 + 6612133 \\
&:= 302006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600203 = 3322066 + 6602233
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 400205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502004 = 4402255 + 5522044 \\ &:= 401105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501104 = 4412155 + 5512144 \\ &:= 402005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500204 = 4422055 + 5502244 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9928299} := 300203 \times 21 + 12 \times 302003 = 6304263 + 3624036$$

$$\mathbf{9930399} := 110014 \times 12 + 21 \times 410011 = 1320168 + 8610231$$

$$\mathbf{9936399} := 100102 \times 33 + 33 \times 201001 = 3303366 + 6633033$$

$$:= 100308 \times 11 + 11 \times 803001 = 1103388 + 8833011$$

$$:= 101002 \times 33 + 33 \times 200101 = 3333066 + 6603333$$

$$:= 101208 \times 11 + 11 \times 802101 = 1113288 + 8823111$$

$$:= 102108 \times 11 + 11 \times 801201 = 1123188 + 8813211$$

$$:= 103008 \times 11 + 11 \times 800301 = 1133088 + 8803311$$

$$:= 200307 \times 11 + 11 \times 703002 = 2203377 + 7733022$$

$$:= 201207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702102 = 2213277 + 7723122$$

$$:= 202107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701202 = 2223177 + 7713222$$

$$:= 203007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700302 = 2233077 + 7703322$$

$$:= 300306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603003 = 3303366 + 6633033$$

$$:= 301103 \times 12 + 21 \times 301103 = 3613236 + 6323163$$

$$:= 301206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602103 = 3313266 + 6623133$$

$$:= 302106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601203 = 3323166 + 6613233$$

$$:= 303006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600303 = 3333066 + 6603333$$

$$:= 400305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503004 = 4403355 + 5533044$$

$$:= 401205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502104 = 4413255 + 5523144$$

$$:= 402105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501204 = 4423155 + 5513244$$

$$:= 403005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500304 = 4433055 + 5503344$$

$$\mathbf{9944499} := 111014 \times 12 + 21 \times 410111 = 1332168 + 8612331$$

$$:= 300203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302003 = 3602436 + 6342063$$

$$\mathbf{9948499} := 100408 \times 11 + 11 \times 804001 = 1104488 + 8844011$$

$$:= 101308 \times 11 + 11 \times 803101 = 1114388 + 8834111$$

$$:= 102208 \times 11 + 11 \times 802201 = 1124288 + 8824211$$

$$:= 103108 \times 11 + 11 \times 801301 = 1134188 + 8814311$$

$$:= 104008 \times 11 + 11 \times 800401 = 1144088 + 8804411$$

$$:= 200407 \times 11 + 11 \times 704002 = 2204477 + 7744022$$

$$:= 201307 \times 11 + 11 \times 703102 = 2214377 + 7734122$$

$$:= 202207 \times 11 + 11 \times 702202 = 2224277 + 7724222$$

$$:= 203107 \times 11 + 11 \times 701302 = 2234177 + 7714322$$

$$:= 204007 \times 11 + 11 \times 700402 = 2244077 + 7704422$$

$$:= 300406 \times 11 + 11 \times 604003 = 3304466 + 6644033$$

$$:= 301306 \times 11 + 11 \times 603103 = 3314366 + 6634133$$

$$:= 302206 \times 11 + 11 \times 602203 = 3324266 + 6624233$$

$$:= 303106 \times 11 + 11 \times 601303 = 3334166 + 6614333$$

$$:= 304006 \times 11 + 11 \times 600403 = 3344066 + 6604433$$

$$:= 400405 \times 11 + 11 \times 504004 = 4404455 + 5544044$$

$$:= 401305 \times 11 + 11 \times 503104 = 4414355 + 5534144$$

$$:= 402205 \times 11 + 11 \times 502204 = 4424255 + 5524244$$

$$:= 403105 \times 11 + 11 \times 501304 = 4434155 + 5514344$$

$$:= 404005 \times 11 + 11 \times 500404 = 4444055 + 5504444$$

$$\mathbf{9952599} := 110114 \times 12 + 21 \times 411011 = 1321368 + 8631231$$

$$\mathbf{9958599} := 100101 \times 45 + 54 \times 101001 = 4504545 + 5454054$$

$$:= 112014 \times 12 + 21 \times 410211 = 1344168 + 8614431$$

$$:= 301203 \times 12 + 21 \times 302103 = 3614436 + 6344163$$

$$\mathbf{9960699} := 130004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400031 = 1560048 + 8400651$$

$$:= 10002 \times 134 + 431 \times 20001 = 1340268 + 8620431$$

$$\mathbf{9966699} := 100101 \times 36 + 63 \times 101001 = 3603636 + 6363063$$

$$:= 111114 \times 12 + 21 \times 411111 = 1333368 + 8633331$$

$$:= 300303 \times 12 + 21 \times 303003 = 3603636 + 6363063$$

$$\mathbf{9974799} := 100101 \times 27 + 72 \times 101001 = 2702727 + 7272072$$

$$:= 110214 \times 12 + 21 \times 412011 = 1322568 + 8652231$$

$$:= 131004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400131 = 1572048 + 8402751$$

$$\mathbf{9982899} := 100101 \times 18 + 81 \times 101001 = 1801818 + 8181081$$

$$:= 130104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401031 = 1561248 + 8421651$$

$$\mathbf{9984899} := 10024 \times 112 + 211 \times 42001 = 1122688 + 8862211$$

$$\mathbf{9988899} := 111214 \times 12 + 21 \times 412111 = 1334568 + 8654331$$

$$:= 132004 \times 12 + 21 \times 400231 = 1584048 + 8404851$$

$$:= 300403 \times 12 + 21 \times 304003 = 3604836 + 6384063$$

$$\mathbf{9990999} := 10002 \times 333 + 333 \times 20001 = 3330666 + 6660333$$

$$:= 10008 \times 111 + 111 \times 80001 = 1110888 + 8880111$$

$$:= 20007 \times 111 + 111 \times 70002 = 2220777 + 7770222$$

$$:= 30006 \times 111 + 111 \times 60003 = 3330666 + 6660333$$

$$:= 40005 \times 111 + 111 \times 50004 = 4440555 + 5550444$$

$$\mathbf{9996999} := 110314 \times 12 + 21 \times 413011 = 1323768 + 8673231$$

$$:= 131104 \times 12 + 21 \times 401131 = 1573248 + 8423751$$

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